

Joint development of a new Agricultural Operator Exposure Model

Project Report

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1 Abstract

A predictive model for the estimation of agricultural operator exposure has been developed on the basis of new exposure data. More than 30 unpublished GLP exposure studies conducted between 1994 and 2009 mainly for the purpose of plant protection product authorisation were chosen for evaluation according to a set of quality criteria defined by an expert group. All data including information about the studies were compiled in a database and used for a statistical analysis of exposure factors.

The statistical analysis resulted in six validated models for typical scenarios of pesticide mixing/loading, and application outdoors including downwards and upwards spraying with vehicle-mounted/-trailed or hand-held equipment. As a major factor contributing to the exposure of operators, the amount of active substance used per day was identified. Other parameters such as formulation type, droplet size, presence of a cabin or density of the canopy were selected as factors for particular sub-scenarios. However, in the case of knapsack mixing/loading, and hand-held application directed downwards, the number of data was too small for identifying reliable exposure factors; instead the relevant percentiles of the exposure distribution were used.

The new operator exposure model represents current application techniques and practices in Europe and allows for a tiered approach considering personal protective equipment (if necessary). The new model is intended to be used for national authorisation and for registration procedures of plant protection products in the EU.

2 Summary

Exposure models have been used for about 20 years to estimate the exposure of professional operators during application of plant protection products. Exposure estimation is an integral part of the approval of plant production products in Europe, but despite several attempts no harmonised European model is available so far. In addition, the existing models pose a further disadvantage: They are based on old data and do not reflect current application equipment and practices.

Faced with these issues a project team was established to develop a new exposure model for relevant outdoor application scenarios that is suitable for the authorisation process of plant protection products in European Member States. For that purpose 34 unpublished exposure studies which all met a set of quality criteria (e.g. GLP conformity, compliance with OECD series No. 9 on the conduct of agricultural exposure studies) were selected and evaluated. The exposure data and additional information such as application rate, number of product containers handled etc. were compiled in a large database and subjected to statistical analysis of the major impact factors of operator exposure. Six scenarios, two for mixing/loading (knapsack, tank) and four for application (low crop hand-held, high crop hand-held, low crop tractor-mounted, high crop tractor-mounted), were identified and modelled with least squares regression assuming different combinations of impact factors. On the basis of diagnostic values, such as the p-value or R^2 the most suitable factors were chosen for each scenario and used for final modelling with quantile regression. The method of quantile regression was used for modelling because it is more robust with respect to measurements below the limit of quantification and does not assume the variability to be independent of the amount of active substance handled. In addition to the model predicting the 75th percentile a second model predicting the 95th percentile was developed to account for acute exposure estimation which might be relevant in the future. Due to only a small number of datasets it was not possible to identify impact factors for two scenarios (knapsack mixing/loading, low crop hand-held application). For these scenarios it was appropriate to calculate the 75th percentile (medium term exposure) and the 95th percentile (acute exposure) of the absolute ex-

posure values. After the modelling process an internal model validation (cross validation) was performed by analysing the model prediction when different sets of data or complete studies were excluded from the database. Additionally, independent study data (a separate set of data which could not be used for modelling because mixing/loading and application exposure were not measured separately) were compared with the exposure estimates calculated with the model. The exposures predicted by the model were in good agreement with those measured.

As most of the exposure data were log normally distributed the exposure is described by log-linear models. The amount of active substance applied per operator per day was identified as the major impact factor. Where appropriate, additional factors were selected such as formulation type for tank mixing/loading or presence of a cabin for high crop tractor-mounted application. Special sub-scenarios such as hand-held application in dense canopy or downward-spraying with equipment for small area application are also addressed using the corresponding factors.

The exposures associated with mixing/loading and application (including cleaning) of the plant protection product are estimated separately. Each task consists of inhalation exposure and dermal exposure of the head, the body and the hands which are all addressed separately by the model. For the overall operator exposure, during a whole working day, the respective single exposures from mixing/loading and from application are added. Depending on the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) different variables are used for the calculation. In general, the model assumes that the operator is wearing at least one layer of work clothing and sturdy footwear. Therefore, the overall exposure for considering no PPE results from the (potential) inhalation exposure for mixing/loading and application, the (potential) head exposure for mixing/loading and application, the total hand (potential hand) exposure for mixing/loading and application and the 'inner' body (actual body) exposure for mixing/loading and application (measured exposure beneath work clothing). Exposure when specific personal protective equipment (e.g. gloves, face shield) is worn was also modelled and can be used instead of potential exposure. Additionally, defined risk reduction factors for further PPE can also be included in the model to allow a tiered approach. The model is based on exposure data that mostly reflect a usual working day. For that reason the areas (hectare/day) from the studies are used to estimate the amount of active substance applied per day. Nonetheless, the default values for the application area can be adapted to national requirements. The results of the exposure modelling have been used to develop an exposure calculator which is distributed with this report.

The new operator exposure model is a novelty: For the first time the model choice was determined by the exposure data using a comprehensive statistical approach. Hence, the new model is believed to give exposure predictions that are closer to 'real' exposures. Furthermore, the model covers the most relevant scenarios for pesticide application outdoors and considers current application techniques.

3 Introduction

A prerequisite for the approval of plant protection products in Europe is the estimation of operator exposure using suitable exposure models where available. Up to now no harmonised European operator exposure model exists; therefore, the Member States apply different approaches resulting in different estimates for the same exposure scenario. With the implementation of zonal registrations this practice has become questionable as different exposure estimates are not compatible with a joint authorisation of plant protection products in European Member States.

EFSA recently addressed this problem in an opinion which included a draft guidance document on pesticide exposure assessment providing proposals for standard exposure models (EFSA, 2010). However, the models recommended by the draft guidance document are based mainly on data obtained for outdated equipment and agricultural practices and are, in some cases, less suitable for the purpose of predicting exposure under present conditions of use.

To overcome these problems a new database was established using data from more recently conducted operator exposure studies. Collected for a range of representative application techniques and scenarios, the new data are much more suitable for the development of a new model that is applicable for present conditions in Europe.

4 Legal requirements

According to Regulation No 1107/2009 on the placing of plant protection products on the market and Commission Regulation No 545/2011 implementing Regulation No 1107/2009 the use of plant protection products shall not have any harmful effects on human health. Therefore, an estimation of operator exposure as part of a risk assessment is required for the approval of plant protection products and should be accomplished by using suitable exposure models where available. It is stated that calculations have to be made for each type of application and equipment used and have to consider the mixing/loading operations, the application of the plant protection product and also the cleaning and the routine maintenance of application equipment. The requirements for handling the undiluted or diluted product, the climatic conditions or the type and the size of the product containers have to be taken into account as well. A tiered approach is considered for the calculation of operator exposure: The first estimation should be based on the assumption that the operator is not using any PPE (only work clothing), but where appropriate, a stepwise evaluation can be carried out for operators using different levels of PPE.

5 Existing models

The current risk assessment for operators is based on the comparison of a reliable exposure estimate with the respective Acceptable Operator Exposure Level (AOEL) normally derived from subacute or subchronic toxicological studies. The use of a plant protection product is considered safe when the exposure estimate calculated for daily systemic exposure is below the AOEL. For the estimation of operator exposure two models are predominantly used in Europe: The German Model (Lundehn et al., 1992) and the UK Predictive Operator Exposure Model (UK POEM; www.pesticides.gov.uk).

Both, the German Model and the UK POEM are deterministic models that rely on empirical data from exposure studies conducted before 1990 and allow exposure predictions for mixing/loading and application. Exposure in the models largely depends on the total amount of active substance used, the duration of exposure or the container size and number of mix-

ing/loading tasks. Moreover, the formulation type and the spray equipment are important factors, too. In the German Model actual exposure is calculated for professional operators wearing T-shirts and shorts that are assumed to completely cover the respective body parts while in the UK-POEM professional operators are assumed to wear work clothes that cover the whole body and are permeable for a certain fraction of the contaminating pesticides. Additional protective equipment for the operators (e.g. protective gloves) can be chosen in both models in order to reduce the exposure prediction.

Both models share the assumption that dermal exposure during mixing/loading is determined only by exposure to the hands while during application the exposure to the whole body surface including head, torso, arms and legs is relevant. Inhalation exposure, which usually contributes relatively little to the overall exposure, is considered for mixing/loading and application in the German Model but only for application and handling solids in the UK POEM.

Despite the large number of studies the above mentioned models do not cover all relevant scenarios, e.g. the German Model does not have a scenario for hand held applications directed downwards.

Historically, efforts have been made to develop a harmonised operator exposure model, e.g. in the EUROPOEM project. However, this database contained in part outdated exposure data that do not represent current agricultural equipment any more or data from research studies that lacked essential transparency and were unsuitable for predictive modelling.

6 Scope

The objective of this project was to develop a harmonised operator exposure model based on empirical data from modern and scientifically valid exposure studies according to present scientific knowledge and agricultural practices, i.e. studies were performed according to accepted criteria and are representative for relevant application systems. Most, if not all, of these studies have been used to support product registrations in the EU in recent years. The new model is intended to provide estimates of daily exposure for current outdoor application techniques, in particular for:

- Low crop application using vehicle-mounted or vehicle-trailed boom sprayers (LCTM)
- Low crop application using hand-held spray equipment directed downwards (LCHH)
- High crop application using vehicle-mounted or vehicle-trailed broadcast air-assisted sprayers (HCTM)
- High crop application using hand-held spray equipment directed upwards (HCHH)

The model is considered to be appropriate for exposure estimation in authorisation procedures within the EU (especially for zonal registration). For this purpose, it was decided to initially use default agronomic parameters (e.g. for areas treated). Nevertheless, the model was designed to be adjustable and allow the use of national agronomic parameters in case the defaults significantly deviate from local conditions.

In order to ensure a flexible use of the model and to allow a defined consideration of risk mitigation measures the exposure from mixing/loading and the exposure from application should be calculated separately and segregated into the different exposure routes:

Mixing/loading

Dermal exposure:

- Potential dermal exposure (body, hands and head separately)
- Actual dermal exposure (body, hands and head separately)

Inhalation exposure:

- Potential inhalation exposure

Application (including cleaning)

Dermal exposure:

- Potential dermal exposure (body, hands and head separately)
- Actual dermal exposure (body, hands and head separately)

Inhalation exposure:

- Potential inhalation exposure

The entire modelling process was intended to be as transparent as possible. Thus, all data used and all decisions made are reported. Since the model was primarily established for assessing the relevant risks of operators (e.g. seasonal uses), the 75th percentile was used for all statistical issues as recommended by EFSA (EFSA, 2010). For assessing the risks from acute exposure, which will become relevant in the near future, a model based on the 95th percentiles has also been developed.

7 Model development

7.1 Database

7.1.1 Exposure studies

The new operator exposure model is based on data from exposure studies that have not previously been used in official regulatory exposure models. The European Crop Protection Association (ECPA), its member companies as well as the companies Agriphar and Globachem NV provided a pool of studies and an expert group consisting of regulatory body representatives and industry representatives analysed the studies regarding their suitability for the model. To ensure a very high quality of data the studies that were accepted for inclusion in the model had to meet a set of criteria, which are listed below.

- Compliance with OECD Series No. 9 ¹⁾
- Full compliance with GLP
- Monitoring of professional agricultural operators (e.g. farmers and contractors) working in accordance with GAP (Good Agricultural Practice)
- Data recording and observations according to current scientific knowledge
- Consistent field recovery (any outlying data must be explainable on a scientific basis)
- Suitable data form for model development (e.g. separately measured head, hand and body exposure)
- Whole body dosimetry for dermal exposure (exclusion of patch data)
- Inhalation exposure determined with appropriate inhalation fraction samplers
- Representative application methods and application techniques reflecting current agricultural application practices in Europe

¹⁾ compliance with the criteria of that guidance was also confirmed for studies conducted before 1997

Figure 1: Study overview; most of the operators were monitored in France, Spain or Germany and they treated grapevine or cereals; in the majority of the studies the operators used vehicle-mounted/vehicle-trailed spray equipment in low crops (LCTM) and high crops (HCTM); hand-held applications in low crops (LCHH) were performed with knapsack sprayers while spray lances (connected to a tank) were used for hand-held application in high crops (HCHH); different formulation types were applied, liquid formulations (EC = emulsifiable concentrate; EW = emulsion, oil in water; SC = suspension concentrate; SL = soluble concentrate) were the most commonly used ones, two studies were performed with powder formulations (WP = wettable powder) and eight studies were performed with granular formulations (WG = water soluble granules).

According to these criteria 34 studies were chosen. Both mixing/loading/application studies (MLA studies), in which the exposure from mixing/loading and application was monitored as one whole operation (using the same dosimeters/air samplers for the whole working day), and mixing/loading + application studies (ML+A studies), in which the exposure from mixing/loading and the exposure from application were monitored separately (using separate sets of dosimeters/air samplers for each task), were selected.

The studies were conducted between 1994 and 2009 in different European countries. Fifteen studies took place in the central zone and 19 studies in the southern zone (one of which was conducted jointly in Switzerland and France). Typical application techniques and scenarios for outdoor treatment of low and high crops were presented in the studies. The equipment used comprised vehicle-mounted/-trailed or self-propelled sprayers as well as hand-held spray guns and knapsack (backpack) sprayers (Figure 1). Cabins were found on almost all large-scale sprayers predominantly used for the treatment of cereals or potatoes but only on half of the sprayers predominantly used for the treatment of vineyards or orchards. Hand-held applications were conducted with knapsack sprayers or lances connected to a tank. By chance the former sprayers were exclusively used for applications directed downwards, whereas the latter ones were used for applications directed upwards.

Most of the selected studies were designed to monitor exposure during a typical working day comprising the mixing and loading as well as the application of the pesticide product. Cleaning of the equipment was not performed by each operator. Thus, the exposure of this task was not always assessed. In the cases where cleaning was performed it was usually not monitored separately but included in the application task. Depending on the study design the exposure from mixing/loading and application was not measured separately in some studies but recorded as overall exposure.

Mixing/loading and application were conducted by either the same operator or different operators performing work according to their usual work practices. Except for one female operator all monitored subjects were male. The operators were experienced but varied in body weight and age (Figure 2). Target area and total amount of active substance (sum of active substance applied per day) varied depending on the type of application and equipment used. The largest areas and highest amounts of active substance per day were observed for vehicle-mounted/vehicle-trailed application in low crops (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Two different scenarios were monitored for the mixing/loading task: filling a tank and filling a knapsack (observed exclusively for LCHH application). With respect to the duration of the task both scenarios were quite similar, though knapsack filling tended to be performed faster (Figure 5). The average duration of application was three to four hours. Working days with ten or eleven hours of spraying were occasionally observed for vehicle-mounted/vehicle-trailed application (Figure 6).

7.1.2 Sampling methodology

According to the selection criteria the exposure data were obtained by whole body dosimetry and personal air sampling. Dermal exposure was sampled with separate dosimeters/procedures for the head, the body and the hands. All dosimeters were supplied by the study team at the beginning of the studies and collected for analysis at the end of the working day. Both actual and potential body exposures were assessed by analysing the outer and inner layers of sampling clothing. The outer body dosimeter usually consisted of a coverall (mainly jacket and long trousers); the inner dosimeter (representing the skin) consisted of a long sleeved shirt and long underpants. Actual exposure and potential exposure were also determined for the hands. The protective gloves worn by the operators during mixing/loading or application were analysed in addition to inner cotton gloves or hand washes, which were analysed for hand exposure. Various dosimeters, ranging from caps and hoods to headbands or face/neck wipes, were used to assess head exposure. In several studies the operators wore face shields during the mixing/loading procedure.

7.1.3 Data entry

The exposure data were extracted from the selected studies and compiled to create a database for the new model. Numerous columns and sections were created to enable the transfer of the original, non-aggregated values without losing information. In addition to the exposure data further information regarding the pesticide product (e.g. total amount used, formulation type), the work task (e.g. duration, size of treated area), the working conditions (e.g. row distance, temperature), the equipment (e.g. sprayer type, cabin present or not) and the operator (e.g. body weight, description of PPE) was collected in the database. Overall, more than 50 parameters which describe application conditions and might affect the extent of exposure were defined and compiled.

Figure 2: Body weight (BW) and age of the monitored subjects; the body weight ranged from 52 to 132 kg (median: 83 kg), the age varied from 16 to 77 years (median: 39 years); all subjects were male except for one female operator.

Figure 3: Target area; most of the LCTM studies were conducted with about 50 ha, small areas of only 4 to 6 ha were sprayed in one study on herbicide application in vineyards and in one study in maize and fallow fields; the maximum target area for HCTM application was 20 ha but areas between 4 to 10 ha were treated most commonly; the target area for application with knapsack sprayers (LCHH) was in a small range of 0.4 to 1.1 ha while up to 6.8 ha were treated during hand-held application using spray guns connected via hose to a tank in high crops; in about half of the HCHH trials the target area was in the same range as for the LCHH scenarios.

Figure 4: Sum of active substance used per day (total amount a.s.); the amount ranged from 0.9 kg to 250 kg for LCTM application (median: 9.0 kg) and from 0.3 to 37.8 for HCTM application (median: 3.8 kg); 0.1 to 1.5 kg were used in LCHH application (median: 0.2 kg) and 0.3 to 13.5 kg in HCHH application (median: 3.8 kg).

Figure 5: Duration of mixing/loading; in case of filling a tank the whole mixing/loading procedure was completed after 10 to 182 min (median: 40 min), in case of filling a knapsack the task was finished after 17 to 130 min (median: 30 min).

Figure 6: Duration of application; the operators sprayed between 40 to 671 min (median: 235 min) with vehicle-mounted/vehicle-trailed equipment, application with hand-held spray equipment was completed after a median duration of 188 min (range: 80 to 304 min).

7.1.4 Quality control

On completion of data entry by an evaluator, to ensure that information had been correctly transcribed, a second evaluator independently checked the data transcription.

7.1.5 Exposure data

The database for the new operator exposure model comprises a large number of exposure values. A total of 595 operators performing mixing/loading, application or both were monitored in the selected studies resulting in 595 sets of data records for operator exposure. In principle, each data record consists of exposure values for inhalation, the head, the body and the hands. The dermal exposure of the body (excluding head and hands) is compiled from the measured residues on inner dosimeters (representing the exposure of the skin below one layer of work clothing) and the measured residues on the outer dosimeters (normal work clothes). Depending on the use of protective gloves the values for the actual hand exposure are categorized as those for gloved hands (protective gloves always used) and those for unprotected/partially gloved hands (no protective gloves used/protective gloves occasionally used). Inhalation exposure and dermal head exposure are determined by the amount of active substance quantified on the respective specimens.

Based on the study design different types of exposure data exist in the database: Mixing/loading data from monitoring mixing/loading (ML data) activities, application data from monitoring application (A data) activities and mixing/loading/application data from monitoring both tasks as a whole (MLA data). In some cases ML data, A data and MLA data were obtained from the same operator depending on the part of the body monitored (e.g. ML and A data for hand exposure but MLA data for body exposure). All types of data were included in the database but only the separate mixing/loading data and application data were used for model development while the MLA data were used to validate the model.

Because of deficiencies in the exposure sampling (e.g. failure of air sampling pump) or unusual operator activities during the trial (e.g. extensive repair of the spray equipment) some values had to be excluded from the database after completion of data entry. The complete application data from one study (LCTM 3, see study descriptions in Appendix 1) were also not considered for the model since the exposure scenario in the study was considered unusual and irrelevant (herbicide application on a small area of maize or fallow fields with small vehicle-mounted/vehicle-trailed spray equipment). Omitting these data as well as all the combined MLA data, more than 2,900 individual values (consisting of 280 mixer/loaders and 344 applicators with the majority being involved in vehicle-mounted or -trailed applications) remained for model development (Table 1).

Different product formulations were used in the selected studies. While liquid formulations were frequently applied throughout all application scenarios no data were available from the database for:

1. High crop hand-held applications with WG formulations
2. Low crop hand-held and vehicle-mounted/-trailed applications with WP formulations

The spray equipment that was used in the studies differed between application types. Sprayers for normal LCTM applications were generally equipped with a cabin while half of the sprayers used for HCTM applications did not have cabins. Induction hoppers were almost exclusively used in combination with spray equipment for LCTM applications. Hand-held applications directed downwards were performed with knapsack sprayers only. Cleaning of the equipment was included in the monitoring of the application task in less than half of the trials.

Table 1: Agricultural operator exposure database and its characteristics; number of values without MLA data and excluded data (see text). Some operators are counted twice (for ML and for A) since they were monitored during mixing/loading and during application with separate sets of dosimeters/personal air samplers.

	Replicates per task		Cleaning	Cabin			Loading	Formulation				Equipment	
	M/L	A	included	cabin	no cabin	closed cabin	induction hopper	WG	WP	EC/EW	SC/SL	tank	knapsack
LCTM	108	97	43	93	4	56	57	34	-	63	41	138	-
HCTM	79	109	41	54	55	33	1	55	-	12	66	133	-
LCHH	49	48	48	-	-	-	-	19	-	60	9	-	88
HCHH	44	90	12	-	-	-	-	-	60	14	60	134	-
all	280	344	144	147	59	89	58	108	60	149	176	405	88

Table 2: Number of mixing/loading data and application data available for the model development.

	Mixing/Loading						Application					
	Inhalation	Hands	Gloves	Body _{inner}	Body _{outer}	Head	Inhalation	Hands	Gloves	Body _{inner}	Body _{outer}	Head
LCTM	77	96	108	56	57	57	66	85	74	45	46	46
HCTM	52	66	77	41	41	40	83	97	92	72	72	71
LCHH	40	49	49	40	40	40	39	48	20	39	39	39
HCHH	32	44	44	32	32	32	90	90	90	90	90	90
all	201	255	278	169	170	169	278	320	276	246	247	246

Table 3: Application parameters from the selected studies. The parameters for LCTM application were separated regarding the use of normal equipment or small equipment.

	Area [ha]			Total amount a.s. [kg a.s.]			Application rate [kg a.s./ha]		
	75 th perc.	95 th perc.	Max.	75 th perc.	95 th perc.	Max.	75 th perc.	95 th perc.	Max.
LCTM	50.1	63.9	180.0	51.0	201.2	250.0	1.1	4.0	4.5
LCTM (small equip.)	4.4	5.6	6.0	1.0	1.2	1.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
HCTM	9.6	14.0	20.0	7.9	17.8	37.8	0.9	1.8	2.1
LCHH / HCHH (tank)	3.8	6.3	6.8	5.9	11.8	13.5	1.4	1.7	1.7
LCHH / HCHH (knapsack)	0.8	1.0	1.1	0.2	1.5	1.5	0.4	1.5	1.5
HCHH (dense culture)	0.7	1.1	1.4	4.1	7.7	9.4	13.1	17.2	18.4

Since in some of these trials cleaning was performed only if necessary (with no further comments made in the study report) the actual number of monitored cleaning tasks remains uncertain.

The total number of mixing/loading data and application data for inhalation and dermal head, body and hand exposure is summarised in Table 2. The majority of the data that were used for modelling were from LCTM and HCTM studies. Nevertheless, hand-held applications in low crop and high crop are represented by reasonably sized data sets. The raw data and a description of the respective studies are presented in Appendix 1.

In most of the selected studies the area treated corresponded to a typical work day. For the different application methods the application area, the total amount of active substance applied per day and the application rate are presented in Table 3.

7.1.6 Data processing

In a first step the original exposure data were transferred from the study reports into the database without modifying the values. Nevertheless some processing was necessary. In cases where the value was below the limit of quantification (LOQ) it was agreed to use 50 % of the LOQ. Moreover, all values below the limit of detection (LOD) were considered as "zero", but due to statistical analysis reasons a value of 0.01 µg per sample was used instead. If the field recovery was below 70 %, a correction for the field recovery was generally made or accepted. Other modifications were only done in rare cases, in which an extrapolation of the value was necessary. In fact, three values for inhalation exposure had to be adjusted for the whole working time since the air sampling pump failed to work the entire time or was not turned on for a certain time of exposure. The extent of adjustment was, however, limited. In seven cases, in which the duration of pump failure exceeded 30 % of the total working time, the values were discarded.

Further processing of the exposure data took place after data entry. Several correction factors were established to account for the different head dosimeters used in the studies. For a conservative estimation of the whole head exposure the values derived from headbands were adjusted by a factor of 4, values from hats or caps by a factor of 2, values from hoods by a factor of 1.5 and values from face/ neck wipes by a factor of 2. Face/neck wipe data for head exposure during mixing/loading were flagged and evaluated separately when it was

stated in the report that the operator was wearing a face shield. These data do not reflect potential exposure as the amount of pesticide on the face shields was not determined.

Actual hand exposure data obtained by sampling hand washes or inner cotton gloves were used for the model without adjustment. Some operators rinsed their protective gloves after completion of the working task or after handling contaminated surfaces in order to follow good occupational practice. Thus, not all of the potential hand exposure would have been captured. Therefore, the respective data for gloves and hands were evaluated separately. In some studies separate hand exposure values for cleaning were recorded. As cleaning is assumed to be part of the application task, hand exposure from cleaning was added to the hand exposure from application. In the case that the actual exposure of the hands was not separately determined for mixing/loading and application but mixing/loading data (ML data) and application data (A data) exist for the protective gloves used in the study, the value for the actual hand exposure was split by calculation into one value for mixing/loading and one value for application according to the individual ratios of the ML and A values obtained for the gloves. This procedure was applied to 24 values in total.

A similar procedure was carried out for 17 MLA values for 'inner' body exposure; these values were split into ML values and A values according to the ratio of the respective mixing/loading exposure and application exposure of the outer body. Body exposure data for different body parts of the same operator (e.g. torso, lower arms/legs, upper arms/legs) were summed up to one value for 'inner' body exposure or 'outer body' exposure. Values for socks (if analysed) were included in the 'inner' body exposure (only relevant for MLA studies). Furthermore, adjustments were adopted for 'inner' body exposure that had been made in some studies to extrapolate from short underwear to long-sleeved or long-legged underwear.

The exposure via inhalation was calculated from the amount of residue determined on the filter or tube of the air sampler and the flow rate of the air sampling pump assuming a default breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. This rate corresponds to light work activity and is used as standard for estimating inhalation exposure of operators applying biocides (TNsG 2007).

All values which had been modified or adjusted during the data processing were annotated and flagged.

7.1.7 Exposure scenarios

The exposure from mixing/loading (handling the undiluted product) and the exposure from application (handling the diluted product) result from inhalation exposure and from dermal exposure of the body, the head and the hands. With respect to risk assessment two different exposure scenarios are possible for each work task: exposure without using any personal protective equipment (PPE) and exposure when using personal protective equipment.

This issue, however, is only partly addressed by exposure studies, which are designed to reflect normal work practice. PPE is only worn according to good agricultural practice or if label instructions on the product recommend their use. Another problem for the development of the model is that actual exposure is not always detectable by the dosimeters/samplers when using PPE. In the case of inhalation exposure, measured exposure values usually neglect personal protective equipment due to the methodology of exposure monitoring (use of external air samplers). Hence, mixing/loading and application data given for inhalation exposure in the database represent exposure without personal protective equipment. Also the majority of the head values were obtained for exposure without using PPE. Operators wore hats or hoods in some studies but only as dosimeters to assess exposure of the head. At least the impact of wearing face shields during mixing/loading on the head exposure was detected by conducting face/neck wipes in several studies. Consequently, head data for both

scenarios (with or without PPE) are available for the mixing/loading task, but only head data for the exposure without PPE are available for the application task.

Two different kinds of exposure were monitored for the body during mixing/loading and application, the first representing an outer layer of clothing (outer body dosimeter) and the second representing the skin below (inner body dosimeter). Following good occupational hygiene practice it is reasonable to assume that operators are wearing long work clothes covering their skin. Thus, the resulting body exposure generally corresponds to the exposure measured below the outer layer of clothing. The outer clothing as used in the studies was not certified as protective clothing but could be considered as usual work clothes. Consequently, the relevant body exposure for both work tasks corresponds to exposure without special personal protective equipment but with work clothes. For the exposure scenario with personal protective equipment (e.g. a Tyvek suit) no data exist in the database.

In the case of the hands the database provides additional exposure data for using protective equipment. During mixing/loading operators continuously wore protective gloves in almost all studies (following good hygienic practice). The residues on the hands beneath protective gloves (determined by a pair of inner gloves or hand wash) give the exposure when using protective equipment, whereas the exposure when using no protective equipment results from the residues found on the gloves plus the residues found on the hands. For the application task the exposure scenarios are more complex: in some studies protective gloves were permanently worn, but in others only sometimes or not at all. Despite the fact that hands were not (always) covered by protective gloves, they can be considered as protected, as long as the operator applied the pesticide while staying in a closed cabin and used protective gloves whenever doing maintenance work outside or cleaning. In all other cases (open or no cabin, maintenance work or cleaning without gloves) hands are considered unprotected. For the exposure without any protective equipment all hand data are used: the residues found on protected or unprotected hands and the residues found on the respective gloves (if used) are summed up to one value for potential or total hand exposure which is consistent with hand exposure without PPE. An overview of the different scenarios is given in Table 4.

7.2 Statistical evaluation

7.2.1 Variables

The new exposure model provides estimates for the following variables which were evaluated separately for mixing/loading and application. All variables refer to exposure data for individual operators; exposure data were not combined from different operators.

Inhalation exposure: All residues that were found on air sampling filters or tubes, calculated for a generic respiration rate of 1.25 m³/h; this is considered to be representative of inhalation exposure.

Head exposure: All residues that were found on head dosimeters including correction factors: headband 4, hat or cap 2, hood 1.5, face/neck wipe 2; this is considered identical to head exposure without using any personal protective equipment.

'Inner' body exposure: All residues that were found on an inner layer of clothing beneath an outer layer of clothing (head and hands excluded); this is considered identical to actual body

Table 4: Relevant exposure scenarios considered for model development.

		Inhalation	Head	Body	Hands
Mixing/ loading (undiluted product)	without PPE (with working clothes)	Exposure determined by personal air sampling (default breathing rate: 1.25 m ³ /h)	Exposure determined by head dosimeters (incl. correction factors)	Exposure determined beneath outer layer of clothing (inner body dosimeter)	Bare hands (no gloves at all); gloves plus hands partially under gloves; gloves plus hands permanently under gloves
	with PPE	No data	Face/neck wipe data in case that face shields were worn	No data	Hands permanently under gloves
Application (diluted product)	without PPE (with work clothes)	Exposure determined by personal air sampling (default breathing rate: 1.25 m ³ /h)	Exposure determined by head dosimeters (incl. correction factors)	Exposure determined beneath outer layer of clothing (inner body dosimeter)	Bare hands (no gloves at all); gloves plus hands partially under gloves; gloves plus hands permanently under gloves
	with PPE	No data	No data	No data	Hands permanently under gloves; hands partially under gloves (gloves worn during maintenance and cleaning, closed cabin); bare hands (closed cabin, no maintenance work or cleaning)

exposure and body exposure without using special personal protective equipment but with normal work clothes (according to good occupational hygiene recommendations).

Total body exposure: All residues that were found on an inner layer of clothing ('inner' body exposure) and on an outer layer of clothing ('outer' body exposure), excluding head and hands; this is considered identical to potential body exposure.

Protected hand exposure: All residues that were found on the hands of operators protected in any case of exposure; this is considered identical to hand exposure using personal protective equipment.

Total hand exposure: All residues that were found on the hands and gloves of the operator; this is considered identical to potential hand exposure and exposure without using any personal protective equipment.

7.2.2 Model structure

The model should allow a separate calculation of exposure for mixing/loading and for application. With respect to mixing/loading it was intended to differentiate between filling a tank and filling a knapsack. Both scenarios are generally possible for hand held equipment while only tank filling is possible for vehicle sprayers. Different scenarios were also considered for the application task: Models were developed for application with vehicle-mounted/vehicle-trailed equipment, either directed downwards (LCTM) or upwards (HCTM), and for hand-held sprayers, either directed downwards (LCHH) or upwards (HCHH). The scenarios for mixing/loading and application as well as their possible combinations are illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Scenarios (and their combinations) for which models were developed.

7.2.3 Form of the model

As expected, the exposure data were close to log-normally distributed. Therefore, a log-linear model was assumed to describe the exposure values X by A , e.g. the total amount of active substance used, and a number of additional categorical factors F_1, F_2, \dots such as formulation type or presence of a cabin (see section 5.2.4). The general form of the model is:

$$\log X = \alpha \cdot \log A + \sum [F_i]$$

This translates into the following form:

$$X = A^\alpha \cdot \prod c_i$$

The logarithmic model has several desirable properties: The factors of the model contribute to the resulting exposure in a multiplicative way and the logarithmic model is capable of de-

scribing the dependency of exposure on the total amount of active substance used as sub-linear ($\alpha < 1$), which is expected to be realistic for an exposure model. However, a logarithmic model may also result in a superlinear dependency ($\alpha > 1$) which is assumed to be implausible. In this case, the exponent needs to be forced to 1.

7.2.4 Choice of factors

The data were collected for different application scenarios and under varying conditions. In order to cope with the information collected in the database and to minimise the number of factors to be checked during model development several decisions were made:

- The location of the test site can be ignored as the model will cover application conditions for the whole of Europe.
- The crop was differentiated into low crop and high crop only.
- Data on weather conditions are not considered.
- The physicochemical properties of the active substance (e.g. vapour pressure, log Kow) are not considered for the model development.

The focus was set on a selection of key factors on which the exposure is expected to mainly depend. For mixing/loading the following factors were considered:

- Formulation type
- Total amount a.s. used
- Number of containers handled
- Number of mixing/loading tasks
- Concentration of active substance in the product
- Equipment (induction hopper)
- Duration of mixing/loading

Eight factors were chosen to be examined for the exposure during application:

- Formulation type
- Total amount a.s. used
- Concentration of active substance in spray solution
- Equipment (cabin/no cabin)
- Size of area treated
- Droplet size
- Cleaning
- Duration of application

The impact of each factor alone and the impact of combinations of several factors (without interactions) were explored by the following process: A large number of models were fitted by least squares regression and model diagnostics such as p-value, R^2 and AIC were tabulated. These tables were discussed at the expert meetings and suitable factors were chosen. With these factors, the fitting process was started, i.e. the fit was inspected in detail and irrelevant factors, if any, were removed (see section 5.2.10). This approach was chosen in order to make consistent choices for the different exposure variables, to avoid over-prediction and to minimise the impact of implausible findings which may arise by chance. For instance, the experts rejected the idea that formulation type (WG, WP, liquid formulation) may have an impact on exposure during application (as opposed to mixing/loading where the impact was judged plausible).

7.2.5 Software

Data entry was organised using MS Excel 2003. Statistical evaluation was performed using R version 2.15.0 (R development core team, 2012) with the packages *quantreg* (Koenker, 2012) and *DAAG* (Maindonald et al., 2012). R is widely used in research; it provides a modern language for statistical computation.

In the box-and-whisker-plots, the bold line represents the median; the box boundaries represent the first and the third quartile and the whiskers represent the “upper and lower level”, i.e. some range which is deemed plausible based on the height of the box (technically: median $\pm 1.58 \times \text{IQR} / \sqrt{n}$).

7.2.6 Special issues

Prior to the statistical analysis a closer look was taken at some aspects which required clarification with respect to the decisions based on them.

Hand dosimeter

The hand exposure values in the database were obtained by different sampling methods. Hand wash specimens, cotton gloves and/or nitrile glove dosimeters were analysed to determine the exposure. Where cotton gloves were used these were worn in the vast majority below protective nitrile gloves. A rather unusual design, however, was chosen in two studies where the hand exposure was determined with two pairs of cotton gloves – one pair worn beneath and one pair worn above a pair of protective nitrile gloves.

To confirm the assumption that the different sampling methods gave equivalent results all values for protected hand exposure and total hand exposure collected for vehicle-mounted/vehicle-trailed applications were compared (Figure 8). As the distribution of the values was quite similar and displayed the same trend with increasing total amount of active substance handled it was concluded that all study results could be used for the model without restriction.

Protected hand exposure

The application scenario for protected hands includes data from operators wearing gloves all the time and data from operators applying the plant protection product from a closed cabin and wearing gloves in case of exposure (e.g. exiting the cabin to deal with blocked nozzles). Data from operators not using gloves in case of exposure or applying while not staying in a closed cabin were not considered for the estimation of protected hand exposure.

The comparison of the different data categories for LCTM and HCTM application (Figure 9) revealed that the results for the two categories representing the protected hand scenario (‘gloves all the time’, ‘gloves when necessary’) are similar (although the data for the scenario of the hands being protected when necessary cover a wider range than the data for the scenario of the hands being protected all the time, which is probably due to the higher number of data points) while the results for the partially protected/unprotected hands are

Figure 8: Comparison of hand exposure data (LCTM and HCTM) with respect to the method of sampling; red: cotton gloves beneath and above protective gloves; blue: protective gloves (if used) and inner cotton gloves or hand wash; o = WG, Δ = WP, + = liquid.

significantly higher. This result justifies the categorization of the actual hand data made for the model.

Total hand exposure

Total hand exposure is defined as the total amount of active substance to which the hands of the operators are potentially exposed to regardless of the use of protective gloves. Nevertheless, the use of protective gloves might have an impact on the working practice of the operator.

This issue was addressed by analysing the different application scenarios for total hand exposure (Figure 10). The analysis revealed that wearing gloves all the time results in a similar total hand exposure to that incurred if the gloves were only worn when operators identified a specific need to do so (e.g. maintenance operations during the application phase). Thus, wearing gloves or not has no impact on the total exposure of the hands and the data from all scenarios can be pooled for total hand exposure.

Figure 9: Distribution of values for protected hands ('gloves (worn) all the time', 'gloves (worn) when necessary') and partially protected/unprotected hands ('other'); shown are box plots of log normalized data for LCTM and HCTM application; the box plots were generated with the statistical program R and represent the first and the third quartile, the median and the upper and lower level.

Figure 10: Total hand exposure data categorised with respect to the use of gloves; shown are box plots of log normalized data for LCTM and HCTM application; the box plots represent the first and the third quartile, the median and the upper and lower level.

The use of induction hoppers might have an impact on exposure during mixing/loading. Therefore, exposure during mixing/loading using induction hoppers and using conventional equipment was compared. However, the data did not show an impact on hand, body and inhalation exposure. The head exposure was even increased in the presence of induction hoppers, albeit at a low level (Figure 11). Hence, the use of an induction hopper was not considered as a factor for the model.

Figure 11: Comparison of mixing/loading data for using an induction hopper (yes) or not (no). Shown are data for vehicle sprayers only; the box plots represent the first and the third quartile, the median and the upper and lower level.

7.2.7 Correlations and dependencies

Before choosing the scalar predictors for the model key parameters were checked for pairwise correlations in order to reveal possible dependencies amongst them. Four parameters were selected for the investigation of the mixing/loading task:

- number of containers handled
- amount of active substance applied per day (total amount a.s.)
- ML duration
- number of ML tasks

In all cases only weak or no correlations were observed between these factors (Figure 12), but different ranges for the different application types (indicated by different colours) were apparent.

Clear correlations were, however, found between some factors of application (Figure 13). The factors chosen were:

- application area
- amount of active substance applied per day (total amount a.s.)
- concentration of active substance in spray solution
- application duration

The amount of active substance applied per day and the application area (ha) were identified to be highly correlated (log scale, Pearson's $r = 72\%$, Spearman's $\rho = 77\%$) and also the amount of active substance and the concentration of the active substance in the spray solution displayed a strong dependency on each other ($r = 67\%$ and $\rho = 56\%$). Area or concentration of the spray solution should, therefore, not be chosen as modelling factors in combination with total amount. The fourth parameter, the application duration, was not correlated with any of these factors.

7.2.8 Choice of exposure reference value and summation of percentiles

The 75th percentile is used for all statistical issues concerning the development of the model. In parallel, the 95th percentile is used to account for acute exposure estimation in order to comply with possible future requirements for acute risk assessment. In general, the confidence in the estimate of a 95th percentile is lower than the confidence in the estimate of the 75th percentile as higher percentiles depend much more on the measured values at the edge of the distribution which are less dense than in the centre of the distribution. In particular, for small (sub) datasets of the available database or for highly variable measurements, the confidence decreases with higher percentiles.

7.2.9 Methods

There are numerous methods for fitting linear regression models, the most common being least squares regression. In this project, two different methods were used in parallel for modelling the data: ordinary least squares regression and quantile regression.

Ordinary least squares regression (for an overview see Montgomery et al., 2012) has the advantage of being well understood, so model selection using diagnostic figures such as R^2 or the p-value is standard. Once fitted, not only the expected value (mean) can be predicted, but also any required percentile (by adding the respective variation to the predicted value) – provided the model assumptions are valid. However, least squares regression is sensitive to outliers and in particular to the assumed values of measurements below the limit of quantification. In order to obtain a prediction for some percentile, the appropriate multiples of the estimated parameters' standard deviations have to be added to the regression line.

Figure 12: Dependencies between total amount of active substance applied per day, mixing/loading duration, number of mixing/loading tasks and number of containers handled; logarithmic scales used; blue = LCTM, red = HCTM, green = LCHH, black = HCHH; o = WG, Δ = WP, + = liquid.

Figure 13: Dependencies between total amount of active substance applied per day, application duration, area and concentration of active substance in the spray solution; logarithmic scales used; blue = LCTM, red = HCTM, green = LCHH, black = HCHH; o = WG, Δ = WP, + = liquid.

In least squares regression a lot of assumptions are implicit. Normality of the distribution is assumed at each exposure level and with the same standard deviation over the whole range. If these assumptions can be trusted then a relatively small dataset can provide the information on the (mean) regression line and on the standard deviation. But these assumptions may be violated even by peculiarities of the given dataset, especially by the presence of non-detected values.

Quantile regression (Koenker, 2005) is a non-parametric method which gives an independent estimate for every percentile. Therefore it seems wise to prefer quantile regression over least squares regression, similar to preferring the empirical percentile over some “theoretical” percentile. As long as the percentile is well within the range of measured data, the resulting fit can be expected to be more robust than the least squares fit. In particular, it will not depend on the actual choice of the value substituted for non-detects.

Non-detected values on a logarithmic scale have to be set to a fixed finite value which is rather arbitrary or might be handled as censored data by some sophisticated method. If the chosen value is too small the standard deviation is over-estimated, if the value is too large the standard deviation is under-estimated. Quantile regression deals with that problem simply by not keeping track of the value but only counting it as small.

In least squares regression the mean is characterised by minimising the “distance” of the regression line to the data points, expressed by the sum of squares of the residuals. Similarly in quantile regression the median is characterised by minimising the sum of absolute values of the residuals; any other percentile can be realised by minimising other variants of ‘distance’ as shown in Figure 14.

Least squares regression	Quantile regression: 50 %	Quantile regression: 75 %
<p data-bbox="1043 1597 1362 1664">absolute value of residuals (weighted)</p>		
<p data-bbox="193 1709 576 1809">small deviations are well tolerated, while large deviations are penalised disproportionate</p>	<p data-bbox="596 1709 991 1776">all distances to the left and to the right will be weighted linearly</p>	<p data-bbox="1000 1709 1374 1809">deviation to the right is penalised three times as much as deviation to the left</p>

Figure 14: The penalty on the residuals determines the type of regression.

The strengths of both methods were used in this project: For model selection, the least squares method was used; for prediction of the 75th percentile (and 95th percentile) the quantile regression method was used. However, the predictions of both methods were similar. In the case of the LCHH studies (knapsack mixing/loading, LCHH application) a meaningful model could not be fitted since the total amount of active substance used per day was very low in most of the cases (< 0.5 kg). In the range up to 1.5 kg no dependence on the total amount of active substance could be established. Therefore, the respective percentile of all measured values was calculated and assumed valid when applying no more than 1.5 kg of active substance. Several variants exist for the definition of percentiles which differ slightly. In order to have a consistent approach, we chose to determine the empirical percentile by quantile regression (without any influencing factors).

7.2.10 Results

A statistical analysis of the selected data was conducted for each variable including various combinations of possible factors. The results of the evaluation are described in the following sections and are summarised in Table 5. Except for knapsack ML and LCHH A, the model fits were generally very good; the diagnostic plots showed no signs of unsuitability of the model.

ML tank

The inhalation exposure and the dermal exposure to head, hands and body were clearly correlated with the total amount of active substance handled and the formulation type both of which have been used to model the exposure. Three categories of formulations can be distinguished: WP formulations which were associated with relatively higher exposure, WG formulations which were associated with relatively lower exposure and liquid formulations which were associated with intermediate exposure. The data for the liquid formulations had to be pooled as no robust differentiation between EC (organic solvent-based) and SC/SL formulations (water-based) was possible.

The data from operators who rinsed their gloves were included in the modelling of total hand exposure and protected hand exposure. In the case of total hand exposure the data form a subset that is considered to be irrelevant with respect to estimating exposure for authorisation purposes. The face/neck wipe data for operators who wore a face shield during mixing/loading also form a subset and can be used as a PPE scenario for head exposure (head protection face shield plus hood).

ML knapsack

Due to the small number of data for knapsack mixing/loading no modelling factors could be identified for predicting the exposure. Instead, it was proposed to calculate the 75th percentile. The 75th percentiles are based on the absolute exposure values and are assumed valid for up to 1.5 kg of active substance. A linear extrapolation for higher amounts will be possible as a 'worst case' assumption, because exposures are not expected to increase as much as this model predicts. Plausibility of the predicted results should be assessed.

All head exposure data were obtained from operators wearing a face shield. As the exposure to the head is generally considered as low during that task it was accepted to apply the data for the non-PPE scenario and the PPE scenario (face shield and hood).

Table 5: Results of the statistical evaluation – modelling factors and subsets for the mixing/loading and application scenarios.

	Mixing/loading		Application			
	Tank	Knapsack	LCTM	HCTM	LCHH	HCHH
Factors	Total amount of active substance Formulation type (WP, WG, liquids)	None (75 th percentile)	Total amount of active substance Droplet size (coarse, other)	Total amount of active substance Cabin status (cabin, no cabin)	None (75 th percentile)	Total amount of active substance
Sub-set	Face shield Glove rinse	None	Herbicide application in high crops	None	None	Application in dense crops

LCTM application

A good correlation with the exposure was observed for the total amount of active substance and the size of the treated area, but using both as predictor was excluded as previously justified (see section 5.2.7 and Figure 13). The impact of the area referred to one exposure study for herbicide application in grapevine where small areas were treated but the resulting exposure was relatively high. The spray equipment used in the study was smaller and the vehicles were not fitted with cabins. Therefore, it was decided to create a subset for herbicide application in high crops consisting of data from this study instead of describing the exposure using the area. As a further factor for the model the droplet size was identified. All nozzles for field crop sprayers that have been classified for at least 50 % drift reduction have a so called “coarse droplet spectrum” (according to the definition developed by the Julius Kühn Institut). Operators using sprayers with this type of nozzle had a lower exposure than operators spraying with other types of nozzles.

In contrast, the cabin status had no great impact on exposure when differentiating between a closed cabin and other (e.g. open cabin or no cabin). Applying plant protection products while sitting in a closed cabin was only correlated with a lower total hand exposure – possibly an artefact. A clear impact on the exposure was obvious when distinguishing between cabin (closed cabin or open cabin) and no cabin. However, only the smaller spraying equipment used for herbicide application in grapevine was not equipped with a cabin, a fact which is already addressed when considering this application scenario as a subset of LCTM application.

A correlation with exposure was found for the concentration of active substance in the spray solution. Nevertheless, it was not considered as a factor as exposure was strongly correlated with the total amount of active substance (see section 5.2.7). The statistical analysis also revealed that cleaning is not a major factor for exposure. The total hand exposure of operators was similar regardless of whether they conducted a cleaning operation or not.

HCTM application

The inhalation exposure and the exposure to the head and the body were clearly correlated with the total amount of active substance and the cabin status (cabin versus no cabin). For the total hand exposure and the protected hand exposure conclusive correlations are less obvious. Nevertheless, it was decided to apply the same model for all exposure variables.

In general, the overall exposure of operators using vehicles with cabins was much lower than the exposure of operators applying the plant protection product without cabins (Figure 15). The impact of cleaning was analysed as well but a clear trend was not observed and cleaning was not considered further as a modelling factor. No data were available to distinguish between coarse and non-coarse droplet size.

Figure 15: Comparison of mixing/loading data with respect to the cabin status; shown are data for HCTM application only; the box plots represent the first and the third quartile, the median and the upper and lower level.

LCHH application

Only a few data were available from the database for LCHH application. Instead of modelling the exposure it was therefore decided to calculate the 75th percentile. The 75th percentile is based on the absolute exposure values and is assumed to be valid for up to 1.5 kg of active substance. A linear extrapolation for higher amounts will be possible as a 'worst case' assumption, because exposures are not expected to increase as far as this model predicts. Plausibility of the individual results should be assessed.

HCHH application

The exposure for HCHH application was highly correlated with the total amount of active substance handled. Additionally, the statistical evaluation indicated a strong dependency between the extent of exposure and the formulation type. The impact of the formulation type was identified as an artefact and referred to two exposure studies with WP formulations conducted in dense citrus orchards. The operators incurred significant exposure to the plant protection product while walking through the dense canopy. It was decided not to consider the formulation type but to define a subset for application in dense crops – a special scenario where intensive contact with sprayed crops cannot be avoided and exposure is mainly based on dislodgeable spray deposits.

7.3 Validation

The model is based on the statistical analysis of an existing group of stand-alone studies. This introduces some complications like data gaps, confounded factors (i.e., factors that appear always together in all the studies) or heteroscedasticity (unequal variances between groups). Consequently, the results of this analysis should not be used to determine the 'true' importance of a factor in relation to exposure. Studies specifically designed to determine the impact of those factors would be required instead. However, the aim of modeling was to obtain realistic predictions for exposure scenarios, not to reveal the importance of factors.

The robustness and predictive capabilities of any mathematical model can be demonstrated independently of the nature of the model by appropriate validation. Robustness was established in what follows through the use of cross-validation; this approach also permits to establish the relative impact of the different studies in the overall exposure estimation. The predictive capability of the model was demonstrated by using it to predict the exposure in the MLA studies and compare it with the measured MLA data from the database.

Ultimately, it is the predictive performance of a model in relation to a novel dataset that provides confidence in its practical use.

7.3.1 Robustness analysis through cross validation

The approach of cross validation is to repeatedly remove a portion of the data ("test set") and to compare the models obtained with the reduced data sets ("training set"). For this purpose, the function `CVlm` for cross validation from the `DAAG` package for R had to be adapted to quantile regression. In addition to random partitioning of the data sets the revised version was also defined to allow the specification of subsets (test sets). Once the subsets were determined, for each of them the following was done:

1. The model equation was fitted to the reduced data set, i.e. data set without subset;
2. For each data point, the 75th percentile predicted by the reduced model was computed;
3. For the test set, the observed values were plotted against these predictions together with a line connecting the points in the test set's specific colour. Additionally, all measurements were plotted against their predicted values (full model, 75th percentile), with colour and plotting character indicating the subsets.

The diagrams in Figure 16, Figure 17, Figure 18 and Figure 19 each show ten random subsets of the data together with the model line (in the same colour) that would be obtained with the subset removed. The comparison revealed that, in general, the resulting models were

quite similar, even if measurements with large deviations from the prediction were removed. This indicates robustness, i.e. to some degree independence from the actual measured data. As a variant, the subsets were not chosen randomly but whole studies were removed (see Appendix 6). It is more difficult to visualise the lines in these pictures as they are quite narrow, but the predictions for the respective excluded studies were reasonable.

7.3.2 Prediction capability

The MLA data originate from studies in which mixing/loading and application were monitored as one process (with the same dosimeter/air sampler for both tasks). These data could not be used for the development of the model which is based on separate sets of values for mixing/loading and application. Instead, the data were used to check the prediction of the model.

A comparison of the measured value for mixing/loading/application (MLA data) with the predicted (75th percentile) exposure for mixing/loading and application (model) is shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21. Ideally, 75 % of the points should be below (Figure 20) or left of the green line (Figure 21) which symbolises the coincidence of the observed exposure with the model's 75th percentile-prediction. The variation is large, but the prediction is in the correct range and not systematically biased. This is particularly impressive with respect to the difference in methodology between ML+A and MLA studies.

A check of the prediction was only possible for the LCTM scenario and the HCTM scenario; for the hand-held scenarios no MLA data or only an insufficient number of MLA data were available from the database.

7.3.3 Whole body prediction

One issue with the approach taken in this project which has not yet been addressed is that body parts are modelled separately and the predictions are added for whole body exposure. It is well known that, in general, the sum of 75th percentiles does not result in the 75th percentile of the sum, but modelling the whole body exposure was not intended because a defined and stepwise consideration of personal protective equipment or clothing must be possible.

In this project, however, it can be expected that the result is reasonably close to the 75th percentile because the single exposures of an operator are correlated, i.e. an operator with a high body exposure will most likely also have a high exposure of the hands.

In order to check whether the approach is reasonable, the observed whole body exposures were plotted against the 75th percentile predictions as is shown in Figure 22 for potential exposure (head exposure + total body exposure + total hand exposure) and for actual exposure considering work wear and protective gloves (head exposure + 'inner' body exposure + protected hand exposure). The approach is judged reasonable as roughly 75 % of the data points were below the green line which represents the correct 75th percentile of whole body exposure. The estimate is consistent across studies and through a large range of values.

Figure 16: Cross validation of the tank mixing/loading model; shown are random subsets of the model (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets.

Figure 17: Cross validation of the LCTM application model; shown are random subsets of the model (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets.

Figure 18: Cross validation of the HCTM application model; shown are random subsets of the model (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets. The model for protected hand exposure does not depend on total amount; therefore the respective part of the figure is realised as a box plot.

Figure 19: Cross validation of the HCHH application model; shown are random subsets of the model (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets.

Figure 20: Comparison of the exposure for mixing/loading/application determined in the MLA studies (observed) with the exposure for mixing/loading and application calculated by the model (predicted); for HCHH and LCHH no or only a small number of MLA values were available in the database.

Figure 21: Comparison of the exposure for mixing/loading/application determined in the MLA studies (observed) with the exposure for mixing/loading and application calculated by the model (predicted); the data presented in Figure 20 are aggregated to a box plot by calculating the difference of observed exposure and predicted exposure. Ideally, the right edge of the boxes should coincide with the vertical green line.

Figure 22: Comparison of the dermal exposure (work wear, protective gloves) as determined in the studies (observed) with the exposure as calculated by the model (sum of 75th percentile predictions); the green line represents the prediction of the 75th percentile of the model. (blue: LCTM, red: HCTM, green: LCHH, black: HCHH)

8 Predictive exposure model

8.1 Model

8.1.1 Calculation

The following exposure scenarios for the application of plant protection products are addressed by the new operator exposure model:

- Low crop tractor-mounted (LCTM)
- High crop tractor-mounted (HCTM)
- Low crop hand-held tank (LCHH_T)
- Low crop hand-held knapsack (LCHH_K)
- High crop hand-held tank (HCHH_T)
- High crop hand-held knapsack (HCHH_K)

For every scenario the model estimates the overall operator exposure (E_O). The overall operator exposure (in mg/kg bw/d) corresponds to the exposure of a professional operator (wearing PPE or not) during a whole working day comprising mixing/loading and application of the pesticide. It is composed of the dermal exposure DE_O (including head, body and hands) and the inhalation exposure IE_O from both tasks:

$$DE_O = DE_{OML(H)} + DE_{OML(B)} + DE_{OML(C)} + DE_{OA(H)} + DE_{OA(B)} + DE_{OA(C)} \quad IE_O = IE_{OML} + IE_{OA}$$

$$E_O = DE_O + IE_O$$

Each single systemic exposure contribution results from the specific dermal exposure ($D_{x(y)}$) or specific inhalation exposure (I_x) taking account of the dermal or inhalative absorption of the active substance (DA; IA), a default body weight of the operator and, if necessary, the risk mitigation factor for using PPE:

$$DE_{OX(Y)} = (D_{X(Y)} \times (PPE) \times DA) / BW \quad IE_{OX} = (I_x \times (PPE) \times IA) / BW$$

The overall exposure for an operator wearing one layer of work clothes covering torso, legs and arms consists of the following specific exposures or variables:

- Inhalation exposure (= potential inhalation exposure) ML, A
- Total hand exposure (= potential hand exposure) ML, A
- Head exposure (= potential head exposure) ML, A
- 'Inner' body exposure (= actual body exposure) ML, A

In the case that protective gloves are considered for the operator the total hand exposure is replaced by protected hand exposure; the total body exposure (= potential body exposure) is used instead of the inner body exposure when reduction factors for wearing PPE for the body (e.g. protective suit against chemicals) are considered.

The values for the specific exposure are based on equations obtained from exposure modelling using quantile regression. In total, six models are available, two for mixing/loading and four for application (see Table 6 for prediction of the 75th percentile and Table 7 for prediction of the 95th percentile). The factors contributing to the specific exposure are discussed in section 5.2.10 and vary between the different scenarios. In most cases the total amount of active

Table 6: Model equations based on quantile regression modelling (prediction level: 75th percentile); the total amount of active substance (TA) is the major parameter for exposure, the slope α was set to 1 in case $\alpha > 1$; exposure is given in $\mu\text{g}/\text{person}$; the 75th percentiles of the respective exposure values from the database (in μg) are given for knapsack ML and LCHH A.

Tank ML		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{formulation type}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{M(H)} = 0.77 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.57 [\text{liquid}] + 1.27 [\text{WP}] - 0.29 [\text{glove wash}] + 3.12$
	protected hands	$\log D_{M(Hb)} = 0.65 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.32 [\text{liquid}] + 1.74 [\text{WP}] + 1.22$
	total body	$\log D_{M(B)} = 0.70 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.46 [\text{liquid}] + 1.83 [\text{WP}] + 3.09$
	inner body	$\log D_{M(Bb)} = 0.89 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.11 [\text{liquid}] + 1.76 [\text{WP}] + 1.27$
	head	$\log D_{M(C)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.90 [\text{liquid}] + 1.28 [\text{WP}] + 1.79 [\text{no face shield}] - 0.98$
	inhalation	$\log I_M = 0.30 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 1.00 [\text{liquid}] + 1.76 [\text{WP}] + 1.57$
Knapsack ML		75th percentile (above 1.5 kg a.s. linear extrapolation)
	total hands	9495
	protected hands	18
	total body	803
	inner body	25
	head	5
	inhalation	25
LCTM A		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{droplets}] + [\text{equipment}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{A(H)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.37 [\text{normal droplets}] - 1.04 [\text{normal equipment}] + 2.84$
	protected hands	$\log D_{A(Hb)} = 0.54 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 1.11 [\text{normal droplets}] + 0.29 [\text{normal equipment}] - 0.23$
	total body	$\log D_{A(B)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.81 [\text{normal droplets}] - 1.43 [\text{normal equipment}] + 2.54$
	inner body	$\log D_{A(Bb)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.70 [\text{normal droplets}] - 1.09 [\text{normal equipment}] + 0.74$
	head	$\log D_{A(C)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.88 [\text{normal droplets}] - 0.53 [\text{normal equipment}] + 0.24$
	inhalation	$\log I_A = 0.50 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.01 [\text{normal droplets}] - 0.71 [\text{normal equipment}] + 0.72$
HCTM A		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{cabin}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{A(H)} = 0.89 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.28 [\text{no cabin}] + 3.12$
	protected hands	$\log D_{A(Hb)} = \log \text{TA} - 1.55$ ¹⁾
	total body	$\log D_{A(B)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.48 [\text{no cabin}] + 3.47$
	inner body	$\log D_{A(Bb)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.23 [\text{no cabin}] + 1.83$
	head	$\log D_{A(C)} = \log \text{TA} + 1.89 [\text{no cabin}] + 1.17$
	inhalation	$\log I_A = 0.57 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.82 [\text{no cabin}] + 0.99$
LCHH A		75th percentile (above 1.5 kg a.s. linear extrapolation)
	total hands	1544
	protected hands	5
	total body	88868
	inner body	8903
	head	12
	inhalation	26
HCHH A		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{culture}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{A(H)} = 0.84 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 0.83 [\text{normal culture}] + 4.26$
	protected hands	$\log D_{A(Hb)} = \log \text{TA} - 0.88 [\text{normal culture}] + 2.26$
	total body	$\log D_{A(B)} = 0.16 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 1.29 [\text{normal culture}] + 6.08$
	inner body	$\log D_{A(Bb)} = -1.64 [\text{normal culture}] + 4.65$ ²⁾
	head	$\log D_{A(C)} = 0.32 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 1.09 [\text{normal culture}] + 3.27$
	inhalation	$\log I_A = 0.83 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 0.26 [\text{normal culture}] + 2.17$

¹⁾ the dependency of the factor [cabin] was not significant

²⁾ the factor [total amount] had an inverse effect on exposure, thus the factor was removed

Table 7: Model equations based on quantile regression modelling (prediction level: 95th percentile; acute exposure); the total amount of active substance (TA) is the major parameter for exposure, the slope α was set to 1 in case $\alpha > 1$; exposure is given in $\mu\text{g}/\text{person}$; the 95th percentiles of the respective exposure values from the database (in μg) are given for knapsack ML and LCHH A.

Tank ML		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{formulation type}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{M(H)} = 0.78 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.45 [\text{liquid}] + 1.15 [\text{WP}] - 0.84 [\text{glove wash}] + 3.80$
	protected hands	$\log D_{M(Hb)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.80 [\text{liquid}] + 1.81 [\text{WP}] + 1.50$
	total body	$\log D_{M(B)} = 0.29 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.65 [\text{liquid}] + 1.25 [\text{WP}] + 4.21$
	inner body	$\log D_{M(Bb)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.37 [\text{liquid}] + 1.50 [\text{WP}] + 1.79$
	head	$\log D_{M(C)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.50 [\text{liquid}] + 0.35 [\text{WP}] + 1.25 [\text{no face shield}] + 0.70$
	inhalation	$\log I_M = 0.02 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 0.96 [\text{liquid}] + 1.28 [\text{WP}] + 2.41$
Knapsack ML		95th percentile (above 1.5 kg a.s. linear extrapolation)
	total hands	25483
	protected hands	164
	total body	2787
	inner body	103
	head	11
	inhalation	26
LCTM A		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{droplets}] + [\text{equipment}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{A(H)} = 0.73 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.61 [\text{normal droplets}] - 0.21 [\text{normal equipment}] + 2.96$
	protected hands	$\log D_{A(Hb)} = 0.12 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 1.79 [\text{normal droplets}] + 2.19 [\text{normal equipment}] - 0.46$
	total body	$\log D_{A(B)} = \log \text{TA} + 1.51 [\text{normal droplets}] - 0.82 [\text{normal equipment}] + 1.94$
	inner body	$\log D_{A(Bb)} = \log \text{TA} + 1.05 [\text{normal droplets}] - 0.77 [\text{normal equipment}] + 0.47$
	head	$\log D_{A(C)} = \log \text{TA} + 1.03 [\text{normal droplets}] - 1.12 [\text{normal equipment}] + 1.16$
	inhalation	$\log I_A = 0.58 \cdot \log \text{TA} + 0.33 [\text{normal droplets}] - 1.14 [\text{normal equipment}] + 1.27$
HCTM A		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{cabin}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{A(H)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.48 [\text{no cabin}] + 3.32$
	protected hands	$\log D_{A(Hb)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.08 [\text{no cabin}] + 2.88$
	total body	$\log D_{A(B)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.79 [\text{no cabin}] + 3.92$
	inner body	$\log D_{A(Bb)} = \log \text{TA} + 0.15 [\text{no cabin}] + 2.21$
	head	$\log D_{A(C)} = \log \text{TA} + 1.56 [\text{no cabin}] + 2.29$
	inhalation	$\log I_A = \log \text{TA} + 0.60 [\text{no cabin}] + 1.32$
LCHH A		95th percentile (above 1.5 kg a.s. linear extrapolation)
	total hands	4213
	protected hands	22
	total body	137007
	inner body	62630
	head	85
	inhalation	26
HCHH A		$\log \text{exp} = \alpha \cdot \log \text{TA} + [\text{culture}] + \text{constant}$
	total hands	$\log D_{A(H)} = 0.77 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 0.47 [\text{normal culture}] + 4.41$
	protected hands	$\log D_{A(Hb)} = \log \text{TA} - 0.51 [\text{normal culture}] + 2.61$
	total body	$\log D_{A(B)} = 0.01 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 1.09 [\text{normal culture}] + 6.34$
	inner body	$\log D_{A(Bb)} = -1.99 [\text{normal culture}] + 5.27^{1)}$
	head	$\log D_{A(C)} = 0.33 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 0.59 [\text{normal culture}] + 3.50$
	inhalation	$\log I_A = 0.60 \cdot \log \text{TA} - 0.26 [\text{normal culture}] + 2.52$

¹⁾ the factor [total amount] had an inverse effect on exposure, thus the factor was removed

substance applied per operator and day (kg a.s./d) is the main factor for exposure which contributes to the estimated exposure with an exponent factor between zero and one (in case the exponent factor was higher than one, the exponent was fixed to a value of one). For two models (ML Knapsack, A LCHH) exposure factors could not be identified due to the small number of data. Instead, the calculations are based on the 75th percentile (or the 95th percentile for acute exposure) of the absolute exposure values calculated with quantile regression.

The model predictions are presented in Appendix 2 and Appendix 4. A comparison of the percentile obtained by quantile regression with the empirical percentile and the parametric estimate of the percentile calculated according to EFSA (EFSA, 2010) is given in Appendix 3 and Appendix 5.

8.1.2 Applicability domain

The new exposure model was developed for the estimation of professional operator exposure as part of the risk assessment for plant protection products. It represents relevant outdoor exposure scenarios and is applicable to conditions all over Europe due to the broad spectrum of exposure studies included in the database.

The model provides two scenarios for LCTM applications. In addition to the typical scenario for application with normal equipment (either trailed or mounted sprayers) a special scenario for application with equipment used on small areas was created. The data for the special scenario are based on one exposure study conducted for herbicide treatment in vineyards. The equipment used in this study was substantially different from the equipment normally used for LCTM application. Some sprayers had cabins and some did not, but all had small booms (1 to 3 m) and small tanks (300 to 400 L). The respective exposure data are assumed to be suitable for other downward spray applications with small equipment in high crops or on small areas.

The spray equipment used in the studies for the treatment of normal areas generally had cabins, large spray booms (12 to 39 m) and large spray tanks (750 to 5200 L). Hence, the model for normal LCTM application is applicable when standard spray equipment is used and normal areas are treated (default assumption: 50 ha). For such sprayers, which are equipped with nozzles classified for at least 50 % drift reduction (according to the definition developed by Julius Kühn Institut) a further sub-scenario exists, because the production of coarse droplets by this type of nozzle is associated with a lower exposure. In general, the model is applicable for liquid formulations as well as for WG and WP formulations. However, the exposure estimation for WP formulations is covered by exposure data for up to 9 kg of active substance only applied per day.

The model for HCTM application is based on representative exposure studies in grapevine and apples/pears conducted in south and central Europe. A broad spectrum of typical, old and modern spray equipment was used either with or without a cabin. As the presence or absence of a cabin had an impact on the exposure, the model addresses different scenarios for applications with or without cabin. No differentiation is made for whether the cabin is totally closed during application or partly open (e.g. open window).

The LCHH model was developed using data for knapsack spray equipment only. However, it is assumed that the exposure from application with hand-held lances either connected to a knapsack or to a tank is similar. For exposure due to mixing/loading a tank the ML model based on data for the tank application types is used. In contrast to LCHH application the model for HCHH application is only based on data for hand-held spray equipment with large tanks. The operators were either walking along the rows or sitting on the spray equipment. Nevertheless, it is again assumed that the exposure for application with tank spray equip-

ment is similar to the application with knapsack sprayers. The ML model for LCHH application with knapsacks is applied for assessing the exposure of knapsack mixing/loading for HCHH.

In most of the selected studies the treated area corresponded to a typical work day. Therefore, the areas used in the model are based on the areas treated in the studies (roughly the 75th percentile of the respective data; see Table 3). The default values for the area range from 50 ha for LCTM with normal equipment to 1 ha for knapsack sprayers in low or high crop as well as for HCHH in dense culture. For HCTM application and LCTM application with small equipment (on small areas) an area of 10 ha is assumed and for hand-held application using tank sprayers with lances a default of 4 ha is used. However, the values for the area can be adjusted to specific conditions in different countries if necessary.

8.1.3 Operations

In general, operator exposure to pesticides results from preparing and/or loading the spray solution (mixing/loading) and from applying the spray solution in the field (application).

The mixing/loading task comprises all operations starting with opening the product containers/bags and ending with filling the tank with product and water. The appropriate amount of product is poured directly into the tank (from the containers or using measuring vessels) or a pre-mix with water is prepared. Loading of the product occurs either via the top opening of the tank or by means of an induction hopper. Rinsing the containers or vessels is also included in the task.

The application task begins with the end of the mixing/loading task. The operator drives or walks to the field, unfolds the boom if necessary and starts spraying. Routine checks and minor repair work (e.g. changing nozzles) are included in the task as well as small breaks in the field. Cleaning the equipment after having finished spraying is also part of application.

8.1.4 Work clothes and personal protective equipment

The model calculation of the overall operator exposure starts with the assumption that the operator is wearing at least one layer of work clothing completely covering the body, arms and legs when mixing/loading or applying pesticides. The respective exposure values for the body were provided by the database and were used for modelling the 'inner' body exposure.

According to the data wearing work clothes reduces the body exposure by 85 to 98 % depending on the scenario considered (Table 8). The work clothing, used in the studies as dermal exposure dosimeters, consisted of coveralls or long-sleeved jackets and trousers that were made of cotton (> 300 g/cm²) or cotton/polyester (> 200 g/cm²). Generally, the clothing was laundered twice in hot water before use (90 °C). The actual exposure can be further reduced by considering personal protective equipment (PPE).

Exposure data for protected hands (using protective (nitrile) gloves continuously during mixing/loading or application) were available from the database and revealed an exposure mitigation of 89 to 99 % in comparison with bare hands (Table 8). For the model, hand exposure values were also considered to represent the 'protected hand' scenario when

Table 8: Spotlight on distribution of penetration factors for gloves and work clothes derived from data available in the database. Shown are percentiles and coefficients of variation of the ratio of gloved hand exposure (gloves continuously worn) and total hand exposure as well as of 'inner' body exposure and total body exposure; n = number of data.

		Gloves			Work clothes		
		n	75th percentile	CV%	n	75th percentile	CV%
ML	Tank WG	29	0.03	152	29	0.04	97
	Tank WP	20	0.05	91	20	0.04	42
	Tank liquid	155	0.02	329	63	0.02	256
	Knapsack	49	0.01	159	40	0.07	156
	all	253	0.02	333	152	0.04	192
A	LCTM	12	0.11	175	44	0.05	134
	HCTM	44	0.11	154	55	0.04	104
	HCHH	90	0.02	214	90	0.03	110
	LCHH	19	0.03	137	39	0.15	121
	all	165	0.03	210	228	0.04	159

gloves were not continuously worn during application but only during contact with the spray solution or when the operator was sitting in a closed cabin during application.

Head exposure data obtained by analysing face and neck wipes of operators who wore a face shield during mixing/loading were used to create a PPE scenario for the head. The model for head exposure during tank mixing/loading considers these data with an additional adjustment factor by which the exposure is increased when a face shield (+hood) is not used. The head exposure of operators wearing a face shield was on average about 50 times lower than the head exposure of operators wearing no face shield (i.e. ca. 2 % of potential head exposure).

The values for head exposure during knapsack mixing/loading are exclusively based on face/neck wipe data for using face shields. As the vast majority of the values were below the limit of quantification (LOQ) no correction was made to create a non-PPE scenario. Instead, the values were used for the non-PPE scenario and for the PPE scenario.

In addition to the risk mitigation derived from the exposure data in the database default factors for specified PPE can be used (see section 8.1.5).

8.1.5 Tiered approach

The model can be used for a tiered approach. The Tier I scenario corresponds to the exposure considering no PPE but one layer of work clothes covering torso, arms and legs; in the Tier II scenario dermal and/or inhalation PPE factors can be chosen if the exposure calculated in Tier I exceeds the AOEL.

Table 9 gives an overview over the PPE that are included in the model.

Table 9: List of PPE with respective reduction factors in relation to stated routes of exposures.

Personal protective equipment	Reduction factor	Concerned exposure
Respiratory protection (ML)	e.g. 0.08	I _M
	e.g. 0.8	D _{M(C)}
Respiratory protection (A)	e.g. 0.08	I _A
	e.g. 0.8	D _{A(C)}
Protective gloves (ML)	acc. model	D _{M(H)}
Protective gloves (A)	acc. model	D _{A(H)}
Workwear + sturdy footwear (ML)	acc. model	D _{M(B)}
Workwear + sturdy footwear (A)	acc. model	D _{A(B)}
Protective suit against chemicals	e.g. 0.01	D _{M(B)}
Protective suit against chemicals	e.g. 0.01	D _{A(B)}
Hood and face shield (ML)	acc. model	D _{M(C)}
Hood and face shield (A)	0.05	D _{A(C)}
Head protection (e.g. hat)	e.g. 0.5	D _{M(C)}
Head protection (e.g. hat)	e.g. 0.5	D _{A(C)}

8.2 Operator exposure calculator and user guidance

An excel spreadsheet (distributed with this report) has been created for users allowing the calculation of operator exposure with the new model. A guidance note for the use of the calculation sheet is given in Appendix 7.

8.3 Data gaps

Despite the large number of data used for the development of the model, additional exposure values are needed to address certain scenarios. As previously mentioned, few data exist in the database for knapsack mixing/loading and for hand-held application in low crops. Due to the limited data (e.g. no available exposure for WP formulations, only a small range of total amount of active substance applied per day) no statistical model could be derived from them. In addition, data are completely lacking for high crop applications with knapsack sprayers and for low crop applications using tank sprayers with hand-held lances. As these data are not available it has to be assumed that hand-held application in low/high crops is the same irrespective of the equipment used.

A further deficiency consists in the availability of exposure data for WP formulations. The database contains only two studies with this formulation type, both conducted in Spain on hand-held application of the same insecticide in citrus. Hence, the application conditions and the equipment used were quite similar and the range of applied amount of active substance is small.

8.4 Future perspectives

The operator exposure model has been developed on the basis of a large database and in due consideration of relevant exposure scenarios including modern application techniques. Nevertheless, the technical progress is continuing and the exposure patterns might change significantly in the future. In addition, the number of data available for certain scenarios (knapsack mixing/loading, application LCHH) is relatively small and less robust for modelling exposure. Therefore, it is reasonable to allow for an update of the model from time to time depending on the availability of new exposure studies. Data from appropriate studies would be incorporated into the existing database in order to enable a more confident statistical analysis of exposure factors or to simply enhance the robustness of the models. In addition, exposure scenarios, for which no data are currently available in the database (e.g. application in greenhouse), could be addressed and modelled accordingly. National authorities should agree on the updating of the model and coordinate the process.

9 Conclusions

A new model for prediction of exposure of professional operators applying plant protection products outdoors has been developed using previously unpublished field data collected between 1994 and 2009. It provides calculations for estimating the exposure for typical scenarios including the mixing/loading and the application of plant protection products. The underlying equations are based on log linear models for prediction of the 75th percentile and consist of exposure factors that were selected after a statistical analysis. The exposure mainly depends on the total amount of active substance used per day and is further described by additional factors or particular sub-scenarios. The model allows a tiered approach starting with estimating exposure for an operator wearing at least one layer of clothing; risk mitigation by using personal protective equipment can be considered if the AOEL is exceeded.

The model reflects current application techniques and typical work conditions in Europe. It is, therefore, applicable for zonal registrations and national authorisations of plant protection products in member states of the EU. Updated versions of the model will be periodically created if new data become available.

10 Supplementary information

Additional information on the data and the model are given in the supplementary information. The file comprises a complete list of the raw data used for the model development, a table with percentiles of the raw data and the detailed model computations.

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12 Abbreviations

A	application
AIC	Akaike information criterion
a.s.	active substance
CV	coefficient of variation
EC	emulsifiable concentrate
EW	emulsion, oil in water
HCHH	high crop hand-held
HCTM	high crop tractor-mounted
IQR	interquartile range
LCHH	low crop hand-held
LCTM	low crop tractor-mounted
ML	mixing/loading
MLA	mixing/loading/application
SC	suspension concentrate
SL	soluble concentrate
TA	total amount of active substance (in kg a.s./d)
WG	water dispersible granules
WP	wettable powder

13 Glossary

A data:	exposure data for the application task, obtained by using a separate set of dosimeters/personal air samplers for the exposure during application
applicator:	professional operator who applies the pesticide product
mixer/loader:	professional operator who handles the formulated product, prepares the spray solution and loads it into the tank of the sprayer

mixer/loader/applicator:	professional operator who mixes and loads the spray solution and applies it afterwards
ML data:	exposure data for the mixing/loading task, obtained by using a separate set of dosimeters/personal air samplers for the exposure during mixing/loading
MLA data:	exposure data for the mixing/loading and application task as a whole, obtained by using one set of dosimeters/personal air samplers for both tasks
MLA study:	exposure study in which the exposure for mixing/loading and application is determined together, usually one operator performing both tasks is monitored throughout the whole work day
ML+A study:	exposure study in which the exposure during mixing/loading and the exposure during application is determined separately; either two different operators, one performing mixing/loading and one performing application, or one operator, performing both but using separate dosimeters/personal air samplers for each task, are monitored
Total amount a.s.:	sum of active substance which was handled per operator per day (in kg a.s./d)

Appendix 1 Study descriptions

LCTM 1

Active substance: Flufenacet (600 g/kg)
Formulation type: Water dispersible granules
Pesticide function: Herbicide
Crop: Maize

Setting:

The dermal and inhalation exposure of workers towards flufenacet during mixing/loading and application in maize fields was determined in this study. Seven mixer/loaders and seven applicators handling 21.3 to 33.0 kg a.s. were monitored during April and May 2000 at different sites in Germany, which were typical and representative for maize cultivation. At each test site one operator performed mixing/loading and one operator performed application. Cleaning was not included in the tasks, but one cleaning operation was sampled separately (results not used for model). The area treated was in the range of 36.0 to 56.5 ha corresponding to a usual working day. The spray equipment was typical for large-scale treatment of low field crops and included mounted or trailed sprayers with spray booms of 15 to 24 m and tank sizes of 1,500 to 3,200 L. Tractors with closed cabins were used only. In two cases the windows of the cabin were temporarily open (operator B and J) so that spray drift could get inside the cab. The product was packed in bags of 5 kg and applied at a rate of 0.8 to 1.3 kg/ha (0.5 to 0.8 kg a.s./ha) in a water volume of 100 to 370 L/ha. Mixing/loading was performed two to eight times by using an induction hopper into which the product was poured. Only one operator (operator K) loaded the product directly via the top opening of the tank. Mixing/loading took between 43 and 110 min whereas application took between 214 and 355 min.

Exposure assessment:

Dermal exposure of the operators was measured by using whole body dosimeters consisting of a long-sleeved T-shirt, long underpants and a long-sleeved shirt as inner layer and long work trousers and a long-sleeved work jacket as outer layer. Head exposure was calculated from residues collected on a cap which was worn by each operator during the whole working time. Gloves worn during mixing/loading and for maintenance tasks during application as well as hand washes conducted after each mixing/loading or application cycle were analysed to quantify hand exposure. Inhalation exposure was determined from residues collected by an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter (mixing/loading) or by a Tenax[®] tube (application) attached to a personal air pump located in the breathing zone of the operator (flow rate ca. 2 L/min). The analysis of flufenacet was performed with LC-MS/MS detection after extraction with 2-propanol.

Results:

The results of the study are given below. All values were above the LOQ and were not corrected for field recovery since the field recovery was above 70 % for all matrices except for the nitrile gloves (mean field recovery only 24 %, due to a solvent effect). Inhalation exposure has been recalculated for a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
A	25.1	338.1	0.291	4.673	0.716	11.184	1.179
C	28.2	31.4	0.036	3.502	0.047	2.243	0.020
E	28.5	63.1	0.065	0.437	0.114	7.550	0.074
G	21.3	824.9	0.104	0.509	0.494	19.866	0.705
I	25.0	280.2	0.046	5.698	0.107	3.170	0.072
K	24.0	73.1	0.002	0.254	0.029	0.850	0.022
M	33.0	235.3	0.031	1.166	0.168	2.623	0.076

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
B	25.1	1.4	0.016	0.209	0.013	0.146	0.006
D	28.2	2.1	0.079	1.5x10 ⁻⁴	0.012	0.268	0.005
F	28.5	0.3	0.006	0.075	0.013	0.075	0.006
H	21.3	1.1	0.046	-	0.008	0.164	0.012
J	25.0	1.4	0.007	-	0.007	0.320	0.002
L	24.0	2.3	0.009	0.009	0.003	0.233	0.001
N	33.0	0.9	0.030	0.028	0.006	0.419	0.003

LCTM 2

Active substance: Fentin-hydroxide (500 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Fungicide
 Crop: Potatoes

Setting:

The study was conducted in the UK during August 1999 to monitor exposure during mixing/loading and application of a fungicide containing fentin-hydroxide with ground boom sprayers in potatoes. Fifteen experienced operators, both mixing/loading and applying the product, were involved in the study. Cleaning of the equipment was not conducted. The farms (19.4 to 41.0 ha) were chosen according to a target area of ca. 30 ha and covered representative working conditions for potato growing. A broad range of large scale sprayers with induction hoppers and tank sizes of 1000 to 3500 L was used for application. All vehicles were equipped with cabins, which were kept closed during application. The product was applied at the recommended rate of 0.5 L/ha (0.25 kg a.s./ha) in a spray volume of 75 to 300 L/ha. The application duration varied from 89 to 205 min. Mixing/loading was performed one to seven times (product container size: 5 L) and took 43 min on average. During mixing/loading a face shield was worn.

Exposure assessment:

The operators were dressed in cotton coveralls with a hood to determine 'outer' body exposure and head exposure and a polyester/viscose long-sleeved T-shirt and a pair of long johns to determine 'inner' body exposure. Inhalation exposure was monitored with a Tenax filled air sampling tube connected to a personal air pump working at a rate of 1 L/min. The dosimeters for inhalation and body exposure were worn during the whole working day and no separation into mixing/loading and application was made. For monitoring hand exposure the operators were provided with cotton inner gloves and chemical resistant outer gloves. Sepa-

rate pairs of gloves were used for mixing/loading and application. During application the chemical resistant gloves were only worn when performing maintenance work outside the cabin. Fentin-hydroxide residues were extracted from the dosimeters with methanol, dissolved in acetonitrile/water (3:1) with 0.5 % glacial acetic acid and analysed using LC-MS/MS.

Results:

The results for the hand exposure are given below. In some cases the field recovery for the cotton gloves (52 to 99 %) and chemical resistant gloves (55 to 113 %) was below 70 %; thus, the respective values were adjusted. Values below the LOQ were set to ½ of the LOQ. The MLA data for inhalation, body and head exposure are not shown since they were not used for the model.

The exposure of operator 8 was significantly higher than that of the other operators. A serious contamination of the lower arms (due to accidental spillage during mixing/loading) as well as filling of the front tank via gravity was mentioned for this operator in the study report.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hood [mg]
1	9.0		* 0.005	** 0.580			
2	6.3		* 0.005	7.200			
3	6.8		n.d.	** 3.077			
4	10.0		* 0.005	1.600			
5	8.8		* 0.005	3.800			
6	7.3		** 0.125	1.500			
7	4.9		* 0.005	** 8.824			
8	10.3		0.740	** 29.412			
9	7.5		n.d.	0.480			
10	3.8		** 0.033	0.440			
11	5.8		* 0.005	** 2.364			
12	7.0		* 0.005	** 1.545			
13	7.9		** 0.066	5.200			
14	8.3		** 0.213	** 3.111			
15	9.6		0.040	0.930			

* ½ LOQ ** adjusted for field recovery n.d. - not detectable

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hood [mg]
1	9.0		*** 0.019	*** 1.594			
2	6.3		*** 0.056	* 0.050			
3	6.8		* 0.005	n.d.			
4	10.0		*** 0.034	0.160			
5	8.8		*** 0.098	0.210			
6	7.3		*** 0.500	0.110			
7	4.9		0.100	0.290			
8	10.3		0.500	n.d.			
9	7.5		n.d.	n.d.			
10	3.8		** 0	* 0.050			
11	5.8		* 0.005	n.d.			
12	7.0		* 0.005	n.d.			
13	7.9		*** 0.066	n.d.			
14	8.3		*** 0.082	n.d.			
15	9.6		0.040	n.d.			

* ½ LOQ ** no value given, calculated as '0' in study report *** adjusted for field recovery n.d. - not detectable

LCTM 3

Active substance: Atrazine (500 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Maize, fallow fields

Setting:

The objective of this study was to assess the operator exposure to atrazine. The study took place in 1994 at ten sites in Switzerland (trial 1-5, maize) and France (trial 6-10, fallow field) and was conducted with different operators for mixing/loading and application. The product was applied to a small target area of 5 ha except in trial 5 which was terminated after treatment of only 3 ha due to heavy wind. About 3 L product (1.5 kg a.s.) diluted in ca. 200 L water were sprayed per hectare using commercial ground boom sprayers. The equipment used in trial 1-5 (600 L tank volume, 15 to 24 m boom, no cabin) was owned by the company conducting the study whereas the sprayers used in trial 6-10 (600 to 2300 L tank volume, 20 to 24 m boom, cabin) were owned by the farmers themselves. Depending on the volume of the spray tank the number of product containers handled (pack size trial 1-5: 1 L; pack size trial 6-10: 5 L) varied between 3 and 15. An induction hopper was used in trial 9 only; in all other cases the product was loaded manually. Each trial (except trial 5) consisted of two tank mix preparations taking 27 min on average and two spraying operations taking 73 min on average. With the exception of trial 9 the boom was manually unfolded and folded. Cleaning of the equipment was not included in the monitoring.

Exposure assessment:

Each operator was provided with a cotton coverall, cotton undertrousers and a long sleeved undershirt for monitoring body exposure. In addition, the operators wore caps which were sampled for head exposure. Inner cotton gloves plus hand wash specimens and protective gloves plus outer glove wash specimens were sampled to determine the actual and potential hand exposure. During application the protective gloves were only worn in case of contact with the pesticide (maintenance). Inhalation exposure was determined by personal air sampling using OVS sampling tubes. The flow rate of the sampling pump was about 2 L/min.

Atrazine was extracted from the samples with methanol/water: After a cleanup by partition into dichloromethane the residues were quantified by GC-MS or HPLC with UV detection.

Results:

With respect to the unusual application scenario for low crop (treatment of small areas) only the results for mixing/loading are given below. The results for application are not used for the model. The mean field recovery ranged from 83 to 97 % for the different sample matrices except the nitrile gloves for which no field recovery was given. $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ was used for values below the LOQ. Inhalation exposure was recalculated for an assumed breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hat [mg]
WM	7.5	** 2.7	0.071	15.890	0.085	** 5.608	0.002
JT	7.5	** 30.1	0.078	21.240	0.135	** 14.626	0.004
HM	7.5	** 2.5	0.030	25.420	0.162	20.229	0.011
JK	7.5	** 1.6	0.045	37.560	0.018	** 3.264	0.003
RV	4.5	** 3.8	0,050	40.910	0.277	9.912	0.005
YB	8.0	** 4.0	0.375	25.170	0.123	9.825	0.009
JM	8.0	** 12.2	0.122	14.260	0.085	65.400	0.007
JD	8.0	** 2.5	0.869	4.645	1.170	** 13.800	0.038
JB	7.5	** 1.6	0.024	0.738	0.289	2.774	0.004
EG	7.5	* 1.0	** 0.035	1.560	0.358	** 0.423	0.011

* $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ ** partly calculated with $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ

LCTM 4

Active substance: Clodinafop-propargyl (240 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Winter wheat

Setting:

Four operators were monitored in the UK in 1994 while applying clodinafop-propargyl at a rate of 0.06 kg a.s./ha. At each site one operator performed mixing/loading and one operator performed application. Cleaning of the tank at the end of the working day was included in the monitoring. A target area of approximately 50 ha of winter wheat were treated in 235 to 349 min with tractor drawn sprayers (tank size: 3500 L) equipped with induction hoppers, closed cabins and hydraulic folding booms (24 m). 150 L spray solution was brought out per hectare. Mixing/loading was performed in three cycles and took 46 to 76 min. All operators wore a face shield during mixing/loading.

Exposure assessment:

A cotton coverall as well as cotton undertrousers and a cotton long-sleeved undershirt were used as outer and inner body dosimeter. The air in the breathing zone of the operator was sampled with a Casella AFC 123 air monitor with GF/C filter. Head exposure was monitored with a cap worn throughout application or mixing/loading. Hand washes were taken at the end of each task and analysed to determine exposure of the hands. Additionally, protective nitrile gloves were provided. They were worn during mixing/loading and for maintenance work during application. The collected dosimeter samples were analysed for the active substance clodinafop-propargyl and its carboxylic acid metabolite by extraction with acetone and quantification with LC-MS/MS.

Results:

The active substance clodinafop-propargyl was shown to be stable during the study and the metabolite was in most cases not detectable or below the limit of quantification. Therefore, the amount of the active substance was considered only. The field recovery, which was only given for the clothing matrix, was on average 83 %. No corrections were made. The values for inhalation exposure were not used for the model since information on the measurement was scarce (flow rate of pump and sampling time not given).

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation* [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
SH	2.5		0.002	0.917	0.001	0.518	0.020
TS	2.3		n.d.	4.761	0.005	0.276	0.005
SC	3.1		0.002	2.133	0.015	0.147	** 0.001

THR	2.9		0.003	0.830	0.003	0.373	0.004
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* poorly documented – not used for model ** ½ LOQ n.d. – not detectable

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation* [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
SC	2.5		n.d.	-	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
THR	2.3		0.009	0.009	** 0.001	0.026	n.d.
SH	3.1		0.007	-	0.002	0.006	n.d.
TS	2.9		0.012	-	n.d.	0.009	n.d.

* poorly documented – not used for model ** ½ LOQ n.d. – not detectable

LCTM 5

Active substance: Prosulfocarb (800 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Cereals

Setting:

The study was conducted during September and October 2004 to determine dermal and inhalation exposure of operators while mixing/loading and applying the herbicide Boxer 800 EC in cereals. Twelve experienced farmers, farm employees or contract operators were monitored for a typical working day at different sites in Germany. The area treated varied from 47 to 80 ha. Each operator performed mixing/loading (35 to 85 min) as well as application (206 to 521 min); cleaning was only performed by operator 2. The spray equipment consisted of trailed or self-propelled ground boom sprayers which were fitted with large tanks (2,500 to 4,000 L volume) and cabins. All operators except for operator 12 applied the product while keeping the door and windows of the cabin closed. Mixing/loading was performed two to five times by using induction hoppers in most of the cases (operator 1 to 10). On average 25 product containers (10 L) were handled. The product was applied at the label recommended rate of 2.5 to 5.0 L/ha (2.0 to 4.0 kg a.s./ha) in a volume of 100 to 250 L spray liquid/ha. Some operators wore a cap, which was not analysed for residues of the active substance.

Exposure assessment:

The operators were provided with outer body dosimeters consisting of cotton/polyester overalls and inner body dosimeters consisting of cotton long-sleeved T-shirts and long johns worn over the operator's regular underwear. Exposure of the head was determined by face/neck wipes taken at the end of the working day. The measurement of dermal body and head exposure was not separated for mixing/loading and application. Hand washes conducted after each mixing/loading or application cycle were analysed to assess hand exposure. Protective nitrile gloves used during the work were analysed as well. Each operator got one pair of gloves for mixing/loading and one pair of gloves for application. During mixing/loading the gloves were continuously worn. The air in the breathing zone of the operator was monitored with personal air sampling equipment (XAD-2/OVS sampling tubes). The air sampling pump was calibrated to a flow rate of 1.5 L/min. All collected samples were stored in a freezer until the residues were extracted from the sample matrices with n-hexane and quantified by LC-MS/MS.

Results:

The results of the study (except the MLA data for body exposure and head exposure) are presented in the following tables. All values were above the LOQ and adjustments for recovery were not necessary since the field recovery for air filters, hand washes and gloves was above 70 %. The exposure from inhalation has been calculated for an average breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. In case of operator 4 the value for inhalation had to be extrapolated because the air sampling pump was not turned on during the first application cycle (four application cycles in total – only ca. 75 % of the working time was monitored, extrapolation to 100 %).

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	200	0.8	0.001	26.226			
2	200	0.7	0.001	29.607			
3	192	9.6	0.029	70.616			
4	160	2.5	0.003	29.734			
5	192	4.5	0.005	278.049			
6	192	7.3	0.015	49.827			
7	208	4.9	0.001	31.823			
8	188	18.7	0.007	36.478			
9	200	3.5	0.021	73.898			
10	200	0.8	0.006	28.443			
11	179	0.8	0.802	315.031			
12	250	19.1	0.141	717.756			

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	200	2.8	0.100	14.723			
2	200	2.1	0.013	-			
3	192	27.9	0.042	8.400			
4	160	* 5.6	0.023	-			
5	192	13.2	0.013	6.373			
6	192	17.3	0.058	9.934			
7	208	1.7	0.001	-			
8	188	12.0	0.024	8.101			
9	200	14.5	0.068	20.866			
10	200	7.5	0.009	** (0.274)			
11	179	12.5	0.313	13.403			
12	250	69.7	0.819	-			

* extrapolated since first application cycle was not monitored ** gloves were not used

LCTM 6

Active substance: Azafenidin (800 g/kg)
 Formulation type: Water dispersible granules
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

Ten mixer/loaders and ten applicators were monitored at ten representative locations in Southern France while using Azafenidin 80WG for herbicidal control in vineyards. The product was applied at the highest recommended rate of 0.3 kg/ha (0.24 kg a.s./ha) and was diluted in a water volume of 200 L/ha. According to the study protocol an area of 3 to 8 ha had to be treated within a working day of 4 to 8 h. Actually, the operators sprayed the herbicide on 4 to 6 ha using a typical range of small ground boom sprayers for herbicide application (tank size: 300 to 400 L). The spray boom (1 to 2 m) was either protected or unprotected and some of the vehicles were equipped with a cabin (open or closed). The product was packed in 0.3 kg bags and was directly loaded via the top opening of the tank. The workers handled 3 to 5 product bags and wore face shields during that operation. Mixing and loading (13 to 34 min) was repeated two to three times; application was finished after 195 to 348 min. All applicators except for operator 3 cleaned the tank at the end of the working day.

Exposure assessment:

Each operator was provided with two layers of clothing – a cotton coverall for sampling outer body exposure and a polyester/viscose long-sleeved T-shirt and long johns to determine ‘inner’ body exposure. After mixing/loading or application was completely finished, face and neck of the operators were wiped and hand washes were collected. Protective nitrile gloves worn during mixing/loading or for maintenance work during application were sampled as well. Exposure via inhalation was assessed with IOM samplers with GF/A filters (flow rate ca. 2.0 L/min). According to the sample matrix the residues were quantified either by HPLC with UV detection (clothing, air filter, face/neck wipes, hand washes) or by LC-MS (gloves).

Results:

The results of the study are summarised below. In general the exposure towards the active substance was very low, especially for inhalation and head. The field recoveries for the sample matrices were on average between 71 % and 94 %, therefore, no correction was made.

Values below the LOQ are reported as ½ of the LOQ. For estimation of exposure via inhalation an average breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h has been assumed. The first mixing/loading cycle of operator 14 and the first application cycle of operator 13 were not considered because the trial was aborted due to increasing wind: The monitoring was restarted with the second cycle.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
2	1.0	16.5	0.030	6.026	0.025	0.939	n.d.
4	0.7	n.d.	0.003	1.034	0.011	0.659	n.d.
6	1.0	n.d.	0.004	1.266	* 0.002	0.991	n.d.
8	1.0	n.d.	2x10 ⁻⁴	0.219	n.d.	0.827	n.d.
10	1,2	n.d.	* 0.002	2.366	* 0.002	0.209	n.d.
12	1.0	n.d.	0.072	0.897	** 0.003	0.167	n.d.
14	0.9	* 5.2	0.003	0.585	* 0.002	0.212	n.d.
16	1.0	* 5.2	0.014	2.071	0.008	1.890	n.d.
18	1.0	* 5.2	0.006	0.853	0.008	0.856	n.d.
20	1.0	n.d.	0.010	6.866	0.008	1.193	n.d.

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ n.d. – not detectable

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	1.0	n.d.	0.021	2.464	0.029	2.105	n.d.
3	0.7	n.d.	0.005	0.007	n.d.	0.455	n.d.
5	1.0	n.d.	0.076	1.480	0.006	2.698	0.075
7	1.0	18.3	0.066	0.256	0.025	2.318	0.006
9	1.2	n.d.	* 0.002	0.750	* 0.002	0.749	* 0.002
11	1.0	n.d.	0.072	0.355	0.027	1.670	* 0.002
13	1.0	40.9	0.062	0.158	0.015	0.829	* 0.002
15	1.0	* 5.2	0.027	3.611	0.012	0.892	0.006
17	1.0	* 5.2	0.080	0.312	0.032	0.865	* 0.002
19	1.0	n.d.	0.009	0.972	0.008	0.792	n.d.

* ½ LOQ n.d. – not detectable

LCTM 7

Active substance: Prothioconazole (250 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Fungicide
 Crop: Cereals

Setting:

The exposure of five experienced operators applying prothioconazole in cereals was assessed at five different sites in Germany in 2005. Each operator performed mixing/loading and application for a usual working day thereby treating an area of 19 to 67 ha. The amount of product varied from 0.7 L and 1.1 L/ha (0.2 to 0.3 kg a.s./ha) and was brought out in a spray volume of 155 to 238 L/ha. Depending on the area treated either small ground boom sprayers (1000 L tank, 15 m boom) or large ground boom sprayers (3000/4000 L tank, 18/30 m boom) were used. All vehicles were equipped with a closed cabin, but two operators

(A, B) applied the product while having one or more windows open. Induction hoppers were used by two operators (A, C), all other operators poured the product which was packed in 5 L containers directly into the tank. Each trial consisted of three to six mixing/loading and application cycles. Mixing/loading was finished in 32 to 87 min, application was completed in 242 to 396 min. Cleaning of the tank was mentioned for operator B.

Exposure assessment:

The exposure towards prothioconazole and its metabolite prothioconazole-desthio was assessed with whole body dosimeters. Each operator was dressed in normal work clothes (cotton long-sleeved shirt, cotton/polyester trousers) and cotton underwear (long-sleeved T-shirt and long johns). Moreover all operators (except for operator E) wore a cap to determine the exposure of the head. The hands of the operators were washed after the last application (and whenever the operators wished to wash their hands) with a wash lotion and (in case of the last wash) additionally with 2-propanol. No separation into mixing/loading and application was made for body, hand and head exposure. The exposure via inhalation was measured with personal air sampling pumps (flow rate 2.0 L/min) connected to an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter. Separate sampling devices were provided for the mixing/loading and application task. The operators also received a pair of protective gloves to be worn during the whole mixing/loading period. Another pair of gloves was provided in case of handling contaminated surfaces during application. Residues of prothioconazole and prothioconazole-desthio were extracted from the collected dosimeter samples with acetonitrile and finally analysed by LC-MS/MS.

Results:

The exposure values are given in the following tables. The results for prothioconazole-desthio were calculated as prothioconazole-equivalents applying a conversion factor of 1.103 (derived from the molecular weight ratio) and added to the results for prothioconazole. Further calculations were made for the hand data; the value obtained for mixing/loading/application was split into one value for mixing/loading and one value for application according to the ratio of exposure detected on the protective gloves. Corrections for field recovery were made for prothioconazole found on glass fibre filters (field recovery: 65 %) and gloves (field recovery: 69 %). For all other matrices (clothing, hand washes) the field recovery was above 70 %. Values below the LOQ have been calculated as ½ LOQ. The results for body and head exposure are not shown since MLA data are not used in the model. Due to a visible contamination during the first mixing/loading cycle operator C received new dosimeters and continued as operator C1. The dosimeter samples from the first mixing/loading cycle were not considered.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
A	14.0	* 3.9	*** 0.265	14.601			
B	4.0	** 1.4	*** 0.009	4.264			
C ₁	6.0	** 1.4	*** 0.011	8.663			
D	13.1	** 1.4	*** 0.008	0.962			
E	5.3	** 1.4	*** 0.011	2.284			

* partly calculated with ½ LOQ ** ½ LOQ *** estimated value

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
A	14.0	* 2.2	*** n.d.	-			
B	4.0	** 1.4	*** 0.003	1.438			
C ₁	6.0	** 1.4	*** n.d.	-			
D	13.1	** 1.4	*** 0.007	0.825			
E	5.3	** 1.4	*** n.d.	-			

* partly calculated with ½ LOQ ** ½ LOQ *** estimated value n.d. – not detectable

LCTM 8

Active substance: Diclofop-methyl (378 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Winter wheat

Setting:

The study was conducted to determine the exposure of operators to diclofop-methyl while applying the herbicide at the maximum recommended rate of 3 L/ha (1.1 kg a.s./ha, diluted in ca. 100 to 200 L water/ha) in winter wheat. Twenty subjects either mixing/loading or applying according to their normal work practice were monitored in 1997/1998 at ten representative locations in the UK. A target area of 50 ha for a working day of 8 h had been defined in the study protocol; 40 to 60 ha were actually treated. The spray equipment used was typical for herbicide application and covered a range of different manufacturer types. Tank sizes ranged from 900 to 3,000 L and boom length from 12 to 24 m. Most of the sprayers were equipped with an induction hopper; if no induction hopper was existent, the product was filled into the tank by gravity. During mixing/loading each operator had to handle about 30 containers with 5 L product, but with the exception of operator 14 who conducted twelve mixing/loading cycles in 180 min three to five mixing/loading cycles in 30 to 100 min were sufficient. All vehicles were fitted with closed cabins; operators 9 and 15, however, applied with open window(s). Spraying was finished within 200 to 420 min. No cleaning was mentioned in the report.

Exposure assessment:

Each operator received clothing to determine potential and actual body exposure as well as head exposure. The clothing consisted of an outer cotton coverall with hood and a short-sleeved cotton T-shirt and a pair of long johns. Protective gloves and cotton inner gloves were provided for monitoring hand exposure. The inner and outer gloves were permanently worn by the operators doing mixing and loading, whereas only the inner gloves were permanently worn by the applicators. The air in the breathing zone of the operators was sampled with personal air samplers (flow rate 0.9 to 1.4 L/min) containing Tenax tubes. All samples were extracted with acetone and analysed by GC with ECD detection.

Results:

The results of the study are given below. No corrections were made since the mean field recoveries for the different sample matrices were between 86 and 91 %. An average breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h was used to calculate the exposure via inhalation. Due to a rather unusual exposure during an extensive repair of the sprayer, the results of operator 3 are not considered for the model. High exposure values were also observed for operator 12, who was not familiar with the sprayer type, and for operator 9, who contaminated his inner gloves while unblocking a nozzle. Nevertheless, these data were used for the model.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hood [mg]
2	56.4	13.4	1.268	1.221	-	41.055	0.501
4	47.3	23.9	0.272	87.060	0.039	10.566	0.911
6	58.6	7.6	0.602	25.762	0.046	12.518	1.898
8	51.0	10.5	13.219	66.998	0.152	45.967	3.037
10	68.0	6.9	1.805	73.804	0.239	43.598	0.985
12	45.9	14.8	23.262	1160.195	0.186	129.840	1.588
14	51.0	31.5	11.486	117.051	1.430	224.290	9.675
16	68.0	1.7	2.006	91.553	0.605	51.956	0.475
18	56.7	11.5	33.747	379.082	0.136	41.388	12.700
19	64.3	7.8	2.383	85.830	0.094	14.760	1.130

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hood [mg]
1	56.4	0.8	1.537	4.727	-	2.231	0.313
3	47.3	* 34.9	* 2.645	* 16.706	* 0.397	* 47.748	* 0.379
5	58.6	7.8	3.964	18.484	0.035	4.825	0.041
7	51.0	4.5	0.781	11.066	0.028	7.432	0.062
9	68.0	4.7	60.496	10.251	0.359	20.846	0.178
11	45.9	4.5	0.339	6.470	0.009	3.232	0.028
13	51.0	24.5	5.272	20.934	0.079	8.300	0.057
15	68.0	2.2	2.344	0.089	0.022	1.003	0.043
17	56.7	2.0	1.213	0.598	0.045	0.711	0.028
20	64.3	11.1	0.365	1.203	0.038	5.246	0.140

* value not used for model

LCTM 9

Active substance: Isoproturon (500 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Barley, wheat

Setting:

A total of 16 operators were monitored in 1997 while applying isoproturon for weed control in barley and wheat. The test sites were located in Northern France and encompassed a target area of 23 to 62 ha resembling a typical day's work. Each operator mixed and loaded the product and applied it on the field using both trailed and mounted ground boom sprayers with large tanks (2,000 to 4,000 L) and cabins. The mixing/loading step was repeated two to three times and took 20 to 94 min. In most of the cases the product was loaded on top of the tank since only two sprayers were equipped with an induction hopper. A face shield was worn during that task. Applications were made with 1.6 to 2.3 L product per ha (0.8 to 1.2 kg a.s./ha) diluted in 100 to 200 L water. Application was finished within 140 to 311 min. If necessary, the equipment was cleaned at the end of the application.

Exposure assessment:

The operators were provided with separate sets of dosimeters for mixing/loading and application. Before the start of the mixing/loading or application task the operators were dressed with the respective set on a clean area. Each set consisted of a pair of protective nitrile gloves (worn at the operators own discretion), a pair of inner cotton gloves (resembling the hand), a cap, a cotton coverall and cotton underwear (long-sleeved shirt and long johns). The inhalation exposure was measured with a GILAIR 3 personal air sampling pump connected to a filter cassette. The pump, which was used during mixing/loading and application, was calibrated to operate at a flow rate of 1 L/min. Separate filter sets were used for the different tasks. The samples were analysed for isoproturon by HPLC with UV detection after extraction with methanol and cleanup on a Florisil cartridge.

Results:

The study results are summarised in the following tables. No corrections were made for the field recovery, which was on average between 89 and 110 %. Some values were below the LOQ; for those $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ was used. The inhalation exposure refers to a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. Operator 16 had only six month of experience and got seriously contaminated during mixing/loading. He was dressed in a new coverall, which was analysed in addition to the contaminated one.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Bodyinner [mg]	Bodyouter [mg]	Cap [mg]
1	33.5	17.8	0.011	28.000	0.198	132.000	2.000
2	40.7	48.5	8.600	0.470	0.117	26.610	0.061
3	40.0	* 1.0	0.120	39.000	0.346	30.200	0.012
4	27.5	4.0	* 0.005	5.800	** 0.120	4.100	0.015
5	42.3	5.3	0.140	27.000	0.179	7.780	0.013
6	26.4	* 1.0	* 0.005	4.700	** 0.039	96.520	0.110
7	40.0	* 1.0	0.058	7.400	** 0.026	3.120	0.056
8	50.0	* 0.9	0.011	0.190	** 0.021	78.000	* 0.005
9	35.0	* 1.0	* 0.005	1.400	* 0.015	6.700	* 0.005
10	56.5	* 1.0	0.072	5.300	1.697	3.080	* 0.005
11	45.0	11.0	0.073	17.000	** 0.021	28.500	1.600
12	47.5	* 1.0	0.250	4.800	0.552	45.000	0.660
13	27.0	* 1.0	0.016	7.200	* 0.015	2.167	* 0.005
14	25.0	* 1.0	8.200	* 0.050	0.042	5.700	* 0.005
15	25.0	* 1.0	0.045	14.000	* 0.015	0.734	* 0.005
16	41.4	5.9	8.200	8.800	13.069	442.190	0.070

* $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ ** partly calculated with $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
1	33.5	5.4	10.000	20.000	** 0.157	0.549	2.300
2	40.7	16.4	0.890	-	** 0.029	1.130	0.017
3	40.0	35.3	3.500	17.000	0.091	26.000	0.037
4	27.5	* 1.0	* 0.005	3.400	* 0.015	0.660	0.015
5	42.3	4.9	45.000	0.520	** 0.525	2.670	0.250
6	26.4	10.0	0.360	4.400	0.134	7.790	0.059
7	40.0	* 1.0	0.150	-	** 0.032	0.172	* 0.005
8	50.0	* 0.9	0.210	37.000	** 0.035	0.200	0.010
9	35.0	* 1.0	0.520	-	** 0.053	0.305	* 0.005
10	56.5	5.5	3.700	-	0.162	2.640	0.087
11	45.0	6.8	0.200	1.900	** 0.047	2.920	0.099
12	47.5	3.6	4.800	* 0.050	0.116	2.480	0.017
13	27.0	9.5	0.350	-	** 0.026	0.850	0.055
14	25.0	* 1.0	1.500	-	0.046	0.968	* 0.005
15	25.0	6.0	3.600	24.000	0.048	10.640	0.016
16	41.4	6.7	5.200	18.000	0.231	6.560	0.200

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ

LCTM 10

Active substance: Prothioconazole (160 g/L; 250 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Fungicide
 Crop: Cereals, canola

Setting:

The study was designed to assess the exposure of operators towards prothioconazole and its degradation product prothioconazole-desthio while applying the fungicides with 160 g prothioconazole/L and 250 g prothioconazole/L on several fields in Germany during May and June 2006. Seven operators were used in the conduct of the study each mixing/loading and applying the product for a usual working day (at least five hours). During that day 23 to 180 ha of cereals and canola were treated with prothioconazole at a rate of 0.2 kg/ha (spray volume 200 to 300 L/ha). The equipment used ranged from sprayers for small fields (15/21 m boom, 840 to 1,500 L water tank volume) to sprayers for large fields (24/36 m boom, 2,600 to 400 L tank volume). All vehicles were equipped with a cabin, but only in four cases (operators B, C, D, H) the cabin was kept closed during application. Operator A and operator E had to leave the cabin to manually unfold and fold the boom. Three operators loaded the product (packed in 5 L containers) exclusively via an induction hopper. Mixing/loading was divided in up to 14 cycles and was completed within 56 to 182 min. Application was finished after 231 to 359 min. Cleaning of the equipment was not included in the study.

Exposure assessment:

The operators wore two layers of sampling clothing above their own underwear throughout the monitoring period. The inner layer consisted of a long-sleeved cotton T-shirt and cotton long johns and the outer layer consisted of a cotton shirt and a pair of cotton/polyester trousers. A cap should be worn for estimation of head exposure, but the operators were not forced to do it. For that reason only three operators wore a cap. Protective gloves were continuously used during mixing/loading. Another pair of protective gloves was provided if the operators would handle contaminated surfaces during application. After the last application

cycle the operators washed their hands. The hand wash water was collected and analysed. Inhalation exposure sampling was performed with personal air sampling pumps (2 L/min flow rate) connected to IOM samplers with glass fibre filters. Separate sampling devices were used for mixing/loading and application. Residues of prothioconazole and prothioconazole-desthio in the dosimeters were determined by LC-MS/MS.

Results:

The values for inhalation and hand exposure as well as for glove contamination are presented below. The exposure of the body and the head is not shown since sampling of the body and the head was not separated into mixing/loading and application. Calculations were necessary for the hand values obtained from mixing/loading/application; the values were split into one value for mixing/loading and one value for application according to the ratio of exposure detected on the protective gloves. The results of prothioconazole-desthio were calculated as prothioconazole-equivalents applying a conversion factor of 1.103 (derived from the molecular weight ratio) and added to the prothioconazole results. The mean field recovery for prothioconazole and for prothioconazole-desthio in the different sample matrices was between 85 and 120 % and 86 and 95 %. Therefore, no corrections for the field recovery were made. Values below the LOQ are given as ½ LOQ and inhalation exposure is calculated for a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
A	4.6	* 2.2	** 0.016	3.526			
B	12.8	* 2.2	** 0.031	7.947			
C	31.3	* 2.2	** 0.032	3.056			
D	12.0	* 2.2	** 0.007	0.560			
E	5.6	* 2.2	** 0.007	1.447			
F	7.1	* 2.2	** 0.011	6.236			
H	15.0	* 2.2	** 0.011	3.502			

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** estimated value

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
A	4.6	* 2.2	*** 0.001	0.287			
B	12.8	** 5.8	*** n.d.	-			
C	31.3	* 2.2	*** n.d.	-			
D	12.0	* 2.2	*** n.d.	-			
E	5.6	** 3.6	*** 0.010	1.971			
F	7.1	** 3.2	*** 1x10 ⁻⁴	0.040			
H	15.0	* 2.2	*** n.d.	-			

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ *** estimated value n.d. – not detectable

LCTM 11

Active substance: Prosulfocarb (800 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Potatoes

Setting:

The study was conducted during April and May 2009 at several potato fields in Belgium. Twelve Operators were monitored while mixing/loading and applying an herbicide containing prosulfocarb according to their usual work practice. At each site the product was applied to an area of ca. 50 ha at a rate of 5 L/ha (4 kg a.s./ha). The requested water volume was 200 L/ha; actually 115 to 400 L/ha were sprayed in the study. The operators used tractor-mounted or stand-alone ground boom spray equipment with large spray booms (27 to 39 m width) and cabins. In four cases, application was conducted with open windows. The product was packed in 20 L containers and was poured directly into the tank or was loaded by an induction hopper. Depending on the tank size the mixing/loading step was repeated two to six times. Altogether mixing/loading took between 50 to 109 min, whereas application took between 117 to 335 min. Where necessary, cleaning of the equipment was conducted and included in the monitoring.

Exposure assessment:

Each operator received a cotton coverall, a long-sleeved cotton T-shirt, cotton underpants and cotton socks. The operator got dressed in the sampling clothing at the beginning of the monitoring and wore it throughout the working day. A headband was issued by the study team as well to monitor the exposure of the head. Separate pairs of monitoring cotton gloves were used for mixing/loading and application. For each mixing/loading or application task two pairs of cotton gloves were worn – one pair beneath and one pair above protective nitrile gloves. The nitrile gloves were not sampled. GGP-U sampling heads with glass fibre filter and adsorbent tubes were used to assess the inhalation exposure. The pump operated at a flow rate of 3.5 L/min. During long breaks (> 30 min) the pump was switched off. The samples were collected and analysed for prosulfocarb by HPLC-MS after an extraction with acetonitrile (filters, tubes) or methanol (cotton clothing).

Results:

The values for hands (inner cotton gloves) and gloves (outer cotton gloves) are reported in the following tables. No corrections were made for the field recovery (mean field recovery for cotton gloves 92 to 98 %). All values were above the LOQ. The results for inhalation, head and body exposure are not given since sampling of body, head and inhalation exposure was not separated into the two tasks.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Headband [mg]
1	197.4		0.044	732.686			
2	189.8		0.013	107.401			
3	207.0		0.011	79.461			
4	205.2		0.011	800.712			
6	203.0		0.008	266.496			
7	205.5		0.005	2346.731			
8	205.0		0.152	596.860			
9	206.8		0.021	1227.478			
11	192.8		0.066	1060.351			
12	193.1		0.167	634.842			
13	205.2		1.493	184.589			
14	157.2		0.078	487.025			

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Headband [mg]
1	197.4		0.023	13.069			
2	189.8		0.019	1.441			
3	207.0		0.019	0.099			
4	205.2		0.009	0.287			
6	203.0		0.007	3.076			
7	205.5		0.008	26.414			
8	205.0		0.253	0.954			
9	206.8		0.034	28.462			
11	192.8		0.109	1.022			
12	193.1		0.177	44.786			
13	205.2		1.911	1.801			
14	157.2		0.231	24.001			

HCTM 1

Active substance: Bitertanol (500 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Insecticide
 Crop: Orchards

Setting:

The objective of this study was to provide data on the operator exposure to bitertanol during mixing/loading and application. The study was conducted in July 2002 in Italy and was designed to reflect representative conditions and work practices for the fruit growing areas in Europe. Ten subjects operating at ten different apple-growing sites were chosen for the study. The apple trees at these sites grew in rows of 1.5 to 8 m spacing and reached a height of 1.8 to 8 m. The application equipment owned by the operators consisted of trailed air blast sprayers without cabin and a tank size of 1,000 to 1,500 L. One of the vehicles had a cabin, but the windows and doors were open during application. The operators poured the product (packed in 0.5 L bottles) directly into the tank while wearing a face shield. In most cases two to four mixing/loading cycles were sufficient. The duration of the whole mixing/loading process was in a range of 24 to 43 min. The product was applied at the label recommended rate of 0.75 L/ha (0.375 kg a.s./ha) in a water volume of 388 to 1,947 L/ha. An area of 2.9 to 5.6 ha was treated during the working day and application was finished within 119 to 257 min. Cleaning was only conducted where necessary.

Exposure assessment:

The operators were dressed in outer and inner whole body dosimeters represented by cotton/polyester coveralls, long sleeved vests and long johns. Face/neck wipes were conducted at the end of the working day to assess head exposure. Caps were worn during application, but were not analysed. In addition each operator was equipped with a personal air sampling pump (flow rate: 2 L/min) connected to Tenax tubes. No separation into mixing/loading and application was made for sampling of the body, head and inhalation exposure. Hand exposure, however, was separately determined for the two tasks. After each mixing/loading or application cycle hand wash samples were taken and after completion of the whole task the protective gloves were collected as well. One pair of protective gloves each was provided by the study team for the whole mixing/loading and the application process. The gloves were worn by the operators throughout the respective task. All specimens were analysed for residues of bitertanol. The active substance was first extracted from the solid sample matrices with 2-propanol or acetonitrile and finally quantified with LC-MS/MS.

Results:

No major contamination events occurred during the field phase of the study. Thus, the exposure towards the hands was relatively low. The mean field recovery for the sample matrices was above 70 % except for the protective gloves (43 %). Since the low recovery for the gloves was ascribed to a solvent effect, no correction was made.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	1.4		0.037	1.960			
2	1.2		0.010	2.760			
3	1.2		0.080	4.410			
4	1.3		0.010	3.150			
5	1.0		0.021	2.490			
6	1.2		0.013	1.320			
7	1.9		0.004	2.760			
8	1.9		0.003	4.000			
9	1.2		0.071	1.860			
10	1.3		0.008	2.480			

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	1.4		0.034	1.140			
2	1.2		0.009	1.360			
3	1.2		0.058	2.700			
4	1.3		0.053	1.460			
5	1.0		0.013	0.803			
6	1.2		0.021	1.870			
7	1.9		0.007	2.580			
8	1.9		0.018	3.030			
9	1,2		0.034	0.056			
10	1,3		0.035	0.299			

HCTM 2

Active substance: Dodine (450 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Fungicide
 Crop: Orchards

Setting:

The exposure of 15 operators was assessed during mixing/loading and application of dodine for fungicidal control in orchards. The field phase of the study took place in July 2008 at 15 farms in the Netherlands. The treated orchards mainly consisted of apples and pears and had a size of 6 to 12 ha. Application was conducted with a broad range of trailed sprayers. In more than half of the trials a mowing machine was placed between the tractor and the sprayer. The tractors were either equipped with a closed cabin or not. All operators used spray drift reducing nozzles. For mixing and loading the operator opened one or two product containers (5 L) and poured the content into the tank. He rinsed the containers, added the required amount of water and started spraying. 1.3 to 2.3 L product (0.6 to 1.0 kg a.s./ha) was applied per hectare diluted in a water volume of about 200 L/ha. In most cases the op-

erator had to fill up the tank twice to treat the whole target area. Mixing/loading and application was completed after 124 to 402 min. If cleaning was conducted it was included in the monitoring.

Exposure assessment:

Whole body dosimeters were issued by the study team. Each operator had to wear a cotton coverall above a cotton long-sleeved shirt and cotton long underpants as well as cotton socks throughout the monitoring period. Exposure of the head was determined with a headband and an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter was used to assess the exposure via inhalation. Two pairs of cotton gloves each were worn during mixing/loading and application to determine potential and actual hand exposure. Between the two layers of cotton gloves the operators wore a further pair of nitrile gloves, which were not analysed. After all samples were collected dodine was extracted from the matrices with an acidic mixture of methanol/water and quantified by HPLC-MS/MS.

Results:

The results for the hand exposure are summarised below. The amount of dodine found on the inner cotton gloves (= hands) was below the limit of quantification. Therefore, one half of the LOQ was used for these values. A larger amount of active substance was found on the outer cotton gloves (= gloves), especially on those worn during mixing and loading. The results for inhalation, head and body exposure are not given since sampling of body, head and inhalation exposure was not separated into mixing/loading and application. The field recovery was above 70 % for all sample matrices.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Headband [mg]
1	5.7		* 0.103	131.017			
2	8.2		* 0.103	38.493			
3	9.1		* 0.103	15.457			
4	6.8		* 0.103	5.169			
5	6.8		* 0.103	6.825			
6	5.3		* 0.103	30.148			
7	3.5		* 0.051	0.216			
8	5.4		* 0.103	127.541			
10	5.2		* 0.154	27.640			
11	4.6		* 0.103	2.218			
12	6.5		* 0.103	34.844			
13	4.7		* 0.103	27.263			
14	7.9		* 0.103	9.355			
15	5.4		* 0.103	2.869			
17	4.0		* 0.103	0.561			

* ½ LOQ

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Headband [mg]
1	5.7		* 0.103	9.708			
2	8.2		* 0.103	24.455			
3	9.1		* 0.103	0.214			
4	6.8		* 0.103	0.802			
5	6.8		* 0.103	* 0.103			
6	5.3		* 0.103	0.676			
7	3.5		* 0.051	6.967			
8	5.4		* 0.103	0.448			
10	5.2		* 0.154	10.710			
11	4.6		* 0.103	10.550			
12	6.5		* 0.103	1.437			
13	4.7		* 0.103	3.233			
14	7.9		* 0.103	0.482			
15	5.4		* 0.103	0.495			
17	4.0		* 0.103	1.981			

* ½ LOQ

HCTM 3

Active substance: Methomyl (200 g/L)
 Formulation type: Soluble (liquid) concentrate
 Pesticide function: Insecticide
 Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

The study was conducted to obtain data on the exposure to methomyl while applying it to grapevines. The field phase took place at several vineyards in Southern France during July and August 2001. Twelve mixer/loaders and twelve applicators were separately monitored for a defined working day of four to eight hours. The insecticide was applied on an area of 5.2 to 8.4 ha at the maximum label rate of 2.25 L/ha (0.45 kg a.s./ha) in a water volume of 300 L/ha. Typical spray equipment was used covering a range of self-propelled mist blowers with tank sizes of 400 to 1,000 L. Up to 16 rows were simultaneously treated. Two operators (3, 7) used a tractor which was equipped with a cabin. Face shields were provided for the mixing/loading task. Mixing/loading was performed in three steps, in some cases four or more steps were necessary. The product was packed in 5 L containers and was directly poured into the tank. The duration of mixing/loading ranged from 17 to 60 min. Application was completed after 169 to 294 min. Cleaning of the equipment was not mentioned in the report.

Exposure assessment:

Dermal exposure of the mixer/loaders and applicators was measured by using whole body dosimeters consisting of a long-sleeved T-shirt and long johns as inner layer and a cotton coverall as outer layer. Gloves worn during mixing/loading and for maintenance tasks during application as well as hand washes conducted after the final mixing/loading or application cycle were analysed to quantify hand exposure. For assessing head exposure the face and neck of the operators were wiped twice after completion of their work. Inhalation exposure was determined from residues collected by an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter attached to a personal air pump located in the breathing zone of the operator (flow rate ca. 2 L/min). The

analysis of methomyl was performed by HPLC with post-column derivatisation and fluorescence detection.

Results:

The results are given in the following tables. Values below the LOQ have been calculated with 50 % of the LOQ. No correction for the field recovery was made since the mean field recovery was above 70 % for all matrices. The value for inhalation exposure refers to an average breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. Operator 10 wore a helmet during application. The helmet was analysed as well and the amount of active substance found was added to the result of the face/neck wipe.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
2	2.7	* 5.2	0.004	18.000	** 0.005	4.393	* 0.001
4	2.4	* 5.2	0.026	42.000	0.017	4.050	* 0.001
6	2.7	* 5.2	0.450	32.000	0.055	19.420	0.004
8	3.0	* 5.2	0.004	1.500	* 0.002	** 0.795	* 0.001
9	3.4	* 5.2	0.007	12.000	0.015	1.930	0.003
12	3.6	* 5.2	0.090	46.000	0.014	2.871	0.005
14	3.6	* 5.2	0.003	3.900	0.006	0.658	* 0.001
16	3.6	* 5.2	0.037	32.000	0.021	94.320	* 0.001
18	3.2	* 5.2	0.009	49.000	0.009	2.089	0.005
19	3.6	* 5.2	0.670	96.000	0.152	4.940	0.029
22	3.0	10.4	0.006	22.000	** 0.004	1.939	* 0.001
24	3.8	10.4	0.021	19.000	0.077	2.900	* 0.001

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Bodyinner [mg]	Bodyouter [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	2.7	54.2	0.300	0.640	0.102	5.150	0.023
3	2.4	28.1	0.110	0.032	0.015	0.664	* 0.001
5	2.7	33.3	6.400	0.410	0.100	8.010	0.017
7	3.0	* 5.2	0.011	0.032	** 0.004	0.064	* 0.001
10	3.4	166.7	0.260	0.660	0.154	8.000	*** 0.024
11	3.6	270.8	1.100	2.800	0.217	24.000	0.028
13	3.6	93.8	0.680	2.500	0.262	17.300	0.024
15	3.6	416.7	1.400	3.300	0.379	29.100	0.020
17	3.2	260.4	0.810	4.900	0.229	22.850	0.058
20	3.6	135.4	0.320	8.700	0.246	10.960	0.008
21	3.0	218.8	0.560	3.600	0.440	17.200	0.047
23	3.8	114.6	0.460	0.098	0.098	12.350	0.007

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ *** including helmet worn during application

HCTM 4

Active substance: Dinocap (350 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Fungicide
 Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

Twelve operators were monitored during application of the fungicide to grapevine at several sites in France in 1995. Mixing/loading as well as cleaning was not included in the study. The operators used trailed air blast sprayers (600 to 800 L tank volume) with up to ten spray cannons (front or rear) and treated an area of 5.3 to 11.4 ha within three to four hours. The tractors used were not equipped with a cabin. In most trials four rows were sprayed at the same time. The product was applied at a rate of about 0.6 L per ha (0.2 kg a.s./ha) diluted in a water volume of ca. 200 to 230 L. Application was conducted in two spraying sessions. Two operators (11, 12) performed a routine check during application including removal, inspection and replacement of all easily accessible sprayer filters.

Exposure assessment:

To assess outer and inner body exposure the operators were provided with cotton coveralls as well as cotton long sleeved T-shirts and cotton trousers worn underneath the coverall. The hood of the coverall was sampled to determine the head exposure. Protective gloves worn by the operators throughout the application task were analysed for potential hand exposure. The actual hand exposure was quantified by sampling cotton gloves worn underneath the protective gloves. Inhalation exposure was assessed by using personal air samplers with glass fibre filters operating at a flow rate of 2 L/min. The samples were extracted with a mixture of dichloromethane and pentane. After a clean up the extract was methylated with diazomethane and analysed by gas chromatography.

Results:

The exposure determined for application is given below. The field recovery for the nitrile gloves was on average 34 %, which was explained by loss of substance from the glove surface. Since the procedural recovery was above 70 %, no correction was made. All values were above the LOQ. Inhalation was recalculated assuming a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hood [mg]
1	2.2	106.3	0.023	0.559	0.061	1.802	0.193
2	1.7	39.6	0.004	0.644	0.063	2.922	0.272
3	1.5	18.8	0.010	0.792	0.057	8.262	1.296
4	1.8	38.5	0.009	0.785	0.026	5.688	0.942
5	1.6	53.1	0.009	0.242	0.035	1.245	0.246
7	2.2	19.8	0.007	0.276	0.018	3.985	0.431
8	1.3	14.6	0.016	0.711	0.042	9.267	0.812
9	1.8	34.4	0.006	0.058	0.033	0.671	0.076
10	2.3	25.0	0.005	0.505	0.018	2.042	0.427
11	1.2	21.9	0.013	0.744	0.031	0.589	0.064
12	1.1	19.8	0.005	0.959	0.032	0.752	0.103
13	1.2	28.1	0.004	0.905	0.028	18.037	1.767

HCTM 5

Active substance: Metiram (700 g/kg)
Formulation type: Water dispersible granules
Pesticide function: Fungicide
Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

The study was conducted during July 2002 to assess data on the exposure of 27 operators either mixing/loading or applying metiram during a typical work day. Twelve farms in Germany were chosen, which reflected typical conditions for fungicide application in vineyards using water rates between 300 to 900 L/ha. The product was applied at a rate of 2.0 to 3.0 kg/ha (1.4 to 2.1 kg a.s./ha) on an area ranging from 3.0 to 14.6 ha. In each trial one operator doing mixing/loading and one or two operators doing application were monitored. The product (packed in 10 kg packages) was mixed with water in a large mixing-tank or directly loaded into the spray tank. Mixing/loading was repeated two to six times; the average duration for the complete task was 74 min. Application was conducted with air blast sprayers (tank volume 400 to 1100 L), which, in most of the cases, were equipped with a cabin. Only four operators sprayed without a cabin (2A, 2B, 7A, 9B), whereas five operators applied the product at least for some time with one or more windows of the cabin open (1B, 4A, 5A, 6A, 8A). Spraying was completed within 130 to 450 min. After finishing application the spray equipment was cleaned if the equipment was not used for the same treatment next day.

Exposure assessment:

Each operator wore two layers of standardised clothing for body sampling. The outer body dosimeter consisted of a polyester/cotton long sleeved shirt/jacket and trousers, the inner body dosimeter consisted of a long sleeved T-shirt and long johns. Head exposure was determined by face/neck wipes conducted at the end of the mixing/loading or application task. Protective gloves used throughout mixing/loading or for maintenance work during application as well as hand wash samples taken at times when the operator would usually wash his hands were analysed to quantify potential and actual hand exposure. Potential inhalation exposure was assessed by using an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter attached to a personal air pump located in the breathing zone of the operator (flow rate ca. 2 L/min). For analysis the sample material was treated with EDTA to release the ethylene-bisdithiocarbamate (EBDC) ligand, which was quantified by HPLC with electrochemical detection after performing a reversed phase chromatography.

Results:

The study results are summarised in the following tables. All values had to be adjusted for the respective field recovery, which was on average between 31 % and 64 %. The LOQ was not given in the study report, but all values were above the LOQ. The inhalation exposure refers to a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. High exposure values for application were measured in those cases where the vehicles were not equipped with a cabin or the cabin was left open. Overfilling of the tank was reported for operator 14M who had a high overall exposure from mixing/loading.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1M	35.5	19.4	0.160	1.583	0.230	11.698	0.030
2M	37.8	16.3	0.020	0.608	0.465	7.389	0.028
3M	17.5	89.8	0.150	12.608	1.491	20.261	0.140
4M	12.3	61.5	0.070	1.014	0.130	4.579	0.073
5M	17.5	105.0	0.008	0.472	0.580	15.216	0.072
6M	7.0	32.2	0.002	6.526	0.104	28.180	0.010
7M	13.5	9.6	0.008	1.200	0.104	1.738	0.021
8M	15.8	34.7	0.012	0.063	0.213	2.479	0.015
9M	21.0	23.9	0.015	1.329	1.307	8.544	0.014
10M	7.0	10.4	0.004	2.145	0.037	3.025	0.006
11M	19.8	33.4	0.026	0.504	0.080	2.559	0.040
14M	16.8	211.8	0.038	1.034	0.530	66.780	0.361

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1A	18.4	16.8	0.233	5.303	0.248	5.105	0.017
1B	15.8	41.8	1.134	5.487	2.533	129.039	0.104
2A	7.1	219.6	1.219	-	1.604	52.687	0.326
2B	30.7	441.6	6.765	-	2.183	97.723	0.873
3A	17.5	117.4	0.512	0.196	1.393	8.849	0.032
4A	12.3	2.8	0.001	0.314	0.007	0.462	0.009
5A	17.5	626.6	2.170	130.142	3.291	52.992	0.806
6A	5.3	0.5	0.010	-	0.026	0.513	n.d.
7A	10.0	34.8	1.819	-	0.709	65.125	0.261
8A	13.7	182.0	0.272	-	0.928	15.556	0.049
9A	5.5	22.1	0.151	0.035	0.480	17.526	0.004
9B	9.8	131.2	0.078	3.399	0.926	61.951	0.211
10A	7.0	12.2	0.182	0.077	0.107	4.111	0.010
11A	10.0	15.6	0.035	0.176	0.102	0.656	0.007
14A	12.9	30.3	0.345	0.047	0.811	33.170	0.021

HCTM 6

Active substance: Phosalone (500 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Insecticide
 Crop: Orchards

Setting:

The objective of this study was to obtain operator exposure data for the application of an insecticide in orchards. The field phase of the study took place during July and August 1996 at 17 farms in France. At each farm one operator was monitored during a normal working day including the mixing/loading task as well as the application task. The operators worked with their own equipment according to their usual practice. Most of the sprayers used were of the jet spray type operating at a pressure of ten to 20 bars. Cabins were present on six vehicles (operator 9 and operators 13 to 17). Mixing/loading was mainly performed in three to five

cycles and was finished after 15 to 79 min. The product was packed in 5 L containers and was directly poured into the tank (1,000 to 3,000 L). A total of 5 to 17 ha were treated with the insecticide at a rate of 0.7 to 1.4 L/ha (0.4 to 0.8 kg a.s./ha) in a water volume of 400 to 1,200 L/ha. After 217 to 671 min spraying was completed. The cultures treated were mainly apple trees of up to 6 m height growing in rows of 4 m distance. Cleaning was reported for six operators (exposure included in application).

Exposure assessment:

The operator exposure was assessed with two different sets of whole body dosimeters, one set for mixing/loading and one set for application. After completion of a mixing/loading or application cycle the sets were changed and stored in a clean area during the time they were not used. Each set consisted of a cotton hat, cotton work suit, a pair of cotton gloves and a pair of protective nitrile gloves. The use of the nitrile gloves was left to the discretion of the operators. For the determination of the 'inner' body exposure undergarment was provided by the study team at the beginning of the trial, but was worn throughout mixing/loading and application. Exposure via inhalation was measured by a filter cassette connected to a personal air sampling pump (flow rate: 1 L/min). The pump was fitted with different filters for each task. At the end of the trials the samples were collected and analysed. The amount of active substance on the samples was determined by gas-liquid chromatography after an extraction with acetone.

Results:

The results for mixing/loading and application are given below. Values below the LOQ are stated as $\frac{1}{2}$ of the LOQ. No correction for the field recovery was made, since the field recovery for the different sample matrices was on average between 76 % and 100 %. Inhalation exposure was recalculated using a generic respiration rate of 1.25 m³/h. In some cases (operator 6, operator 9) the air sampling pump was not turned on at the beginning of the task. Extrapolation of the value to the whole working time was, however, only done, if the work duration without air sampling was short (< 30 % of total working time). If not, the value was not used for the model. Further calculations were necessary for the undergarment. The data representing exposure during mixing/loading/application were split into values for mixing/loading and values for application according to the ratio of exposure detected on the overall (outer body). Except for operator 6 and operator 17 all monitored persons wore gloves during the whole mixing/loading task resulting in a lower exposure of the hands. During application only seven operators (2, 4, 8, 11 to 14) continuously wore gloves. A major contamination was reported for operator 2 and operator 8, who had a high exposure of the body during mixing/loading.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Bodyinner [mg]	Bodyouter [mg]	Hat [mg]
1	4.5	* 1.0	0.170	8.500	**** 0.017	5.060	0.080
2	3.6	* 1.0	0.210	7.600	**** 0.912	117.690	0.070
3	3.6	6.3	0.340	11.300	**** 0.076	22.220	0.040
4	5.0	31.3	0.010	2.000	**** 0.082	10.070	0.120
5	2.4	10.4	0.090	10.200	**** 0.154	92.730	0.200
6	7.2	** 31.3	8.230	0.800	**** 0.372	28.220	0.010
7	8.0	145.8	0.360	6.200	**** 0.041	2.720	0.260
8	6.3	4.2	0.060	30.900	**** 3.403	159.010	2.320
9	6.7	*** 1.3	0.610	10.300	**** 2.206	14.190	-
10	10.0	10.4	0.180	28.300	**** 0.250	17.750	0.010
11	6.3	14.6	0.250	19.400	**** 0.160	32.300	0.020
12	6.0	12.5	0.100	5.800	**** 0.004	0.470	0.180
13	3.8	* 1.0	0.090	4.100	**** 0.084	6.450	0.130
14	5.0	31.3	0.090	6.500	**** 0.028	2.060	0.150
15	3.6	* 1.0	0.130	18.500	**** 0.022	4.540	0.010
16	5.4	10.4	0.030	1.900	**** 0.047	1.000	0.010
17	3.8	4.2	10.590	-	**** 0.022	2.210	0.010

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** not used for model (pump not on during first two cycles) *** extrapolated (air sampling pump was not on during first ML cycle) **** estimated value

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hat [mg]
1	4.5	72.9	9.660	-	*** 0.793	230.580	8.280
2	3.6	50.0	9.080	88.900	*** 0.398	51.320	6.590
3	3.6	56.3	66.920	-	*** 1.474	431.470	36.320
4	5.0	35.4	3.850	5.600	*** 0.278	33.960	1.620
5	2.4	33.3	6.260	-	*** 0.426	257.090	43.930
6	7.2	** 16.7	6.620	3.200	*** 0.828	62.750	6.140
7	8.0	23614.6	0.220	0.600	*** 0.929	61.230	2.410
8	6.3	45.8	0.180	38.800	*** 4.017	187.680	22.210
9	6.7	12.5	0.610	2.300	*** 0.844	5.430	-
10	10.0	54.2	28.240	-	*** 1.070	76.030	5.790
11	6.3	16.7	3.530	6.200	*** 0.250	50.400	3.790
12	6.0	31.3	0.260	12.100	*** 0.796	95.430	10.660
13	3.8	12.5	2.860	1.700	*** 0.156	11.990	1.700
14	5.0	12.5	0.380	5.200	*** 0.112	8.100	0.240
15	3.6	20.8	6.800	-	*** 0.188	38.100	0.350
16	5.4	4.2	0.190	-	*** 0.013	0.280	0.020
17	3.8	12.5	3.300	-	*** 0.218	21.960	0.110

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** not used for model (pump not on during first two cycles) *** estimated value

HCTM 7

Active substance: Tolyfluanid (500 g/kg)
Formulation type: Water dispersible granules
Pesticide function: Fungicide
Crop: Orchards

Setting:

A total of twelve operators were monitored in August 2000 at several farms in the Netherlands, Belgium and Germany to obtain data on the exposure from mixing/loading and application of a fungicide to pome fruits. The operators, both mixing/loading and applying the product, were working for a typical working day in professional fruit plantations (tree height: 2 to 4 m, row distance: 2.8 to 3.5 m) using different types of trailed air blast sprayers (tank size: 600 to 1,500 L). All tractors were equipped with a closed cabin; however, in three cases (operator G, K and L) the window/door of the cabin was (temporarily) open during spraying. For preparation of the spray solution the operators opened the product bags (5 kg bags) and added an appropriate amount of product to the tank, which was finally filled up with water. The mixing/loading step had to be at least repeated twice and was completed within 24 to 64 min. During application an area of 6.5 to 12 ha was treated. The operators applied the product at a rate of 1.0 to 2.3 kg/ha (0.5 to 1.2 kg a.s./ha) diluted in water volume of 150 to 640 L water/ha. After 3½ to 6 h spraying was finished. Cleaning was included in the monitoring, but was actually reported for only three operators (operators F to H).

Exposure assessment:

All operators were dressed in sampling clothing consisting of a hat, long cotton underpants, a long-sleeved cotton T-shirt and a long-sleeved cotton shirt plus long work trousers worn above the underpants and the T-shirt. During mixing/loading the operators also wore a work jacket, which they took off for application. The whole clothing was not changed until the end of the trial. In addition to the clothing every operator was provided with protective nitrile gloves, one pair of gloves for mixing/loading (continuously worn) and one pair of gloves for application (worn for maintenance work). Most of the operators rinsed their mixing/loading gloves with running water before they took them off. At the end of the trials the hands of the operators were rinsed with 2-propanol. The rinsing of both hands were collected and analysed for the actual hand exposure. Inhalation exposure sampling was performed by use of a personal air sampling pump connected to an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter and a Tenax adsorbent tube. Different sets of filters and tubes were used for mixing/loading and application. Prior to use the pumps were calibrated to operate at a flow rate of 2 L/min. Residues of the active substance tolyfluanid and its degradation product DMST were extracted from the samples and quantified by liquid chromatography using MS/MS-detection.

Results:

The exposure data for inhalation as well as for the hands and gloves are presented below. No separate values exist for the body and head exposure with respect to mixing/loading and application. The separate mixing/loading and application values for the hand exposure given in the table are calculated from mixing/loading/application data by using the ratio of exposure detected on the protective gloves. Results for DMST were calculated as tolyfluanid equivalents by multiplication with the molar ratio factor of 1.62 and added to the results for tolyfluanid. The field recovery was above 70 % for all matrices except for the nitrile gloves (mean field recovery 48 %, due to a solvent effect) and the Tenax tubes (no field recovery data). No correction for the field recovery was made. Values below the LOQ were calculated with ½ of the LOQ. Inhalation exposure refers to a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hat [mg]
A	4.0	24.6	** 0.003	0.283			
B	8.0	1.8	** 0.064	0.326			
C	7.5	* 42.7	** 0.009	1.209			
D	4.5	* 8.3	** 0.015	2.142			
E	7.5	* 24.8	** 0.948	1.204			
F	8.0	* 106.3	** 0.147	1.030			
G	13.5	187.5	** 0.099	4.257			
H	10.0	132.3	** 0.024	2.022			
I	7.5	* 3.9	** 0.024	0.244			
J	3.8	* 44.9	** 0.006	1.757			
K	6.0	63.6	** 0.086	3.523			
L	4.8	* 45.1	** 0.008	0.583			

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** estimated value

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Hat [mg]
A	4.0	* 4.8	** 0.043	4.475			
B	7.6	* 3.4	** n.d.	-			
C	7.5	* 5.1	** 0.222	29.709			
D	4.5	* 2.5	** 0.001	0.180			
E	7.5	* 0.9	** n.d.	-			
F	8.0	* 2.2	** 0.003	0.019			
G	13.5	* 4.4	** 3x10 ⁻⁴	0.013			
H	10.0	* 2.5	** 0.007	0.568			
I	7.5	* 0.8	** 0.018	0.188			
J	3.8	* 0.9	** n.d.	-			
K	4.3	* 14.5	** 0.001	0.025			
L	4.8	18.1	** n.d.	-			

* calculated with ½ LOQ ** estimated value

HCTM 8

Active substance: Iprovalicarb (90 g/kg)
 Formulation type: Water dispersible granules
 Pesticide function: Fungicide
 Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

The dermal and inhalation exposure of operators towards iprovalicarb during application of a fungicide in grapevine was assessed in this study. Sixteen applicators were monitored at different representative vineyards in the major grape production areas of France during June 2005. Mixing and loading were not part of the study and were conducted by the study team or farm workers not involved in the study. The area treated was in the range of 5.3 to 20.0 ha corresponding to a typical working day. Application was performed as closely as possible to normal practice using diverse spray equipment with or without a cabin. Seven operators

sprayed while sitting in a completely closed cabin whereas five operators sprayed without a cabin. The fungicidal product was applied at a rate of 0.7 to 1.4 kg/ha (0.06 to 0.13 kg a.s./ha) in a water volume of 80 to 367 L/ha. After 220 to 620 min application was finished. Cleaning was included in the monitoring when it was part of the operator's usual daily routine. Actually, six operators did a monitored cleaning of the equipment (rinsing sprayer outside and tank inside).

Exposure assessment:

Dermal exposure of the operators was determined by using whole body dosimeters consisting of a long-sleeved vest and long johns (inner layer of clothing) and long work trousers and a long-sleeved jacket/shirt (outer layer of clothing). For the cleaning activities the operators wore a Tyvek coverall instead of the outer body dosimeter. Face/neck wipe samples were collected when requested by the operator and at the end of the trial to assess head exposure. Gloves (if used for maintenance tasks) as well as hand washes conducted when requested by the operator and at the end of the trial were analysed to quantify hand exposure. Inhalation exposure was calculated from residues collected by an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter attached to a personal air pump located in the breathing zone of the operator (flow rate ca. 2 L/min). The analysis of iprovalicarb residues was performed with HPLC-MS/MS after extraction with 2-propanol.

Results:

The results of the study are given below. The mean field recovery for all sample matrices was between 83 to 108 %. Values below the LOQ were calculated with $\frac{1}{2}$ of the LOQ and inhalation exposure has been recalculated for a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. The results for the Tyvek coverall (cleaning) were added to the outer sampling clothing.

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	1.6	29.1	0.373	2.280	0.117	12.964	0.011
2	1.3	26.7	0.127	1.528	0.119	0.867	0.002
3	1.5	69.1	0.408	0.450	0.045	3.411	0.005
4	1.6	3.4	0.032	0.477	0.009	0.803	0.001
5	1.2	12.3	1.723	0.644	0.022	0.602	0.003
6	0.8	0.6	0.011	0.667	0.003	0.116	4x10 ⁻⁴
7	0.9	20.9	2.973	-	0.079	7.411	0.012
8	0.9	9.1	1.349	0.934	0.173	8.107	0.071
9	1.4	18.4	0.169	1.202	0.038	4.085	0.027
10	0.8	56.4	0.013	3.542	0.169	8.759	0.027
11	1.2	0.5	0.020	0.161	* 0.003	0.676	0.002
12	0.9	9.0	0.066	0.596	0.014	0.879	0.002
13	2.2	2.2	2.083	2.531	0.021	0.144	0.005
14	1.8	5.2	0.189	1.986	0.070	1.295	0.004
15	1.2	46.3	0.614	0.080	0.094	* 1.992	0.014
16	0.9	23.8	0.366	1.895	0.082	4.927	0.005

* partly calculated with $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ

LCHH 1

Active substance: Azafenidin (800 g/kg)
 Formulation type: Water dispersible granules
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

The exposure of 20 operators applying azafenidin for herbicidal control in vineyards at several sites in France in 2000 was determined in this study. Ten operators were monitored while conducting mixing and loading and 10 operators were monitored while spraying the spray solution. Cleanout of the spray tank was included in the application task. The operators were requested to treat an area of 0.5 to 1.0 ha during a usual working day of 2 to 4 h and used typical hand-held spray equipment (knapsack sprayers) with either protected or unprotected lances. Mixing/loading was completed within 18 to 80 min and application within 92 to 169 min. During mixing/loading all operators wore a face shield. The product (0.3 kg bag) was directly loaded into the tank except for operator 20 who prepared a pre-mix in a large vessel and used it to refill the sprayer when empty. Overall five to ten mixing/loading steps were necessary. The product was sprayed at the highest recommended rate of 0.3 kg/ha (0.24 kg a.s./ha) in a water volume of 200 L/ha.

Exposure assessment:

All operators were dressed in body dosimeters consisting of an inner layer of clothing (polyester/viscose T-shirt plus long johns) and an outer layer of clothing (cotton coverall). In addition to that, each operator wore protective nitrile gloves for the duration of the working task. Hand washes and face/neck wipes were collected at the end of the mixing/loading or application task to assess the actual hand and head exposure. Inhalation exposure was determined with IOM samplers with glass fibre filter. The personal air sampling pump operated at a flow rate of 2 L/min. The determination of azafenidin was carried by extraction into methanol followed by detection with HPLC-UV or LC-MS.

Results:

The following tables summarise the results of the study. The exposure from inhalation and the head exposure were generally low with most of the values below the limit of quantification (reported as ½ LOQ). The mean field recovery was in a range of 72 to 97 %; hence, no corrections were made. Inhalation exposure was recalculated using a generic respiration rate of 1.25 m³/h. The exposure data of operator 7 are not considered for the model. The trial had to be restarted after a defect of the sprayer and only the dosimeters of the second part were analysed. Operator 17 sprayed tall weed, this might explain the high amount of active substance found on the legs of his coverall.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
2	0.1	* 5.2	* 0.002	0.519	* 0.002	** 0.032	* 0.002
4	0.1	n.d.	n.d.	0.166	0.038	** 0.054	n.d.
6	0.1	n.d.	0.006	0.638	n.d.	0.163	* 0.002
8	0.1	n.d.	* 0.002	0.595	n.d.	** 0.071	* 0.002
10	0.1	n.d.	0.007	0.350	* 0.001	0.367	* 0.002
12	0.1	* 5.2	0.018	3.598	0.010	0.905	* 0.002
14	0.1	n.d.	* 0.002	0.449	0.006	0.855	n.d.
16	0.1	n.d.	0.009	0.194	n.d.	1.084	n.d.
18	0.1	* 5.2	0.005	0.721	0.006	0.046	n.d.
20	0.1	n.d.	0.131	2.638	0.169	8.919	* 0.002

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½

Application

	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	0.1	n.d.	* 0.002	0.156	** 0.010	5.307	* 0.002
3	0.1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.036	** 0.231	n.d.
5	0.1	n.d.	n.d.	0.149	0.003	3.320	* 0.002
*** 7	0.1	n.d.	* 0.002	1.126	0.020	3.083	* 0.002
9	0.1	n.d.	n.d.	0.120	0.013	4.102	* 0.002
11	0.1	* 5.2	0.022	1.761	0.071	12.596	* 0.002
13	0.1	n.d.	0.004	0.181	0.075	6.532	* 0.002
15	0.1	* 5.2	* 0.002	0.942	0.089	4.398	n.d.
17	0.1	* 5.2	n.d.	0.218	0.233	72.987	* 0.002
19	0.1	n.d.	0.012	0.491	0.260	13.804	0.008

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ *** not used for model

LCHH 2

Active substance: Simazine (500 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Stubble field

Setting:

Ten operators were monitored while applying the herbicidal substance simazine with commercial knapsack sprayers according to the product label recommendations. The field phase of the study took place in October 1994 in the UK. In each trial 0.8 to 1.0 ha of stubble field were treated with the herbicide at a rate of 3 L product/ha (1.5 kg a.s./ha) and a water volume of 200 L/ha. Each operator performed the mixing/loading as well as the application task including cleaning. Mixing/loading was performed in eight to ten cycles and was finished within 17 to approximately 130 min. Spraying was completed after 140 to approximately 220 min.

Exposure assessment:

The body exposure was determined with two layers of sampling clothing. The inner layer consisted of a cotton long-sleeved undershirt and undertrousers and the outer layer was represented by a cotton coverall. Both layers of clothing were worn during mixing/loading and during application. Head exposure was calculated from residues collected on a cap which was also worn during the whole working day. Inhalation exposure and hand exposure were separately assessed for both tasks. At the beginning of each mixing/loading or application cycle the operators got a new pair of nitrile gloves (outer gloves) and cotton gloves (inner gloves), which they wore throughout the working task. A separate set of inner and outer gloves was also used for cleaning. Inhalation exposure was determined from residues collected on a face shield, but with respect to the sampling method the results were not considered for the model. Residues of simazine were extracted from the samples with methanol and quantified by GLC.

Results:

The results for the hands (= inner cotton gloves) and gloves (= outer nitrile gloves) are given below; the results for the body exposure and the hat are not shown, since no separate data exist for mixing/loading and application. In case that the values were below the LOQ they were calculated with ½ of the LOQ. No field recovery for the cotton gloves or nitrile gloves was given in the study report. The procedural recovery, however, was above 70 %. The results for application include the data obtained for cleaning.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
AA	1.5		* 0.003	0.631			
AB	1.5		* 0.003	0.873			
AC	1.5		0.005	9.490			
AD	1.5		* 0.003	0.268			
AE	1.5		0.005	2.892			
AF	1.5		0.048	0.979			
*** AG	1.4		** 0.009	0.351			
AH	1.2		* 0.003	0.887			
AI	1.4		0.008	1.110			
AJ	1.2		0.005	0.715			

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ *** not used for model

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Cap [mg]
AA	1.5		* 0.005	* 0.100			
AB	1.5		* 0.005	0.210			
AC	1.5		0.064	0.310			
AD	1.5		* 0.005	** 0.212			
AE	1.5		** 0.008	0.640			
AF	1.5		0.011	** 0.428			
*** AG	1.4		0.005	0.100			
AH	1.2		* 0.003	0.104			
AI	1.4		0.005	0.100			
AJ	1.2		0.010	0.100			

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ *** not used for model

LC_{HH} 3

Active substance: Fluazifop-P-butyl (125 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

The exposure of 15 mixer/loaders and 15 applicators applying fluazifop-P-butyl for inter-row weed control at several sites in Portugal during March 2002 was recorded in this study. The farms were located in the Torres Vedres region and were chosen to cover a range of representative working conditions for vine growers. Application (spot spraying as well as broadcast application) was monitored for a typical working day and was conducted with hydraulically operated knapsack sprayers with flat-fan nozzles. The product was supplied in 1 L containers and was directly poured into the tanks of the knapsack sprayers. In each trial, which consisted of eight or nine tank mix preparations and eight or nine spraying operations, one mixer/loader and one applicator worked together as a pair. All mixer/loaders used a face shield during their work. The whole mixing/loading process was finished after 26 to 44 min. Application was performed for 131 to 246 min; in that time an area of 0.5 to 1.1 ha was treated. The product was used at a rate of 1.7 to 3.5 L/ha (target rate: 3 L/ha) in a water volume of 113 to 211 L/ha. At the end of the working day the applicators cleaned their equipment. The cleaning procedure was included in the monitoring of the application task.

Exposure assessment:

Operator exposure was determined by passive dosimetry using whole body dosimeters. The operators were provided with an inner dosimeter consisting of a short-sleeved cotton T-shirt and briefs and an outer dosimeter consisting of a polyester/cotton coverall. The exposure to the head was determined from face/neck wipe specimen taken whenever the operator wished to wash his face and at the end of the monitored procedure. Face shields were mostly worn during mixing/loading, but were not taken for analysis. Protective nitrile gloves used during mixing/loading or during application were sampled to measure potential hand exposure. Actual hand exposure was assessed with hand washes also taken whenever the operator wished to wash his hands and at the end of the monitored procedure. Glass fibre filters were collected from IOM samplers (pump flow rate: ca. 2 L/min) after the operators had finished their task to determine the exposure via inhalation. Besides passive dosimetry operator exposure was also assessed with biomonitoring (results not used for model). The samples were analysed for residues of the active substance by extraction in acetonitrile followed by detection with GC-MS.

Results:

The results from passive dosimetry are summarised in the following tables. The actual exposure to the legs and lower arms was estimated from the respective outer exposure based on the permeation values of the torso and is included in the 'inner' body exposure. The hand wash data were corrected for recovery, since the field recovery was below 70 % (24 % at the low and 35 % at the high fortification level). All air filter and face/neck wipe specimens were found to be below the LOQ. The respective values are reported as ½ of the LOQ. Inhalation exposure refers to a respiration rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
2	0.2	* 26.0	* 0.003	5.174	** 0.082	** 0.278	* 0.003
3	0.2	* 26.0	0.022	5.125	** 0.059	** 0.771	* 0.003
4	0.2	* 26.0	0.150	11.110	** 0.025	** 0.209	* 0.003
5	0.2	* 26.0	** 0.164	5.557	** 0.012	0.622	* 0.003
7	0.2	* 25.4	0.140	6.222	** 0.012	0.531	** 0.008
8	0.2	* 23.7	* 0.003	13.650	** 0.029	2.758	* 0.003
9	0.2	* 26.7	0.145	9.244	** 0.013	** 0.365	* 0.003
10	0.2	* 26.0	0.124	3.837	** 0.010	** 0.110	0.010
11	0.2	* 25.4	0.340	6.985	** 0.023	** 0.376	* 0.003
12	0.2	* 26.0	0.165	2.341	** 0.052	** 0.097	0.006
13	0.2	* 26.0	* 0.005	3.847	** 0.016	* 0.015	* 0.003
14	0.2	* 26.0	0.046	3.692	** 0.012	** 0.853	* 0.003
15	0.2	* 24.2	* 0.003	2.685	** 0.103	** 0.240	* 0.003
16	0.2	* 26.0	0.123	9.909	** 0.017	0.704	* 0.003
17	0.2	* 23.7	* 0.003	25.480	** 0.061	** 0.913	* 0.003

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ

Application

Operator	TA [kg]	a.s.	Inhalation [μ g]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Bodyinner [mg]	Bodyouter [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
19		0.2	* 26.0	* 0.003	2.494	** 2.341	70.059	* 0.003
20		0.2	* 26.0	0.111	4.102	** 1.244	28.189	* 0.003
21		0.2	* 24.8	0.480	-	40.254	63.459	* 0.003
22		0.2	* 26.7	*** 1.259	-	** 0.974	42.362	* 0.003
23		0.2	* 26.0	2.397	-	62.630	74.377	* 0.003
24		0.2	* 26.0	1.106	-	** 37.405	75.172	* 0.003
25		0.2	* 26.0	0.859	-	70.260	92.602	* 0.003
26		0.2	* 26.0	0.228	-	** 1.695	31.749	* 0.003
27		0.2	* 26.0	0.520	-	17.159	80.062	* 0.003
28		0.2	* 23.7	2.013	-	** 0.879	19.300	* 0.003
29		0.2	* 26.0	0.362	-	7.326	65.438	* 0.003
30		0.2	* 26.0	1.544	-	5.491	47.339	* 0.003
31		0.2	* 24.8	0.302	-	** 1.425	40.329	* 0.003
32		0.2	* 26.0	0.410	-	** 1.846	36.214	* 0.003
33		0.2	* 26.0	0.405	-	24.404	96.582	* 0.003

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ *** exposure of one hand only

LCHH 4

Active substance: Fluazifop-P-butyl (125 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Herbicide
 Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

The objective of the study was to obtain data for the dermal and inhalation exposure of operators who mixed/loaded or applied fluazifop-P-butyl to weeds growing in vine by using knapsack spray equipment. The field phase of the study took place in March 2003 at several sites in the Douro region of Portugal. The operators worked in pairs of one mixer/loader and one applicator each. Application (spot spraying as well as broadcast application) was monitored for a typical working day and was conducted with hydraulically operated knapsack sprayers with flat-fan nozzles. The product was supplied in 1 L containers and was directly filled into the tanks without pre-mixing. Mixing and loading was repeated seven to eight times and was completed after 20 to 32 min. The product was sprayed over an area of 0.5 to 0.8 ha at a mean rate of 3 L/ha (0.4 kg a.s./ha) in 146 to 250 L water per ha. Application was finished within 141 to 260 min and included the cleaning of the sprayer.

Exposure assessment:

To measure potential and actual dermal exposure the mixer/loaders and the applicators wore two layers of sampling clothing. The outer layer consisted of a polyester/cotton coverall and the inner layer consisted of a short-sleeved cotton T-shirt and briefs. Exposure to the hands was determined by collecting hand wash specimens whenever the operators wished to wash their hands and at the end of the operation. Protective nitrile gloves used during the mixing/loading procedure were analysed as well. Actual exposure to the head was measured by wiping the operators face and neck. Face shields were mostly worn during mixing/loading but were not included in the analysis. Inhalation exposure was determined from residues collected by an IOM sampler with glass fibre filter attached to a personal air pump located in the breathing zone of the operator (flow rate ca. 2 L/min). Exposure was also assessed by bio-monitoring, but the results were not considered for the model. The samples were analysed

for residues of fluazifop-P-butyl by extraction in acetonitrile followed by detection with GC-MS.

Results:

The data given below were obtained by passive dosimetry. The actual exposure to the legs and lower arms was estimated from the respective outer exposure based on the permeation values of the torso and is included in the inner body exposure. Moreover, the hand wash data was corrected for the field recovery, which was 39 % at the high and 44 % at the low fortification level. Values below the LOQ were calculated with ½ of the LOQ and inhalation exposure was recalculated using a respiration rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	0.2	* 2.6	0.004	4.810	** 0.040	0.105	* 0.003
4	0.2	* 2.6	0.005	12.110	0.120	0.487	* 0.003
5	0.2	* 2.6	0.005	19.430	** 0.006	0.242	* 0.003
6	0.2	* 2.6	0.012	46.630	** 0.025	0.472	* 0.003
7	0.2	* 2.6	0.002	13.580	** 0.005	0.798	* 0.003
8	0.2	* 2.6	0.003	4.797	** 0.004	0.407	* 0.003
9	0.2	* 2.6	0.001	2.923	** 0.002	0.242	* 0.003
10	0.2	* 2.6	0.001	9.072	** 0.012	1.082	* 0.003
11	0.2	8.0	0.006	9.312	** 0.002	0.259	* 0.003
12	0.2	8.3	0.008	54.760	0.023	17.455	* 0.003
13	0.2	* 2.5	0.002	14.790	** 0.015	0.350	* 0.003
14	0.2	* 2.4	* 3x10 ⁻⁴	9.934	** 0.004	0.292	* 0.003
15	0.2	10.3	0.003	6.784	** 0.003	0.126	* 0.003
17	0.2	* 2.6	0.002	12.870	** 0.001	0.458	* 0.003
18	0.2	* 2.6	* 3x10 ⁻⁴	9.042	** 0.002	0.092	* 0.003

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
19	0.2	6.9	1.198	-	8.516	80.352	0.024
20	0.2	9.4	3.231	-	8.903	66.313	0.017
21	0.2	2.6	4.813	-	24.321	95.528	0.042
23	0.2	12.5	3.256	-	0.620	42.967	0.014
24	0.2	10.2	2.610	-	0.917	39.198	* 0.003
25	0.2	8.0	0.312	-	1.735	43.352	0.006
26	0.2	7.3	1.794	-	25.260	70.315	0.011
27	0.2	7.5	4.636	-	1.251	44.589	0.112
28	0.2	12.7	0.879	-	1.661	33.155	* 0.003
30	0.2	14.6	0.493	-	0.625	23.384	* 0.003
31	0.2	9.8	0.928	-	5.672	29.781	0.008
33	0.2	8.6	0.899	-	35.806	70.591	* 0.003
34	0.2	8.6	0.166	-	1.525	38.686	* 0.003
35	0.2	7.1	2.089	-	0.518	16.439	0.018
36	0.2	12.5	0.186	-	0.765	20.042	* 0.003

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ

HCHH 1

Active substance: Thiodicarb (375 g/L)
Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
Pesticide function: Insecticide
Crop: Grapevine

Setting:

The study presents exposure data obtained from twelve trials which were conducted during May and June 2001 in Greece. In each trial 0.5 to 1.4 ha of vine were treated with 0.9 to 1.4 L product/ha (0.36 to 0.53 kg a.s./ha) during a typical working day. The spray volume applied ranged from ca. 500 to 900 L to yield good crop coverage. The vine grew in rows of 2.0 to 2.5 m distance and had a height of 1.5 to 2.0 m. Mixing/loading and application were performed by different operators working in pairs of one mixer/loader and one applicator. The operators used spray guns which were connected to mix-tanks of 200 to 1,100 L size. Most of the applicators sat on a vehicle whilst spraying; applicator 20 and applicator 26 walked behind the vehicle. None of the vehicles were equipped with a cabin. Application was completed after 80 to 291 min including cleaning if necessary. Mixing/loading was conducted between one to four times and was finished after 17 to 48 min. The product was contained in 0.75 L bottles and was directly poured into the tank.

Exposure assessment:

For the mixer/loader replicates the exposure of the hands only was determined. The operators were provided with a pair of nitrile gloves, which was worn throughout all mixing/loading cycles and collected for analysis at the end of the trial. Actual exposure beneath the gloves was determined by hand washes, which were taken after each mixing/loading cycle and whenever the operator would have usually washed his hands. During application protective gloves were used as well and were collected in addition to hand wash specimens according to the procedure described for mixing/loading. Besides hand exposure also the body, head and inhalation exposure of the applicators were determined. Each applicator wore an inner body dosimeter (cotton long-sleeved vest, cotton long johns) and an outer body dosimeter (polyester/cotton coverall) to measure actual and potential body exposure. Head exposure was assessed by face/neck wipes collected during and at the end of the work period and Tenax sampling tubes which were connected to a personal air sampling pump (flow rate: 2 L/min) were used to determine inhalation exposure. Thiodicarb present in the specimens was extracted with a mix of dichloromethane/methanol and quantified by HPLC with fluorescence detection.

Results:

The results are given below. The values for the gloves were corrected for the field recovery, which was 69 % at the low and 67 % at the high fortification level. For all other sample matrices the field recovery was above 70 %. One half of the LOQ was used for values below the LOQ. Exposure via inhalation has been recalculated for a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. High body exposure was observed for some applicators. This was ascribed to several factors mentioned in the field observations. In the case of operator 10 wind gusts of up to 3 m/s were recorded while operator 12 applied in dense crop and operator 14 sprayed with high pressure.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	0.2		* 0.002	0.558			
3	0.3		* 0.002	0.559			
7	0.4		0.007	0.064			
9	0.8		0.266	0.008			
11	0.5		* 0.004	0.153			
13	0.3		* 0.006	7.383			
15	0.5		0.021	2.699			
17	0.4		* 0.002	1.725			
19	0.6		* 0.002	0.169			
21	0.7		* 0.002	0.539			
23	0.4		* 0.004	0.154			
25	0.4		* 0.008	0.531			

* ½ LOQ

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
2	0.2	6.5	* 0.002	0.188	* 0.006	** 2.263	* 0.002
4	0.3	11.4	* 0.002	0.085	** 0.027	2.428	* 0.002
8	0.4	* 2.1	* 0.002	0.028	** 0.019	2.369	0.009
10	0.6	135.6	* 0.002	17.478	1.938	218.252	0.460
12	0.5	44.1	* 0.002	1.712	8.980	168.555	0.079
14	0.3	34.4	* 0.002	3.784	0.561	51.158	0.060
16	0.5	20.8	* 0.002	1.380	** 0.050	7.562	0.016
18	0.3	19.6	0.004	0.538	** 0.021	2.464	0.005
20	0.3	12.0	* 0.002	0.009	** 0.015	2.460	* 0.002
22	0.5	18.8	* 0.002	2.351	0.075	9.255	0.029
24	0.3	5.9	* 0.002	0.015	** 0.010	2.119	* 0.002
26	0.4	14.9	* 0.002	0.193	** 0.105	19.667	* 0.002

* ½ LOQ ** partly calculated with ½ LOQ

HCHH 2

Active substance: Carbaryl (850 g/kg)
 Formulation type: Wettable powder
 Pesticide function: Insecticide
 Crop: Citrus

Setting:

Ten mixer/loaders and 20 applicators were monitored in August 2001 while applying an insecticide in citrus during a typical working day of 4 to 6 h. The citrus groves were located in the Valencia region of Spain and were in most of the cases characterised by a dense canopy. A single application of the product was performed at a rate of 7.9 to 21.7 kg/ha (6.7 to 16.1 kg a.s./ha) over an area of 0.29 to 0.82 ha per trial (0.14 to 0.41 ha per applicator). Water volumes ranged from ca. 7,200 to 10,800 L/ha. In each trial the test subjects worked in groups of one mixer/loader and two applicators. The applicators walked through the citrus grove and sprayed the citrus trees at close range using commercial hand-held spray equip-

ment, which consisted of a tank (1,100 to 4,000 L) with two lances. The product (5 kg bags) was weighed in a bowl and directly added to the tank without pre-mixing (except for operator 30 who prepared a pre-mix prior to loading). Each trial consisted of two to three tank mix preparations and two to three spraying operations. Mixing/loading was finished after 21 to 45 min; application was finished after 169 to 260 min. Cleaning of the spray equipment was not mentioned in the report.

Exposure assessment:

Whole body dosimeters consisting of a cotton coverall, a cotton long-sleeved vest and long johns were issued to the operators to assess the potential and actual exposure of the body during mixing/loading or application. In addition, hand wash and face wipe specimens were taken at various times during the working period to monitor exposure of the hands and face. Protective nitrile gloves were worn throughout mixing/loading or application and were sampled as well. To assess the exposure by inhalation the operators wore personal air sampling pumps connected to Tenax sampling tubes. The pumps operated at a mean flow rate of 1.7 to 2.0 L/min. The analysis of residues of carbaryl in the samples was performed with LC-MS after an extraction in acetone.

Results:

The exposure data are summarised below. The mean field recovery for the different sample matrices was between 82 to 102 %; thus, no corrections were made. All values were above the limit of quantification. Inhalation exposure has been recalculated for a breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. The mixer/loaders and applicators were highly exposed towards carbaryl. Due to the formulation of the product a lot of dust arose while loading the product resulting in contamination of the mixer/loaders. The applicators sprayed the citrus trees at close range thus working in dense spray mist and rubbing against previously sprayed trees.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	7.7	3978.3	3.389	93.130	13.231	332.930	0.514
4	5.6	1217.9	1.069	31.640	3.439	102.052	0.053
9	5.1	1411.2	4.179	52.300	24.891	425.190	0.353
10	6.8	665.2	0.283	85.620	2.190	49.994	0.035
13	6.8	1697.4	0.614	18.940	1.333	63.999	0.045
16	9.4	559.4	0.916	71.240	7.687	214.874	0.412
22	7.5	2801.3	2.997	38.600	2.780	97.223	0.090
25	7.7	4982.5	2.200	77.390	15.105	426.450	0.477
26	6.8	897.9	0.095	58.680	2.266	53.639	0.112
30	9.2	4272.0	0.350	132.800	5.213	187.518	0.364

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
2	3.8	385.7	0.710	36.910	23.313	1373.600	0.689
3	3.8	389.3	0.741	46.720	10.531	1172.160	0.610
5	2.7	252.4	0.269	43.780	39.583	1498.600	0.202
6	2.7	421.7	0.335	33.390	40.507	2145.500	0.181
7	2.6	121.1	0.431	13.940	23.146	565.690	0.267
8	2.6	101.5	1.257	12.810	6.295	422.070	0.082
11	3.4	333.2	0.239	31.940	217.320	1638.000	0.265
12	3.4	168.1	0.062	21.270	77.549	609.180	0.065
14	2.6	155.8	0.251	28.480	8.533	831.570	0.104
15	2.6	161.4	0.015	18.100	12.467	540.590	0.201
17	4.2	364.4	0.266	60.080	305.040	2041.000	1.882
18	4.2	328.7	0.763	56.710	188.037	2030.100	2.024
19	3.3	270.6	0.081	14.950	8.216	738.200	0.681
20	3.2	230.9	0.067	28.480	11.567	729.800	0.190
21	3.2	214.4	1.043	21.760	5.732	430.550	0.235
23	3.5	185.0	0.126	30.670	30.327	1110.100	0.352
24	3.5	234.0	0.254	28.590	52.057	1296.900	0.984
27	3.3	237.7	0.056	29.340	14.508	672.150	0.847
28	5.1	255.5	0.119	45.780	66.565	1538.600	1.748
29	5.1	313.5	0.145	73.560	103.924	1681.900	1.640

HCHH 3

Active substance: Carbaryl (850 g/kg)
 Formulation type: Wettable powder
 Pesticide function: Insecticide
 Crop: Citrus

Setting:

This study was performed to monitor dermal and inhalation exposure to carbaryl when applying it to citrus. The study was conducted during July 2002 at several sites in the Valencia region of Spain and reflected a typical working day of about 4 to 6 h. At each test site one mixer/loader and two applicators operated as a team and treated 0.3 to 1.4 ha per trial (0.17 to 0.70 ha per applicator) at a rate of 6.2 to 22.6 kg product/ha (5.3 to 19.2 kg a.s./ha) diluted in 3,100 to 11,300 L water. Application was performed with a broad range of commercial hand-held sprayers which consisted of a pair of hand-held lances connected to a spray tank (1,000 to 4,000 L). The product was supplied in 5 kg bags and was either directly filled into the tank or pre-mixed with water before loading. Mixing/loading was repeated two to three times and was completed within 23 to 85 min. During application the tank was parked in or close to the citrus grove and both applicators walked through the grove and sprayed the trees at close range. The duration of spraying was 145 to 243 min.

Exposure assessment:

Operator exposure was assessed with biomonitoring (results not used for the model) and passive dosimetry. The latter one was conducted by using two layers of sampling clothing for the body. The inner layer consisted of a short-sleeved cotton T-shirt and briefs and the outer layer consisted of a polyester/cotton coverall. In addition to that all operators wore protective nitrile gloves, which were sampled to determine potential hand exposure. Actual hand exposure was assessed with hand washes taken whenever the operator requested to wash his hands and at the end of the monitored procedure. Face/neck wipe specimen were collected

according to the procedure described for the hand washes and were used to determine head exposure. Inhalation exposure was calculated from residues collected in Tenax sorbent tubes. The flow rate of the air sampling pumps was adjusted to approximately 1.9 to 2.0 L/min. The samples were extracted in acetone and analysed by LC-MS.

Results:

The results obtained from passive dosimetry are reported in the following tables. The actual exposure to the legs and lower arms was estimated from the respective outer exposure based on the permeation values of the torso and is included in the 'inner' body exposure. All values were above the LOQ. The mean field recovery for the different sample matrices was in a range of 82 to 98 %. Therefore, no correction for the field recovery was made. Inhalation exposure has been recalculated for a respiration rate of 1.25 m³/h. The mixer/loaders and applicators were highly exposed towards carbaryl. Due to the formulation of the product a lot of dust arose while loading the product resulting in contamination of the mixer/loaders. The applicators sprayed the citrus trees at close range thus working in dense spray mist and rubbing against previously sprayed trees.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
3	5.1	964.6	11.210	134.500	3.124	152.398	0.507
6	7.7	8504.4	8.082	171.500	15.222	553.230	1.305
7	3.4	1684.68	0.290	48.450	1.173	56.338	0.081
10	5.6	2284.9	11.310	117.700	4.333	467.332	0.300
18	7.0	1857.3	9.265	86.650	5.982	233.540	0.212
21	6.8	958.8	0.115	48.700	1.450	27.851	0.202
24	6.8	1765.6	0.105	5.740	2.129	25.731	0.033
30	8.5	4861.8	2.225	90.580	15.060	408.930	0.739
33	9.4	3528.1	1.292	80.240	4.631	129.336	0.231
34	7.7	5132.7	0.970	63.680	3.036	76.473	0.150

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	2.6	345.3	0.338	29.910	2.390	202.640	0.559
2	2.6	249.2	0.537	39.470	4.411	305.130	0.355
4	3.8	397.0	0.436	32.850	4.290	316.110	0.565
5	3.8	355.6	0.218	44.620	8.092	543.900	1.607
8	1.7	185.5	0.066	21.650	10.106	331.360	0.179
9	1.7	229.1	0.128	29.750	8.554	473.980	0.370
12	2.6	540.5	1.025	52.470	71.781	1326.480	0.570
16	3.2	266.1	1.357	29.740	6.161	569.650	0.388
17	3.2	156.3	0.103	13.910	3.901	263.910	0.226
19	3.4	2136.3	0.254	36.580	6.727	662.420	0.568
20	3.4	551.4	1.381	56.790	41.000	1850.400	2.588
22	3.4	562.2	0.836	63.940	51.393	1945.200	1.394
23	3.4	692.4	0.075	50.310	3.423	584.100	0.568
26	4.3	399.0	0.073	28.460	3.642	376.720	1.024
27	4.3	503.7	0.463	28.210	3.039	406.760	2.141
29	4.3	675.4	0.390	43.630	4.889	496.620	0.424
31	4.7	528.4	0.163	51.510	4.835	962.460	2.637
32	4.7	449.9	0.345	33.810	11.669	1184.300	2.124
35	3.4	949.1	1.368	76.670	136.393	2334.000	2.697
36	3.4	392.8	0.356	66.430	44.920	1278.800	0.947

HCHH 4

Active substance: Carbaryl (480 g/L)
 Formulation type: Suspension concentrate
 Pesticide function: Insecticide
 Crop: Olives

Setting:

The study provides exposure data obtained from twelve trials which were conducted during July 2002 in Spain. A minimum of 6 to a maximum of 13.5 ha of olive trees with a height of 1 to 8 m and growing in a distance of 6 to 16 m were treated in each trial (3.3 to 6.8 ha per applicator). The insecticide was applied for a typical working day of at least 4 h at a rate of 1.7 to 3.5 L product /ha (0.8 to 1.7 kg a.s./ha) diluted in a water volume of about 480 to 1,000 L. Mixing/loading and application were performed by different operators using a variety of typical hand-held sprayers. The sprayers consisted of a pair of spray guns, which were connected to a tank (2,000 to 6,000 L tank volume). Two operators sprayed in parallel standing back to back or side by side on a vehicle at the rear of the spraying device while the vehicle drove between the rows. Mixing/loading was conducted two or three times by pouring the product directly into the spray tank. Overall five to six product containers (5 L) were handled by the mixer/loaders while wearing a face shield (except for operator 24 who did not use a face shield). The duration of mixing/loading was between 17 and 51 min the duration of application was in a range of 143 to 304 min.

Exposure assessment:

Body dosimeters consisting of a cotton coverall, a cotton short-sleeved T-shirt and briefs were issued to the mixer/loaders and applicators to assess actual and potential body exposure. Exposure to the head and hands was determined by face/neck wipes and hand washes

which were taken at the end of the working task and whenever the operator requested it. Face shields were worn during mixing/loading but were not part of the analysis. The protective nitrile gloves used by the operators were analysed. After the last mixing/loading or application cycle the protective gloves were removed and collected. Tenax sorbent tubes were used to determine the exposure via inhalation. The average flow rate of the air sampling pump was about 2 L/min.

Residues of carbaryl were extracted in acetone and quantified by gas chromatography with mass selective detection.

Passive dosimetry and biomonitoring were concurrently applied in the study; the data from biomonitoring, however, was not used for the model.

Results:

The following tables summarise the results obtained by passive dosimetry. The actual exposure to the legs and lower arms was estimated from the respective outer exposure based on the permeation values of the torso and is included in the 'inner' body exposure. Values below the limit of quantification were calculated with $\frac{1}{2}$ of the LOQ. The mean field recovery for the sample matrices was in a range of 71 to 84 %. Inhalation exposure is based on a generic breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Mixing/loading

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
3	10.1	* 0.5	0.062	2.010	0.029	1.162	0.007
6	12.1	1.1	0.143	6.264	0.045	1.011	5x10 ⁻⁴
9	10.1	* 0.5	0.071	3.712	0.050	0.514	3x10 ⁻⁴
12	11.8	* 0.5	** 0.030	0.677	0.004	0.153	2x10 ⁻⁴
15	11.8	1.6	1.774	9.657	0.244	11.054	0.002
18	10.1	* 0.5	0.150	15.080	0.020	1.454	5x10 ⁻⁴
21	13.5	* 0.5	0.414	7.820	0.047	3.717	5x10 ⁻⁴
24	10.1	* 0.5	3.903	10.940	0.215	39.653	0.003
27	13.5	1.6	0.102	14.810	0.058	1.353	0.005
30	10.1	* 0.5	0.080	7.401	0.006	0.350	0.001
33	11.8	* 0.5	0.003	3.317	0.119	5.062	1.816
36	10.4	* 0.5	0.051	0.544	0.004	0.736	0.006

* calculated with $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ ** one hand wash discarded in error

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
1	5.1	44.6	0.006	1.240	0.088	5.736	0.004
2	5.1	57.6	0.009	1.632	0.042	4.878	0.005
4	6.0	359.4	0.878	29.670	1.033	180.749	0.528
5	6.0	177.6	0.192	12.050	0.674	115.419	0.092
7	4.2	334.0	0.121	7.731	0.303	76.723	0.063
8	4.2	207.5	0.060	6.480	0.351	35.313	0.018
10	5.9	214.1	1.958	4.011	0.242	21.358	0.009
11	5.9	134.9	0.353	3.988	0.123	14.270	0.020
13	5.9	378.5	0.142	34.160	1.732	150.462	0.148
14	5.9	2165.6	0.252	60.290	1.113	253.260	0.736
16	5.1	28.0	0.213	8.821	0.366	55.345	0.087
17	5.1	29.2	0.365	6.178	0.411	52.440	0.128
19	6.8	238.0	0.033	5.547	0.201	36.031	0.049
20	6.8	154.3	0.006	2.106	0.171	10.802	0.033
22	5.1	257.4	0.629	13.260	0.658	39.180	0.009
23	5.1	229.8	0.350	2.123	0.201	11.328	0.014
25	6.8	132.5	0.020	5.155	0.139	8.877	0.019
26	6.8	123.9	0.264	7.362	0.200	37.275	0.023
28	5.1	42.3	0.079	2.731	0.269	30.972	0.075
29	5.1	38.9	0.177	14.120	0.241	22.042	0.034
31	5.9	95.6	0.045	4.048	0.638	15.399	0.006
32	5.9	* 0.5	0.087	2.443	0.200	10.929	0.005
34	5.1	480.2	0.048	3.858	0.530	5.440	0.022
35	5.1	400.2	0.047	2.948	0.204	1.535	0.012

* calculated with ½ LOQ

HCHH 5

Active substance: Fenthion (500 g/L)
 Formulation type: Emulsifiable concentrate
 Pesticide function: Insecticide
 Crop: Olives

Setting:

Fourteen operators were monitored during September 2001 to obtain data on the exposure derived from applying an insecticide to olives. The field phase took place at nine representative locations in the Abruzzi and Puglia region of Italy and comprised application but not mixing and loading of the product. The area ranged from 1.0 ha to 2.55 ha per operator and was treated in 123 to 253 min. Application was performed with typical hand-held spray guns which were connected to a tank with a capacity of 800 to 1,200 L. Four operators (7, 8, 13, 14) had their own tank with a single spray gun and sprayed both sides of the row while walking behind the tractor. The rest of the operators worked in pairs spraying either side of the row. The trees were 4 to 6 m high and grew in a distance of 1 to 10 m of each other. On average the operators sprayed 1 L product per ha (0.5 kg a.s./ha) diluted in 1,000 L/ha. Cleaning of the equipment was not mentioned in the study report.

Exposure assessment:

The operators were dressed in two layers of sampling clothing represented by a cotton/polyester coverall and a long-sleeved cotton shirt with long underpants worn beneath the coverall. The clothing was collected at the end of the working task and used to determine the

exposure of the body. Hand exposure was assessed by analysing the protective gloves used during application as well as the hand wash specimens taken after the gloves had been removed. Face/neck wipe samples were collected to estimate the exposure to the head and exposure via inhalation was monitored by Tenax sorbent tubes located in the breathing zone of the operators (pump flow rate 2 L/min). During application all operators wore a hat, which was not part of the monitoring clothing. For analysis fenthion was extracted from the samples with 2-propanol and oxidised to fenoxon sulphone, which was finally quantified by gas chromatography using flame photometric detection.

Results:

The results for applicator exposure are given below. All values shown were not corrected for field recovery, which was higher than 70 %, except for protective gloves. Recovery for the gloves was only 9 %, but was attributed to field exposure conditions not relevant for the monitoring of the operators. Actual exposure of the hands was generally low with half of the values below the limit of detection (reported as $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ). Inhalation exposure has been recalculated for a respiration rate of 1.25 m³/h.

Application

Operator	TA a.s. [kg]	Inhalation [µg]	Hands [mg]	Gloves [mg]	Body _{inner} [mg]	Body _{outer} [mg]	Face/neck [mg]
3	0.8	66.9	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	3.309	2.834	129.970	0.385
4	0.8	25.6	0.004	2.543	1.704	80.010	0.059
5	1.0	58.1	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	1.256	1.472	69.879	0.191
6	1.0	83.8	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	1.633	1.496	51.885	0.114
7	1.1	77.1	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	3.213	1.523	91.665	0.233
8	1.2	36.5	2x10 ⁻⁴	2.642	0.789	23.220	0.155
9	0.6	9.4	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	1.271	0.766	16.347	0.048
10	0.6	16.9	0.002	1.212	0.230	9.516	0.028
11	0.6	3.3	0.001	0.372	0.071	4.525	0.013
12	0.6	3.9	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	0.597	0.240	12.342	0.042
13	0.6	62.5	0.003	0.973	1.720	68.663	0.065
14	0.6	41.3	0.001	0.475	0.126	11.275	0.010
15	0.5	87.3	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	0.834	1.881	34.826	0.061
16	0.5	157.3	* 5x10 ⁻⁵	0.547	1.644	28.789	0.036

* $\frac{1}{2}$ LOQ

Appendix 2 Model predictions (75th percentile)

A 2.1 ML tank

Figure A 1: Model prediction for ML tank; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: liquid formulations, thin broken line: WP formulations, thick broken line: WG formulations

A 2.2 LCTM application

Figure A 2: Model prediction for LCTM; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: normal equipment, broken line: equipment for small areas; impact of droplet size (normal, coarse) is not shown

A 2.3 HCTM application

Figure A 3: Model prediction for HCTM; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: cabin, broken line: no cabin

A 2.4 HCHH application

Figure A 4: Model prediction for HCHH; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: dense culture, broken line: normal culture

Appendix 3 Estimation of the 75th percentile

A 3.1 Knapsack mixing/loading

Figure A 5: Comparison of the empirical 75th percentile (green line) with the parametric estimate of the percentile calculated acc. to EFSA (blue line) and the 75th percentile obtained by quantile regression (orange line); the y-axis gives the proportion of data with values below a certain level of exposure.

A 3.2 LCHH application

Figure A 6: Comparison of the empirical 75th percentile (green line) with the parametric estimate of the percentile calculated acc. to EFSA (blue line) and the 75th percentile obtained by quantile regression (orange line); the y-axis gives the proportion of data with values below a certain level of exposure.

Appendix 4 Model predictions (95th percentile)

A 4.1 Tank mixing/loading

Figure A 7: Model prediction (95th percentile) for ML tank; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: liquid formulations, thin broken line: WP formulations, thick broken line: WG formulations

A 4.2 LCTM application

Figure A 8: Model prediction (95th percentile) for LCTM; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: normal equipment, broken line: equipment for small areas; impact of droplet size (normal, coarse) is not shown

A 4.3 HCTM application

Figure A 9: Model prediction (95th percentile) for HCTM; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: cabin, broken line: no cabin

A 4.4 HCHH application

Figure A 10: Model prediction (95th percentile) for HCHH; green: prediction with least squares regression, red: prediction with quantile regression; solid line: dense culture, broken line: normal culture

Appendix 5 Estimation of the 95th percentile

A 5.1 Knapsack mixing/loading

Figure A 11: Comparison of the empirical 95th percentile (green line) with the parametric estimate of the percentile calculated acc. to EFSA (blue line) and the 95th percentile obtained by quantile regression (orange line); the y-axis gives the proportion of data with values below a certain level of exposure.

A 5.2 LCHH application

Figure A 12: Comparison of the empirical 95th percentile (green line) with the parametric estimate of the percentile calculated acc. to EFSA (blue line) and the 95th percentile obtained by quantile regression (orange line); the y-axis gives the proportion of data with values below a certain level of exposure.

Appendix 6 Cross validation (study impact)

A 6.1 Tank mixing/loading

Figure A 13: Cross validation by study of the tank mixing/loading model; shown are the measurements from the studies (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets.

A 6.2 LCTM application

Figure A 14: Cross validation by study of the tank mixing/loading model; shown are the measurements from the studies (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets. Empty diagrams indicate poor coverage of some combination of factor levels.

A 6.3 HCTM application

Figure A 15: Cross validation by study of the tank mixing/loading model; shown are the measurements from the studies (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets. Empty diagrams indicate poor coverage of some combination of factor levels.

A 6.4 HCHH application

Figure A 16: Cross validation by study of the tank mixing/loading model; shown are the measurements from the studies (in different colours) together with the model prediction (same colour line) of the reduced datasets. Empty diagrams indicate poor coverage of some combination of factor levels.

Appendix 7 User Guidance to the Agricultural Operator Exposure Model

Purpose

The Agricultural Operator Exposure Model has been developed for estimating the exposure of professional operators to pesticides during mixing/loading and application. It is based on empirical data from various exposure studies conducted between 1994 and 2009 and covers the main outdoor scenarios for low crops and high crops considering modern application equipment. The model is applicable for conditions in Europe and is intended e.g. to be used for assessing operator exposure as part of the (zonal) authorisation of plant protection products within the EU.

Scenarios

The following outdoor application scenarios can be chosen by the user: Application with tractor-mounted/-trailed equipment in low crops (LCTM), application with tractor-mounted/-trailed equipment in high crops (HCTM), application with hand-held equipment in low crops (LCHH) and application with hand-held equipment in high crops (HCHH). For estimating the exposure for mixing and loading the plant protection product two scenarios are possible: Tank mixing/loading and knapsack mixing/loading. If tractor-mounted/-trailed equipment is selected tank mixing/loading is automatically taken into account; if hand-held equipment is selected two separate scenarios either including tank mixing/loading or knapsack mixing/loading are automatically considered and calculated.

For several of these scenarios a specification is possible by choosing different subsets. In case of LCTM application the droplet size ('coarse' instead of 'normal' if drift reducing nozzles are used) and the equipment type ('small' instead of 'normal' if the equipment used is suitable for the treatment of small areas/high crops) can be specified. The cabin status can be changed for the HCTM scenario from 'no cabin' to 'cabin' and the culture type ('dense culture' instead of 'normal culture' if direct contact with sprayed crop cannot be avoided by the operator while applying the plant protection product) can be refined for the HCHH scenario.

Additionally, the formulation type has an impact on the modelled exposure for tank mixing/loading. Therefore, powder formulations (WP), granular formulations (WG) and liquid formulations are distinguished. Apart from this no difference is made between mixing/loading a tank for LCTM, HCTM, LCHH or HCHH application. The exposure estimates for knapsack mixing/loading are identical for LCHH and HCHH.

Cleaning of the spray equipment is considered as a separate task but included in the exposure for the application.

Model data

The exposure predictions for the different scenarios are mainly based on statistical models and depend largely on the total amount of active substance used per day. The number of data available for knapsack mixing/loading and LCHH application was, however, not sufficient for modelling; instead the 75th percentile was calculated. This value is valid up to a total amount of 1.5 kg active substance (a.s.); above 1.5 kg a.s. linear extrapolation is performed (considered to be an overestimation since the dependency of exposure on the total amount of active substance used is generally sub-linear).

Work rate/area treated

The model gives the exposure for a typical working day. The corresponding area treated per day is based on available datasets (roughly the 75th percentile) and ranges from 50 ha for the LCTM scenario to 1 ha for all hand-held scenarios with knapsack sprayers as well as for HCHH application in dense culture.

Operator

The model is only suitable for calculating the exposure of professional operators. An average body weight of 60 kg is assumed (precautionary principle). The exposure by inhalation is based on a default breathing rate of 1.25 m³/h. If other default values are agreed on EU-level, these values could be adapted accordingly.

Personal protective equipment (PPE)

The exposure is calculated for a professional operator wearing at least one layer of work clothes and sturdy footwear during mixing/loading and application. Additional PPE can be selected from a list if the estimated systemic exposure exceeds the AOEL. Multiple PPE can be selected if their combination is logical. The PPE can be chosen separately for mixing/loading (m/l) and application (a). The risk mitigation factors applied are either based on data used for the model ('acc. model') or can be chosen from other sources.

Operating instructions

1. Select the sheet 'Data entry' and fill out the orange boxes on the active substance and the product. Orange boxes generally indicate information which should be inserted or selected. For each active substance a separate excel sheet has to be filled out.
2. Choose the formulation type of the product from the pull-down menu: 'WG' for water soluble or dispersible granules, 'WP' for wettable powder and 'Liquid' for all liquid formulations (either based on water or organic solvents).
3. Enter the value for the systemic AOEL (in mg/kg bw/d) and the value for the dermal absorption (in %) of the active substance in the undiluted product (for mixing/loading) as well as in the ready-to-use/diluted product (for application). Give the formulation which was used to assess the dermal absorption. Use default values (e.g. 25 % or 75 %, acc. EFSA guidance on dermal absorption²) if no appropriate data on the dermal absorption exist.

The absorption via inhalation is assumed to be 100 % if no other information is available; the average body weight of the operator is defined to be 60 kg. Both values can be changed if a different body weight or inhalation absorption value is required appropriate.

4. Choose all relevant application scenarios for the product by placing a check mark in the white boxes behind (click on the box). Enter the amount of active substance applied per hectare (in kg a.s./ha) and the intended use.

5. Select the sheet for the respective application scenario. Refine the scenario if necessary by choosing a subset from the pull-down menu (orange box on top of the sheet). Choose appropriate PPE (with the respective reduction factor) if necessary by placing a check mark in the white box behind it (click on the box). Workwear and sturdy footwear for mixing/loading and application are automatically pre-selected but can be replaced by a protective suit against chemicals. Respiratory protection and head protection with respective reduction factors can be defined according to individual requirements. Reduction factors in orange boxes can be changed.

²) EFSA (European Food Safety Authority): Guidance on dermal absorption; EFSA Journal 10(4):2665, 2012

6. The resulting total systemic exposure (in mg/kg bw and % of the AOEL) is given in a summary box. In addition to the exposure when using workwear (and/or PPE) the potential exposure without any workwear and PPE is also listed. All calculations and parameters are shown in the tables below.

In case a different value is required for the treated area per day the default value in the parameter box (cell B45) can be changed.

7. For an overall summary of all scenarios select the sheet 'Summary'. In the top box information on the product is given (generated from the information entered in the 'Data entry' sheet). The box below shows the results for the potential exposure and the exposure with workwear (and PPE if necessary). Only the scenarios selected in the 'Data entry' sheet are presented.

Notes

- LCTM: Nozzles are assumed to produce a 'coarse' droplet spectrum when they are classified for at least 50 % drift reduction (according to the definition developed by the Julius Kühn Institut).
- LCTM: The combination of the parameters 'coarse droplets' and 'small area equipment' is not covered by data.
- HCTM: The modelled exposure for the protected hand (application) is independent from the cabin status.
- HCHH: The modelled exposure for the protected body (application) is independent from the total amount of active substance.
- LCHH/HCHH: The head exposure for knapsack mixing/loading is based on data from operators wearing a face shield. The exposure when choosing hood and face shield for mixing/loading is therefore the same as the exposure when choosing no head protection.

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16 Supplementary information on the new Agricultural Operator Exposure Model

2013-01-29

17 Raw data used for the model

17.1 Mixing/loading

Study code	Op.#	ML type	TA (kg a.s.)	Form. type	Face shield ML	Glove wash ML	Total Hand ML (µg)	Prot. hand ML (µg)	Total body ML (µg)	Inner body ML (µg)	Head ML (µg)	Inhalation ML (µg)
LCTM_1	A	tank	25.1	WG	no	yes	4963.9	290.5	11900.7	716.5	2358.9	338.1
LCTM_1	B	tank	25.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	C	tank	28.2	WG	no		3537.9	36.1	2289.6	46.6	41.2	31.4
LCTM_1	D	tank	28.2	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	E	tank	28.5	WG	no	yes	501.6	64.8	7664.7	114.5	148.9	63.1
LCTM_1	F	tank	28.5	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	G	tank	21.3	WG	no	yes	612.9	104.4	20359.8	494.0	1409.8	824.9
LCTM_1	H	tank	21.3	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	I	tank	25.0	WG	no		5743.9	45.6	3277.1	107.3	144.2	280.2
LCTM_1	J	tank	25.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	K	tank	24.0	WG	no		256.1	2.5	879.1	29.1	43.9	73.1
LCTM_1	L	tank	24.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	M	tank	33.0	WG	no		1196.8	31.1	2791.2	167.9	152.6	235.3
LCTM_1	N	tank	33.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	1	tank	9.0	liquid	no		584.7	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	2	tank	6.3	liquid	no		7205.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	3	tank	6.8	liquid	no		3076.9	0.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	4	tank	10.0	liquid	no		1605.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	5	tank	8.8	liquid	no		3805.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	6	tank	7.3	liquid	no		1625.0	125.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	7	tank	4.9	liquid	no		8828.5	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	8	tank	10.3	liquid	no		30151.8	740.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	9	tank	7.5	liquid	no		480.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	10	tank	3.8	liquid	no		472.8	32.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	11	tank	5.8	liquid	no		2368.6	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	12	tank	7.0	liquid	no		1550.5	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	13	tank	7.9	liquid	no		5265.6	65.6	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	14	tank	8.3	liquid	no		3324.2	213.1	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	15	tank	9.6	liquid	no		970.0	40.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	WM	tank	7.5	liquid	no		15960.8	70.8	5693.1	85.1	4.8	2.7

Study code	Op.#	ML type	TA (kg a.s.)	Form. type	Face shield ML	Glove wash ML	Total Hand ML (µg)	Prot. hand ML (µg)	Total body ML (µg)	Inner body ML (µg)	Head ML (µg)	Inhalation ML (µg)
LCTM_3	JT	tank	7.5	liquid	no		21317.8	77.8	14761.0	135.0	7.4	30.1
LCTM_3	HM	tank	7.5	liquid	no		25450.0	30.0	20391.0	162.0	21.0	2.5
LCTM_3	JK	tank	7.5	liquid	no		37604.6	44.6	3281.7	17.7	5.7	1.6
LCTM_3	RV	tank	4.5	liquid	no		40960.0	50.0	10139.0	227.0	10.0	3.8
LCTM_3	YB	tank	8.0	liquid	no		25545.0	375.0	9948.0	123.0	17.1	4.0
LCTM_3	JM	tank	8.0	liquid	no		14381.8	121.8	65484.9	84.9	14.3	12.2
LCTM_3	JD	tank	8.0	liquid	no		5514.0	869.0	14970.0	1170.0	76.2	2.5
LCTM_3	JB	tank	7.5	liquid	no		762.1	24.1	3063.0	289.0	8.5	1.6
LCTM_3	EG	tank	7.5	liquid	no		1595.0	35.0	781.0	358.0	22.8	1.0
LCTM_4	SH	tank	2.5	liquid	no		918.6	1.7	518.0	0.5	39.6	NA
LCTM_4	SC	tank	2.5	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	TS	tank	2.3	liquid	no		4760.8	0.0	281.6	5.3	10.0	NA
LCTM_4	THR	tank	2.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	SC	tank	3.1	liquid	no		2135.1	1.9	161.8	14.7	1.0	NA
LCTM_4	SH	tank	3.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	THR	tank	2.9	liquid	no		832.4	2.6	376.0	2.9	7.2	NA
LCTM_4	TS	tank	2.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_5	1	tank	200.0	liquid	no		26226.8	0.8	NA	NA	NA	0.8
LCTM_5	2	tank	200.0	liquid	no		29608.1	1.1	NA	NA	NA	0.7
LCTM_5	3	tank	192.0	liquid	no		70644.6	28.6	NA	NA	NA	9.6
LCTM_5	4	tank	160.0	liquid	no		29736.9	2.9	NA	NA	NA	2.5
LCTM_5	5	tank	192.0	liquid	no		278054.4	5.4	NA	NA	NA	4.5
LCTM_5	6	tank	192.0	liquid	no		49842.3	15.3	NA	NA	NA	7.3
LCTM_5	7	tank	208.0	liquid	no		31823.6	0.6	NA	NA	NA	4.9
LCTM_5	8	tank	188.0	liquid	no		36485.1	7.1	NA	NA	NA	18.7
LCTM_5	9	tank	200.0	liquid	no		73918.8	20.8	NA	NA	NA	3.5
LCTM_5	10	tank	200.0	liquid	no		28449.4	6.4	NA	NA	NA	0.8
LCTM_5	11	tank	179.0	liquid	no		315833.0	802.0	NA	NA	NA	0.8
LCTM_5	12	tank	250.0	liquid	no		717897.0	141.0	NA	NA	NA	19.1
LCTM_6	1	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	2	tank	1.0	WG	yes		6056.2	30.2	963.8	25.1	0.0	16.5
LCTM_6	3	tank	0.7	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	4	tank	0.7	WG	yes		1036.7	2.7	670.2	11.4	0.0	0.0
LCTM_6	5	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Study code	Op.#	ML type	TA (kg a.s.)	Form. type	Face shield ML	Glove wash ML	Total Hand ML (µg)	Prot. hand ML (µg)	Total body ML (µg)	Inner body ML (µg)	Head ML (µg)	Inhalation ML (µg)
LCTM_6	6	tank	1.0	WG	yes		1270.4	4.4	992.6	2.0	0.0	0.0
LCTM_6	7	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	8	tank	1.0	WG	yes		218.7	0.2	827.4	0.0	0.0	0.0
LCTM_6	9	tank	1.2	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	10	tank	1.2	WG	yes		2367.6	2.0	211.5	2.0	0.0	0.0
LCTM_6	11	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	12	tank	1.0	WG	yes		968.1	71.6	169.8	3.0	0.0	0.0
LCTM_6	13	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	14	tank	0.9	WG	yes		587.7	2.5	214.0	2.0	0.0	5.2
LCTM_6	15	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	16	tank	1.0	WG	yes		2085.3	14.3	1897.8	8.2	0.0	5.2
LCTM_6	17	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	18	tank	1.0	WG	yes		858.6	5.5	864.0	8.2	0.0	5.2
LCTM_6	19	tank	1.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	20	tank	1.0	WG	yes		6875.8	9.8	1200.1	7.6	0.0	0.0
LCTM_7	A	tank	14.0	liquid	no	yes	14865.5	264.5	NA	NA	NA	3.9
LCTM_7	B	tank	4.0	liquid	no		4273.2	9.2	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_7	C1	tank	6.0	liquid	no		8673.6	10.8	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_7	D	tank	13.1	liquid	no	yes	969.7	7.8	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_7	E	tank	5.3	liquid	no	yes	2294.3	10.8	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_8	1	tank	56.4	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	2	tank	56.4	liquid	no		2489.0	1268.0	NA	NA	751.5	13.4
LCTM_8	4	tank	47.3	liquid	no		87332.2	271.9	10604.7	38.8	1365.9	23.9
LCTM_8	5	tank	58.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	6	tank	58.6	liquid	no		26363.6	602.0	12563.9	46.3	2847.0	7.6
LCTM_8	7	tank	51.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	8	tank	51.0	liquid	no		80216.7	13219.0	46118.9	152.3	4555.6	10.5
LCTM_8	9	tank	68.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	10	tank	68.0	liquid	no		75609.2	1805.2	43837.2	239.3	1478.0	6.9
LCTM_8	11	tank	45.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	12	tank	45.9	liquid	no		1183456.6	23262.0	130025.8	186.1	2381.5	14.8
LCTM_8	13	tank	51.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	14	tank	51.0	liquid	no		128537.3	11486.1	225719.4	1429.5	14512.5	31.5
LCTM_8	15	tank	68.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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LCTM_8	16	tank	68.0	liquid	no		93558.5	2005.8	52561.3	604.9	713.1	1.7
LCTM_8	17	tank	56.7	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	18	tank	56.7	liquid	no		412829.8	33747.5	41524.4	136.4	19050.5	11.5
LCTM_8	19	tank	64.3	liquid	no		88213.0	2383.3	14854.6	94.3	1695.3	7.8
LCTM_8	20	tank	64.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_9	1	tank	33.5	liquid	no		28011.0	11.0	132198.0	198.0	4000.0	17.8
LCTM_9	2	tank	40.7	liquid	no		9070.0	8600.0	26727.0	117.0	122.0	48.5
LCTM_9	3	tank	40.0	liquid	no		39120.0	120.0	30546.0	346.0	24.0	1.0
LCTM_9	4	tank	27.5	liquid	no		5805.0	5.0	4220.0	120.0	30.0	4.0
LCTM_9	5	tank	42.3	liquid	no		27140.0	140.0	7959.0	179.0	26.0	5.3
LCTM_9	6	tank	26.4	liquid	no		4705.0	5.0	96559.0	39.0	220.0	1.0
LCTM_9	7	tank	40.0	liquid	no		7458.0	58.0	3146.0	26.0	112.0	1.0
LCTM_9	8	tank	50.0	liquid	no		201.0	11.0	78021.0	21.0	10.0	0.9
LCTM_9	9	tank	35.0	liquid	no	yes	1405.0	5.0	6715.0	15.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	10	tank	56.5	liquid	no		5372.0	72.0	4777.0	1697.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	11	tank	45.0	liquid	no		17073.0	73.0	28521.0	21.0	3200.0	11.0
LCTM_9	12	tank	47.5	liquid	no		5050.0	250.0	45552.0	552.0	1320.0	1.0
LCTM_9	13	tank	27.0	liquid	no		7216.0	16.0	2182.0	15.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	14	tank	25.0	liquid	no		8250.0	8200.0	5742.0	42.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	15	tank	25.0	liquid	no		14045.0	45.0	749.0	15.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	16	tank	41.4	liquid	no		17000.0	8200.0	455259.0	13069.0	140.0	5.9
LCTM_10	A	tank	4.6	liquid	no		3542.6	16.3	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	B	tank	12.8	liquid	no		7977.7	30.9	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	C	tank	31.3	liquid	no	yes	3088.1	32.3	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	D	tank	12.0	liquid	no	yes	567.4	7.2	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	E	tank	5.6	liquid	no		1454.0	7.4	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	F	tank	7.1	liquid	no		6246.7	10.7	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	H	tank	15.0	liquid	no		3513.3	11.1	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_11	1	tank	203.8	liquid	no		732729.9	44.1	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	2	tank	195.8	liquid	no		107414.1	12.9	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	3	tank	213.6	liquid	no		79471.7	10.9	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	4	tank	211.8	liquid	no		800722.6	10.9	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	6	tank	209.5	liquid	no		266503.4	7.6	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	7	tank	212.1	liquid	no		2346735.6	4.9	NA	NA	NA	NA

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LCTM_11	8	tank	211.6	liquid	no		597012.0	151.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	9	tank	213.4	liquid	no		1227499.0	21.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	11	tank	199.0	liquid	no		1060416.4	65.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	12	tank	199.3	liquid	no		635008.7	167.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	13	tank	211.8	liquid	no		186082.7	1493.4	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	14	tank	162.3	liquid	no		487103.2	78.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	1	tank	1.4	liquid	yes		1996.7	36.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	2	tank	1.2	liquid	yes		2769.9	9.9	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	3	tank	1.2	liquid	yes		4489.8	79.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	4	tank	1.3	liquid	yes	yes	3159.8	9.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	5	tank	1.0	liquid	yes	yes	2510.8	20.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	6	tank	1.2	liquid	yes	yes	1332.7	12.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	7	tank	1.9	liquid	yes		2763.7	3.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	8	tank	1.9	liquid	yes	yes	4002.9	2.9	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	9	tank	1.2	liquid	yes	yes	1931.2	71.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	10	tank	1.3	liquid	yes	yes	2487.6	7.6	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	1	tank	5.8	liquid	no		131119.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	2	tank	8.3	liquid	no		38595.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	3	tank	9.3	liquid	no		15559.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	4	tank	6.9	liquid	no		5271.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	5	tank	6.9	liquid	no		6927.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	6	tank	5.4	liquid	no		30250.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	7	tank	3.6	liquid	no		267.4	51.3	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	8	tank	5.5	liquid	no		127643.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	10	tank	5.3	liquid	no		27793.8	153.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	11	tank	4.7	liquid	no		2320.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	12	tank	6.6	liquid	no		34946.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	13	tank	4.8	liquid	no		27365.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	14	tank	8.0	liquid	no		9457.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	15	tank	5.5	liquid	no		2971.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	17	tank	4.0	liquid	no		663.0	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	1	tank	2.7	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	2	tank	2.7	liquid	yes		18004.0	4.0	4397.7	4.7	2.0	5.2
HCTM_3	3	tank	2.4	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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HCTM_3	4	tank	2.4	liquid	yes		42026.0	26.0	4066.8	16.8	2.0	5.2
HCTM_3	5	tank	2.7	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	6	tank	2.7	liquid	yes		32450.0	450.0	19475.0	55.0	8.2	5.2
HCTM_3	7	tank	3.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	8	tank	3.0	liquid	yes		1503.9	3.9	797.0	2.0	2.0	5.2
HCTM_3	9	tank	3.4	liquid	yes		12006.8	6.8	1945.4	15.4	5.6	5.2
HCTM_3	10	tank	3.4	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	11	tank	3.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	12	tank	3.6	liquid	yes		46090.0	90.0	2885.3	14.3	10.2	5.2
HCTM_3	13	tank	3.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	14	tank	3.6	liquid	yes		3903.4	3.4	664.3	6.3	2.0	5.2
HCTM_3	15	tank	3.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	16	tank	3.6	liquid	yes		32037.0	37.0	94341.0	21.0	2.0	5.2
HCTM_3	17	tank	3.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	18	tank	3.2	liquid	yes		49008.9	8.9	2097.9	8.9	10.0	5.2
HCTM_3	19	tank	3.6	liquid	yes		96670.0	670.0	5092.0	152.0	58.0	5.2
HCTM_3	20	tank	3.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	21	tank	3.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	22	tank	3.0	liquid	yes		22005.9	5.9	1943.0	4.0	2.0	10.4
HCTM_3	23	tank	3.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	24	tank	3.8	liquid	yes		19021.0	21.0	2976.7	76.7	2.0	10.4
HCTM_4	1	tank	2.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	2	tank	1.7	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	3	tank	1.5	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	4	tank	1.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	5	tank	1.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	7	tank	2.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	8	tank	1.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	9	tank	1.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	10	tank	2.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	11	tank	1.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	12	tank	1.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_4	13	tank	1.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	1A	tank	18.4	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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HCTM_5	1B	tank	15.8	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	1M	tank	35.5	WG	no		5392.2	285.7	11928.8	230.4	125.0	19.4
HCTM_5	2A	tank	7.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	2B	tank	30.7	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	2M	tank	37.8	WG	no		1997.0	35.7	7853.7	465.2	116.7	16.3
HCTM_5	3A	tank	17.5	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	3M	tank	17.5	WG	no		40938.8	267.9	21752.0	1491.3	583.3	89.8
HCTM_5	4A	tank	12.3	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	4M	tank	12.3	WG	no		3396.0	125.0	4709.1	130.4	304.2	61.5
HCTM_5	5A	tank	17.5	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	5M	tank	17.5	WG	no		1536.9	14.3	15796.8	580.4	300.0	105.0
HCTM_5	6A	tank	5.3	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	6M	tank	7.0	WG	no		21055.2	3.6	28284.7	104.3	41.7	32.2
HCTM_5	7A	tank	10.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	7M	tank	13.5	WG	no		3885.3	14.3	1842.1	104.3	87.5	9.6
HCTM_5	8A	tank	13.7	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	8M	tank	15.8	WG	no		224.7	21.4	2691.7	213.0	62.5	34.7
HCTM_5	9A	tank	5.5	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	9B	tank	9.8	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	9M	tank	21.0	WG	no		4313.9	26.8	9850.8	1306.5	58.3	23.9
HCTM_5	10A	tank	7.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	10M	tank	7.0	WG	no		6926.5	7.1	3061.5	37.0	25.0	10.4
HCTM_5	11A	tank	10.0	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	11M	tank	19.8	WG	no		1672.2	46.4	2639.5	80.4	166.7	33.4
HCTM_5	14A	tank	12.9	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	14M	tank	16.8	WG	no		3403.3	67.9	67310.8	530.4	1504.2	211.8
HCTM_6	1	tank	4.5	liquid	no		8670.0	170.0	5077.4	17.4	160.0	1.0
HCTM_6	2	tank	3.6	liquid	no		7810.0	210.0	118602.2	912.2	140.0	1.0
HCTM_6	3	tank	3.6	liquid	no		11640.0	340.0	22295.9	75.9	80.0	6.3
HCTM_6	4	tank	5.0	liquid	no		2010.0	10.0	10152.3	82.3	240.0	31.3
HCTM_6	5	tank	2.4	liquid	no		10290.0	90.0	92883.7	153.7	400.0	10.4
HCTM_6	6	tank	7.2	liquid	no		9030.0	NA	28592.3	372.3	20.0	NA
HCTM_6	7	tank	8.0	liquid	no		6560.0	360.0	2761.3	41.3	520.0	145.8
HCTM_6	8	tank	6.3	liquid	no		30960.0	60.0	162413.2	3403.2	4640.0	4.2

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HCTM_6	9	tank	6.7	liquid	no	yes	10910.0	610.0	16395.9	2205.9	NA	1.3
HCTM_6	10	tank	10.0	liquid	no		28480.0	180.0	17999.8	249.8	20.0	10.4
HCTM_6	11	tank	6.3	liquid	no		19650.0	250.0	32460.1	160.1	40.0	14.6
HCTM_6	12	tank	6.0	liquid	no		5900.0	100.0	473.9	3.9	360.0	12.5
HCTM_6	13	tank	3.8	liquid	no		4190.0	90.0	6533.9	83.9	260.0	1.0
HCTM_6	14	tank	5.0	liquid	no		6590.0	90.0	2088.4	28.4	300.0	31.3
HCTM_6	15	tank	3.6	liquid	no		18630.0	130.0	4562.4	22.4	20.0	1.0
HCTM_6	16	tank	5.4	liquid	no		1930.0	30.0	1046.9	46.9	20.0	10.4
HCTM_6	17	tank	3.8	liquid	no		10590.0	NA	2231.9	21.9	20.0	4.2
HCTM_7	A	tank	4.0	WG	no	yes	285.7	2.7	NA	NA	NA	24.6
HCTM_7	B	tank	8.0	WG	no	yes	389.7	64.0	NA	NA	NA	1.8
HCTM_7	C	tank	7.5	WG	no		1218.1	9.1	NA	NA	NA	42.7
HCTM_7	D	tank	4.5	WG	no	yes	2157.2	15.2	NA	NA	NA	8.3
HCTM_7	E	tank	7.5	WG	no		2152.1	948.1	NA	NA	NA	24.8
HCTM_7	F	tank	8.0	WG	no	yes	1176.6	146.6	NA	NA	NA	106.3
HCTM_7	G	tank	13.5	WG	no		4355.6	98.6	NA	NA	NA	187.5
HCTM_7	H	tank	10.0	WG	no		2045.6	23.6	NA	NA	NA	132.3
HCTM_7	I	tank	7.5	WG	no		267.3	23.6	NA	NA	NA	3.9
HCTM_7	J	tank	3.8	WG	no		1763.3	6.3	NA	NA	NA	44.9
HCTM_7	K	tank	6.0	WG	no	yes	3608.8	85.8	NA	NA	NA	63.6
HCTM_7	L	tank	4.8	WG	no	yes	590.1	7.5	NA	NA	NA	45.1
HCTM_8	1	tank	1.6	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	2	tank	1.3	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	3	tank	1.5	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	4	tank	1.6	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	5	tank	1.2	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	6	tank	0.8	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	7	tank	0.9	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	8	tank	0.9	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	9	tank	1.4	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	10	tank	0.8	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	11	tank	1.2	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	12	tank	0.9	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	13	tank	2.2	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Study code	Op.#	ML type	TA (kg a.s.)	Form. type	Face shield ML	Glove wash ML	Total Hand ML (µg)	Prot. hand ML (µg)	Total body ML (µg)	Inner body ML (µg)	Head ML (µg)	Inhalation ML (µg)
HCTM_8	14	tank	1.8	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	15	tank	1.2	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_8	16	tank	0.9	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	1	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	2	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		520.7	2.0	33.6	2.0	4.0	5.2
LCHH_1	3	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	4	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		165.6	0.0	92.7	38.5	0.0	0.0
LCHH_1	5	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	6	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		643.6	6.1	163.4	0.0	4.0	0.0
LCHH_1	8	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		597.1	2.0	70.7	0.0	4.0	0.0
LCHH_1	9	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	10	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		356.3	6.5	367.6	1.0	4.0	0.0
LCHH_1	11	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	12	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		3616.4	18.4	914.2	9.5	4.0	5.2
LCHH_1	13	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	14	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		450.8	2.0	861.2	6.2	0.0	0.0
LCHH_1	15	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	16	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		202.7	9.1	1083.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
LCHH_1	17	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	18	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		725.8	5.2	52.3	6.3	0.0	5.2
LCHH_1	19	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_1	20	knapsack	0.1	WG	no		2768.9	130.9	9087.9	168.6	4.0	0.0
LCHH_2	AA	knapsack	1.5	liquid	no		633.5	2.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AB	knapsack	1.5	liquid	no		875.5	2.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AC	knapsack	1.5	liquid	no		9495.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AD	knapsack	1.5	liquid	no		270.5	2.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AE	knapsack	1.5	liquid	no		2897.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AF	knapsack	1.5	liquid	no		1027.0	48.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AH	knapsack	1.2	liquid	no		889.5	2.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AI	knapsack	1.4	liquid	no		1118.0	8.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_2	AJ	knapsack	1.2	liquid	no		720.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	2	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		5176.5	2.5	360.2	81.9	5.0	26.0
LCHH_3	3	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		5146.8	21.8	830.3	59.4	5.0	26.0
LCHH_3	4	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		11260.4	150.4	234.4	24.9	5.0	26.0

Study code	Op.#	ML type	TA (kg a.s.)	Form. type	Face shield ML	Glove wash ML	Total Hand ML (µg)	Prot. hand ML (µg)	Total body ML (µg)	Inner body ML (µg)	Head ML (µg)	Inhalation ML (µg)
LCHH_3	5	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		5720.7	163.7	634.4	12.4	15.0	26.0
LCHH_3	7	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		6361.5	139.5	542.7	11.7	5.0	25.4
LCHH_3	8	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		13652.5	2.5	2786.9	29.3	5.0	23.7
LCHH_3	9	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		9388.6	144.6	378.6	13.2	19.0	26.7
LCHH_3	10	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		3960.5	123.5	120.4	10.2	5.0	26.0
LCHH_3	11	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		7325.4	340.4	399.0	22.8	11.4	25.4
LCHH_3	12	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		2506.0	165.0	148.9	51.8	5.0	26.0
LCHH_3	13	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		3852.0	5.0	31.0	16.0	5.0	26.0
LCHH_3	14	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		3737.7	45.7	865.2	12.2	5.0	26.0
LCHH_3	15	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		2687.5	2.5	342.6	102.6	5.0	24.2
LCHH_3	16	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		10031.6	122.6	720.6	16.9	5.0	26.0
LCHH_3	17	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		25482.5	2.5	974.1	60.7	5.0	23.7
LCHH_3	19	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	20	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	21	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	22	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	23	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	24	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	25	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	26	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	27	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	28	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	29	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	30	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	31	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	32	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_3	33	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	1	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		4813.7	3.7	144.7	39.8	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	4	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		12115.0	5.0	606.8	119.9	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	5	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		19435.0	5.0	248.0	6.0	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	6	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		46641.8	11.8	496.5	24.6	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	7	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		13582.3	2.3	802.9	5.2	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	8	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		4800.0	3.0	410.1	3.5	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	9	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		2924.3	1.3	243.5	1.7	5.0	2.6

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LCHH_4	10	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		9073.4	1.4	1094.0	11.9	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	11	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		9317.6	5.6	261.0	2.4	5.0	8.0
LCHH_4	12	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		54768.3	8.3	17478.5	23.2	5.0	8.3
LCHH_4	13	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		14791.6	1.6	365.2	15.0	5.0	2.5
LCHH_4	14	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		9934.3	0.3	296.5	4.3	5.0	2.4
LCHH_4	15	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		6786.9	2.9	128.5	2.6	5.0	10.3
LCHH_4	17	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		12871.9	1.9	459.8	1.5	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	18	knapsack	0.2	liquid	yes		9042.3	0.3	94.4	2.4	5.0	2.6
LCHH_4	19	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	20	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	21	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	23	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	24	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	25	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	26	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	27	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	28	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	30	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	31	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	33	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	34	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	35	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	36	knapsack	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	1	tank	0.2	liquid	yes	yes	559.5	2.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	2	tank	0.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	3	tank	0.3	liquid	yes		560.7	2.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	4	tank	0.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	7	tank	0.4	liquid	yes		71.5	7.3	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	8	tank	0.4	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	9	tank	0.8	liquid	yes		274.3	266.3	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	10	tank	0.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	11	tank	0.5	liquid	yes		156.9	4.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	12	tank	0.5	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	13	tank	0.3	liquid	yes		7388.6	6.0	NA	NA	NA	NA

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HCHH_1	14	tank	0.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	15	tank	0.5	liquid	yes		2720.0	21.4	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	16	tank	0.5	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	17	tank	0.4	liquid	yes		1726.6	2.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	18	tank	0.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	19	tank	0.6	liquid	yes		171.1	2.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	20	tank	0.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	21	tank	0.7	liquid	yes		541.1	2.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	22	tank	0.5	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	23	tank	0.4	liquid	yes		158.1	4.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	24	tank	0.3	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	25	tank	0.4	liquid	yes		538.7	8.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	26	tank	0.4	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	1	tank	7.7	WP	no		96519.0	3389.0	346161.0	13231.0	1028.8	3978.3
HCHH_2	4	tank	5.6	WP	no	yes	32709.0	1069.0	105490.9	3438.9	105.0	1217.9
HCHH_2	9	tank	5.1	WP	no		56479.0	4179.0	450080.7	24890.7	705.8	1411.2
HCHH_2	10	tank	6.8	WP	no		85903.1	283.1	52183.8	2189.8	69.5	665.2
HCHH_2	13	tank	6.8	WP	no	yes	19554.2	614.2	65332.5	1333.5	90.5	1697.4
HCHH_2	16	tank	9.4	WP	no	yes	72156.0	916.0	222560.5	7686.5	823.8	559.4
HCHH_2	22	tank	7.5	WP	no		41597.0	2997.0	100002.8	2779.8	180.3	2801.3
HCHH_2	25	tank	7.7	WP	no	yes	79590.0	2200.0	441555.3	15105.3	954.2	4982.5
HCHH_2	26	tank	6.8	WP	no		58774.6	94.6	55904.5	2265.5	224.8	897.9
HCHH_2	30	tank	9.2	WP	no		133149.7	349.7	192730.9	5212.9	728.6	4272.0
HCHH_2	2	tank	3.8	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	3	tank	3.8	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	5	tank	2.7	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	6	tank	2.7	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	7	tank	2.6	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	8	tank	2.6	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	11	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	12	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	14	tank	2.6	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	15	tank	2.6	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	17	tank	4.2	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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HCHH_2	18	tank	4.2	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	19	tank	3.3	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	27	tank	3.3	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	20	tank	3.1	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	21	tank	3.1	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	23	tank	3.5	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	24	tank	3.5	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	28	tank	5.1	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	29	tank	5.1	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	3	tank	5.1	WP	no		145710.0	11210.0	155522.1	3124.1	1014.6	964.6
HCHH_3	6	tank	7.7	WP	no		179582.0	8082.0	568452.2	15222.2	2610.0	8504.4
HCHH_3	7	tank	3.4	WP	no		48739.6	289.6	57510.6	1172.6	161.5	1684.7
HCHH_3	10	tank	5.6	WP	no		129010.0	11310.0	471664.7	4332.7	599.2	2284.9
HCHH_3	18	tank	7.0	WP	no		95915.0	9265.0	239521.8	5981.8	423.8	1857.3
HCHH_3	21	tank	6.8	WP	no		48815.3	115.3	29301.0	1450.0	403.2	958.8
HCHH_3	24	tank	6.8	WP	no		5844.7	104.7	27859.6	2128.6	65.8	1765.6
HCHH_3	30	tank	8.5	WP	no		92805.0	2225.0	423989.5	15059.5	1477.0	4861.8
HCHH_3	33	tank	9.4	WP	no		81532.0	1292.0	133966.9	4630.9	462.2	3528.1
HCHH_3	34	tank	7.7	WP	no		64649.6	969.6	79508.6	3035.6	300.2	5132.7
HCHH_3	1	tank	2.6	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	2	tank	2.6	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	4	tank	3.8	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	5	tank	3.8	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	8	tank	1.7	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	9	tank	1.7	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	12	tank	2.6	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	16	tank	3.2	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	17	tank	3.2	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	19	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	20	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	22	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	23	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	26	tank	4.3	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	27	tank	4.3	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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HCHH_3	29	tank	4.3	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	31	tank	4.7	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	32	tank	4.7	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	35	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	36	tank	3.4	WP	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	3	tank	10.1	liquid	yes		2072.5	62.5	1192.9	29.1	13.2	0.5
HCHH_4	6	tank	12.1	liquid	yes		6407.1	143.1	1056.3	45.3	1.0	1.2
HCHH_4	9	tank	10.1	liquid	yes		3783.1	71.1	564.0	49.6	0.5	0.5
HCHH_4	12	tank	11.8	liquid	yes		707.0	29.7	157.5	4.1	0.5	0.5
HCHH_4	15	tank	11.8	liquid	yes		11431.0	1774.0	11298.4	243.9	3.5	1.6
HCHH_4	18	tank	10.1	liquid	yes	yes	15229.7	149.7	1473.6	19.9	1.1	0.5
HCHH_4	21	tank	13.5	liquid	yes		8233.5	413.5	3763.6	46.6	0.9	0.5
HCHH_4	24	tank	10.1	liquid	yes		14843.0	3903.0	39868.2	215.2	5.4	0.5
HCHH_4	27	tank	13.5	liquid	yes		14912.1	102.1	1410.5	57.8	9.1	1.6
HCHH_4	30	tank	10.1	liquid	yes		7481.4	80.4	355.4	5.6	1.9	0.5
HCHH_4	33	tank	11.8	liquid	yes		3319.9	2.9	5180.8	119.1	3632.0	0.5
HCHH_4	36	tank	10.1	liquid	yes		593.8	50.1	740.2	4.5	12.2	0.5
HCHH_4	1	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	2	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	4	tank	6.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	5	tank	6.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	7	tank	4.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	8	tank	4.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	10	tank	5.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	11	tank	5.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	13	tank	5.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	14	tank	5.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	16	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	17	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	19	tank	6.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	20	tank	6.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	22	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	23	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	25	tank	6.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Study code	Op.#	ML type	TA (kg a.s.)	Form. type	Face shield ML	Glove wash ML	Total Hand ML (µg)	Prot. hand ML (µg)	Total body ML (µg)	Inner body ML (µg)	Head ML (µg)	Inhalation ML (µg)
HCHH_4	26	tank	6.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	28	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	29	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	31	tank	5.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	32	tank	5.9	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	34	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	35	tank	5.1	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	3	tank	0.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	4	tank	0.8	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	5	tank	1.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	6	tank	1.0	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	7	tank	1.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	8	tank	1.2	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	9	tank	0.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	10	tank	0.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	11	tank	0.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	12	tank	0.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	13	tank	0.6	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	14	tank	0.7	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	15	tank	0.5	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_5	16	tank	0.5	liquid	no		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

17.2 Application

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
LCTM_1	A	LCTM	25.1	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	B	LCTM	25.1	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	225.8	16.5	159.0	12.6	12.9	1.4
LCTM_1	C	LCTM	28.2	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	D	LCTM	28.2	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	79.5	79.3	279.8	12.1	9.6	2.1
LCTM_1	E	LCTM	28.5	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	F	LCTM	28.5	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	80.2	5.6	87.9	12.9	12.9	0.3
LCTM_1	G	LCTM	21.3	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	H	LCTM	21.3	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	46.1	46.1	172.6	8.2	23.4	1.1
LCTM_1	I	LCTM	25.0	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	J	LCTM	25.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	6.7	NA	327.5	7.3	4.2	1.4
LCTM_1	K	LCTM	24.0	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	L	LCTM	24.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	17.5	8.9	235.1	2.5	2.4	2.3
LCTM_1	M	LCTM	33.0	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_1	N	LCTM	33.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	58.7	30.2	425.4	6.0	5.3	0.9
LCTM_2	1	LCTM	9.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	1613.4	19.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	2	LCTM	6.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	105.6	55.6	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	3	LCTM	6.8	cabin	other	normal	NA	5.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	4	LCTM	10.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	193.9	33.9	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	5	LCTM	8.8	cabin	other	normal	NA	308.4	98.4	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	6	LCTM	7.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	610.0	500.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	7	LCTM	4.9	cabin	other	normal	NA	390.0	100.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	8	LCTM	10.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	500.0	500.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	9	LCTM	7.5	cabin	other	normal	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	10	LCTM	3.8	cabin	other	normal	NA	50.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	11	LCTM	5.8	cabin	other	normal	NA	5.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	12	LCTM	7.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	5.0	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	13	LCTM	7.9	cabin	other	normal	NA	65.6	65.6	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	14	LCTM	8.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	82.0	82.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_2	15	LCTM	9.6	cabin	other	normal	NA	40.0	40.0	NA	NA	NA	NA

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
LCTM_3	WM	LCTM	7.5	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	JT	LCTM	7.5	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	HM	LCTM	7.5	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	JK	LCTM	7.5	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	RV	LCTM	4.5	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	YB	LCTM	8.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	JM	LCTM	8.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	JD	LCTM	8.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	JB	LCTM	7.5	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_3	EG	LCTM	7.5	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	SH	LCTM	2.5	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	SC	LCTM	2.5	cabin	other	normal	NA	0.0	NA	0.0	0.0	0.0	NA
LCTM_4	TS	LCTM	2.3	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	THR	LCTM	2.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	17.9	NA	26.2	0.5	0.0	NA
LCTM_4	SC	LCTM	3.1	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	SH	LCTM	3.1	cabin	other	normal	NA	6.8	NA	8.3	2.0	0.0	NA
LCTM_4	THR	LCTM	2.9	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_4	TS	LCTM	2.9	cabin	other	normal	NA	12.3	NA	9.3	0.0	0.0	NA
LCTM_5	1	LCTM	200.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	14822.7	99.7	NA	NA	NA	2.8
LCTM_5	2	LCTM	200.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	13.2	13.2	NA	NA	NA	2.1
LCTM_5	3	LCTM	192.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	8441.9	41.9	NA	NA	NA	27.9
LCTM_5	4	LCTM	160.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	22.9	22.9	NA	NA	NA	5.6
LCTM_5	5	LCTM	192.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	6386.0	13.0	NA	NA	NA	13.2
LCTM_5	6	LCTM	192.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	9991.5	57.5	NA	NA	NA	17.3
LCTM_5	7	LCTM	208.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	1.2	1.2	NA	NA	NA	1.7
LCTM_5	8	LCTM	188.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	8125.2	24.2	NA	NA	NA	12.0
LCTM_5	9	LCTM	200.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	20934.3	68.3	NA	NA	NA	14.5
LCTM_5	10	LCTM	200.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	9.4	9.4	NA	NA	NA	7.5
LCTM_5	11	LCTM	179.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	13716.0	313.0	NA	NA	NA	12.5
LCTM_5	12	LCTM	250.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	819.0	NA	NA	NA	NA	69.7
LCTM_6	1	LCTM	1.0	cabin	other	small area	NA	2485.3	21.3	2134.2	29.0	0.0	0.0

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
LCTM_6	2	LCTM	1.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	3	LCTM	0.7	no cabin	other	small area	NA	11.2	NA	454.7	0.0	0.0	0.0
LCTM_6	4	LCTM	0.7	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	5	LCTM	1.0	cabin	other	small area	NA	1555.5	NA	2704.4	6.3	150.0	0.0
LCTM_6	6	LCTM	1.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	7	LCTM	1.0	no cabin	other	small area	NA	321.9	NA	2342.2	24.7	12.8	18.3
LCTM_6	8	LCTM	1.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	9	LCTM	1.2	cabin	other	small area	NA	752.3	2.0	750.7	2.0	4.0	0.0
LCTM_6	10	LCTM	1.2	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	11	LCTM	1.0	cabin	other	small area	NA	426.2	NA	1696.8	26.7	4.0	0.0
LCTM_6	12	LCTM	1.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	13	LCTM	1.0	no cabin	other	small area	NA	219.4	NA	844.5	15.1	4.0	40.9
LCTM_6	14	LCTM	0.9	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	15	LCTM	1.0	no cabin	other	small area	NA	3637.7	NA	903.5	11.8	12.9	5.2
LCTM_6	16	LCTM	1.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	17	LCTM	1.0	cabin	other	small area	NA	392.4	NA	896.3	31.5	4.0	5.2
LCTM_6	18	LCTM	1.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_6	19	LCTM	1.0	cabin	other	small area	NA	980.7	NA	800.4	8.3	0.0	0.0
LCTM_6	20	LCTM	1.0	NA	other	small area	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_7	A	LCTM	14.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	0.0	NA	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_7	B	LCTM	4.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	1440.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_7	C1	LCTM	6.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_7	D	LCTM	13.1	cabin	other	normal	NA	831.7	6.7	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_7	E	LCTM	5.3	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	1.4
LCTM_8	1	LCTM	56.4	cabin	other	normal	NA	6264.0	1537.0	NA	NA	469.5	0.8
LCTM_8	2	LCTM	56.4	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	4	LCTM	47.3	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	5	LCTM	58.6	cabin	other	normal	NA	22448.4	3963.9	4859.9	35.1	61.1	7.8
LCTM_8	6	LCTM	58.6	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	7	LCTM	51.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	11846.2	780.5	7460.4	28.3	92.5	4.5
LCTM_8	8	LCTM	51.0	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
LCTM_8	9	LCTM	68.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	70746.8	NA	21204.9	359.0	266.5	4.7
LCTM_8	10	LCTM	68.0	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	11	LCTM	45.9	cabin	other	normal	NA	6808.1	338.5	3241.4	9.4	41.3	4.5
LCTM_8	12	LCTM	45.9	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	13	LCTM	51.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	26205.7	5271.8	8378.9	79.3	85.9	24.5
LCTM_8	14	LCTM	51.0	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	15	LCTM	68.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	2432.2	NA	1024.2	21.6	63.9	2.2
LCTM_8	16	LCTM	68.0	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	17	LCTM	56.7	cabin	other	normal	NA	1811.3	NA	755.5	44.8	42.5	2.0
LCTM_8	18	LCTM	56.7	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	19	LCTM	64.3	NA	other	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_8	20	LCTM	64.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	1568.4	365.5	5284.2	38.2	210.2	11.1
LCTM_9	1	LCTM	33.5	cabin	other	normal	NA	30000.0	10000.0	706.0	157.0	4600.0	5.4
LCTM_9	2	LCTM	40.7	cabin	other	normal	NA	890.0	NA	1159.0	29.0	34.0	16.4
LCTM_9	3	LCTM	40.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	20500.0	NA	26091.0	91.0	74.0	35.3
LCTM_9	4	LCTM	27.5	cabin	other	normal	NA	3405.0	NA	675.0	15.0	30.0	1.0
LCTM_9	5	LCTM	42.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	45520.0	NA	3195.0	525.0	500.0	4.9
LCTM_9	6	LCTM	26.4	cabin	other	normal	NA	4760.0	NA	7924.0	134.0	118.0	10.0
LCTM_9	7	LCTM	40.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	150.0	NA	204.0	32.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	8	LCTM	50.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	37210.0	NA	235.0	35.0	20.0	0.9
LCTM_9	9	LCTM	35.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	520.0	NA	358.0	53.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	10	LCTM	56.5	cabin	other	normal	NA	3700.0	NA	2802.0	162.0	174.0	5.5
LCTM_9	11	LCTM	45.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	2100.0	NA	2967.0	47.0	198.0	6.8
LCTM_9	12	LCTM	47.5	cabin	other	normal	NA	4850.0	NA	2596.0	116.0	34.0	3.6
LCTM_9	13	LCTM	27.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	350.0	NA	876.0	26.0	110.0	9.5
LCTM_9	14	LCTM	25.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	1500.0	NA	1014.0	46.0	10.0	1.0
LCTM_9	15	LCTM	25.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	27600.0	NA	10688.0	48.0	32.0	6.0
LCTM_9	16	LCTM	41.4	cabin	other	normal	NA	23200.0	NA	6791.0	231.0	400.0	6.7
LCTM_10	A	LCTM	4.6	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	288.7	NA	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	B	LCTM	12.8	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	5.8
LCTM_10	C	LCTM	31.3	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	2.2

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
LCTM_10	D	LCTM	12.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_10	E	LCTM	5.6	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	1980.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.6
LCTM_10	F	LCTM	7.1	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	40.5	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.2
LCTM_10	H	LCTM	15.0	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	2.2
LCTM_11	1	LCTM	203.8	cabin	other	normal	NA	13092.6	23.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	2	LCTM	195.8	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	1460.7	19.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	3	LCTM	213.6	cabin	other	normal	NA	118.0	18.6	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	4	LCTM	211.8	cabin	other	normal	NA	296.3	9.3	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	6	LCTM	209.5	cabin	other	normal	NA	3083.4	7.4	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	7	LCTM	212.1	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	26422.2	8.3	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	8	LCTM	211.6	cabin	other	normal	NA	1207.0	252.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	9	LCTM	213.4	cabin	coarse	normal	NA	28496.3	34.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	11	LCTM	199.0	cabin	other	normal	NA	1130.8	109.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	12	LCTM	199.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	44963.5	177.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	13	LCTM	211.8	cabin	other	normal	NA	3711.9	1910.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCTM_11	14	LCTM	162.3	cabin	other	normal	NA	24231.7	231.0	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	1	HCTM	1.4	no cabin	other	NA	NA	1173.7	33.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	2	HCTM	1.2	no cabin	other	NA	NA	1369.2	9.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	3	HCTM	1.2	no cabin	other	NA	NA	2757.8	57.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	4	HCTM	1.3	no cabin	other	NA	NA	1513.2	53.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	5	HCTM	1.0	no cabin	other	NA	NA	815.5	12.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	6	HCTM	1.2	no cabin	other	NA	NA	1890.6	20.6	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	7	HCTM	1.9	cabin	other	NA	NA	2586.8	6.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	8	HCTM	1.9	no cabin	other	NA	NA	3047.8	17.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	9	HCTM	1.2	no cabin	other	NA	NA	89.5	33.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_1	10	HCTM	1.3	no cabin	other	NA	NA	333.9	34.9	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	1	HCTM	5.8	cabin	other	NA	NA	9810.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	2	HCTM	8.3	no cabin	other	NA	NA	24557.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	3	HCTM	9.3	cabin	other	NA	NA	316.0	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	4	HCTM	6.9	cabin	other	NA	NA	904.9	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	5	HCTM	6.9	cabin	other	NA	NA	205.0	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
HCTM_2	6	HCTM	5.4	cabin	other	NA	NA	778.4	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	7	HCTM	3.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	7018.3	51.3	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	8	HCTM	5.5	cabin	other	NA	NA	550.1	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	10	HCTM	5.3	cabin	other	NA	NA	10863.8	153.8	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	11	HCTM	4.7	no cabin	other	NA	NA	10652.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	12	HCTM	6.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	1539.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	13	HCTM	4.8	cabin	other	NA	NA	3335.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	14	HCTM	8.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	584.4	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	15	HCTM	5.5	cabin	other	NA	NA	597.7	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_2	17	HCTM	4.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	2083.5	102.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	1	HCTM	2.7	no cabin	other	NA	NA	940.0	NA	5252.0	102.0	46.0	54.2
HCTM_3	2	HCTM	2.7	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	3	HCTM	2.4	cabin	other	NA	NA	142.0	NA	679.2	15.2	2.0	28.1
HCTM_3	4	HCTM	2.4	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	5	HCTM	2.7	no cabin	other	NA	NA	6810.0	NA	8110.0	100.0	34.0	33.3
HCTM_3	6	HCTM	2.7	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	7	HCTM	3.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	43.0	NA	68.0	4.0	2.0	5.2
HCTM_3	8	HCTM	3.0	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	9	HCTM	3.4	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	10	HCTM	3.4	no cabin	other	NA	NA	920.0	NA	8154.0	154.0	48.4	166.7
HCTM_3	11	HCTM	3.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	3900.0	NA	24217.0	217.0	56.0	270.8
HCTM_3	12	HCTM	3.6	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	13	HCTM	3.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	3180.0	NA	17562.0	262.0	48.0	93.8
HCTM_3	14	HCTM	3.6	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	15	HCTM	3.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	4700.0	NA	29479.0	379.0	40.0	416.7
HCTM_3	16	HCTM	3.6	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	17	HCTM	3.2	no cabin	other	NA	NA	5710.0	NA	23079.0	229.0	116.0	260.4
HCTM_3	18	HCTM	3.2	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	19	HCTM	3.6	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_3	20	HCTM	3.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	9020.0	NA	11206.0	246.0	16.4	135.4
HCTM_3	21	HCTM	3.0	no cabin	other	NA	NA	4160.0	NA	17640.0	440.0	94.0	218.8

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
HCTM_5	8A	HCTM	13.7	cabin	other	NA	NA	485.7	NA	16484.0	928.3	204.2	182.0
HCTM_5	8M	HCTM	15.8	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	9A	HCTM	5.5	cabin	other	NA	NA	382.5	269.6	18006.7	480.4	16.7	22.1
HCTM_5	9B	HCTM	9.8	no cabin	other	NA	NA	11103.8	NA	62876.9	926.1	879.2	131.2
HCTM_5	9M	HCTM	21.0	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	10A	HCTM	7.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	573.4	325.0	4218.0	106.5	41.7	12.2
HCTM_5	10M	HCTM	7.0	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	11A	HCTM	10.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	630.2	62.5	757.9	102.2	29.2	15.6
HCTM_5	11M	HCTM	19.8	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_5	14A	HCTM	12.9	cabin	other	NA	NA	767.7	616.1	33981.4	810.9	87.5	30.3
HCTM_5	14M	HCTM	16.8	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCTM_6	1	HCTM	4.5	no cabin	other	NA	NA	9660.0	NA	231372.6	792.6	16560.0	72.9
HCTM_6	2	HCTM	3.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	97980.0	9080.0	51717.8	397.8	13180.0	50.0
HCTM_6	3	HCTM	3.6	no cabin	other	NA	NA	66920.0	NA	432944.1	1474.1	72640.0	56.3
HCTM_6	4	HCTM	5.0	no cabin	other	NA	NA	9450.0	3850.0	34237.7	277.7	3240.0	35.4
HCTM_6	5	HCTM	2.4	no cabin	other	NA	NA	6260.0	NA	257516.3	426.3	87860.0	33.3
HCTM_6	6	HCTM	7.2	no cabin	other	NA	NA	9820.0	6620.0	63577.7	827.7	12280.0	NA
HCTM_6	7	HCTM	8.0	no cabin	other	NA	NA	820.0	220.0	62158.7	928.7	4820.0	23614.6
HCTM_6	8	HCTM	6.3	no cabin	other	NA	NA	38980.0	180.0	191696.8	4016.8	44420.0	45.8
HCTM_6	9	HCTM	6.7	cabin	other	NA	NA	2910.0	NA	6274.1	844.1	NA	12.5
HCTM_6	10	HCTM	10.0	no cabin	other	NA	NA	28240.0	NA	77100.2	1070.2	11580.0	54.2
HCTM_6	11	HCTM	6.3	no cabin	other	NA	NA	9730.0	3530.0	50649.9	249.9	7580.0	16.7
HCTM_6	12	HCTM	6.0	no cabin	other	NA	NA	12360.0	260.0	96226.1	796.1	21320.0	31.3
HCTM_6	13	HCTM	3.8	cabin	other	NA	NA	4560.0	2860.0	12146.1	156.1	3400.0	12.5
HCTM_6	14	HCTM	5.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	5580.0	380.0	8211.6	111.6	480.0	12.5
HCTM_6	15	HCTM	3.6	cabin	other	NA	NA	6800.0	6800.0	38287.6	187.6	700.0	20.8
HCTM_6	16	HCTM	5.4	cabin	other	NA	NA	190.0	190.0	293.1	13.1	40.0	4.2
HCTM_6	17	HCTM	3.8	cabin	other	NA	NA	3300.0	NA	22178.1	218.1	220.0	12.5
HCTM_7	A	HCTM	4.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	4518.0	43.0	NA	NA	NA	4.8
HCTM_7	B	HCTM	8.0	cabin	other	NA	NA	0.0	0.0	NA	NA	NA	3.4
HCTM_7	C	HCTM	7.5	cabin	other	NA	NA	29931.6	222.4	NA	NA	NA	5.1

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
LCHH_4	13	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	14	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	15	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	17	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	18	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCHH_4	19	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	1197.7	NA	88868.4	8516.3	48.1	6.9
LCHH_4	20	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	3230.8	NA	75215.8	8902.8	34.5	9.4
LCHH_4	21	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	4812.8	NA	119849.3	24321.3	85.0	2.6
LCHH_4	23	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	3256.4	NA	43587.4	620.3	27.8	12.5
LCHH_4	24	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	2610.3	NA	40115.4	917.3	5.0	10.2
LCHH_4	25	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	311.5	NA	45087.2	1735.3	11.9	8.0
LCHH_4	26	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	1793.8	NA	95575.0	25260.2	21.1	7.3
LCHH_4	27	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	4635.9	NA	45839.9	1250.7	224.4	7.5
LCHH_4	28	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	879.0	NA	34815.8	1661.3	5.0	12.7
LCHH_4	30	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	493.3	NA	24009.5	625.5	5.0	14.6
LCHH_4	31	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	928.2	NA	35453.4	5672.5	15.0	9.8
LCHH_4	33	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	899.2	NA	106397.3	35806.0	5.0	8.6
LCHH_4	34	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	166.0	NA	40211.1	1525.0	5.0	8.6
LCHH_4	35	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	2088.7	NA	16957.0	517.9	35.4	7.1
LCHH_4	36	LCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	NA	186.2	NA	20806.4	764.7	5.0	12.5
HCHH_1	1	HCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	2	HCHH	0.2	NA	other	NA	normal	190.0	2.0	2269.2	6.0	4.0	6.5
HCHH_1	3	HCHH	0.3	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	4	HCHH	0.3	NA	other	NA	normal	86.8	2.0	2455.4	27.1	4.0	11.4
HCHH_1	7	HCHH	0.4	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	8	HCHH	0.4	NA	other	NA	normal	29.6	2.0	2387.5	18.7	18.4	2.1
HCHH_1	9	HCHH	0.8	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	10	HCHH	0.6	NA	other	NA	normal	17479.6	2.0	220190.2	1938.2	919.2	135.6
HCHH_1	11	HCHH	0.5	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	12	HCHH	0.5	NA	other	NA	normal	1713.6	2.0	177535.1	8980.1	157.9	44.1
HCHH_1	13	HCHH	0.3	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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HCHH_1	14	HCHH	0.3	NA	other	NA	normal	3785.6	2.0	51719.3	561.3	119.1	34.4
HCHH_1	15	HCHH	0.5	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	16	HCHH	0.5	NA	other	NA	normal	1382.0	2.0	7612.6	50.2	32.6	20.8
HCHH_1	17	HCHH	0.4	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	18	HCHH	0.3	NA	other	NA	normal	542.1	4.2	2484.3	20.8	10.9	19.6
HCHH_1	19	HCHH	0.6	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	20	HCHH	0.3	NA	other	NA	normal	11.4	2.0	2475.2	14.7	4.0	12.0
HCHH_1	21	HCHH	0.7	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	22	HCHH	0.5	NA	other	NA	normal	2352.7	2.0	9330.0	75.1	58.1	18.8
HCHH_1	23	HCHH	0.4	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	24	HCHH	0.3	NA	other	NA	normal	16.6	2.0	2129.3	10.4	4.0	5.9
HCHH_1	25	HCHH	0.4	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_1	26	HCHH	0.4	NA	other	NA	normal	194.8	2.0	19771.6	104.7	4.0	14.9
HCHH_2	1	HCHH	7.7	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	4	HCHH	5.6	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	9	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	10	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	13	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	16	HCHH	9.4	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	22	HCHH	7.5	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	25	HCHH	7.7	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	26	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	30	HCHH	9.2	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_2	2	HCHH	3.8	NA	other	NA	dense	37620.3	710.3	1396912.5	23312.5	1377.8	385.7
HCHH_2	3	HCHH	3.8	NA	other	NA	dense	47461.0	741.0	1182691.1	10531.1	1219.4	389.3
HCHH_2	5	HCHH	2.7	NA	other	NA	dense	44048.7	268.7	1538183.2	39583.2	403.8	252.4
HCHH_2	6	HCHH	2.7	NA	other	NA	dense	33725.0	335.0	2186007.2	40507.2	361.2	421.7
HCHH_2	7	HCHH	2.6	NA	other	NA	dense	14370.6	430.6	588835.7	23145.7	534.8	121.1
HCHH_2	8	HCHH	2.6	NA	other	NA	dense	14067.0	1257.0	428364.9	6294.9	164.5	101.5
HCHH_2	11	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	32178.7	238.7	1855320.0	217320.0	530.0	333.2
HCHH_2	12	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	21332.4	62.4	686729.0	77549.0	129.7	168.1

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HCHH_2	14	HCHH	2.6	NA	other	NA	dense	28730.8	250.8	840102.6	8532.6	208.0	155.8
HCHH_2	15	HCHH	2.6	NA	other	NA	dense	18115.0	15.0	553056.6	12466.6	402.0	161.4
HCHH_2	17	HCHH	4.2	NA	other	NA	dense	60345.6	265.6	2346040.0	305040.0	3764.0	364.4
HCHH_2	18	HCHH	4.2	NA	other	NA	dense	57473.0	763.0	2218137.0	188037.0	4048.0	328.7
HCHH_2	19	HCHH	3.3	NA	other	NA	dense	15030.9	80.9	746416.2	8216.2	1361.0	270.6
HCHH_2	27	HCHH	3.3	NA	other	NA	dense	29395.7	55.7	686657.8	14507.8	1694.0	237.7
HCHH_2	20	HCHH	3.1	NA	other	NA	dense	28546.6	66.6	741366.5	11566.5	379.0	230.9
HCHH_2	21	HCHH	3.1	NA	other	NA	dense	22803.0	1043.0	436281.8	5731.8	470.0	214.4
HCHH_2	23	HCHH	3.5	NA	other	NA	dense	30796.1	126.1	1140427.0	30327.0	703.6	185.0
HCHH_2	24	HCHH	3.5	NA	other	NA	dense	28844.0	254.0	1348956.7	52056.7	1967.8	234.0
HCHH_2	28	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	dense	45899.0	119.0	1605165.0	66565.0	3496.0	255.5
HCHH_2	29	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	dense	73704.6	144.6	1785824.0	103924.0	3280.0	313.5
HCHH_3	3	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	6	HCHH	7.7	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	7	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	10	HCHH	5.6	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	18	HCHH	7.0	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	21	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	24	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	30	HCHH	8.5	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	33	HCHH	9.4	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	34	HCHH	7.7	NA	other	NA	dense	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_3	1	HCHH	2.6	NA	other	NA	dense	30248.2	338.2	205029.9	2389.9	1117.2	345.3
HCHH_3	2	HCHH	2.6	NA	other	NA	dense	40007.1	537.1	309541.0	4411.0	709.0	249.2
HCHH_3	4	HCHH	3.8	NA	other	NA	dense	33286.2	436.2	320400.4	4290.4	1129.8	397.0
HCHH_3	5	HCHH	3.8	NA	other	NA	dense	44837.7	217.7	551992.2	8092.2	3214.0	355.6
HCHH_3	8	HCHH	1.7	NA	other	NA	dense	21715.9	65.9	341465.5	10105.5	357.2	185.5
HCHH_3	9	HCHH	1.7	NA	other	NA	dense	29877.8	127.8	482533.9	8553.9	740.2	229.1
HCHH_3	12	HCHH	2.6	NA	other	NA	dense	53495.0	1025.0	1398261.1	71781.1	1139.0	540.5
HCHH_3	16	HCHH	3.2	NA	other	NA	dense	31097.0	1357.0	575811.3	6161.3	776.8	266.1
HCHH_3	17	HCHH	3.2	NA	other	NA	dense	14012.5	102.5	267811.1	3901.1	452.6	156.3

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HCHH_3	19	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	36834.0	254.0	669147.2	6727.2	1136.4	2136.3
HCHH_3	20	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	58171.0	1381.0	1891400.0	41000.0	5176.0	551.4
HCHH_3	22	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	64775.9	835.9	1996593.0	51393.0	2788.0	562.2
HCHH_3	23	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	50385.3	75.3	587522.8	3422.8	1136.4	692.4
HCHH_3	26	HCHH	4.3	NA	other	NA	dense	28532.7	72.7	380362.0	3642.0	2048.0	399.0
HCHH_3	27	HCHH	4.3	NA	other	NA	dense	28672.9	462.9	409798.9	3038.9	4282.0	503.7
HCHH_3	29	HCHH	4.3	NA	other	NA	dense	44019.9	389.9	501508.7	4888.7	848.2	675.4
HCHH_3	31	HCHH	4.7	NA	other	NA	dense	51673.3	163.3	967294.5	4834.5	5274.0	528.4
HCHH_3	32	HCHH	4.7	NA	other	NA	dense	34154.9	344.9	1195969.0	11669.0	4248.0	449.9
HCHH_3	35	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	78038.0	1368.0	2470393.0	136393.0	5394.0	949.1
HCHH_3	36	HCHH	3.4	NA	other	NA	dense	66785.8	355.8	1323720.0	44920.0	1893.8	392.8
HCHH_4	3	HCHH	10.1	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	6	HCHH	12.1	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	9	HCHH	10.1	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	12	HCHH	11.8	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	15	HCHH	11.8	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	18	HCHH	10.1	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	21	HCHH	13.5	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	24	HCHH	10.1	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	27	HCHH	13.5	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	30	HCHH	10.1	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	33	HCHH	11.8	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	36	HCHH	10.1	NA	other	NA	normal	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
HCHH_4	1	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	1245.9	5.9	5824.0	88.4	8.4	44.6
HCHH_4	2	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	1640.7	8.7	4920.2	42.1	9.3	57.6
HCHH_4	4	HCHH	6.0	NA	other	NA	normal	30547.5	877.5	181782.1	1033.1	1055.8	359.4
HCHH_4	5	HCHH	6.0	NA	other	NA	normal	12242.0	192.0	116092.6	673.6	184.4	177.6
HCHH_4	7	HCHH	4.2	NA	other	NA	normal	7852.2	121.2	77026.3	303.3	126.8	334.0
HCHH_4	8	HCHH	4.2	NA	other	NA	normal	6539.9	59.9	35664.0	351.0	36.5	207.5
HCHH_4	10	HCHH	5.9	NA	other	NA	normal	5969.0	1958.0	21599.9	241.9	17.1	214.1
HCHH_4	11	HCHH	5.9	NA	other	NA	normal	4341.3	353.3	14393.3	123.3	40.0	134.9

Study code	Op.#	A type	TA (kg a.s.)	Cabin status	Droplet type	Equipment type	Culture type	Total hand A (µg)	Prot. hand A (µg)	Total body A (µg)	Inner body A (µg)	Head A (µg)	Inhalation A (µg)
HCHH_4	13	HCHH	5.9	NA	other	NA	normal	34301.5	141.5	152194.2	1732.2	295.6	378.5
HCHH_4	14	HCHH	5.9	NA	other	NA	normal	60542.4	252.4	254373.0	1113.0	1471.6	2165.6
HCHH_4	16	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	9034.3	213.3	55710.8	365.8	174.4	28.0
HCHH_4	17	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	6543.1	365.1	52851.0	411.0	256.6	29.2
HCHH_4	19	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	normal	5579.6	32.6	36232.0	201.1	98.9	238.0
HCHH_4	20	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	normal	2112.3	6.3	10973.6	171.5	66.5	154.3
HCHH_4	22	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	13889.4	629.4	39838.1	658.1	17.4	257.4
HCHH_4	23	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	2472.9	349.9	11528.1	200.6	27.1	229.8
HCHH_4	25	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	normal	5174.8	19.8	9015.8	139.0	38.6	132.5
HCHH_4	26	HCHH	6.8	NA	other	NA	normal	7626.2	264.2	37474.7	200.2	46.7	123.9
HCHH_4	28	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	2810.2	79.2	31240.6	268.6	149.0	42.3
HCHH_4	29	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	14297.3	177.3	22283.4	241.4	67.2	38.9
HCHH_4	31	HCHH	5.9	NA	other	NA	normal	4092.7	44.7	16036.4	637.6	12.5	95.6
HCHH_4	32	HCHH	5.9	NA	other	NA	normal	2529.7	86.7	11128.8	199.5	9.3	0.5
HCHH_4	34	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	3905.6	47.6	5969.7	530.2	44.5	480.2
HCHH_4	35	HCHH	5.1	NA	other	NA	normal	2994.9	46.9	1739.6	204.4	24.1	400.2
HCHH_5	3	HCHH	0.8	NA	other	NA	normal	3309.1	0.1	132803.6	2833.6	769.0	66.9
HCHH_5	4	HCHH	0.8	NA	other	NA	normal	2547.0	4.0	81714.1	1704.1	118.7	25.6
HCHH_5	5	HCHH	1.0	NA	other	NA	normal	1256.1	0.1	71351.4	1472.4	382.0	58.1
HCHH_5	6	HCHH	1.0	NA	other	NA	normal	1633.1	0.1	53381.4	1496.4	227.4	83.8
HCHH_5	7	HCHH	1.2	NA	other	NA	normal	3213.1	0.1	93188.3	1523.3	466.6	77.1
HCHH_5	8	HCHH	1.2	NA	other	NA	normal	2642.2	0.2	24009.3	789.3	309.0	36.5
HCHH_5	9	HCHH	0.6	NA	other	NA	normal	1271.1	0.1	17113.0	766.0	94.9	9.4
HCHH_5	10	HCHH	0.6	NA	other	NA	normal	1214.0	2.0	9745.9	229.8	56.6	16.9
HCHH_5	11	HCHH	0.6	NA	other	NA	normal	373.0	1.0	4595.7	70.8	25.7	3.3
HCHH_5	12	HCHH	0.6	NA	other	NA	normal	596.8	0.1	12581.7	240.2	83.0	3.9
HCHH_5	13	HCHH	0.6	NA	other	NA	normal	975.8	3.0	70383.1	1720.1	129.6	62.5
HCHH_5	14	HCHH	0.7	NA	other	NA	normal	476.4	1.0	11400.7	126.2	20.6	41.3
HCHH_5	15	HCHH	0.5	NA	other	NA	normal	834.2	0.1	36706.6	1880.6	122.7	87.3
HCHH_5	16	HCHH	0.5	NA	other	NA	normal	547.3	0.1	30433.2	1644.2	72.6	157.3

NA: not available

18 Tables of empirical percentiles

18.1 ML tank

Total hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
WG	41	10.7	227.8	894.4	2172.2	3007.9	7162.3
WP	20	859.5	10661.1	13904.6	23044.3	23729.6	28570.6
liquid	169	4.0	1068.3	2842.4	5652.6	11636.4	26852.8
all	230	4.0	996.5	3110.0	8737.9	14076.9	28570.6

Protected hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
WG	41	0.1	2.8	8.1	15.3	31.5	126.4
WP	20	13.9	164.4	537.1	1397.9	2025.1	2198.0
liquid	167	0.0	6.1	18.9	62.2	194.5	595.2
all	228	0.0	7.0	22.1	130.2	313.9	2198.0

Total body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
WG	29	36.6	437.4	955.9	1395.5	3194.7	4040.7
WP	20	4097.0	19899.4	46407.6	75284.3	84284.5	88251.1
liquid	80	13.3	661.3	1895.5	5293.6	11746.1	38701.6
all	129	13.3	861.9	3971.1	21556.4	36966.8	88251.1

Inner body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
WG	29	0.0	7.9	15.8	31.9	50.6	85.2
WP	20	196.1	590.2	1076.1	1976.1	2134.4	4880.5
liquid	80	0.2	4.8	20.5	48.0	151.6	544.5
all	129	0.0	8.6	38.5	416.5	802.2	4880.5

Head exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
WG	29	0.0	3.5	6.5	39.9	80.2	94.0
WP	20	9.7	60.0	127.2	176.3	206.1	341.2
liquid	80	0.0	2.8	23.3	69.5	172.6	742.4
all	129	0.0	4.0	38.9	96.5	170.9	742.4

Inhalation exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
WG	41	0.0	4.6	9.4	13.3	13.9	38.7
WP	20	59.8	325.6	501.6	653.3	693.0	1111.7
liquid	100	0.0	0.2	0.9	1.9	3.5	18.2
all	161	0.0	0.5	5.4	141.0	377.3	1111.7

18.2 ML knapsackTotal hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	49	180.3	21394.0	41727.2	64839.0	102504.5	243414.5

Protected hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	49	0.2	20.8	63.3	647.9	730.9	1512.8

Total body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	40	137.6	1737.6	3530.8	7533.7	15553.4	77682.1

Inner body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	40	0.1	54.5	115.6	373.4	639.5	1405.3

Head exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	40	0.1	22.2	23.3	41.7	51.3	84.7

Inhalation exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	40	0.1	36.1	112.9	115.7	115.7	118.7

18.3 Application LCTM

Total hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal droplets	80	0.0	71.1	447.8	1155.6	2626.0	5451.1
coarse droplets *	27	0.0	2.8	57.4	128.2	287.7	360.2
normal equip.	87	0.0	19.4	103.4	369.4	689.1	1104.0
small equip.	20	15.6	646.9	2336.2	3828.0	4239.8	5451.1
all	107	0.0	46.7	273.2	1029.1	2072.8	5451.1

Protected hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal droplets	43	0.0	3.4	21.4	70.8	100.3	298.5
coarse droplets *	21	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.9	2.2	2.8
normal equip.	58	0.0	0.6	5.3	22.6	67.8	298.5
small equip.	6	1.7	52.0	72.0	91.1	100.5	109.9
all	64	0.0	0.8	8.9	62.0	72.1	298.5

Total body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal droplets	49	0.0	164.0	827.9	1858.6	2666.1	4298.8
coarse droplets *	6	3.1	9.0	12.1	13.0	13.0	13.1
normal equip.	35	0.0	24.5	78.9	245.8	346.5	652.3
small equip.	20	99.0	937.4	1881.4	2949.0	4144.4	4298.8
all	55	0.0	82.9	667.6	1695.7	2553.0	4298.8

Inner body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal droplets	49	0.0	2.4	14.5	32.3	45.7	56.7
coarse droplets *	6	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5
normal equip.	35	0.0	0.7	1.9	4.9	5.4	12.4
small equip.	20	0.0	18.6	32.3	49.9	52.5	56.7
all	55	0.0	1.8	12.4	31.4	42.7	56.7

Head exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal droplets	50	0.0	2.5	8.3	24.9	147.7	362.7
coarse droplets *	6	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.8	1.0	1.1
normal equip.	36	0.0	0.9	3.1	6.4	10.2	137.3
small equip.	20	0.0	6.7	16.5	159.2	194.6	362.7
all	56	0.0	1.7	6.1	17.8	142.0	362.7

Inhalation exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal droplets	49	0.0	0.1	0.4	5.9	22.3	40.8
coarse droplets *	24	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.7
normal equip.	56	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.9
small equip.	17	0.0	1.1	8.0	30.7	40.2	40.8
all	73	0.0	0.1	0.4	2.6	12.4	40.8

* nozzles are assumed to produce a 'coarse' droplet spectrum when they are classified for at least 50 % drift reduction (according to definition by Julius Kühn Institut)

18.4 Application HCTMTotal hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
no cabin	55	34.9	1136.3	2216.9	2903.3	4970.1	27216.7
cabin	54	0.0	137.4	1126.1	1831.2	2051.8	24210.7
all	109	0.0	699.3	1644.0	2539.4	3793.6	27216.7

Protected hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
no cabin	32	2.2	13.7	28.4	513.1	837.3	2522.2
cabin	35	0.0	18.6	40.8	93.4	394.2	1888.9
all	67	0.0	17.7	32.4	157.5	767.8	2522.2

Total body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
no cabin	42	386.9	6517.1	8655.9	15998.0	50378.9	120262.2
cabin	30	22.7	765.7	2862.0	6151.2	8322.6	10635.5
all	72	22.7	3157.1	7630.4	11070.0	22622.9	120262.2

Inner body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
no cabin	42	7.9	71.1	113.8	184.5	224.0	642.7
cabin	30	0.5	24.7	66.7	96.3	145.2	188.1
all	72	0.5	48.9	95.2	174.6	198.4	642.7

Head exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
no cabin	42	3.7	144.3	1110.3	3650.3	6935.8	36608.3
cabin	29	0.0	4.9	15.0	115.2	193.4	906.7
all	71	0.0	36.8	262.0	1705.6	3670.6	36608.3

Inhalation exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
no cabin	41	2.7	18.9	33.7	72.9	82.7	2951.8
cabin	42	0.1	2.0	5.3	13.3	20.8	45.4
all	83	0.1	10.4	21.3	43.8	72.6	2951.8

18.5 Application LCHHTotal hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	48	0.2	2114.1	7139.8	14393.2	17372.2	21390.3

Protected hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	20	0.1	3.5	15.6	110.0	200.3	493.9

Total body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	39	4440.1	192606.4	409874.2	533674.2	583893.8	723831.6

Inner body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	39	34.9	6777.6	38709.1	160559.6	181348.0	312267.1

Head exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	39	0.1	22.2	47.2	154.3	230.2	997.3

Inhalation exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
all	39	0.1	52.0	115.7	115.7	115.7	118.7

18.6 Application HCHH

Total hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal crop	50	42.3	1261.0	2516.7	4471.0	8232.1	28749.4
dense crop	40	4392.6	10595.6	14509.9	17722.8	19492.7	22685.5
all	90	42.3	4399.2	10324.9	14900.1	18387.3	28749.4

Protected hand exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal crop	50	0.0	5.8	21.8	60.6	100.7	330.7
dense crop	40	5.7	83.5	184.1	398.1	407.1	492.9
all	90	0.0	24.2	87.6	196.5	368.0	492.9

Total body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal crop	50	343.1	11868.3	39750.4	101233.8	159723.5	367567.5
dense crop	40	80089.8	233322.3	385370.5	564948.3	593778.4	824286.3
all	90	343.1	81872.6	229477.8	401624.2	560133.6	824286.3

Inner body exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal crop	50	8.3	107.0	583.7	2737.7	3363.0	18592.3
dense crop	40	715.0	4553.8	14928.7	29299.4	46085.5	73238.9
all	90	8.3	1186.6	3685.0	15131.5	25746.0	73238.9

Head exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal crop	50	1.6	32.8	153.1	330.1	378.9	1511.8
dense crop	40	38.2	348.4	659.2	975.5	1146.7	1568.0
all	90	1.6	152.4	371.5	845.6	991.5	1568.0

Inhalation exposure ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg a.s.}$)

	n	min	50 th perc.	75 th perc.	90 th perc.	95 th perc.	max
normal crop	50	0.1	38.6	68.4	98.2	199.7	365.8
dense crop	40	39.8	95.7	122.6	169.2	215.2	628.3
all	90	0.1	63.6	97.9	162.5	218.1	628.3

19 Model computations (75th percentile)

ML - tank

Model: log total hands ML/TA ~ form + glove.wash.ML

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	41	218.70000	1997.005	3885.253	6056.21	6926.498	40938.82
WP	20	5844.70000	75873.000	96066.000	134405.73	147403.600	179582.00
liquid	169	71.49891	8250.000	30250.500	127822.26	553048.508	2346735.63

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	glove.wash.ML	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP		0	29670.1581	14335.1765
2	10	WP		1	296701.5812	143351.7647
3	100	WP		2	2967015.8123	1433517.6471
4	1	WG		0	826.2926	989.4997
5	10	WG		1	8262.9260	9894.9967
6	100	WG		2	82629.2599	98949.9671
7	1	liquid		0	2730.3876	3144.0000
8	10	liquid		1	27303.8760	31440.0000
9	100	liquid		2	273038.7604	314400.0000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.39441	-0.43021	0.01458	0.47816	1.43035

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.4752	0.1049	23.589	< 2e-16 ***
formWP	1.5498	0.1761	8.799	3.62e-16 ***
formliquid	0.5235	0.1137	4.603	6.96e-06 ***
glove.wash.MLyes	-0.2752	0.1321	-2.084	0.0383 *

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6457 on 226 degrees of freedom

(273 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2676, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2579

F-statistic: 27.53 on 3 and 226 DF, p-value: 3.275e-15

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total hands ML/TA ~ form + glove.wash.ML

N: 230 tau: 0.75 AIC: 487.015245897035

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.9954157	2.7220722	3.1789693	0.1752578	17.091485
0.000000000000					
formWP	1.1609874	1.0630038	1.3975553	0.2342417	4.956365
0.000001408633					
formliquid	0.5020669	0.3037828	0.7832727	0.1774336	2.829604
0.005079946194					
glove.wash.MLyes	-0.2162037	-0.3174291	-0.1421132	0.1279344	-1.689958
0.092414890107					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total hands ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.475 + 1.55 \text{ formWP} + 0.523 \text{ formliquid} + -0.275 \text{ glove.wash.MLyes}$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total hands ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.995 + 1.161 \text{ formWP} + 0.502 \text{ formliquid} + -0.216 \text{ glove.wash.MLyes}$

=====
Model: log total hands ML ~ logTA + form + glove.wash.ML

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	41	218.70000	1997.005	3885.253	6056.21	6926.498	40938.82
WP	20	5844.70000	75873.000	96066.000	134405.73	147403.600	179582.00
liquid	169	71.49891	8250.000	30250.500	127822.26	553048.508	2346735.63

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	glove.wash.ML	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP		0	50768.092	24160.752
2	10	WP		1	261444.210	142214.928
3	100	WP		2	1358732.619	837104.971
4	1	WG		0	1416.019	1310.937
5	10	WG		1	7291.778	7716.433
6	100	WG		2	37897.700	45420.440
7	1	liquid		0	5191.412	4856.967
8	10	liquid		1	26693.708	28589.062
9	100	liquid		2	138544.100	168280.830

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.20324	-0.42676	0.01194	0.40950	1.59322

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.72681	0.11377	23.968	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.71328	0.06106	11.682	< 2e-16 ***
formWP	1.54937	0.16846	9.197	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	0.56778	0.10919	5.200	0.000000447 ***
glove.wash.MLyes	-0.33484	0.12698	-2.637	0.00895 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6176 on 225 degrees of freedom

(273 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5191, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5105

F-statistic: 60.71 on 4 and 225 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)`

Formula: `log total hands ML ~ logTA + form + glove.wash.ML`

N: 230 tau: 0.75 AIC: 469.946267705629

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	3.1175819	2.8754018	3.2851596	0.17488598	17.826368
0.0000000000000000					
lTA	0.7698347	0.6051726	0.8928660	0.08008650	9.612540
0.0000000000000000					
formWP	1.2655286	1.1441228	1.5906277	0.21947736	5.766101
0.00000002659407					

```
formliquid      0.5687833  0.4339356  0.8596325  0.15934428  3.569525
0.00043712533823
glove.wash.MLyes -0.2865531 -0.4339894 -0.2724298  0.09230508 -3.104413
0.00215121712002
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(total hands ML) = 2.727 + 0.713 log(TA) + 1.549 formWP + 0.568 formliquid + -
0.335 glove.wash.MLyes
```

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(total hands ML) = 3.118 + 0.77 log(TA) + 1.266 formWP + 0.569 formliquid + -
0.287 glove.wash.MLyes
```

```
=====
Model: log protected hands ML/TA ~ form
```

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	41	0.20	23.57881	67.85714	146.6098	285.7143	948.10
WP	20	94.60	1180.50000	3586.50000	9459.5000	11215.0000	11310.00
liquid	167	0.01	44.11000	127.50000	698.0000	2270.0844	33747.49

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0	918.07622	443.006536
2	10	WP	1	9180.76221	4430.065359
3	100	WP	2	91807.62212	44300.653595
4	1	WG	0	16.42872	8.050558
5	10	WG	1	164.28718	80.505575
6	100	WG	2	1642.87182	805.055750
7	1 liquid		0	18.59977	18.889693
8	10 liquid		1	185.99771	188.896929
9	100 liquid		2	1859.97713	1888.969286

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.4465	-0.5423	0.1350	0.6738	2.2032

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.51120	0.16089	3.177	0.00169 **
formWP	1.73852	0.28098	6.187	0.00000000286 ***
formliquid	0.06026	0.17955	0.336	0.73748

```
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Residual standard error: 1.03 on 225 degrees of freedom

(275 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.1795, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1722

F-statistic: 24.61 on 2 and 225 DF, p-value: 2.157e-10

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log protected hands ML/TA ~ form

N: 228 tau: 0.75 AIC: 650.151037692079

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.9058260	0.7019279	1.1615873	0.1486089	6.095369	0.000000004696293
formWP	1.7405842	1.4216869	2.2430219	0.3278408	5.309235	0.000000263703363
formliquid	0.3703989	0.1133886	0.6456845	0.1671939	2.215386	0.027735803395846

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$$\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.511 + 1.739 \text{ formWP} + 0.06 \text{ formliquid}$$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$$\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.906 + 1.741 \text{ formWP} + 0.37 \text{ formliquid}$$

=====
Model: log protected hands ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	41	0.20	23.57881	67.85714	146.6098	285.7143	948.10
WP	20	94.60	1180.50000	3586.50000	9459.5000	11215.0000	11310.00
liquid	167	0.01	44.11000	127.50000	698.0000	2270.0844	33747.49

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0	2617.69487	901.39898
2	10	WP	1	6345.57685	4034.53616
3	100	WP	2	15597.25659	18058.02126
4	1	WG	0	46.74768	16.53407
5	10	WG	1	113.31914	74.00421
6	100	WG	2	278.57739	331.23253
7	1	liquid	0	69.01694	34.42993
8	10	liquid	1	166.85567	154.10358
9	100	liquid	2	409.15076	689.74614

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.5338	-0.6104	-0.0085	0.5460	2.6548

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.02157	0.16664	6.130	3.91e-09 ***
lTA	0.38657	0.09305	4.155	4.64e-05 ***
formWP	1.74015	0.25771	6.752	1.23e-10 ***
formliquid	0.17395	0.16559	1.051	0.295

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.9449 on 224 degrees of freedom

(275 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2334, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2231

F-statistic: 22.73 on 3 and 224 DF, p-value: 6.916e-13

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log protected hands ~ logTA + form

N: 228 tau: 0.75 AIC: 640.949581294589

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.2183799	0.93262259	1.6186306	0.15100214	8.068627	4.307665e-14
lTA	0.6508765	0.25209209	0.9370533	0.09434751	6.898715	5.307998e-11
formWP	1.7365372	1.34585508	2.2625254	0.31896416	5.444302	1.362472e-07
formliquid	0.3185563	0.06098777	0.5744334	0.16234052	1.962272	5.096899e-02

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$$\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = 1.022 + 0.387 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.74 \text{ formWP} + 0.174 \text{ formliquid}$$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = 1.218 + 0.651 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.737 \text{ formWP} + 0.319 \text{ formliquid}$

=====

Model: log total body ML/TA ~ form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	29	169.8190	2691.732	9850.784	20638.24	25671.59	67310.76
WP	20	27859.6000	144744.500	365618.125	452239.10	476504.08	568452.20
liquid	80	157.4779	5717.550	28538.814	93029.47	130134.43	455259.00

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0	59215.639	45249.8039
2	10	WP	1	592156.392	452498.0392
3	100	WP	2	5921563.921	4524980.3922
4	1	WG	0	1195.379	955.8595
5	10	WG	1	11953.787	9558.5948
6	100	WG	2	119537.867	95585.9484
7	1	liquid	0	1834.777	1968.1333
8	10	liquid	1	18347.767	19681.3333
9	100	liquid	2	183477.669	196813.3333

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.69538	-0.46898	0.00179	0.40943	1.76812

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.6287	0.1211	21.703	< 2e-16 ***
formWP	1.6916	0.1896	8.922	4.5e-15 ***
formliquid	0.1909	0.1414	1.350	0.179

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6523 on 126 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.4361, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4271

F-statistic: 48.72 on 2 and 126 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)`

Formula: `log total body ML/TA ~ form`

N: 129 tau: 0.75 AIC: 283.575261648587

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.9803941	2.9520942	3.0959954	0.04876137	61.122032	0.00000000
formWP	1.6752226	1.4464152	1.8743363	0.14883266	11.255746	0.00000000
formliquid	0.3136605	0.1343803	0.4136578	0.13020191	2.409031	0.01744181

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total body ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.629 + 1.692 \text{ formWP} + 0.191 \text{ formliquid}$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total body ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.98 + 1.675 \text{ formWP} + 0.314 \text{ formliquid}$

=====

Model: log total body ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	29	169.8190	2691.732	9850.784	20638.24	25671.59	67310.76
WP	20	27859.6000	144744.500	365618.125	452239.10	476504.08	568452.20
liquid	80	157.4779	5717.550	28538.814	93029.47	130134.43	455259.00

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0	102138.185	82817.453
2	10	WP	1	520609.776	417884.775
3	100	WP	2	2742854.212	2108585.556
4	1	WG	0	2065.124	1235.077
5	10	WG	1	10524.616	6232.019
6	100	WG	2	55454.708	31445.857
7	1	liquid	0	3602.302	3567.253
8	10	liquid	1	18243.548	17999.840
9	100	liquid	2	95561.440	90824.565

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.68026	-0.40599	0.02671	0.40490	1.58382

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.8696	0.1548	18.538	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.7121	0.1186	6.006	1.92e-08 ***
formWP	1.6910	0.1860	9.091	1.87e-15 ***
formliquid	0.2438	0.1404	1.736	0.085 .

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.64 on 125 degrees of freedom
(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5019, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4899

F-statistic: 41.98 on 3 and 125 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total body ML ~ logTA + form

N: 129 tau: 0.75 AIC: 281.164941358761

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	3.0916941	2.9737693	3.4791115	0.1658509	18.641406	0.000000e+00
lTA	0.7029347	0.5206110	0.9770069	0.1478848	4.753257	5.408988e-06
formWP	1.8264278	1.4055338	2.1365026	0.1960941	9.314038	4.440892e-16
formliquid	0.4606399	0.1537582	0.6904007	0.1646189	2.798220	5.953184e-03

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total body ML) = 2.87 + 0.712 log(TA) + 1.691 formWP + 0.244 formliquid

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total body ML) = 3.092 + 0.703 log(TA) + 1.826 formWP + 0.461 formliquid

=====

Model: log inner body ML/TA ~ form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	29	0.01	104.34783	230.4348	607.6532	1070.524	1491.304

```
WP      20 1172.62 3885.80000 9072.6250 15116.9900 15705.625 24890.700
liquid 80   0.50  56.38165 180.7781  557.2857 1442.907 13069.000
```

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0	2015.03013	858.22095
2	10	WP	1	20150.30131	8582.20947
3	100	WP	2	201503.01308	85822.09469
4	1	WG	0	20.44845	15.80833
5	10	WG	1	204.48454	158.08333
6	100	WG	2	2044.84536	1580.83333
7	1	liquid	0	17.43670	20.61462
8	10	liquid	1	174.36701	206.14624
9	100	liquid	2	1743.67014	2061.46238

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.81139	-0.38382	-0.03199	0.47632	1.97094

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.82912	0.12997	6.379	0.00000000308 ***
formWP	1.99002	0.20343	9.782	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	-0.06405	0.15171	-0.422	0.674

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6999 on 126 degrees of freedom
(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5322, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5247

F-statistic: 71.66 on 2 and 126 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inner body ML/TA ~ form

N: 129 tau: 0.75 AIC: 296.741656712858

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.1988861	1.0827137	1.482428	0.1432624	8.3684648	9.459100e-14
formWP	1.7347130	1.4587825	2.146617	0.2061261	8.4157854	7.305268e-14
formliquid	0.1152893	-0.2424625	0.239787	0.1900452	0.6066415	5.451803e-01

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body ML) = log(TA) + 0.829 + 1.99 formWP + -0.064 formliquid

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body ML) = log(TA) + 1.199 + 1.735 formWP + 0.115 formliquid

=====

Model: log inner body ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	29	0.01	104.34783	230.4348	607.6532	1070.524	1491.304
WP	20	1172.62	3885.80000	9072.6250	15116.9900	15705.625	24890.700
liquid 80		0.50	56.38165	180.7781	557.2857	1442.907	13069.000

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0	2272.61613	1070.07660

```

2 10      WP      1 19823.08521 8237.31732
3 100     WP      2 179299.93565 63409.84965
4 1       WG      0   23.07097  18.59572
5 10     WG      1  201.20592  143.14758
6 100    WG      2 1820.10098 1101.93233
7 1 liquid 0   20.25718  23.76790
8 10 liquid 1  175.45152  182.96232
9 100 liquid 2 1576.89992 1408.42132

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.85758 -0.37844 -0.03886  0.47897  1.95879

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  0.87435    0.16985   5.148 9.95e-07 ***
lTA          0.94594    0.13010   7.271 3.42e-11 ***
formWP       1.98992    0.20410   9.750 < 2e-16 ***
formliquid  -0.05411    0.15408  -0.351  0.726
---

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7022 on 125 degrees of freedom
(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5864, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5765

F-statistic: 59.07 on 3 and 125 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inner body ML ~ logTA + form

N: 129 tau: 0.75 AIC: 298.500218309388

```

              coefficients lower bd upper bd Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.2694131  0.9491635 2.0551478  0.2617355 4.8499848 3.597983e-06
lTA          0.8863709  0.6802906 1.2349656  0.1923795 4.6074079 9.905306e-06
formWP       1.7600018  1.4516838 2.1379769  0.2234322 7.8771190 1.397105e-12
formliquid   0.1065777 -0.3371854 0.1986804  0.2009334 0.5304129 5.967667e-01

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body ML) = 0.874 + 0.946 log(TA) + 1.99 formWP + -0.054 formliquid

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body ML) = 1.269 + 0.886 log(TA) + 1.76 formWP + 0.107 formliquid

=====
Model: log head ML/TA ~ form + face.shield.ML

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	29	0.01	58.33333	152.622	748.6179	1466.402	2358.922
WP	20	65.76	443.00000	856.400	1073.6200	1533.650	2610.000
liquid	80	0.45	20.00000	245.000	2428.0764	4027.780	19050.450

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	form	face.shield.ML	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	no	0	219.04983	124.732026
2	10	WP	no	1	2190.49835	1247.320261
3	100	WP	no	2	21904.98346	12473.202614
4	1	WG	no	0	10.78158	6.493506
5	10	WG	no	1	107.81575	64.935065

```

6 100      WG          no    2  1078.15752   649.350649
7   1 liquid         no    0    37.92948    51.885229
8  10 liquid         no    1   379.29478   518.852288
9 100 liquid         no    2  3792.94781  5188.522876

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.75616 -0.65556  0.03817  0.48372  3.00737

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   -1.0730     0.1938  -5.536 1.74e-07 ***
formWP         1.3050     0.2523   5.173 8.92e-07 ***
formliquid     0.5528     0.1829   3.023 0.00304 **
face.shield.MLno 1.5243     0.1744   8.738 1.31e-14 ***
---

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8429 on 125 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5152, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5036

F-statistic: 44.29 on 3 and 125 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log head ML/TA ~ form + face.shield.ML

N: 129 tau: 0.75 AIC: 343.897100923684

```

              coefficients  lower bd  upper bd Std. Error  t value
Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   -0.9817457 -1.2491246  0.006850153  0.3393912 -2.892667
4.507360e-03
formWP         1.2834987  0.6797631  1.432409758  0.3043390  4.217332
4.704993e-05
formliquid     0.9025645  0.1673691  1.083707118  0.2976351  3.032453
2.950162e-03
face.shield.MLno 1.7942250  1.3733840  1.988838624  0.2510616  7.146552
6.522383e-11

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(head ML) = log(TA) + -1.073 + 1.305 formWP + 0.553 formliquid + 1.524
```

```
face.shield.MLno
```

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(head ML) = log(TA) + -0.982 + 1.283 formWP + 0.903 formliquid + 1.794
```

```
face.shield.MLno
```

=====
Model: log head ML ~ logTA + form + face.shield.ML

Table of measured values:

```

      n  min    50%    75%    90%    95%    max
WG   29  0.01  58.33333 152.622  748.6179 1466.402 2358.922
WP   20 65.76 443.00000 856.400 1073.6200 1533.650 2610.000
liquid 80  0.45  20.00000 245.000 2428.0764 4027.780 19050.450

```

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

```

      TA  form face.shield.ML lTA      LS.75      QR.75
1   1    WP                no    0  125.237212   76.704849
2  10    WP                no    1 2435.312101 1329.773388

```

```

3 100      WP          no    2 50378.924527 23053.265539
4   1      WG          no    0   5.371002   3.738957
5   10     WG          no    1  103.023506   64.819442
6 100     WG          no    2 2103.128963 1123.725155
7   1 liquid         no    0  17.056123   28.634814
8  10 liquid         no    1 323.688399  496.419907
9 100 liquid         no    2 6540.867567 8606.052761

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.9142 -0.6371  0.0174  0.5035  2.8635

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   -1.1990    0.2080  -5.763 6.15e-08 ***
lTA             1.2979    0.1859   6.981 1.56e-10 ***
formWP         1.3704    0.2540   5.395 3.34e-07 ***
formliquid     0.5030    0.1844   2.728 0.00729 **
face.shield.MLno 1.3362    0.2094   6.382 3.16e-09 ***
---

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8377 on 124 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6771, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6667

F-statistic: 65 on 4 and 124 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: lhd.ML ~ lTA + form + face.shield.ML

N: 129 tau: 0.75 AIC: 344.13316899082

```

              coefficients  lower bd  upper bd  Std. Error  t value
Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   -1.0541785 -1.6499671  0.1398584  0.3576879 -2.947202
0.0038321514649
lTA             1.2389548  0.8893727  1.7172198  0.2334025  5.308233
0.0000004931497
formWP         1.3120723  0.7211551  1.6108772  0.3108296  4.221195
0.0000465717697
formliquid     0.8841439  0.2246836  1.2392333  0.3017006  2.930534
0.0040295315885
face.shield.MLno 1.6269289  1.2743508  1.9460320  0.2879880  5.649295
0.0000001045863

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(head ML) = -1.199 + 1.298 log(TA) + 1.37 formWP + 0.503 formliquid + 1.336
face.shield.MLno
```

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(head ML) = -1.054 + 1.239 log(TA) + 1.312 formWP + 0.884 formliquid + 1.627
face.shield.MLno
```

Model: log inhalation ML/ML ~ form

Table of measured values:

```

      n      min      50%      75%      90%      95%      max
WG    41  0.0100000  31.437500  73.125000  211.75130  280.2083  824.8958
WP    20 559.4298246 1811.458333 4051.741372 4997.47807 5301.2610 8504.3860

```

liquid 100 0.5208333 3.096413 7.677895 15.10592 30.1828 145.8333

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0 1117.3126493	495.495495
2	10	WP	1 11173.1264930	4954.954955
3	100	WP	2 111731.2649298	49549.549550
4	1	WG	0 6.0025047	9.396701
5	10	WG	1 60.0250474	93.967014
6	100	WG	2 600.2504742	939.670139
7	1	liquid	0 0.7415128	1.041667
8	10	liquid	1 7.4151277	10.416667
9	100	liquid	2 74.1512771	104.166667

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.2969	-0.4902	0.0638	0.5603	1.9473

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.2178	0.1279	1.702	0.0907 .
formWP	2.2629	0.2234	10.127	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	-0.9043	0.1519	-5.952	0.0000000165 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8193 on 158 degrees of freedom

(342 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6179, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6131

F-statistic: 127.8 on 2 and 158 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inhalation ML/TA ~ form

N: 161 tau: 0.75 AIC: 396.41224307945

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.9729754	0.764994	1.1076091	0.1000743	9.722533	0.000000000000000
formWP	1.7220643	1.545980	2.0159344	0.1279940	13.454261	0.000000000000000
formliquid	-0.9552467	-1.370573	-0.6159043	0.1702491	-5.610876	0.00000008811108

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation ML) = log(TA) + 0.218 + 2.263 formWP + -0.904 formliquid

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation ML) = log(TA) + 0.973 + 1.722 formWP + -0.955 formliquid

Model: log inhalation ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
WG	41	0.0100000	31.437500	73.125000	211.75130	280.2083	824.8958
WP	20	559.4298246	1811.458333	4051.741372	4997.47807	5301.2610	8504.3860
liquid 100		0.5208333	3.096413	7.677895	15.10592	30.1828	145.8333

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

TA	form	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	WP	0 2620.235243	2171.296524
2	10	WP	1 8804.650411	4308.469902

```

3 100      WP      2 30360.878198 8549.229777
4   1      WG      0   14.047459  37.341272
5   10     WG      1   47.201219  74.095705
6 100     WG      2  162.808299 147.026955
7   1 liquid  0    2.604823   3.701686
8  10 liquid  1    8.668413   7.345198
9 100 liquid  2   29.617240  14.574963

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.65066 -0.33244  0.06755  0.54541  1.80872

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   0.6087     0.1555   3.915  0.000135 ***
lTA            0.5301     0.1157   4.582  0.00000935 ***
formWP        2.2641     0.2132  10.618 < 2e-16 ***
formliquid   -0.7323     0.1510  -4.848  0.00000297 ***
---

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7818 on 157 degrees of freedom

(342 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6001, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5925

F-statistic: 78.53 on 3 and 157 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inhalation ML ~ logTA + form

N: 161 tau: 0.75 AIC: 341.820187831289

```

              coefficients lower bd upper bd Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.5721891  1.4380717  1.8824508  0.1718112  9.150678 2.220446e-16
lTA          0.2976039  0.1873417  0.3415566  0.1164563  2.555500 1.155349e-02
formWP       1.7645300  1.4785136  1.9618551  0.1743337  10.121564 0.000000e+00
formliquid  -1.0037895 -1.2723112 -0.8706971  0.1678691 -5.979598 1.455240e-08

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation ML) = 0.609 + 0.53 log(TA) + 2.264 formWP + -0.732 formliquid

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation ML) = 1.572 + 0.298 log(TA) + 1.765 formWP + -1.004 formliquid

A - LCTM

Model: log total hands A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

```

      n min    50%    75%    90%    95%    max
coarse 27 0.01  58.661 1720.779 17267.34 24775.81 28496.25
other  70 0.01 1055.710 5910.500 24429.13 33965.50 70746.80

```

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

```

      TA droplets LCTM.equipment lTA      LS.75      QR.75
1   1   coarse      normal      0      8.178169     62.76085
2  10   coarse      normal      1     81.781688    627.60848
3 100   coarse      normal      2    817.816883   6276.08478
4   1   other      normal      0    216.943202    148.32399
5  10   other      normal      1   2169.432022   1483.23987

```

6	100	other	normal	2	21694.320218	14832.39869
7	1	coarse	small area	0	238.472112	685.61732
8	10	coarse	small area	1	2384.721125	6856.17316
9	100	coarse	small area	2	23847.211250	68561.73156
10	1	other	small area	0	6106.678572	1620.33333
11	10	other	small area	1	61066.785720	16203.33333
12	100	other	small area	2	610667.857202	162033.33333

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-4.1980	-0.6925	0.2305	0.8675	2.6674

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.2979	0.5819	2.230	0.02810 *
dropletsother	1.4338	0.3440	4.168	0.0000682 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.4087	0.5070	-2.779	0.00659 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.484 on 94 degrees of freedom
(95 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2502, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2342

F-statistic: 15.68 on 2 and 94 DF, p-value: 0.000001327

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total hands A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 97 tau: 0.75 AIC: 335.014147161201

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.8360818	2.33624800	3.453735	0.4390596	6.4594464
0.000000004600125					
dropletsother	0.3735226	-0.09799894	1.300570	0.3963927	0.9423045
0.348452253847874					
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.0383930	-1.54072772	-0.606228	0.2562966	-4.0515285
0.000104692842625					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total hands A) = log(TA) + 1.298 + 1.434 dropletsother + -1.409

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total hands A) = log(TA) + 2.836 + 0.374 dropletsother + -1.038

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Model: log total hands A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	27	0.01	58.661	1720.779	17267.34	24775.81	28496.25
other	70	0.01	1055.710	5910.500	24429.13	33965.50	70746.80

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	coarse	normal	0	0.9088747	15.30925
2	10	coarse	normal	1	35.4569267	303.82406
3	100	coarse	normal	2	1481.8540204	6029.62482

4	1	other	normal	0	25.6553864	46.65483
5	10	other	normal	1	1003.2614056	925.90142
6	100	other	normal	2	42063.7775292	18375.23379
7	1	coarse	small area	0	215.5051156	538.19427
8	10	coarse	small area	1	9325.2272770	10680.88387
9	100	coarse	small area	2	430092.6183876	211970.44668
10	1	other	small area	0	5900.8466846	1640.14277
11	10	other	small area	1	256316.4484252	32549.90886
12	100	other	small area	2	11880726.2647416	645978.25438

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-4.0687	-0.6639	0.2672	0.9163	3.2574

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.2806	0.5676	2.256	0.026393 *
lTA	1.6226	0.2579	6.293	0.0000000101 ***
dropletsother	1.4623	0.3357	4.356	0.0000340243 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-2.3563	0.6312	-3.733	0.000326 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.448 on 93 degrees of freedom

(95 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3806, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3607

F-statistic: 19.05 on 3 and 93 DF, p-value: 0.00000000103

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total hands A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 97 tau: 0.75 AIC: 333.582643408078

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.7309391	1.72038048	3.4247683	0.3581786	7.624518
2.047273e-11					
lTA	1.2976681	0.96312849	2.1921733	0.2826829	4.590543
1.381722e-05					
dropletsother	0.4839426	0.08650673	1.2908475	0.3058415	1.582331
1.169690e-01					
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.5459850	-2.71179712	-0.6350416	0.6337058	-2.439594
1.660016e-02					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total hands A) = 1.281 + 1.623 log(TA) + 1.462 dropletsother + -2.356

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total hands A) = 2.731 + 1.298 log(TA) + 0.484 dropletsother + -1.546

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Model: log protected hands A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	21	0.01	16.45300	41.90	68.300	79.339	99.7
other	39	0.01	55.55556	325.75	1611.702	4094.715	10000.0

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	0.3906018	0.3415000
2	10	coarse	normal	1	3.9060185	3.4150000
3	100	coarse	normal	2	39.0601846	34.1500000
4	1	other	normal	0	10.9526692	9.9354198
5	10	other	normal	1	109.5266923	99.3541977
6	100	other	normal	2	1095.2669226	993.5419771
7	1	coarse	small area	0	2.5342606	0.7615541
8	10	coarse	small area	1	25.3426058	7.6155407
9	100	coarse	small area	2	253.4260583	76.1554071
10	1	other	small area	0	68.3095852	22.1562500
11	10	other	small area	1	683.0958523	221.5625000
12	100	other	small area	2	6830.9585234	2215.6250000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.0451	-0.7160	0.2216	0.8217	2.3049

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.6728	0.9581	-0.702	0.485
dropletsother	1.4565	0.3453	4.218	0.0000893 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.6137	0.9176	-0.669	0.506

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.264 on 57 degrees of freedom

(132 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2536, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2274

F-statistic: 9.682 on 2 and 57 DF, p-value: 0.0002399

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log protected hands A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 60 tau: 0.75 AIC: 199.08881393109

value	Pr(> t)	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t
(Intercept)	0.3101947	-0.1182993	-1.318964e+00	1.797693e+308	0.3813710	-
dropletsother	0.7575442743	1.4637955	1.016440e+00	1.948735e+00	0.3813710	
LCTM.equipmentnormal	3.8382453	-0.3483100	-1.797693e+308	4.503777e-01	0.2526824	-
	0.0003129333					
	0.1734509897					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(protected hands A) = log(TA) + -0.673 + 1.456 dropletsother + -0.614 LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(protected hands A) = log(TA) + -0.118 + 1.464 dropletsother + -0.348 LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====

Model: log protected hands A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	21	0.01	16.45300	41.90	68.300	79.339	99.7

other 39 0.01 55.55556 325.75 1611.702 4094.715 10000.0

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	LTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	coarse	normal	0	0.4000359	3.309380
2	10	coarse	normal	1	3.8641138	11.555412
3	100	coarse	normal	2	40.6600617	40.348210
4	1	other	normal	0	11.0856121	42.376964
5	10	other	normal	1	108.6529559	147.968298
6	100	other	normal	2	1162.5333082	516.663190
7	1	coarse	small area	0	2.5547616	1.698289
8	10	coarse	small area	1	28.0158841	5.929943
9	100	coarse	small area	2	329.7051836	20.705672
10	1	other	small area	0	69.6430098	21.746777
11	10	other	small area	1	774.8131686	75.933557
12	100	other	small area	2	9256.3593017	265.138372

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.0241	-0.7178	0.2222	0.8134	2.3056

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.6796	0.9684	-0.702	0.485709
LTA	1.0312	0.2733	3.773	0.000391 ***
dropletsother	1.4623	0.3521	4.153	0.000113 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.6609	1.0141	-0.652	0.517243

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.275 on 56 degrees of freedom

(132 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3311, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2953

F-statistic: 9.241 on 3 and 56 DF, p-value: 0.00004631

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log protected hands A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 60 tau: 0.75 AIC: 198.020779388257

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	0.2300117	-1.022036e+00	1.797693e+308	0.3363632	0.6838194
0.496909200					
LTA	0.5430388	-1.402333e-01	1.247271e+00	0.2589134	2.0973760
0.040487120					
dropletsother	1.1073832	5.644328e-01	1.837555e+00	0.3370646	3.2853737
0.001760425					
LCTM.equipmentnormal	0.2897349	-1.797693e+308	1.906963e+00	0.5174021	0.5599802
0.577726175					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(protected hands A) = -0.68 + 1.031 log(TA) + 1.462 dropletsother + -0.661

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(protected hands A) = 0.23 + 0.543 log(TA) + 1.107 dropletsother + 0.29

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====

Model: log total body A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	6	87.897	226.2195	315.5865	376.4275	400.8892	425.351
other	39	0.010	1024.1643	3218.1916	8014.9882	11739.6877	26091.000

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	31.67679	12.88942
2	10	coarse	normal	1	316.76787	128.89424
3	100	coarse	normal	2	3167.67874	1288.94242
4	1	other	normal	0	105.50568	82.93354
5	10	other	normal	1	1055.05685	829.33538
6	100	other	normal	2	10550.56849	8293.35375
7	1	coarse	small area	0	1425.66906	345.52107
8	10	coarse	small area	1	14256.69065	3455.21070
9	100	coarse	small area	2	142566.90649	34552.10699
10	1	other	small area	0	4577.37847	2223.16250
11	10	other	small area	1	45773.78467	22231.62500
12	100	other	small area	2	457737.84671	222316.25000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-3.8627	-0.2834	0.0499	0.3687	1.3531

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.5237	0.4457	5.663	0.00000121 ***
dropletsother	0.5574	0.3642	1.530	0.133
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.6198	0.2978	-5.439	0.00000253 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8121 on 42 degrees of freedom

(147 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.4686, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4433

F-statistic: 18.52 on 2 and 42 DF, p-value: 0.000001711

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total body A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 45 tau: 0.75 AIC: 91.4566336845678

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.5384745	2.063462e+00	2.5889507	0.2625157	9.669801
					3.027800e-12
dropletsother	0.8084967	-1.797693e+308	1.2328140	0.1980425	4.082440
					1.954018e-04
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.4282410	-1.546558e+00	-0.8550629	0.2563946	-5.570480
					1.643488e-06

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total body A) = log(TA) + 2.524 + 0.557 dropletsother + -1.62

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total body A) = log(TA) + 2.538 + 0.808 dropletsother + -1.428

LCTM.equipmentnormal

```
=====
Model: log total body A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment
```

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	6	87.897	226.2195	315.5865	376.4275	400.8892	425.351
other	39	0.010	1024.1643	3218.1916	8014.9882	11739.6877	26091.000

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	coarse	normal	0	0.2839690
2	10	coarse	normal	1	61.6524308
3	100	coarse	normal	2	15722.8996312
4	1	other	normal	0	0.8884225
5	10	other	normal	1	190.5714464
6	100	other	normal	2	48381.9072489
7	1	coarse	small area	0	1233.4257078
8	10	coarse	small area	1	338647.9825377
9	100	coarse	small area	2	105956572.9273142
10	1	other	small area	0	3690.2641667
11	10	other	small area	1	1015417.7265585
12	100	other	small area	2	321011125.3926291

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.38770	-0.20025	0.05726	0.30601	1.24847

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.5898	0.3546	7.304	6.16e-09 ***
lTA	2.4010	0.2778	8.643	8.82e-11 ***
dropletsother	0.5164	0.2897	1.782	0.0821 .
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-3.6823	0.4725	-7.793	1.28e-09 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6457 on 41 degrees of freedom

(147 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6611, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6363

F-statistic: 26.65 on 3 and 41 DF, p-value: 9.979e-10

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total body A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 45 tau: 0.75 AIC: 82.3514498075204

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.4644566	2.303608e+00	2.8807472	0.2818583	8.743603
6.470091e-11					
lTA	1.8339415	-6.595997e-01	2.4397702	0.3669664	4.997574
1.130405e-05					
dropletsother	0.8972993	-1.797693e+308	0.9849692	0.2251100	3.986048
2.696675e-04					
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-2.6205750	-3.601294e+00	1.5713177	0.5388277	-4.863475
1.738273e-05					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(total body A) = 2.59 + 2.401 log(TA) + 0.516 dropletsother + -3.682
LCTM.equipmentnormal
Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):
log(total body A) = 2.464 + 1.834 log(TA) + 0.897 dropletsother + -2.621
LCTM.equipmentnormal
```

=====
Model: log inner body A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	6	5.955	10.149	12.45875	12.729	12.8040	12.879
other	39	0.010	29.036	50.50000	158.000	243.7996	525.000

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	coarse	normal	0	1.386636	0.4518947
2	10	coarse	normal	1	13.866359	4.5189474
3	100	coarse	normal	2	138.663585	45.1894737
4	1	other	normal	0	2.786106	2.2750000
5	10	other	normal	1	27.861061	22.7500000
6	100	other	normal	2	278.610612	227.5000000
7	1	coarse	small area	0	12.933548	5.5224682
8	10	coarse	small area	1	129.335478	55.2246819
9	100	coarse	small area	2	1293.354781	552.2468190
10	1	other	small area	0	25.055983	27.8020833
11	10	other	small area	1	250.559834	278.0208333
12	100	other	small area	2	2505.598344	2780.2083333

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.68019	-0.11277	0.09724	0.47062	1.20745

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.4852	0.4430	1.095	0.2796
dropletsother	0.3377	0.3621	0.933	0.3564
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.9365	0.2960	-3.163	0.0029 **

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8073 on 42 degrees of freedom

(147 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2318, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1952

F-statistic: 6.335 on 2 and 42 DF, p-value: 0.003939

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inner body A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 45 tau: 0.75 AIC: 86.1675527830627

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	0.7421332	6.336129e-01	0.8803569	0.2018088	3.677407
0.000663743613					
dropletsother	0.7019441	-1.797693e+308	0.8327705	0.1578401	4.447185
0.000062646678					
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.0870959	-1.239119e+00	-0.7966023	0.1993288	-5.453783
0.000002413731					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.485 + 0.338 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.936$
LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.742 + 0.702 \text{ dropletsother} + -1.087$
LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log inner body A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	6	5.955	10.149	12.45875	12.729	12.8040	12.879
other	39	0.010	29.036	50.50000	158.000	243.7996	525.000

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1 coarse	normal	0	0.02635330	0.07990643
2	10 coarse	normal	1	3.57524952	2.62898714
3	100 coarse	normal	2	576.20386029	86.49583384
4	1 other	normal	0	0.05021627	0.35587323
5	10 other	normal	1	6.72523898	11.70852127
6	100 other	normal	2	1078.65652915	385.21995652
7	1 coarse	small area	0	11.97478982	6.37577805
8	10 coarse	small area	1	2088.50463441	209.76832906
9	100 coarse	small area	2	418909.95438985	6901.55013858
10	1 other	small area	0	21.75275416	28.39532072
11	10 other	small area	1	3802.77155840	934.22934968
12	100 other	small area	2	771251.91925157	30736.91212889

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.5303	-0.3485	0.1148	0.4460	1.0738

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.5418	0.3794	1.428	0.161
lTA	2.2013	0.2972	7.406	0.0000000443 ***
dropletsother	0.3025	0.3100	0.976	0.335
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-2.7050	0.5056	-5.350	0.00000361874 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6909 on 41 degrees of freedom

(147 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5936, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5639

F-statistic: 19.96 on 3 and 41 DF, p-value: 0.0000003916

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inner body A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 45 tau: 0.75 AIC: 80.3873590947363

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	0.8045332	7.600549e-01	0.9225802	0.2009722	4.003206
0.00025599764423					
lTA	1.5172067	-1.836949e+00	2.0075805	0.2277324	6.662236
0.00000004952021					

```
dropletsother          0.6487136 -1.797693e+308 0.6810359  0.1537386  4.219588
0.00013200146074
LCTM.equipmentnormal  -1.9019515  -2.525700e+00 2.4057042  0.3246297 -5.858833
0.00000068693195
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body A) = 0.542 + 2.201 log(TA) + 0.303 dropletsother + -2.705

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body A) = 0.805 + 1.517 log(TA) + 0.649 dropletsother + -1.902

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====

Model: log head A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	6	4.204	11.245	12.8935	18.1510	20.7735	23.396
other	40	0.010	33.000	112.0000	279.8842	471.0250	4600.000

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	coarse	normal	0	2.494476	0.5141833
2	10	coarse	normal	1	24.944755	5.1418327
3	100	coarse	normal	2	249.447554	51.4183267
4	1	other	normal	0	4.647910	3.9196765
5	10	other	normal	1	46.479096	39.1967647
6	100	other	normal	2	464.790956	391.9676471
7	1	coarse	small area	0	4.570010	1.7460608
8	10	coarse	small area	1	45.700100	17.4606082
9	100	coarse	small area	2	457.000999	174.6060823
10	1	other	small area	0	8.104609	13.3104167
11	10	other	small area	1	81.046093	133.1041667
12	100	other	small area	2	810.460932	1331.0416667

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.3758	-0.3223	0.1525	0.6263	2.2560

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.2212	0.6223	-0.356	0.724
dropletsother	0.3194	0.5081	0.629	0.533
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.2165	0.4148	-0.522	0.604

Residual standard error: 1.136 on 43 degrees of freedom

(146 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.01908, Adjusted R-squared: -0.02654

F-statistic: 0.4183 on 2 and 43 DF, p-value: 0.6608

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log head A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 46 tau: 0.75 AIC: 131.376093919198

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	0.2420594	-3.331101e-01	0.655232392	0.6353594	0.3809802
0.705093784					

```
dropletsother          0.8821323 -1.797693e+308 1.080739257 0.2727340 3.2344052
0.002345475
LCTM.equipmentnormal  -0.5309414 -1.692161e+00 0.006734941 0.6087614 -0.8721668
0.387961491
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(head A) = log(TA) + -0.221 + 0.319 dropletsother + -0.217 LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(head A) = log(TA) + 0.242 + 0.882 dropletsother + -0.531 LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log head A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	6	4.204	11.245	12.8935	18.1510	20.7735	23.396
other	40	0.010	33.000	112.0000	279.8842	471.0250	4600.000

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	coarse	normal	0	1.970193e-03	2.673215e-04
2	10	coarse	normal	1	2.050244e+00	5.934102e-01
3	100	coarse	normal	2	2.636990e+03	1.317274e+03
4	1	other	normal	0	3.194781e-03	5.814136e-04
5	10	other	normal	1	3.265539e+00	1.290644e+00
6	100	other	normal	2	4.165501e+03	2.865019e+03
7	1	coarse	small area	0	3.698235e+00	6.735002e+00
8	10	coarse	small area	1	5.252276e+03	1.495061e+04
9	100	coarse	small area	2	8.857247e+06	3.318792e+07
10	1	other	small area	0	5.641072e+00	1.464836e+01
11	10	other	small area	1	8.018415e+03	3.251698e+04
12	100	other	small area	2	1.368819e+07	7.218241e+07

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.08083	-0.44113	-0.05607	0.43842	2.12791

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.1013	0.4729	-0.214	0.831
lTA	3.1020	0.3682	8.425	1.44e-10 ***
dropletsother	0.2371	0.3860	0.614	0.542
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-3.3317	0.6300	-5.288	4.16e-06 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8626 on 42 degrees of freedom

(146 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6748, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6515

F-statistic: 29.04 on 3 and 42 DF, p-value: 2.493e-10

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log head A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 46 tau: 0.75 AIC: 119.784983567789

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					

```
(Intercept)          0.8283377   1.640359e-01  1.3728284   0.6786008   1.2206554
0.229025437393304
lTA                  3.3463212  -1.250799e+00  3.4841618   0.4616793   7.2481514
0.000000006433505
dropletsother       0.3374513  -1.797693e+308  0.6059289   0.3615965   0.9332261
0.356037490015100
LCTM.equipmentnormal -4.4013039  -4.560889e+00  3.6526031   0.9174153  -4.7975045
0.000020489114180
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(head A) = -0.101 + 3.102 log(TA) + 0.237 dropletsother + -3.332
LCTM.equipmentnormal
```

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(head A) = 0.828 + 3.346 log(TA) + 0.337 dropletsother + -4.401
LCTM.equipmentnormal
```

=====
Model: log inhalation A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	24	0.2916667	2.190625	4.144376	12.38739	16.89189	27.87162
other	42	0.0100000	4.787498	9.905196	18.06176	34.77029	69.67905

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	0.3159927	0.2292882
2	10	coarse	normal	1	3.1599269	2.2928819
3	100	coarse	normal	2	31.5992695	22.9288194
4	1	other	normal	0	0.3048900	0.1723102
5	10	other	normal	1	3.0488995	1.7231019
6	100	other	normal	2	30.4889954	17.2310194
7	1	coarse	small area	0	0.6598439	7.2193527
8	10	coarse	small area	1	6.5984386	72.1935274
9	100	coarse	small area	2	65.9843856	721.9352739
10	1	other	small area	0	0.6150635	5.4253472
11	10	other	small area	1	6.1506353	54.2534722
12	100	other	small area	2	61.5063531	542.5347222

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.32771	-0.42373	-0.01846	0.41085	2.35455

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.7386	0.3158	-2.339	0.0225 *
dropletsother	-0.0129	0.2051	-0.063	0.9501
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.2876	0.2752	-1.045	0.2999

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7595 on 63 degrees of freedom

(126 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.0183, Adjusted R-squared: -0.01286

F-statistic: 0.5872 on 2 and 63 DF, p-value: 0.5589

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inhalation A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 66 tau: 0.75 AIC: 152.174586696982

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	0.8584983	-0.6196656	1.7636241	1.4352010	0.5981729
0.5518691					
dropletsother	-0.1240707	-0.4716392	0.2323238	0.1875928	-0.6613831
0.5107784					
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.4981166	-2.3936953	1.2129236	1.4291876	-1.0482294
0.2985377					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation A) = log(TA) + -0.739 + -0.013 dropletsother + -0.288

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation A) = log(TA) + 0.858 + -0.124 dropletsother + -1.498

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log inhalation A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
coarse	24	0.2916667	2.190625	4.144376	12.38739	16.89189	27.87162
other	42	0.0100000	4.787498	9.905196	18.06176	34.77029	69.67905

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	coarse	normal	0	2.0402489	1.019834
2	10	coarse	normal	1	5.3617037	3.232397
3	100	coarse	normal	2	15.4829386	10.245183
4	1	other	normal	0	2.8260848	1.035609
5	10	other	normal	1	7.2610598	3.282396
6	100	other	normal	2	20.4418081	10.403656
7	1	coarse	small area	0	0.4454778	5.234974
8	10	coarse	small area	1	1.3735425	16.592414
9	100	coarse	small area	2	4.5760787	52.590175
10	1	other	small area	0	0.5729611	5.315949
11	10	other	small area	1	1.7292726	16.849066
12	100	other	small area	2	5.6771019	53.403643

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.2752	-0.3880	0.0428	0.3138	2.3689

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.8889	0.3094	-2.873	0.00555 **
lTA	0.4586	0.2167	2.116	0.03838 *
dropletsother	0.1278	0.2049	0.623	0.53525
LCTM.equipmentnormal	0.6499	0.4591	1.416	0.16188

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7297 on 62 degrees of freedom
(126 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3581, Adjusted R-squared: 0.327

F-statistic: 11.53 on 3 and 62 DF, p-value: 0.00000421

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
 Formula: log inhalation A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

N: 66 tau: 0.75 AIC: 140.240062633317

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	0.718914533	-0.75503927	1.4921159	1.4685936	0.48952586
0.62619701					
lTA	0.500995042	0.28846780	0.6533667	0.2029621	2.46841621
0.01634254					
dropletsother	0.006666262	-0.08609104	0.4849030	0.1976382	0.03372962
0.97320112					
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.710384882	-1.51094830	-0.1518216	1.5010104	-0.47327113
0.63768188					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation A) = -0.889 + 0.459 log(TA) + 0.128 dropletsother + 0.65
 LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation A) = 0.719 + 0.501 log(TA) + 0.007 dropletsother + -0.71
 LCTM.equipmentnormal

A - HCTM

Model: log total hands A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	54	0.01	722.8822	2845.750	8907.35	18293.39	423687.9
no cabin	55	63.60	2283.0000	8019.125	12248.14	31462.00	97980.0

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	586.8352	1129.495
2	10	cabin	1.00000	5868.3523	11294.955
3	50	cabin	1.69897	29341.7613	56474.773
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	6046.9293	2287.171
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	60469.2928	22871.712
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	302346.4642	114358.561

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-4.8534	-0.3990	0.0938	0.6827	2.4337

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.9503	0.1630	11.964	< 2e-16 ***
cabinno cabin	1.0132	0.2295	4.415	0.0000243 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.198 on 107 degrees of freedom

(48 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.1541, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1462

F-statistic: 19.49 on 1 and 107 DF, p-value: 0.00002425

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total hands A/TA ~ cabin

N: 109 tau: 0.75 AIC: 283.746678011629

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	3.0528845	2.9238344	3.1293128	0.1100186	27.748814	0.00000000
cabinno cabin	0.3064142	0.1737269	0.4544226	0.1223811	2.503771	0.01379777

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total hands A) = log(TA) + 1.95 + 1.013 cabinno cabin

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total hands A) = log(TA) + 3.053 + 0.306 cabinno cabin

Model: log total hands A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	54	0.01	722.8822	2845.750	8907.35	18293.39	423687.9
no cabin	55	63.60	2283.0000	8019.125	12248.14	31462.00	97980.0

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	1319.357
2	10	cabin	1.00000	4001.022
3	50	cabin	1.69897	9424.682
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	9999.209
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	31374.791
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	75578.673

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-4.7383	-0.3698	0.1652	0.5563	2.7213

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.2936	0.2747	8.350	2.81e-13 ***
lTA	0.4924	0.3280	1.501	0.136267
cabinno cabin	0.8879	0.2419	3.670	0.000382 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.19 on 106 degrees of freedom

(48 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.1134, Adjusted R-squared: 0.09663

F-statistic: 6.776 on 2 and 106 DF, p-value: 0.001701

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total hands A ~ logTA + cabin

N: 109 tau: 0.75 AIC: 284.506041441222

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	3.1210578	2.9892568	3.1928774	0.1462035	21.347349	0.00000000000000
lTA	0.8867665	0.5906531	1.1008597	0.1606896	5.518507	0.0000002442601
cabinno cabin	0.2809222	0.2008339	0.4157297	0.1353510	2.075509	0.0403595661587

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total hands A) = 2.294 + 0.492 log(TA) + 0.888 cabinno cabin
 Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):
 log(total hands A) = 3.121 + 0.887 log(TA) + 0.281 cabinno cabin

=====
Model: log protected hands A/TA ~ 1

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
TRUE	67	0.01	62.5	189.3	735.3571	3754	9080

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	0.00000	77.07232	35.18519
2	10	1.00000	770.72316	351.85185
3	50	1.69897	3853.61582	1759.25926

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-4.0132	-0.3011	0.1385	0.3991	2.2916

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.1101	0.1389	7.993	2.72e-11 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.137 on 66 degrees of freedom
 (90 observations deleted due to missingness)

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log protected hands A/TA ~ 1

N: 67 tau: 0.75 AIC: 189.152527410218

	[,1]	[,2]
Std. Error	1.54636	0.226660523877326
t value	1.54636	6.822360659356746
Pr(> t)	1.54636	0.000000003348474

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(protected hands A) = log(TA) + 1.11

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(protected hands A) = log(TA) + 1.546

=====
Model: log protected hands A ~ logTA

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
TRUE	67	0.01	62.5	189.3	735.3571	3754	9080

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	0.00000	93.67653	26.50184
2	10	1.00000	708.05627	451.14882
3	50	1.69897	3302.95100	3271.76821

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-3.9727	-0.3073	0.1115	0.4220	2.2919

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.1747	0.2644	4.442	0.0000354 ***
lTA	0.8836	0.4047	2.183	0.0326 *

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.145 on 65 degrees of freedom

(90 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.06833, Adjusted R-squared: 0.054

F-statistic: 4.767 on 1 and 65 DF, p-value: 0.03262

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log protected hands A ~ logTA

N: 67 tau: 0.75 AIC: 189.174852486929

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.423276	1.2136836	1.646346	0.1933376	7.361608	3.971954e-10
lTA	1.231044	0.8300814	1.528645	0.4985753	2.469123	1.618145e-02

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(protected hands A) = 1.175 + 0.884 log(TA)

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(protected hands A) = 1.423 + 1.231 log(TA)

Model: log total body A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	30	68.0	3789.3	12847.30	34411.99	48185.15	131572.0
no cabin	42	620.6	15005.0	60191.87	99537.61	229388.82	432944.1

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	1960.869	2936.609
2	10	cabin	1.00000	19608.693	29366.090
3	50	cabin	1.69897	98043.463	146830.449
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	14124.214	8811.600
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	141242.142	88116.000
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	706210.710	440580.000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.50148	-0.39690	0.07254	0.33688	1.36373

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.8569	0.1154	24.759	< 2e-16 ***

```
cabinno cabin    0.8595      0.1511    5.689 0.000000274 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 0.632 on 70 degrees of freedom
(85 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared:  0.3162,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.3064
F-statistic: 32.37 on 1 and 70 DF,  p-value: 0.0000002742
```

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

```
Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
Formula: log total body A/TA ~ cabin
```

```
N: 72      tau: 0.75      AIC: 145.090453236418
```

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	3.4678461	3.1549120	3.6296310	0.2218090	15.634383	0.00000000
cabinno cabin	0.4772087	0.3793818	0.7828825	0.2563102	1.861841	0.06682364

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(total body A) = log(TA) + 2.857 + 0.86 cabinno cabin
```

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(total body A) = log(TA) + 3.468 + 0.477 cabinno cabin
```

Model: log total body A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	30	68.0	3789.3	12847.30	34411.99	48185.15	131572.0
no cabin	42	620.6	15005.0	60191.87	99537.61	229388.82	432944.1

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75	
1	1	cabin	0.00000	1516.785	2935.623
2	10	cabin	1.00000	23780.715	29423.173
3	50	cabin	1.69897	171734.800	147350.259
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	11501.102	8813.017
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	182393.644	88331.122
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	1327217.960	442359.280

Summary of LS fit (mean):

```
Call:
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.47799	-0.40715	0.07089	0.35937	1.34654

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.7384	0.1636	16.738	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	1.1991	0.1949	6.151	0.0000000442 ***
cabinno cabin	0.8844	0.1530	5.781	0.0000001968 ***

```
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 0.6318 on 69 degrees of freedom
(85 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared:  0.4712,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.4558
F-statistic: 30.74 on 2 and 69 DF,  p-value: 2.847e-10
```

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
 Formula: log total body A ~ logTA + cabin

N: 72 tau: 0.75 AIC: 147.087832553993

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	3.4677004	3.0512121	3.6450659	0.2369142	14.636947	0.0000000000
lTA	1.0009892	0.8774469	1.4987240	0.2759931	3.626863	0.0005452442
cabinno cabin	0.4774242	0.3806906	0.9112588	0.2217922	2.152575	0.0348516563

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total body A) = 2.738 + 1.199 log(TA) + 0.884 cabinno cabin

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total A) = 3.468 + 1.001 log(TA) + 0.477 cabinno cabin

=====
Model: log inner body A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	30	2.513	104.3478	240.3834	974.7826	2020.000	3291.304
no cabin	42	18.000	195.2000	641.5217	1056.0182	1597.835	4016.803

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	46.20855	68.00446
2	10	cabin	1.00000	462.08546	680.04459
3	50	cabin	1.69897	2310.42732	3400.22297
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	146.31294	114.96464
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	1463.12937	1149.64640
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	7315.64687	5748.23201

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
 lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.57773	-0.33219	0.04825	0.37584	1.00428

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.30149	0.09622	13.526	< 2e-16 ***
cabinno cabin	0.50224	0.12598	3.987	0.000162 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.527 on 70 degrees of freedom

(85 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.185, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1734

F-statistic: 15.89 on 1 and 70 DF, p-value: 0.0001625

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
 Formula: log inner body A/TA ~ cabin

N: 72 tau: 0.75 AIC: 114.762236677029

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.8325374	1.6726848	1.9516426	0.1245534	14.712862	0.000000
cabinno cabin	0.2280269	0.1021839	0.4283918	0.1542446	1.478346	0.143801

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body A) = log(TA) + 1.301 + 0.502 cabinno cabin
 Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):
 log(inner body A) = log(TA) + 1.833 + 0.228 cabinno cabin

=====
Model: log inner body A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	30	2.513	104.3478	240.3834	974.7826	2020.000	3291.304
no cabin	42	18.000	195.2000	641.5217	1056.0182	1597.835	4016.803

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	28.25414	44.40084
2	10	cabin	1.00000	631.14039	710.33718
3	50	cabin	1.69897	5779.07254	4932.59819
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	98.54550	92.04603
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	2221.84370	1472.57859
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	20470.25049	10225.62061

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.75220	-0.31112	0.01928	0.36241	0.88951

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.0919	0.1328	8.224	7.78e-12 ***
lTA	1.3521	0.1582	8.546	2.00e-12 ***
cabinno cabin	0.5463	0.1242	4.400	3.85e-05 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.5127 on 69 degrees of freedom

(85 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5446, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5314

F-statistic: 41.25 on 2 and 69 DF, p-value: 1.643e-12

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inner body A ~ logTA + cabin

N: 72 tau: 0.75 AIC: 112.6963078482

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.6473911	1.3649053	1.8866263	0.1683707	9.784311	1.132427e-14
lTA	1.2040734	1.0599906	1.7371778	0.1918388	6.276484	2.649529e-08
cabinno cabin	0.3166139	0.1081182	0.5920687	0.1583272	1.999745	4.946644e-02

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body A) = 1.092 + 1.352 log(TA) + 0.546 cabinno cabin

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body A) = 1.647 + 1.204 log(TA) + 0.317 cabinno cabin

=====
Model: log head A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
--	---	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

```
cabin    29 0.010 29.16667 133.3333 524 2295 3400
no cabin 42 9.706 523.80000 3538.1250 16222 43265 87860
```

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	32.13015	14.95726
2	10	cabin	1.00000	321.30146	149.57265
3	50	cabin	1.69897	1606.50729	747.86325
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	924.09599	1158.00000
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	9240.95990	11580.00000
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	46204.79950	57900.00000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-3.5363	-0.5973	-0.1260	0.6652	2.2851

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.8161	0.1860	4.388	0.0000402314 ***
cabinno cabin	1.4624	0.2418	6.047	0.0000000674 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.002 on 69 degrees of freedom

(86 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3464, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3369

F-statistic: 36.57 on 1 and 69 DF, p-value: 0.00000006745

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log head A/TA ~ cabin

N: 71 tau: 0.75 AIC: 220.326120739326

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.174852	0.8644907	1.904791	0.3589889	3.272670	0.00166612196
cabinno cabin	1.888856	1.0732378	2.353883	0.4333453	4.358779	0.00004463465

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(head A) = log(TA) + 0.816 + 1.462 cabinno cabin

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(head A) = log(TA) + 1.175 + 1.889 cabinno cabin

Model: log head A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	29	0.010	29.16667	133.3333	524	2295	3400
no cabin	42	9.706	523.80000	3538.1250	16222	43265	87860

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	18.93465	6.028619
2	10	cabin	1.00000	473.65377	214.240817
3	50	cabin	1.69897	4891.35871	2598.867210
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	601.93757	575.103816
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	15315.53667	20437.634934
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	159963.65494	247920.541047

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-3.5900	-0.5753	-0.0296	0.6225	2.3213

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.5791	0.2589	2.237	0.0286 *
lTA	1.4037	0.3083	4.553	0.0000224805 ***
cabinno cabin	1.5097	0.2433	6.205	0.0000000371 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.9965 on 68 degrees of freedom

(86 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.4333, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4166

F-statistic: 26 on 2 and 68 DF, p-value: 0.000000004113

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log head A ~ logTA + cabin

N: 71 tau: 0.75 AIC: 219.05624673354

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.7802178	0.6497944	1.699527	0.3528133	2.211418	0.0303717434151
lTA	1.5506844	1.0202520	2.495199	0.4464379	3.473460	0.0008983307293
cabinno cabin	1.9795284	0.9345993	2.313762	0.3457341	5.725581	0.0000002547704

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(head A) = 0.579 + 1.404 log(TA) + 1.51 cabinno cabin

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(head A) = 0.78 + 1.551 log(TA) + 1.98 cabinno cabin

Model: log inhalation A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	42	0.4882812	12.23041	20.21498	40.67383	114.9386	626.6276
no cabin	41	9.0679825	46.32143	114.58333	260.41667	416.6667	23614.5833

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	4.79766
			4.79766	5.787037
2	10	cabin	1.00000	47.97660
			47.97660	57.870370
3	50	cabin	1.69897	239.88299
			239.88299	289.351852
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	56.97570
			56.97570	33.730159
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	569.75700
			569.75700	337.301587
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	2848.78499
			2848.78499	1686.507937

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.29458	-0.36355	-0.02158	0.28687	2.13246

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   0.26309    0.09407   2.797 0.00645 **
cabinno cabin 1.07454    0.13384   8.028 6.61e-12 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

Residual standard error: 0.6096 on 81 degrees of freedom
(74 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared: 0.4431,    Adjusted R-squared: 0.4363
F-statistic: 64.45 on 1 and 81 DF,  p-value: 6.605e-12

```

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

```

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
Formula: log inhalation A/TA ~ cabin

```

```

N: 83      tau: 0.75      AIC: 172.692616768888

```

```

              coefficients lower bd upper bd Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   0.7624563 0.4557273 1.076942  0.1517406 5.024736 0.000002955432
cabinno cabin 0.7655621 0.4366039 1.153757  0.1858920 4.118316 0.000091421071

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(inhalation A) = log(TA) + 0.263 + 1.075 cabinno cabin
```

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(inhalation A) = log(TA) + 0.762 + 0.766 cabinno cabin
```

Model: log inhalation A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
cabin	42	0.4882812	12.23041	20.21498	40.67383	114.9386	626.6276
no cabin	41	9.0679825	46.32143	114.58333	260.41667	416.6667	23614.5833

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	1	cabin	0.00000	8.395456	9.76800
2	10	cabin	1.00000	35.442112	35.88884
3	50	cabin	1.69897	101.776594	89.12202
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	83.423846	63.80529
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	357.986062	234.42854
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	1038.975682	582.15153

Summary of LS fit (mean):

```

Call:
lm(formula = frm)

```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.27225	-0.37160	-0.05694	0.30073	2.29570

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   0.5064    0.1501   3.374 0.001145 **
lTA            0.6312    0.1795   3.517 0.000724 ***
cabinno cabin 1.0011    0.1360   7.359 1.44e-10 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

Residual standard error: 0.5979 on 80 degrees of freedom
(74 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared: 0.4154,    Adjusted R-squared: 0.4008
F-statistic: 28.42 on 2 and 80 DF,  p-value: 4.721e-10

```

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
Formula: log inhalation A ~ logTA + cabin

N: 83 tau: 0.75 AIC: 167.389586225296

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.9898056	0.6189254	1.1445207	0.2204011	4.490928	0.00002357554
lTA	0.5651538	0.3172190	1.0047892	0.2747784	2.056762	0.04296834469
cabinno cabin	0.8150510	0.4314457	0.9744438	0.2052451	3.971112	0.00015542901

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation A) = 0.506 + 0.631 log(TA) + 1.001 cabinno cabin

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation A) = 0.99 + 0.565 log(TA) + 0.815 cabinno cabin

A - HCHH

Model: log total hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14012.50000	33505.60	48192.07	60788.63	67131.74	78038.0
normal	50	11.42899	2538.35	5871.65	13930.19	24666.95	60542.4

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	4075.2024	2897.7479
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	20376.0118	14488.7395
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	101880.0590	72443.6975
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	466.8722	526.7295
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	2334.3611	2633.6475
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	11671.8055	13168.2377

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.45276	-0.19272	0.01306	0.21206	1.37923

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.01965	0.06675	60.22	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.94024	0.08955	-10.50	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4222 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5561, Adjusted R-squared: 0.551

F-statistic: 110.2 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
Formula: log total hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 92.2304054589573

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
--	--------------	----------	----------	------------	---------	----------

```
(Intercept)          4.161031  4.1000863  4.2274697  0.04821723  86.297587
0.0000000000000000
HCHH.culturenormal  -0.740473 -0.9078952 -0.6409805  0.11099436 -6.671267
0.000000002163713
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 4.02 + -0.94 \text{ HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 4.161 + -0.74 \text{ HCHH.culturenormal}$

=====
Model: log total hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14012.50000	33505.60	48192.07	60788.63	67131.74	78038.0
normal	50	11.42899	2538.35	5871.65	13930.19	24666.95	60542.4

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	3844.2915	4744.7676
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	19761.1423	18228.0345
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	103740.0328	70026.8736
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	444.7233	708.2275
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	2306.7763	2720.8067
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	12225.8957	10452.5579

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.42657	-0.20494	0.01478	0.21196	1.39359

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.00222	0.08839	45.280	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	1.03355	0.11079	9.329	9.51e-15 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.92993	0.09624	-9.662	1.98e-15 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4244 on 87 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.7624, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7569

F-statistic: 139.6 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)`

Formula: `log total hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture`

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 91.783850155563

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	4.2607398	4.0601172	4.3467143	0.09907554	43.004961
0.000000000000000					
lTA	0.8362661	0.5619509	1.1325130	0.17215730	4.857570
0.0000052041660					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.8260422	-0.9103580	-0.6399492	0.13932259	-5.928989
0.0000000600931					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = 4.002 + 1.034 \log(\text{TA}) + -0.93 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = 4.261 + 0.836 \log(\text{TA}) + -0.826 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

=====
Model: log protected hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14.96	267.15	580.400	1064.40	1357.550	1381
normal	50	0.05	4.12	112.575	350.24	510.465	1958

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	57.848861	36.638655
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	289.244307	183.193277
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	1446.221537	915.966387
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	3.164249	4.780405
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	15.821246	23.902027
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	79.106229	119.510135

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.0303	-0.4054	0.0761	0.5027	1.8766

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.9036	0.1286	14.802	< 2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.2607	0.1725	-7.307	1.18e-10 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8133 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3776, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3705

F-statistic: 53.39 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: 1.179e-10

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)`

Formula: `log protected hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture`

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 215.865596980336

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.2629095	2.076615	2.4624996	0.1344074	16.836203
	0.0000000000				
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.8844748	-1.210279	-0.5619251	0.2348540	-3.766062
	0.0002990514				

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.904 + -1.261 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.263 + -0.884 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

=====
Model: log protected hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14.96	267.15	580.400	1064.40	1357.550	1381
normal	50	0.05	4.12	112.575	350.24	510.465	1958

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1 0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	6.0065615	5.1395560
2 1.0	dense culture	0.00000	102.6241790	76.0307989
3 5.0	dense culture	0.69897	1819.8505679	1124.7435409
4 0.2	normal	-0.69897	0.5616543	0.8693045
5 1.0	normal	0.00000	9.7504679	12.8598496
6 5.0	normal	0.69897	175.8469801	190.2391262

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.9307	-0.4726	0.1691	0.5092	1.4326

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.4920	0.1563	9.545	3.45e-15 ***
lTA	1.7924	0.1959	9.148	2.23e-14 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.0171	0.1702	-5.976	4.90e-08 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7505 on 87 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.675, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6675

F-statistic: 90.34 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log protected hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 193.393622557388

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	1.8809896	1.7899347	2.112410	0.1643803	11.442911
0.000000e+00					
lTA	1.6739831	1.4922738	1.845165	0.1944332	8.609553
2.828848e-13					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.7717537	-0.9929029	-0.605342	0.1774365	-4.349465
3.696362e-05					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(protected hands A) = 1.492 + 1.792 log(TA) + -1.017 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(protected hands A) = 1.881 + 1.674 log(TA) + -0.772 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log total body A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	205029.900	743891.35	1433241.63	2015534.4	2224532.1	2470393
normal	50	1739.584	21941.66	55128.48	134742.7	179870.9	254373

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	118738.745	76960.465
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	593693.727	384802.326
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	2968468.636	1924011.628
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	6134.736	8593.682
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	30673.678	42968.412
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	153368.388	214842.061

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.57788	-0.31279	-0.03126	0.33281	1.45202

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	5.39920	0.08632	62.55	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.28588	0.11582	-11.10	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.546 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5835, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5787

F-statistic: 123.3 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log total body A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 161.39484076558

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	5.5852377	5.508614	5.742505	0.06162287	90.635786
	0.000000000000000				
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.9520884	-1.328522	-0.746140	0.17418488	-5.465965
	0.0000004243098				

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total body A) = log(TA) + 5.399 + -1.286 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total body A) = log(TA) + 5.585 + -0.952 HCHH.culturenormal

=====
Model: log total body A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	205029.900	743891.35	1433241.63	2015534.4	2224532.1	2470393
normal	50	1739.584	21941.66	55128.48	134742.7	179870.9	254373

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	736899.83	938758.26
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	1199733.40	1207693.11
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	1999622.92	1553672.24
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	23190.05	47775.05
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	38137.10	61461.61
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	64243.17	79069.10

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:
Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
-1.24318 -0.29821 -0.01523 0.31477 1.15490

Coefficients:
Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept) 5.75181 0.09853 58.38 <2e-16 ***
lTA 0.32106 0.12350 2.60 0.011 *
HCHH.culturenormal -1.49453 0.10728 -13.93 <2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.473 on 87 degrees of freedom
(44 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared: 0.7484, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7427
F-statistic: 129.4 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
Formula: logtotal body A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 139.961403513638

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	6.081957	5.8033622	6.3503375	0.1512085	40.2223276
0.000000e+00					
lTA	0.156520	-0.3203005	0.6660829	0.2559031	0.6116379
5.423724e-01					
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.293353	-1.5601880	-1.0322111	0.1598204	-8.0925371
3.209211e-12					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total body A) = 5.752 + 0.321 log(TA) + -1.495 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total body A) = 6.082 + 0.157 log(TA) + -1.293 HCHH.culturenormal

=====
Model: log inner body A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	2389.9	11617.750	46538.250	107170.900	189501.150	305040.0
normal	50	6.0	255.251	972.135	1721.309	1912.291	8980.1

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	3086.1552	2985.1584
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	15430.7761	14925.7919
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	77153.8803	74628.9593
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	102.0456	129.3984
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	510.2280	646.9918
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	2551.1399	3234.9590

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:
Min 1Q Median 3Q Max

-1.3168 -0.5376 -0.1802 0.4585 2.0331

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	3.7157	0.1090	34.09	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.4795	0.1462	-10.12	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6894 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5377, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5324

F-statistic: 102.3 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inner body A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 229.807828692636

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	4.173937	4.013135	4.3378198	0.1847551	22.591725
0.000000000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.363039	-1.819007	-0.9292632	0.3324126	-4.100442
0.00009168582					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body A) = log(TA) + 3.716 + -1.479 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body A) = log(TA) + 4.174 + -1.363 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log inner body A ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	2389.9	11617.750	46538.250	107170.900	189501.150	305040.0
normal	50	6.0	255.251	972.135	1721.309	1912.291	8980.1

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	47386.8463	44920.00
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	47386.8463	44920.00
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	47386.8463	44920.00
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	772.3104	1033.07
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	772.3104	1033.07
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	772.3104	1033.07

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.67010	-0.43413	-0.07057	0.46915	1.50503

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.2350	0.1016	41.68	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.7868	0.1363	-13.11	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6426 on 88 degrees of freedom
 (44 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.6613, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6575
 F-statistic: 171.8 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
 Formula: log inner body A ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 198.181054848504

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.65244	4.533592	4.874557	0.1756244	26.49086	0.0000e+00
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.63831	-2.020595	-1.424602	0.2169680	-7.55093	3.7921e-11

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body A) = 4.235 + -1.787 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body A) = 4.652 + -1.638 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log head A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	129.72	1136.40	2894.50	4251.40	5180.90	5394.0
normal	50	4.00	62.29	155.68	390.46	851.61	1471.6

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1 0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	183.23646	129.70835
2 1.0	dense culture	0.00000	916.18231	648.54177
3 5.0	dense culture	0.69897	4580.91157	3242.70885
4 0.2	normal	-0.69897	19.05529	31.11475
5 1.0	normal	0.00000	95.27646	155.57377
6 5.0	normal	0.69897	476.38229	777.86885

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
 lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.35628	-0.38421	-0.00847	0.42494	1.62893

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.53252	0.09903	25.574	< 2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.98195	0.13286	-7.391	7.98e-11 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6263 on 88 degrees of freedom
 (44 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.383, Adjusted R-squared: 0.376
 F-statistic: 54.62 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: 7.983e-11

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)
 Formula: log head A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 183.810933611642

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.8119380	2.6943462	2.9570867	0.08284337	33.942823
0.000000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.6200016	-0.8154153	-0.3671444	0.19327437	-3.207883
0.001865531					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(head A) = log(TA) + 2.533 + -0.982 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(head A) = log(TA) + 2.812 + -0.62 HCHH.culturenormal

=====
Model: log head A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	129.72	1136.40	2894.50	4251.40	5180.90	5394.0
normal	50	4.00	62.29	155.68	390.46	851.61	1471.6

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1 0.2 dense culture	-0.69897	1108.15073	1121.86855		
2 1.0 dense culture	0.00000	1853.82379	1881.59144		
3 5.0 dense culture	0.69897	3189.99577	3155.79428		
4 0.2 normal	-0.69897	70.99248	90.81339		
5 1.0 normal	0.00000	120.20909	152.31170		
6 5.0 normal	0.69897	209.51282	255.45630		

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.00654	-0.38986	0.00658	0.42513	1.34706

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.8745	0.1185	24.257	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.3416	0.1485	2.300	0.0238 *
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.1843	0.1290	-9.178	1.94e-14 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.5689 on 87 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5785, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5688

F-statistic: 59.71 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log head A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 174.550492400507

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	3.2745253	2.69544882	3.5046349	0.1610892	20.327409
0.00000000000					
lTA	0.3213061	0.03030095	1.0895270	0.2455845	1.308332
0.19420661943					
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.0917921	-1.37936930	-0.4471906	0.2087528	-5.230072
0.00000115453					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{head A}) = 2.874 + 0.342 \log(\text{TA}) + -1.184 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{head A}) = 3.275 + 0.321 \log(\text{TA}) + -1.092 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

=====

Model: log inhalation A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	101.5315315	330.97728	428.7562	573.4975	705.2123	2136.261
normal	50	0.5208333	57.84375	156.5365	336.5000	390.4583	2165.625

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	40.48203	23.70271
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	202.41015	118.51357
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	1012.05076	592.56784
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	13.15918	13.97321
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	65.79588	69.86607
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	328.97942	349.33036

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.55824	-0.20138	0.01866	0.22641	1.06065

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.98988	0.07295	27.278	< 2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.48726	0.09787	-4.979	0.00000316 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4614 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2198, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2109

F-statistic: 24.79 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: 0.000003159

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)`

Formula: `log inhalation A/TA ~ HCHH.culture`

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 96.9541298620591

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.0737681	2.0256229	2.2061435	0.06892195	30.088643
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.2295017	-0.4055022	-0.1271319	0.10063017	-2.280645

0.02498486

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.99 + -0.487 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.074 + -0.23 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

=====

Model: log inhalation A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	90%	95%	max
dense culture	40	101.5315315	330.97728	428.7562	573.4975	705.2123	2136.261
normal	50	0.5208333	57.84375	156.5365	336.5000	390.4583	2165.625

Table of predicted values (75 th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.75	QR.75
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	85.62221	38.70512
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	273.81494	147.39514
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	895.47117	561.30378
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	22.80875	21.18048
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	73.64498	80.65859
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	243.30085	307.16054

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.41240	-0.16074	-0.00015	0.23767	1.20649

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.12507	0.09405	22.596	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.73970	0.11788	6.275	0.0000000132 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.56726	0.10240	-5.539	0.0000003182 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4515 on 87 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5543, Adjusted R-squared: 0.544

F-statistic: 54.1 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: 5.417e-16

Summary of RQ fit (75 th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = TAU)

Formula: log inhalation A ~ lTA + HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.75 AIC: 93.9953959079024

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.1684832	2.0596035	2.3750716	0.09589396	22.613344
	0.000000000000000				
lTA	0.8308151	0.6293360	1.0236831	0.13451506	6.176372
	0.00000002039931				
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.2618326	-0.4684561	-0.1752491	0.08930619	-2.931852
	0.00430477702971				

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation A) = 2.125 + 0.74 log(TA) + -0.567 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 75th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation A) = 2.168 + 0.831 log(TA) + -0.262 HCHH.culturenormal

=====

20 Model computations (95th percentile)

ML - tank

Model: log total hands ML/TA ~ form + glove.wash.ML

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	41	218.70000	1997.005	3885.253	6926.498	40938.82
WP	20	5844.70000	75873.000	96066.000	147403.600	179582.00
liquid	169	71.49891	8250.000	30250.500	553048.508	2346735.63

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	glove.wash.ML	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP		0	131415.044	36940.235
2	10	WP		1	1314150.437	369402.352
3	100	WP		2	13141504.368	3694023.518
4	1	WG		0	3594.576	3007.883
5	10	WG		1	35945.761	30078.835
6	100	WG		2	359457.614	300788.348
7	1	liquid		0	11706.751	12018.519
8	10	liquid		1	117067.507	120185.185
9	100	liquid		2	1170675.074	1201851.852

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.39441	-0.43021	0.01458	0.47816	1.43035

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.4752	0.1049	23.589	< 2e-16 ***
formWP	1.5498	0.1761	8.799	3.62e-16 ***
formliquid	0.5235	0.1137	4.603	6.96e-06 ***
glove.wash.MLyes	-0.2752	0.1321	-2.084	0.0383 *

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6457 on 226 degrees of freedom

(273 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2676, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2579

F-statistic: 27.53 on 3 and 226 DF, p-value: 3.275e-15

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log total hands ML/TA ~ form + glove.wash.ML

N: 230 tau: 0.95 AIC: 574.934332011854

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	3.4782610	3.3812566	1.797693e+308	0.3058971	11.370690
0.000000000000000					
formWP	1.0892386	0.6135219	1.797693e+308	0.3499321	3.112714
0.0020929729294					
formliquid	0.6015899	0.1046676	7.940540e-01	0.3419521	1.759281
0.0798829033719					
glove.wash.MLyes	-0.6800388	-0.8003503	1.797693e+308	0.1243340	-5.469451
0.0000001192885					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total hands ML) = log(TA) + 2.475 + 1.55 formWP + 0.523 formliquid + -0.275 glove.wash.MLyes
 Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):
 log(total hands ML) = log(TA) + 3.478 + 1.089 formWP + 0.602 formliquid + -0.68 glove.wash.MLyes

=====
Model: log total hands ML ~ logTA + form + glove.wash.ML

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	41	218.70000	1997.005	3885.253	6926.498	40938.82
WP	20	5844.70000	75873.000	96066.000	147403.600	179582.00
liquid	169	71.49891	8250.000	30250.500	553048.508	2346735.63

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

TA	form	glove.wash.ML	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	0	211829.082	88490.755
2	10	WP	1	1085465.642	531567.071
3	100	WP	2	5687802.843	3193142.055
4	1	WG	0	5807.999	6251.808
5	10	WG	1	29757.650	37554.828
6	100	WG	2	155950.511	225593.172
7	1	liquid	0	21042.671	17796.138
8	10	liquid	1	107425.191	106902.025
9	100	liquid	2	561082.546	642164.218

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
 lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:
 Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
 -2.20324 -0.42676 0.01194 0.40950 1.59322

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.72681	0.11377	23.968	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.71328	0.06106	11.682	< 2e-16 ***
formWP	1.54937	0.16846	9.197	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	0.56778	0.10919	5.200	0.000000447 ***
glove.wash.MLyes	-0.33484	0.12698	-2.637	0.00895 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6176 on 225 degrees of freedom
 (273 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.5191, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5105
 F-statistic: 60.71 on 4 and 225 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
 Formula: log total hands ML ~ logTA + form + glove.wash.ML

N: 230 tau: 0.95 AIC: 548.585657672922

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	3.7960056	3.6249198	3.858266e+00	0.12228994	31.041030
0.000000e+00					
lTA	0.7786602	0.6581955	8.036805e-01	0.08840868	8.807508
4.440892e-16					
formWP	1.1508923	0.7655981	1.797693e+308	0.16476918	6.984876
3.182898e-11					

```
formliquid          0.4543202  0.3701585  6.513177e-01 0.11475598  3.959011
1.009693e-04
glove.wash.MLyes   -0.8445578 -0.8970980 1.797693e+308 0.09698032 -8.708548
6.661338e-16
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$$\log(\text{total hands ML}) = 2.727 + 0.713 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.549 \text{ formWP} + 0.568 \text{ formliquid} + -0.335 \text{ glove.wash.MLyes}$$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$$\log(\text{total hands ML}) = 3.796 + 0.779 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.151 \text{ formWP} + 0.454 \text{ formliquid} + -0.845 \text{ glove.wash.MLyes}$$

=====
Model: log protected hands ML/TA ~ form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	41	0.20	23.57881	67.85714	285.7143	948.10
WP	20	94.60	1180.50000	3586.50000	11215.0000	11310.00
liquid	167	0.01	44.11000	127.50000	2270.0844	33747.49

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	WP	0	9845.5941	2016.04278
2	10	WP	1	98455.9415	20160.42781
3	100	WP	2	984559.4150	201604.27807
4	1	WG	0	171.1291	31.46875
5	10	WG	1	1711.2911	314.68750
6	100	WG	2	17112.9113	3146.87500
7	1	liquid	0	189.6903	198.06763
8	10	liquid	1	1896.9033	1980.67633
9	100	liquid	2	18969.0332	19806.76329

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.4465	-0.5423	0.1350	0.6738	2.2032

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.51120	0.16089	3.177	0.00169 **
formWP	1.73852	0.28098	6.187	0.00000000286 ***
formliquid	0.06026	0.17955	0.336	0.73748

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.03 on 225 degrees of freedom

(275 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.1795, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1722

F-statistic: 24.61 on 2 and 225 DF, p-value: 2.157e-10

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log protected hands ML/TA ~ form

N: 228 tau: 0.95 AIC: 749.581628856977

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	1.497879	1.235315e+00	1.797693e+308	0.4108617	3.645702
					0.00033125141

```
formWP      1.806620    1.185979e+00 1.797693e+308  0.4117043 4.388150
0.00001757679
formliquid  0.798934   -1.797693e+308  1.112073e+00  0.4380121 1.824000
0.06947860284
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):
 $\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.511 + 1.739 \text{ formWP} + 0.06 \text{ formliquid}$
 Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):
 $\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.498 + 1.807 \text{ formWP} + 0.799 \text{ formliquid}$

=====
Model: log protected hands ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	41	0.20	23.57881	67.85714	285.7143	948.10
WP	20	94.60	1180.50000	3586.50000	11215.0000	11310.00
liquid	167	0.01	44.11000	127.50000	2270.0844	33747.49

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	0	23228.3155	1689.52798
2	10	WP	1	55931.1599	21390.43128
3	100	WP	2	139322.0976	270815.60985
4	1	WG	0	403.9063	31.60064
5	10	WG	1	972.5122	400.08294
6	100	WG	2	2423.3790	5065.28846
7	1	liquid	0	586.9531	150.54063
8	10	liquid	1	1404.0642	1905.93416
9	100	liquid	2	3477.1500	24130.26247

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.5338	-0.6104	-0.0085	0.5460	2.6548

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.02157	0.16664	6.130	3.91e-09 ***
lTA	0.38657	0.09305	4.155	4.64e-05 ***
formWP	1.74015	0.25771	6.752	1.23e-10 ***
formliquid	0.17395	0.16559	1.051	0.295

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.9449 on 224 degrees of freedom
 (275 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.2334, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2231
 F-statistic: 22.73 on 3 and 224 DF, p-value: 6.916e-13

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)`
 Formula: $\log \text{ protected hands ML} \sim \log \text{TA} + \text{form}$

N: 228 tau: 0.95 AIC: 748.956405920501

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	1.4996959	1.175213e+00	2.053562e+00	0.4289192	3.496453
	0.0005683700293				

```

lTA          1.1024542    6.434132e-01  1.499053e+00  0.2070463  5.324674
0.0000002454625
formWP       1.7280695    1.142468e+00  1.797693e+308  0.4042927  4.274303
0.0000283717922
formliquid   0.6779579   -1.797693e+308  1.181122e+00  0.4362767  1.553963
0.1216049263326

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$$\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = 1.022 + 0.387 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.74 \text{ formWP} + 0.174 \text{ formliquid}$$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$$\log(\text{protected hands ML}) = 1.5 + 1.102 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.728 \text{ formWP} + 0.678 \text{ formliquid}$$

Model: log total body ML/TA ~ form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	29	169.8190	2691.732	9850.784	25671.59	67310.76
WP	20	27859.6000	144744.500	365618.125	476504.08	568452.20
liquid	80	157.4779	5717.550	28538.814	130134.43	455259.00

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	WP	0	267819.993	84075.704
2	10	WP	1	2678199.931	840757.041
3	100	WP	2	26781999.311	8407570.410
4	1	WG	0	5346.273	4006.593
5	10	WG	1	53462.731	40065.930
6	100	WG	2	534627.314	400659.301
7	1	liquid	0	8075.691	25986.111
8	10	liquid	1	80756.910	259861.114
9	100	liquid	2	807569.099	2598611.144

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.69538	-0.46898	0.00179	0.40943	1.76812

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.6287	0.1211	21.703	< 2e-16 ***
formWP	1.6916	0.1896	8.922	4.5e-15 ***
formliquid	0.1909	0.1414	1.350	0.179

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6523 on 126 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.4361, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4271

F-statistic: 48.72 on 2 and 126 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log total body ML/TA ~ form

N: 129 tau: 0.95 AIC: 354.486892421103

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	3.6027752	3.217406e+00	1.797693e+308	0.1495698	24.087582
0.000000e+00					

```

formWP      1.3218953    1.289313e+00 1.797693e+308  0.1500675  8.808674
8.437695e-15
formliquid  0.8119661    -1.797693e+308  1.173778e+00  0.2750485  2.952083
3.765769e-03

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total body ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.629 + 1.692 \text{ formWP} + 0.191 \text{ formliquid}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total body ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 3.603 + 1.322 \text{ formWP} + 0.812 \text{ formliquid}$

=====

Model: log total body ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	29	169.8190	2691.732	9850.784	25671.59	67310.76
WP	20	27859.6000	144744.500	365618.125	476504.08	568452.20
liquid	80	157.4779	5717.550	28538.814	130134.43	455259.00

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	0	456626.075	285786.66
2	10	WP	1	2290292.199	557911.87
3	100	WP	2	12457026.311	1089153.87
4	1	WG	0	9133.499	16070.53
5	10	WG	1	45794.207	31372.84
6	100	WG	2	249135.929	61245.97
7	1	liquid	0	15817.348	72024.35
8	10	liquid	1	78093.847	140605.73
9	100	liquid	2	418768.757	274490.08

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.68026	-0.40599	0.02671	0.40490	1.58382

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.8696	0.1548	18.538	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.7121	0.1186	6.006	1.92e-08 ***
formWP	1.6910	0.1860	9.091	1.87e-15 ***
formliquid	0.2438	0.1404	1.736	0.085 .

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.64 on 125 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5019, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4899

F-statistic: 41.98 on 3 and 125 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)`

Formula: `log total body ML ~ logTA + form`

N: 129 tau: 0.95 AIC: 336.128084718612

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	4.2060302	3.515313e+00	1.797693e+308	0.4119966	10.208896
					0.00000000000

```

lTA          0.2905236   5.983216e-02  1.189557e+00  0.2850692  1.019134
0.31010797424
formWP       1.2500117   9.794553e-01  1.797693e+308  0.2891650  4.322832
0.00003114506
formliquid   0.6514491  -1.797693e+308  1.129022e+00  0.3172415  2.053480
0.04211174869

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total bpdY ML}) = 2.87 + 0.712 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.691 \text{ formWP} + 0.244 \text{ formliquid}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total body ML}) = 4.206 + 0.291 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.25 \text{ formWP} + 0.651 \text{ formliquid}$

=====

Model: log inner body ML/TA ~ form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	29	0.01	104.34783	230.4348	1070.524	1491.304
WP	20	1172.62	3885.80000	9072.6250	15705.625	24890.700
liquid	80	0.50	56.38165	180.7781	1442.907	13069.000

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	0	10175.38606	1989.83007
2	10	WP	1	101753.86058	19898.30065
3	100	WP	2	1017538.60585	198983.00654
4	1	WG	0	102.02672	62.21532
5	10	WG	1	1020.26716	622.15321
6	100	WG	2	10202.67159	6221.53209
7	1	liquid	0	85.51871	146.25000
8	10	liquid	1	855.18707	1462.50000
9	100	liquid	2	8551.87067	14625.00000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.81139	-0.38382	-0.03199	0.47632	1.97094

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.82912	0.12997	6.379	0.00000000308 ***
formWP	1.99002	0.20343	9.782	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	-0.06405	0.15171	-0.422	0.674

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6999 on 126 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5322, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5247

F-statistic: 71.66 on 2 and 126 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)`

Formula: `log inner body ML/TA ~ form`

N: 129 tau: 0.95 AIC: 377.182868326582

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	1.7938973	1.512269e+00	1.797693e+308	0.1974280	9.086335
					1.776357e-15

```

formWP      1.5049186    1.366484e+00 1.797693e+308  0.3001189 5.014407
1.763693e-06
formliquid  0.3711985   -1.797693e+308  9.840475e-01  0.3588683 1.034359
3.029497e-01

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inner body ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.829 + 1.99 \text{ formWP} + -0.064 \text{ formliquid}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inner body ML}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.794 + 1.505 \text{ formWP} + 0.371 \text{ formliquid}$

=====
Model: log inner body ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	29	0.01	104.34783	230.4348	1070.524	1491.304
WP	20	1172.62	3885.80000	9072.6250	15705.625	24890.700
liquid	80	0.50	56.38165	180.7781	1442.907	13069.000

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	0	11753.4349	1124.56181
2	10	WP	1	100724.6155	21450.84626
3	100	WP	2	943459.4181	409171.64369
4	1	WG	0	117.9146	26.48904
5	10	WG	1	1010.1048	505.27449
6	100	WG	2	9463.8167	9638.03428
7	1	liquid	0	102.7160	111.10570
8	10	liquid	1	865.1584	2119.32433
9	100	liquid	2	7978.4295	40425.79058

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.85758	-0.37844	-0.03886	0.47897	1.95879

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.87435	0.16985	5.148	9.95e-07 ***
lTA	0.94594	0.13010	7.271	3.42e-11 ***
formWP	1.98992	0.20410	9.750	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	-0.05411	0.15408	-0.351	0.726

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7022 on 125 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5864, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5765

F-statistic: 59.07 on 3 and 125 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)`

Formula: `log inner body ML ~ logTA + form`

N: 129 tau: 0.95 AIC: 377.573830363579

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	1.4230663	1.327185e+00	1.797693e+308	0.3608720	3.943410
	0.0001330071682				

```

lTA          1.2804611  -1.706662e-01  1.482441e+00  0.3190572  4.013265
0.0001024993734
formWP       1.6279171   1.119118e+00  1.797693e+308  0.2880818  5.650884
0.0000001024896
formliquid   0.6226701  -1.797693e+308  9.416483e-01  0.3646865  1.707412
0.0902281421990

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inner body ML}) = 0.874 + 0.946 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.99 \text{ formWP} + -0.054 \text{ formliquid}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inner body ML}) = 1.423 + 1.28 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.628 \text{ formWP} + 0.623 \text{ formliquid}$

=====
Model: log head ML/TA ~ form + face.shield.ML

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	29	0.01	58.33333	152.622	1466.402	2358.922
WP	20	65.76	443.00000	856.400	1533.650	2610.000
liquid	80	0.45	20.00000	245.000	4027.780	19050.450

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	face.shield.ML	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	no	0	1540.34830	198.94118
2	10	WP	no	1	15403.48303	1989.41176
3	100	WP	no	2	154034.83029	19894.11765
4	1	WG	no	0	75.08315	89.53373
5	10	WG	no	1	750.83151	895.33730
6	100	WG	no	2	7508.31508	8953.37302
7	1	liquid	no	0	258.44649	284.55806
8	10	liquid	no	1	2584.46493	2845.58059
9	100	liquid	no	2	25844.64928	28455.80588

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.75616	-0.65556	0.03817	0.48372	3.00737

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-1.0730	0.1938	-5.536	1.74e-07 ***
formWP	1.3050	0.2523	5.173	8.92e-07 ***
formliquid	0.5528	0.1829	3.023	0.00304 **
face.shield.MLno	1.5243	0.1744	8.738	1.31e-14 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8429 on 125 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5152, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5036

F-statistic: 44.29 on 3 and 125 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)`

Formula: `log head ML/TA ~ form + face.shield.ML`

N: 129 tau: 0.95 AIC: 417.287560639801

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					

```
(Intercept)      0.7049413  -5.756861e-01  1.797693e+308  0.7891821  0.8932555
0.37343689
formWP           0.3467380   2.986884e-01  1.797693e+308  0.1698111  2.0419037
0.04326501
formliquid       0.5021842  -1.797693e+308  1.095434e+00  0.2986862  1.6813102
0.09519961
face.shield.ML no 1.2470454  -1.797693e+308  2.377515e+00  0.7955561  1.5675141
0.11952263
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(hd.ML) = log(TA) + -1.073 + 1.305 formWP + 0.553 formliquid + 1.524
face.shield.MLno
```

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(head ML) = log(TA) + 0.705 + 0.347 formWP + 0.502 formliquid + 1.247
face.shield.ML no
```

=====
Model: log head ML ~ logTA + form + face.shield.ML

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	29	0.01	58.33333	152.622	1466.402	2358.922
WP	20	65.76	443.00000	856.400	1533.650	2610.000
liquid	80	0.45	20.00000	245.000	4027.780	19050.450

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	face.shield.ML	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	no	0	897.97264	138.63024
2	10	WP	no	1	16942.65776	2309.70074
3	100	WP	no	2	371992.28580	38481.62960
4	1	WG	no	0	38.86211	45.99762
5	10	WG	no	1	709.07515	766.36047
6	100	WG	no	2	15070.31179	12768.23418
7	1	liquid	no	0	122.90985	137.26404
8	10	liquid	no	1	2184.73997	2286.93867
9	100	liquid	no	2	45289.57262	38102.39362

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.9142	-0.6371	0.0174	0.5035	2.8635

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-1.1990	0.2080	-5.763	6.15e-08 ***
lTA	1.2979	0.1859	6.981	1.56e-10 ***
formWP	1.3704	0.2540	5.395	3.34e-07 ***
formliquid	0.5030	0.1844	2.728	0.00729 **
face.shield.MLno	1.3362	0.2094	6.382	3.16e-09 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8377 on 124 degrees of freedom

(374 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6771, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6667

F-statistic: 65 on 4 and 124 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log head ML ~ logTA + form + face.shield.ML

N: 129 tau: 0.95 AIC: 413.747209236552

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	0.6089731	-1.548457e+00	1.797693e+308	1.6470789	0.3697291
0.7122150					
lTA	1.2216977	6.014051e-01	3.234390e+00	0.7757631	1.5748335
0.1178429					
formWP	0.4791226	3.956502e-01	1.797693e+308	0.5307039	0.9028059
0.3683793					
formliquid	0.4748214	-1.797693e+308	1.911982e+00	0.6229477	0.7622171
0.4473778					
face.shield.MLno	1.0537623	-1.859106e-01	2.485119e+00	0.9784825	1.0769353
0.2835999					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(head ML) = -1.199 + 1.298 log(TA) + 1.37 formWP + 0.503 formliquid + 1.336 face.shield.MLno

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(head ML) = 0.609 + 1.222 log(TA) + 0.479 formWP + 0.475 formliquid + 1.054 face.shield.MLno

=====
Model: log inhalation ML/TA ~ form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	41	0.0100000	31.437500	73.125000	280.2083	824.8958
WP	20	559.4298246	1811.458333	4051.741372	5301.2610	8504.3860
liquid	100	0.5208333	3.096413	7.677895	30.1828	145.8333

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	0	7406.721622	670.937966
2	10	WP	1	74067.216221	6709.379658
3	100	WP	2	740672.162211	67093.796583
4	1	WG	0	38.878033	13.888889
5	10	WG	1	388.780326	138.888889
6	100	WG	2	3887.803261	1388.888889
7	1	liquid	0	4.739923	4.016885
8	10	liquid	1	47.399234	40.168845
9	100	liquid	2	473.992343	401.688453

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.2969	-0.4902	0.0638	0.5603	1.9473

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.2178	0.1279	1.702	0.0907 .
formWP	2.2629	0.2234	10.127	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	-0.9043	0.1519	-5.952	0.0000000165 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8193 on 158 degrees of freedom

(342 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6179, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6131

F-statistic: 127.8 on 2 and 158 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
 Formula: log inhalation ML/TA ~ form

N: 161 tau: 0.95 AIC: 430.886378321356

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.1426675	1.127165	1.797693e+308	0.2000766	5.711151	5.421156e-08
formWP	1.6840149	1.476925	1.797693e+308	0.2424690	6.945280	9.287549e-11
formliquid	-0.5387782	-1.123763	-4.920402e-01	0.2376888	-2.266738	2.476288e-02

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation ML) = log(TA) + 0.218 + 2.263 formWP + -0.904 formliquid

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation ML) = log(TA) + 1.143 + 1.684 formWP + -0.539 formliquid

=====
Model: log inhalation ML ~ logTA + form

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
WG	41	0.0100000	31.437500	73.125000	280.2083	824.8958
WP	20	559.4298246	1811.458333	4051.741372	5301.2610	8504.3860
liquid	100	0.5208333	3.096413	7.677895	30.1828	145.8333

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

TA	form	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	WP	0	16142.89095
2	10	WP	1	53567.47217
3	100	WP	2	189368.11784
4	1	WG	0	84.65508
5	10	WG	1	280.88771
6	100	WG	2	993.65328
7	1	liquid	0	15.72313
8	10	liquid	1	50.95116
9	100	liquid	2	176.10705

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
 lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.65066	-0.33244	0.06755	0.54541	1.80872

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.6087	0.1555	3.915	0.000135 ***
lTA	0.5301	0.1157	4.582	0.00000935 ***
formWP	2.2641	0.2132	10.618	< 2e-16 ***
formliquid	-0.7323	0.1510	-4.848	0.00000297 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7818 on 157 degrees of freedom

(342 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6001, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5925

F-statistic: 78.53 on 3 and 157 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
 Formula: log inhalation ML ~ logTA + form

N: 161 tau: 0.95 AIC: 409.612935251085

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.41417891	1.3106630	3.086235e+00	0.6360971	3.79529962
0.000210176					
lTA	0.02382229	-0.1266278	9.235126e-01	0.4429797	0.05377739
0.957180895					
formWP	1.27511405	0.9741828	1.797693e+308	0.3946513	3.23098878
0.001503015					
formliquid	-0.95607427	-1.6048096	-7.189633e-01	0.3864038	-2.47428827
0.014413990					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inhalation ML}) = 0.609 + 0.53 \log(\text{TA}) + 2.264 \text{ formWP} + -0.732 \text{ formliquid}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inhalation ML}) = 2.414 + 0.024 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.275 \text{ formWP} + -0.956 \text{ formliquid}$

A - LCTM

Model: log total hands A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	11.219	589.24	1411.807	3119.117	3637.72
normal	87	0.010	819.00	6597.035	29548.875	70746.80

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	251.290	353.7335
2	10	coarse	normal	1	2512.900	3537.3346
3	100	coarse	normal	2	25128.996	35373.3459
4	1	other	normal	0	6444.409	1040.3941
5	10	other	normal	1	64444.091	10403.9407
6	100	other	normal	2	644440.908	104039.4074
7	1	coarse	small area	0	8838.937	1288.3573
8	10	coarse	small area	1	88389.375	12883.5725
9	100	coarse	small area	2	883893.745	128835.7251
10	1	other	small area	0	207881.383	3789.2917
11	10	other	small area	1	2078813.831	37892.9167
12	100	other	small area	2	20788138.315	378929.1667

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-4.1980	-0.6925	0.2305	0.8675	2.6674

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.2979	0.5819	2.230	0.02810 *
dropletsother	1.4338	0.3440	4.168	0.0000682 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.4087	0.5070	-2.779	0.00659 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.484 on 94 degrees of freedom

(95 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2502, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2342

F-statistic: 15.68 on 2 and 94 DF, p-value: 0.000001327

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.298 + 1.434 \text{ dropletsother} + -1.409$
LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 3.11 + 0.469 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.561$
LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log total hands A ~ lTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	11.219	589.24	1411.807	3119.117	3637.72
normal	87	0.010	819.00	6597.035	29548.875	70746.80

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	coarse	normal	0	28.96012	560.8890
2	10	coarse	normal	1	1017.01101	3028.9777
3	100	coarse	normal	2	42289.29779	16357.4349
4	1	other	normal	0	786.38558	2291.6552
5	10	other	normal	1	27778.49639	12375.6607
6	100	other	normal	2	1164189.30483	66832.4717
7	1	coarse	small area	0	7308.79876	917.3643
8	10	coarse	small area	1	330973.81219	4954.0566
9	100	coarse	small area	2	17526974.41248	26753.4682
10	1	other	small area	0	184183.32606	3748.1258
11	10	other	small area	1	8419215.26732	20241.0615
12	100	other	small area	2	451330141.46465	109308.1166

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-4.0687	-0.6639	0.2672	0.9163	3.2574

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.2806	0.5676	2.256	0.026393 *
lTA	1.6226	0.2579	6.293	0.0000000101 ***
dropletsother	1.4623	0.3357	4.356	0.0000340243 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-2.3563	0.6312	-3.733	0.000326 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.448 on 93 degrees of freedom

(95 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3806, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3607

F-statistic: 19.05 on 3 and 93 DF, p-value: 0.00000000103

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = 1.281 + 1.623 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.462 \text{ dropletsother} + -2.356$
LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = 2.963 + 0.732 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.611 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.214$
LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log ptotected hands A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	2	2.00	11.63500	16.4525	20.3065	21.27
normal	58	0.01	32.04515	106.7800	2218.5234	10000.00

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	7.527131	2.1643192
2	10	coarse	normal	1	75.271308	21.6431925
3	100	coarse	normal	2	752.713084	216.4319249
4	1	other	normal	0	204.986147	103.3677255
5	10	other	normal	1	2049.861469	1033.6772549
6	100	other	normal	2	20498.614692	10336.7725490
7	1	coarse	small area	0	95.308199	0.4639088
8	10	coarse	small area	1	953.081993	4.6390881
9	100	coarse	small area	2	9530.819932	46.3908808
10	1	other	small area	0	2354.882774	22.1562500
11	10	other	small area	1	23548.827737	221.5625000
12	100	other	small area	2	235488.277366	2215.6250000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-3.0451	-0.7160	0.2216	0.8217	2.3049

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.6728	0.9581	-0.702	0.485
dropletsother	1.4565	0.3453	4.218	0.0000893 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.6137	0.9176	-0.669	0.506

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.264 on 57 degrees of freedom

(132 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.2536, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2274

F-statistic: 9.682 on 2 and 57 DF, p-value: 0.0002399

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + -0.673 + 1.456 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.614$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + -0.334 + 1.679 \text{ dropletsother} + 0.669$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log protected hands A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	2	2.00	11.63500	16.4525	20.3065	21.27
normal	58	0.01	32.04515	106.7800	2218.5234	10000.00

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	9.588512	53.7495817
2	10	coarse	normal	1	79.255499	70.3046043
3	100	coarse	normal	2	808.857802	91.9586206
4	1	other	normal	0	248.670808	3333.0177951

5	10	other	normal	1	2130.588853	4359.5966697
6	100	other	normal	2	22656.507068	5702.3647310
7	1	coarse	small area	0	99.591887	0.3446452
8	10	coarse	small area	1	1125.261040	0.4507969
9	100	coarse	small area	2	15129.855016	0.5896437
10	1	other	small area	0	2480.408559	21.3714908
11	10	other	small area	1	29039.437403	27.9539702
12	100	other	small area	2	405169.412512	36.5638718

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.0241	-0.7178	0.2222	0.8134	2.3056

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.6796	0.9684	-0.702	0.485709
lTA	1.0312	0.2733	3.773	0.000391 ***
dropletsother	1.4623	0.3521	4.153	0.000113 ***
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.6609	1.0141	-0.652	0.517243

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.275 on 56 degrees of freedom

(132 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3311, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2953

F-statistic: 9.241 on 3 and 56 DF, p-value: 0.00004631

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = -0.68 + 1.031 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.462 \text{dropletsother} + -0.661 \text{LCTM.equipmentnormal}$$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = -0.463 + 0.117 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.792 \text{dropletsother} + 2.193 \text{LCTM.equipmentnormal}$$

Model: log total body A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	454.69	899.9205	2024.874	2541.393	2704.369
normal	35	0.01	876.0000	4050.644	13843.063	26091.000

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	239.5013	13.10016
2	10	coarse	normal	1	2395.0131	131.00160
3	100	coarse	normal	2	23950.1306	1310.01600
4	1	other	normal	0	708.8850	427.52000
5	10	other	normal	1	7088.8505	4275.20000
6	100	other	normal	2	70888.5046	42752.00000
7	1	coarse	small area	0	12073.7270	86.32069
8	10	coarse	small area	1	120737.2698	863.20685
9	100	coarse	small area	2	1207372.6983	8632.06853
10	1	other	small area	0	32637.1664	2817.05104
11	10	other	small area	1	326371.6642	28170.51042
12	100	other	small area	2	3263716.6422	281705.10417

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.8627	-0.2834	0.0499	0.3687	1.3531

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.5237	0.4457	5.663	0.00000121 ***
dropletsother	0.5574	0.3642	1.530	0.133
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-1.6198	0.2978	-5.439	0.00000253 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8121 on 42 degrees of freedom

(147 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.4686, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4433

F-statistic: 18.52 on 2 and 42 DF, p-value: 0.000001711

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.524 + 0.557 \text{ dropletsother} + -1.62$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.936 + 1.514 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.819$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log total body A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	454.69	899.9205	2024.874	2541.393	2704.369
normal	35	0.01	876.0000	4050.644	13843.063	26091.000

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	coarse	normal	0	1.807590	0.1304745
2	10	coarse	normal	1	315.484740	35.2740033
3	100	coarse	normal	2	81982.678570	9536.3850185
4	1	other	normal	0	5.265868	3.3143207
5	10	other	normal	1	892.046916	896.0320758
6	100	other	normal	2	229240.435804	242243.7508436
7	1	coarse	small area	0	6753.195877	117.5742579
8	10	coarse	small area	1	2106289.024292	31786.3947198
9	100	coarse	small area	2	907507307.291877	8593504.2845758
10	1	other	small area	0	17615.469146	2986.6274472
11	10	other	small area	1	5524036.432433	807439.6606024
12	100	other	small area	2	2441781583.404030	218292645.1423756

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.38770	-0.20025	0.05726	0.30601	1.24847

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.5898	0.3546	7.304	6.16e-09 ***
lTA	2.4010	0.2778	8.643	8.82e-11 ***
dropletsother	0.5164	0.2897	1.782	0.0821 .

```
LCTM.equipmentnormal -3.6823      0.4725  -7.793 1.28e-09 ***
```

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 0.6457 on 41 degrees of freedom
(147 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
Multiple R-squared:  0.6611,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.6363
```

```
F-statistic: 26.65 on 3 and 41 DF,  p-value: 9.979e-10
```

```
Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):
```

```
Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):
```

```
log(total body A) = 2.59 + 2.401 log(TA) + 0.516 dropletsother + -3.682
```

```
LCTM.equipmentnormal
```

```
Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):
```

```
log(total body A) = 2.07 + 2.432 log(TA) + 1.405 dropletsother + -2.955
```

```
LCTM.equipmentnormal
```

```
=====
```

Model: log inner body A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

```
Table of measured values:
```

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	0.01	13.4385	26.19250	30.41375	31.541
normal	35	0.01	32.0000	66.17458	269.39884	525.000

```
Table of predicted values (95th percentile):
```

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	10.35814	0.5011554
2	10	coarse	normal	1	103.58135	5.0115538
3	100	coarse	normal	2	1035.81354	50.1155378
4	1	other	normal	0	18.50786	5.5797101
5	10	other	normal	1	185.07861	55.7971014
6	100	other	normal	2	1850.78606	557.9710145
7	1	coarse	small area	0	108.14302	2.9509713
8	10	coarse	small area	1	1081.43021	29.5097128
9	100	coarse	small area	2	10814.30210	295.0971276
10	1	other	small area	0	176.56784	32.8552083
11	10	other	small area	1	1765.67844	328.5520833
12	100	other	small area	2	17656.78440	3285.5208333

```
Summary of LS fit (mean):
```

```
Call:
```

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

```
Residuals:
```

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.68019	-0.11277	0.09724	0.47062	1.20745

```
Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.4852	0.4430	1.095	0.2796
dropletsother	0.3377	0.3621	0.933	0.3564
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.9365	0.2960	-3.163	0.0029 **

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 0.8073 on 42 degrees of freedom
(147 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
Multiple R-squared:  0.2318,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1952
```

```
F-statistic: 6.335 on 2 and 42 DF,  p-value: 0.003939
```

```
Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):
```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.485 + 0.338 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.936$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.47 + 1.047 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.77$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log inner body A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	0.01	13.4385	26.19250	30.41375	31.541
normal	35	0.01	32.0000	66.17458	269.39884	525.000

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	coarse	normal	0	0.1909661	0.02206981
2	10	coarse	normal	1	20.5110454	2.05456549
3	100	coarse	normal	2	3372.7989047	191.26757447
4	1	other	normal	0	0.3371457	0.21285236
5	10	other	normal	1	35.0736392	19.81526208
6	100	other	normal	2	5699.0741167	1844.68060612
7	1	coarse	small area	0	73.8540291	3.54406905
8	10	coarse	small area	1	14763.6126204	329.93131348
9	100	coarse	small area	2	4170244.3665726	30714.60234628
10	1	other	small area	0	115.8483868	34.18078294
11	10	other	small area	1	23293.0828068	3182.02338792
12	100	other	small area	2	6762270.6612796	296227.06006907

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.5303	-0.3485	0.1148	0.4460	1.0738

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.5418	0.3794	1.428	0.161
lTA	2.2013	0.2972	7.406	0.00000000443 ***
dropletsother	0.3025	0.3100	0.976	0.335
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-2.7050	0.5056	-5.350	0.00000361874 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6909 on 41 degrees of freedom

(147 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5936, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5639

F-statistic: 19.96 on 3 and 41 DF, p-value: 0.00000003916

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = 0.542 + 2.201 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.303 \text{ dropletsother} + -2.705$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = 0.55 + 1.969 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.984 \text{ dropletsother} + -2.206$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====
Model: log head A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	0.01	4	10.5835	88.3266	150
normal	36	0.01	34	112.0000	477.1250	4600

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	42.18142	1.098404
2	10	coarse	normal	1	421.81419	10.984038
3	100	coarse	normal	2	4218.14192	109.840376
4	1	other	normal	0	66.54133	11.820331
5	10	other	normal	1	665.41327	118.203310
6	100	other	normal	2	6654.13271	1182.033097
7	1	coarse	small area	0	90.43582	14.519525
8	10	coarse	small area	1	904.35823	145.195246
9	100	coarse	small area	2	9043.58229	1451.952465
10	1	other	small area	0	126.26068	156.250000
11	10	other	small area	1	1262.60677	1562.500000
12	100	other	small area	2	12626.06774	15625.000000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.3758	-0.3223	0.1525	0.6263	2.2560

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.2212	0.6223	-0.356	0.724
dropletsother	0.3194	0.5081	0.629	0.533
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.2165	0.4148	-0.522	0.604

Residual standard error: 1.136 on 43 degrees of freedom

(146 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.01908, Adjusted R-squared: -0.02654

F-statistic: 0.4183 on 2 and 43 DF, p-value: 0.6608

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$$\log(\text{head A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + -0.221 + 0.319 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.217 \text{ LCTM.equipmentnormal}$$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$$\log(\text{head A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.162 + 1.032 \text{ dropletsother} + -1.121 \text{ LCTM.equipmentnormal}$$

=====

Model: log head A ~ logTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	0.01	4	10.5835	88.3266	150
normal	36	0.01	34	112.0000	477.1250	4600

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95	
1	1	coarse	normal	0	2.319798e-02	1.695891e-04
2	10	coarse	normal	1	1.811477e+01	1.254818e+00
3	100	coarse	normal	2	2.388161e+04	9.284613e+03
4	1	other	normal	0	3.430464e-02	3.727660e-04
5	10	other	normal	1	2.562686e+01	2.758159e+00
6	100	other	normal	2	3.310167e+04	2.040808e+04
7	1	coarse	small area	0	3.574882e+01	7.991875e+01
8	10	coarse	small area	1	6.021658e+04	5.913324e+05
9	100	coarse	small area	2	1.550901e+08	4.375368e+09

```

10  1  other  small area  0 4.544572e+01 1.756658e+02
11 10  other  small area  1 7.671346e+04 1.299781e+06
12 100 other  small area  2 2.036375e+08 9.617298e+09

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.08083 -0.44113 -0.05607  0.43842  2.12791

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    -0.1013    0.4729  -0.214    0.831
lTA              3.1020    0.3682   8.425 1.44e-10 ***
dropletsother    0.2371    0.3860   0.614   0.542
LCTM.equipmentnormal -3.3317    0.6300  -5.288 4.16e-06 ***
---

```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Residual standard error: 0.8626 on 42 degrees of freedom

(146 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6748, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6515

F-statistic: 29.04 on 3 and 42 DF, p-value: 2.493e-10

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(head A) = -0.101 + 3.102 log(TA) + 0.237 dropletsother + -3.332
LCTM.equipmentnormal
```

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(head A) = 1.903 + 3.869 log(TA) + 0.342 dropletsother + -5.673
LCTM.equipmentnormal
```

=====

Model: log inhalation A/TA ~ droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

```

      n      min      50%      75%      95%      max
small area 10 0.0100000 0.010000 5.208333 30.70521 40.89583
normal     56 0.2916667 3.399313 7.548564 25.34423 69.67905

```

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

```

      TA droplets LCTM.equipment lTA      LS.95      QR.95
1     1   coarse      normal    0   1.852881   0.4762228
2     10  coarse      normal    1  18.528815  4.7622283
3     100 coarse      normal    2 185.288147 47.6222826
4     1   other      normal    0   1.771998   0.4804267
5     10  other      normal    1  17.719979  4.8042672
6     100 other      normal    2 177.199792 48.0426725
7     1   coarse  small area  0   4.310932  39.7431184
8     10  coarse  small area  1  43.109320 397.4311839
9     100 coarse  small area  2 431.093200 3974.3118386
10    1   other  small area  0   3.787097  40.0939542
11    10  other  small area  1  37.870965 400.9395425
12   100 other  small area  2 378.709652 4009.3954248

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max

```

-1.32771 -0.42373 -0.01846 0.41085 2.35455

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.7386	0.3158	-2.339	0.0225 *
dropletsother	-0.0129	0.2051	-0.063	0.9501
LCTM.equipmentnormal	-0.2876	0.2752	-1.045	0.2999

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7595 on 63 degrees of freedom

(126 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.0183, Adjusted R-squared: -0.01286

F-statistic: 0.5872 on 2 and 63 DF, p-value: 0.5589

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + -0.739 + -0.013 \text{ dropletsother} + -0.288$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.599 + 0.004 \text{ dropletsother} + -1.921$

LCTM.equipmentnormal

=====

Model:log inhalation A ~ lTA + droplets + LCTM.equipment

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
small area	10	0.0100000	0.010000	5.208333	30.70521	40.89583
normal	56	0.2916667	3.399313	7.548564	25.34423	69.67905

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	droplets	LCTM.equipment	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	coarse	normal	0	12.924097	1.354606
2	10	coarse	normal	1	29.789409	5.093432
3	100	coarse	normal	2	86.588531	19.151733
4	1	other	normal	0	18.747855	2.909464
5	10	other	normal	1	40.877300	10.939831
6	100	other	normal	2	111.617199	41.134681
7	1	coarse	small area	0	2.720041	18.824879
8	10	coarse	small area	1	9.290334	70.783126
9	100	coarse	small area	2	38.394466	266.150493
10	1	other	small area	0	3.287538	40.432655
11	10	other	small area	1	10.653514	152.030177
12	100	other	small area	2	42.462744	571.646224

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.2752	-0.3880	0.0428	0.3138	2.3689

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.8889	0.3094	-2.873	0.00555 **
lTA	0.4586	0.2167	2.116	0.03838 *
dropletsother	0.1278	0.2049	0.623	0.53525
LCTM.equipmentnormal	0.6499	0.4591	1.416	0.16188

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7297 on 62 degrees of freedom

(126 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.3581, Adjusted R-squared: 0.327
 F-statistic: 11.53 on 3 and 62 DF, p-value: 0.00000421

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = -0.889 + 0.459 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.128 \text{dropletsother} + 0.65 \text{LCTM.equipmentnormal}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = 1.275 + 0.575 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.332 \text{dropletsother} + -1.143 \text{LCTM.equipmentnormal}$

A - HCTM

Model: log total hands A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	54	0.01	722.8822	2845.750	18293.39	423687.9
no cabin	55	63.60	2283.0000	8019.125	31462.00	97980.0

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	9041.814	2075.574
2	10	cabin	1.00000	90418.140	20755.735
3	50	cabin	1.69897	452090.700	103778.677
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	93127.500	6236.800
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	931275.003	62368.000
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	4656375.016	311840.000

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-4.8534	-0.3990	0.0938	0.6827	2.4337

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.9503	0.1630	11.964	< 2e-16 ***
cabinno cabin	1.0132	0.2295	4.415	0.0000243 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.198 on 107 degrees of freedom

(48 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.1541, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1462

F-statistic: 19.49 on 1 and 107 DF, p-value: 0.00002425

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.95 + 1.013 \text{cabinno cabin}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 3.317 + 0.478 \text{cabinno cabin}$

Model: log total hands ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	54	0.01	722.8822	2845.750	18293.39	423687.9
no cabin	55	63.60	2283.0000	8019.125	31462.00	97980.0

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	20918.63	1910.373
2	10	cabin	1.00000	61231.95	44335.446
3	50	cabin	1.69897	158350.16	399289.220
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	154197.17	4796.941
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	490707.37	111326.208
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	1340603.17	1002614.353

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-4.7383	-0.3698	0.1652	0.5563	2.7213

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.2936	0.2747	8.350	2.81e-13 ***
lTA	0.4924	0.3280	1.501	0.136267
cabinno cabin	0.8879	0.2419	3.670	0.000382 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.19 on 106 degrees of freedom
 (48 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.1134, Adjusted R-squared: 0.09663

F-statistic: 6.776 on 2 and 106 DF, p-value: 0.001701

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$$\log(\text{total hands A}) = 2.294 + 0.492 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.888 \text{cabinno cabin}$$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$$\log(\text{total hands A}) = 3.281 + 1.366 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.4 \text{cabinno cabin}$$

Model: log protected hands A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	35	0.01	102.500	246.0452	1498.0	6800
no cabin	32	4.00	28.325	102.5000	5096.5	9080

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	718.9384	762.6667
2	10	cabin	1.00000	7189.3838	7626.6667
3	50	cabin	1.69897	35946.9191	38133.3333
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	1627.7753	919.4444
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	16277.7531	9194.4444
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	81388.7653	45972.2222

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
--	-----	----	--------	----	-----

-3.8449 -0.4004 0.1514 0.4369 2.3344

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.9418	0.1913	4.924	0.00000611 ***
cabinno cabin	0.3524	0.2768	1.273	0.207

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.132 on 65 degrees of freedom

(90 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.02434, Adjusted R-squared: 0.009329

F-statistic: 1.622 on 1 and 65 DF, p-value: 0.2074

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.942 + 0.352 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.882 + 0.081 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

=====
Model: log protected hands A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	35	0.01	102.500	246.0452	1498.0	6800
no cabin	32	4.00	28.325	102.5000	5096.5	9080

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	636.4986	127.20878
2	10	cabin	1.00000	8650.1137	28808.87811
3	50	cabin	1.69897	81874.2866	1275284.80527
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	1481.5123	86.97209
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	26120.5725	19696.50450
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	289668.5968	871906.66756

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-3.8810	-0.3344	0.1279	0.4731	2.3692

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.7934	0.3930	2.019	0.0477 *
lTA	1.2043	0.4715	2.554	0.0130 *
cabinno cabin	0.4260	0.3262	1.306	0.1963

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.139 on 64 degrees of freedom

(90 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.09251, Adjusted R-squared: 0.06416

F-statistic: 3.262 on 2 and 64 DF, p-value: 0.04476

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = 0.793 + 1.204 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.426 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(protected hands A) = 2.105 + 2.355 log(TA) + -0.165 cabinno cabin

=====
Model: log total body A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	30	68.0	3789.3	12847.30	48185.15	131572.0
no cabin	42	620.6	15005.0	60191.87	229388.82	432944.1

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	8467.507	8353.775
2	10	cabin	1.00000	84675.074	83537.748
3	50	cabin	1.69897	423375.370	417688.740
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	60581.048	51416.135
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	605810.481	514161.348
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	3029052.403	2570806.739

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.50148	-0.39690	0.07254	0.33688	1.36373

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.8569	0.1154	24.759	< 2e-16 ***
cabinno cabin	0.8595	0.1511	5.689	0.000000274 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.632 on 70 degrees of freedom
 (85 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3162, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3064

F-statistic: 32.37 on 1 and 70 DF, p-value: 0.0000002742

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total body A) = log(TA) + 2.857 + 0.86 cabinno cabin

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total body A) = log(TA) + 3.922 + 0.789 cabinno cabin

=====
Model: log total body A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	30	68.0	3789.3	12847.30	48185.15	131572.0
no cabin	42	620.6	15005.0	60191.87	229388.82	432944.1

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	6706.461	8270.677
2	10	cabin	1.00000	103822.658	83400.253
3	50	cabin	1.69897	803261.916	419442.115
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	50067.183	51136.464
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	797205.678	515652.318
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	6284162.974	2593353.032

Summary of LS fit (mean):

```

Call:
lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.47799 -0.40715  0.07089  0.35937  1.34654

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  2.7384     0.1636  16.738  < 2e-16 ***
lTA          1.1991     0.1949   6.151 0.0000000442 ***
cabinno cabin  0.8844     0.1530   5.781 0.0000001968 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6318 on 69 degrees of freedom
(85 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared:  0.4712,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.4558
F-statistic: 30.74 on 2 and 69 DF,  p-value: 2.847e-10

```

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

```

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):
log(total body A) = 2.738 + 1.199 log(TA) + 0.884 cabinno cabin
Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):
log(total body A) = 3.918 + 1.004 log(TA) + 0.791 cabinno cabin

```

Model: log inner body A ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	30	2.513	104.3478	240.3834	2020.000	3291.304
no cabin	42	18.000	195.2000	641.5217	1597.835	4016.803

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	156.5004	160.8006
2	10	cabin	1.00000	1565.0035	1608.0055
3	50	cabin	1.69897	7825.0176	8040.0276
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	492.7523	224.6986
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	4927.5229	2246.9858
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	24637.6144	11234.9288

Summary of LS fit (mean):

```

Call:
lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.57773 -0.33219  0.04825  0.37584  1.00428

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.30149     0.09622  13.526  < 2e-16 ***
cabinno cabin  0.50224     0.12598   3.987 0.000162 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.527 on 70 degrees of freedom
(85 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared:  0.185, Adjusted R-squared:  0.1734
F-statistic: 15.89 on 1 and 70 DF,  p-value: 0.0001625

```

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.301 + 0.502 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 2.206 + 0.145 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

=====
Model: linner body A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	30	2.513	104.3478	240.3834	2020.000	3291.304
no cabin	42	18.000	195.2000	641.5217	1597.835	4016.803

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	94.40761	61.98984
2	10	cabin	1.00000	2087.30247	1513.86722
3	50	cabin	1.69897	20211.99416	14128.48204
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	325.14631	229.73278
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	7354.84246	5610.35399
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	72307.04735	52359.80039

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.75220	-0.31112	0.01928	0.36241	0.88951

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.0919	0.1328	8.224	7.78e-12 ***
lTA	1.3521	0.1582	8.546	2.00e-12 ***
cabinno cabin	0.5463	0.1242	4.400	3.85e-05 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.5127 on 69 degrees of freedom

(85 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5446, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5314

F-statistic: 41.25 on 2 and 69 DF, p-value: 1.643e-12

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = 1.092 + 1.352 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.546 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inner body A}) = 1.792 + 1.388 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.569 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

=====
Model: log head A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	29	0.010	29.16667	133.3333	2295	3400
no cabin	42	9.706	523.80000	3538.1250	43265	87860

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	327.0796	194.4444

```

2 10 cabin 1.00000 3270.7956 1944.4444
3 50 cabin 1.69897 16353.9778 9722.2222
4 1 no cabin 0.00000 9294.9198 7107.2000
5 10 no cabin 1.00000 92949.1983 71072.0000
6 50 no cabin 1.69897 464745.9914 355360.0000

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.5363 -0.5973 -0.1260  0.6652  2.2851

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value    Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    0.8161     0.1860   4.388 0.0000402314 ***
cabinno cabin  1.4624     0.2418   6.047 0.0000000674 ***
---

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.002 on 69 degrees of freedom

(86 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3464, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3369

F-statistic: 36.57 on 1 and 69 DF, p-value: 0.00000006745

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

```
log(head A) = log(TA) + 0.816 + 1.462 cabinno cabin
```

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

```
log(head A) = log(TA) + 2.289 + 1.563 cabinno cabin
```

Model: log head A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

```

      n  min      50%      75%     95%    max
cabin  29 0.010 29.16667 133.3333 2295 3400
no cabin 42 9.706 523.80000 3538.1250 43265 87860

```

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

```

  TA  cabin  lTA      LS.95      QR.95
1  1  cabin  0.00000   197.6841   82.46489
2 10  cabin  1.00000  4854.9178  3854.04130
3 50  cabin  1.69897 55983.9688 56617.37545
4  1 no cabin  0.00000   6129.9418  2083.24163
5 10 no cabin  1.00000 156966.7471 97361.42659
6 50 no cabin  1.69897 1861186.2041 1430277.47075

```

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

```

      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.5900 -0.5753 -0.0296  0.6225  2.3213

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error t value    Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    0.5791     0.2589   2.237    0.0286 *
lTA            1.4037     0.3083   4.553 0.0000224805 ***
cabinno cabin  1.5097     0.2433   6.205 0.0000000371 ***
---

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.9965 on 68 degrees of freedom
 (86 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.4333, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4166
 F-statistic: 26 on 2 and 68 DF, p-value: 0.000000004113

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):
 $\log(\text{head A}) = 0.579 + 1.404 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.51 \text{ cabinno cabin}$
 Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):
 $\log(\text{head A}) = 1.916 + 1.67 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.402 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

Model: log inhalation A/TA ~ cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
cabin	42	0.4882812	12.23041	20.21498	114.9386	626.6276
no cabin	41	9.0679825	46.32143	114.58333	416.6667	23614.5833

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	19.47447	20.93666
2	10	cabin	1.00000	194.74470	209.36657
3	50	cabin	1.69897	973.72348	1046.83285
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	231.36539	82.67196
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	2313.65391	826.71958
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	11568.26955	4133.59788

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.29458	-0.36355	-0.02158	0.28687	2.13246

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.26309	0.09407	2.797	0.00645 **
cabinno cabin	1.07454	0.13384	8.028	6.61e-12 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6096 on 81 degrees of freedom
 (74 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.4431, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4363
 F-statistic: 64.45 on 1 and 81 DF, p-value: 6.605e-12

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):
 $\log(\text{inhalation A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 0.263 + 1.075 \text{ cabinno cabin}$
 Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):
 $\log(\text{inhalation A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 1.321 + 0.596 \text{ cabinno cabin}$

Model: log inhalation A ~ logTA + cabin

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
--	---	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

```
cabin    42 0.4882812 12.23041 20.21498 114.9386 626.6276
no cabin 41 9.0679825 46.32143 114.58333 416.6667 23614.5833
```

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	cabin	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	1	cabin	0.00000	34.0542	19.91302
2	10	cabin	1.00000	141.0456	319.26142
3	50	cabin	1.69897	428.7310	2220.30035
4	1	no cabin	0.00000	334.0465	73.42179
5	10	no cabin	1.00000	1440.2406	1177.15636
6	50	no cabin	1.69897	4493.5015	8186.52222

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.27225	-0.37160	-0.05694	0.30073	2.29570

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.5064	0.1501	3.374	0.001145 **
lTA	0.6312	0.1795	3.517	0.000724 ***
cabinno cabin	1.0011	0.1360	7.359	1.44e-10 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.5979 on 80 degrees of freedom

(74 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.4154, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4008

F-statistic: 28.42 on 2 and 80 DF, p-value: 4.721e-10

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = 0.506 + 0.631 \log(\text{TA}) + 1.001 \text{cabinno cabin}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = 1.299 + 1.205 \log(\text{TA}) + 0.567 \text{cabinno cabin}$

A - HCHH

Model: log total hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14012.50000	33505.60	48192.07	67131.74	78038.0
normal	50	11.42899	2538.35	5871.65	24666.95	60542.4

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	10744.014	3882.895
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	53720.071	19414.477
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	268600.356	97072.384
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	1227.969	2045.351
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	6139.844	10226.757
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	30699.218	51133.784

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.45276	-0.19272	0.01306	0.21206	1.37923

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.01965	0.06675	60.22	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.94024	0.08955	-10.50	<2e-16 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4222 on 88 degrees of freedom
 (44 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.5561, Adjusted R-squared: 0.551
 F-statistic: 110.2 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
 Formula: log total hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 145.938392319042

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	4.2881257	4.2697255	1.797693e+308	0.02758175	155.469681
0.0000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.2783878	-0.6173111	-5.593555e-02	0.24712226	-1.126518
0.2630088					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total hands A) = log(TA) + 4.02 + -0.94 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total hands A) = log(TA) + 4.288 + -0.278 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log total hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14012.50000	33505.60	48192.07	67131.74	78038.0
normal	50	11.42899	2538.35	5871.65	24666.95	60542.4

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	10678.12	7576.702
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	52828.93	25954.114
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	275220.46	88906.235
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	1207.50	2568.890
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	6107.82	8799.775
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	32573.12	30143.772

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
 lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.42657	-0.20494	0.01478	0.21196	1.39359

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.00222	0.08839	45.280	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	1.03355	0.11079	9.329	9.51e-15 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.92993	0.09624	-9.662	1.98e-15 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4244 on 87 degrees of freedom
 (44 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.7624, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7569
 F-statistic: 139.6 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
 Formula: log total hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 142.862005667458

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	4.4142062	4.3001110	4.73212120	0.1959222	22.530407
0.00000000					
lTA	0.7650200	0.2486867	1.32245313	0.3271734	2.338270
0.02166676					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.4697346	-0.5637189	-0.03111358	0.1423647	-3.299516
0.00140485					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(total hands A) = 4.002 + 1.034 log(TA) + -0.93 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(total hands A) = 4.414 + 0.765 log(TA) + -0.47 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log protected hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14.96	267.15	580.400	1357.550	1381
normal	50	0.05	4.12	112.575	510.465	1958

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	374.49410	81.23529
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	1872.47050	406.17647
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	9362.35248	2030.88235
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	20.39107	24.82840
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	101.95535	124.14201
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	509.77673	620.71006

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
 lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.0303	-0.4054	0.0761	0.5027	1.8766

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.9036	0.1286	14.802	< 2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.2607	0.1725	-7.307	1.18e-10 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8133 on 88 degrees of freedom
 (44 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.3776, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3705
 F-statistic: 53.39 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: 1.179e-10

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
Formula: log protected hands A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 233.747352132785

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.608715	2.6028269	1.797693e+308	0.03223789	80.920763
0.00000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.514796	-0.8430704	-2.934116e-01	0.22378891	-2.300364
0.02379235					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(protected hands A) = log(TA) + 1.904 + -1.261 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(protected hands A) = log(TA) + 2.609 + -0.515 HCHH.culturenormal

=====

Model: log protected hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	14.96	267.15	580.400	1357.550	1381
normal	50	0.05	4.12	112.575	510.465	1958

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1 0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	36.584931	12.657397
2 1.0	dense culture	0.00000	584.164209	203.674486
3 5.0	dense culture	0.69897	10219.736796	3277.395629
4 0.2	normal	-0.69897	3.286021	2.445655
5 1.0	normal	0.00000	54.565714	39.353865
6 5.0	normal	0.69897	994.948873	633.256469

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.9307	-0.4726	0.1691	0.5092	1.4326

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.4920	0.1563	9.545	3.45e-15 ***
lTA	1.7924	0.1959	9.148	2.23e-14 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.0171	0.1702	-5.976	4.90e-08 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.7505 on 87 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.675, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6675

F-statistic: 90.34 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
Formula: log protected hands A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 206.195230951648

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.3089366	2.2264449	2.4002113	0.09796646	23.568644
0.0000000000					
lTA	1.7262432	0.1989191	1.8929807	0.14927969	11.563818
0.0000000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.7139492	-0.8154612	-0.3405046	0.19484366	-3.664216
0.0004258183					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = 1.492 + 1.792 \log(\text{TA}) + -1.017 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{protected hands A}) = 2.309 + 1.726 \log(\text{TA}) + -0.714 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

Model: log total body A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	205029.900	743891.35	1433241.63	2224532.1	2470393
normal	50	1739.584	21941.66	55128.48	179870.9	254373

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	415989.19	117446.65
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	2079945.95	587233.24
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	10399729.73	2936166.18
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	21426.72	32589.84
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	107133.62	162949.20
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	535668.11	814746.01

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.57788	-0.31279	-0.03126	0.33281	1.45202

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	5.39920	0.08632	62.55	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.28588	0.11582	-11.10	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.546 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5835, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5787

F-statistic: 123.3 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)`

Formula: `log total body A/TA ~ HCHH.culture`

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 190.039417040803

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	5.7688106	5.7597297	1.797693e+308	0.05553349	103.879859
0.000000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.5567584	-0.7864454	-2.018612e-01	0.17934165	-3.104457
0.002564275					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 5.399 + -1.286 \text{ HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total body A}) = \log(\text{TA}) + 5.769 + -0.557 \text{ HCHH.culturenormal}$

=====

Model: log total body A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	205029.900	743891.35	1433241.63	2224532.1	2470393
normal	50	1739.584	21941.66	55128.48	179870.9	254373

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	2301384.82	2156000.0
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	3590379.65	2188718.3
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	5933306.32	2221933.1
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	70610.29	176076.3
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	112913.22	178748.3
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	191527.68	181460.9

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

`lm(formula = frm)`

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.24318	-0.29821	-0.01523	0.31477	1.15490

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	5.75181	0.09853	58.38	<2e-16 ***
lTA	0.32106	0.12350	2.60	0.011 *
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.49453	0.10728	-13.93	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.473 on 87 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.7484, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7427

F-statistic: 129.4 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: `rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)`

Formula: `log total body A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture`

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 149.256397383259

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	6.340189868	6.1713694	6.4369540	0.06733459	94.1594825
0.000000					
lTA	0.009358227	-0.1401279	1.1022710	0.11784533	0.0794111
0.936888					
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.087947945	-1.1665282	-0.2460348	0.06393434	-17.0166445
0.000000					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{total body A}) = 5.752 + 0.321 \log(\text{TA}) + -1.495 \text{ HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{total body A}) = 6.34 + 0.009 \log(\text{TA}) + -1.088 \text{ HCHH.culturenormal}$

```
=====
Model: log inner body A ~ HCHH.culture
```

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	2389.9	11617.750	46538.250	189501.150	305040.0
normal	50	6.0	255.251	972.135	1912.291	8980.1

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2 dense culture	-0.69897	15029.4331	9029.388
2	1.0 dense culture	0.00000	75147.1656	45146.939
3	5.0 dense culture	0.69897	375735.8282	225734.694
4	0.2 normal	-0.69897	495.0399	695.362
5	1.0 normal	0.00000	2475.1993	3476.810
6	5.0 normal	0.69897	12375.9964	17384.049

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.3168	-0.5376	-0.1802	0.4585	2.0331

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	3.7157	0.1090	34.09	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.4795	0.1462	-10.12	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6894 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5377, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5324

F-statistic: 102.3 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log inner body A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 252.511603193986

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	4.654628	4.554884	1.797693e+308	0.0969588	48.006248
0.000000000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.113447	-1.358390	-7.393541e-01	0.2674025	-4.163938
0.00007275973					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body A) = log(TA) + 3.716 + -1.479 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body A) = log(TA) + 4.655 + -1.113 HCHH.culturenormal

```
=====
Model: log inner body A ~ HCHH.culture
```

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	2389.9	11617.750	46538.250	189501.150	305040.0
normal	50	6.0	255.251	972.135	1912.291	8980.1

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	207255.648	188037.00
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	207255.648	188037.00
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	207255.648	188037.00
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	3365.701	1938.22
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	3365.701	1938.22
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	3365.701	1938.22

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.67010	-0.43413	-0.07057	0.46915	1.50503

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.2350	0.1016	41.68	<2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.7868	0.1363	-13.11	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6426 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.6613, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6575

F-statistic: 171.8 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log inner body A ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 222.008235452382

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	5.274243	5.100385	1.797693e+308	0.1271757	41.472096
	0.000000e+00				
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.986840	-2.224905	-1.474155e+00	0.2650627	-7.495738
	4.902989e-11				

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inner body A) = 4.235 + -1.787 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inner body A) = 5.274 + -1.987 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log head A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	129.72	1136.40	2894.50	5180.90	5394.0
normal	50	4.00	62.29	155.68	851.61	1471.6

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	772.02822	225.3846
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	3860.14109	1126.9231
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	19300.70543	5634.6154
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	80.00397	76.4918
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	400.01986	382.4590
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	2000.09928	1912.2951

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.35628	-0.38421	-0.00847	0.42494	1.62893

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.53252	0.09903	25.574	< 2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.98195	0.13286	-7.391	7.98e-11 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6263 on 88 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.383, Adjusted R-squared: 0.376

F-statistic: 54.62 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: 7.983e-11

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log head A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 207.89745205755

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	3.0518943	2.998703	1.797693e+308	0.0698863	43.66942
0.00000000					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.4693094	-0.629691	5.664356e-02	0.2149896	-2.18294
0.03170261					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(head A) = log(TA) + 2.533 + -0.982 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(head A) = log(TA) + 3.052 + -0.469 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log head A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	129.72	1136.40	2894.50	5180.90	5394.0
normal	50	4.00	62.29	155.68	851.61	1471.6

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	4359.4751	1879.2681
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	6928.2490	3182.4765
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	11800.1292	5389.4158
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	270.8947	485.5438
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	443.4959	822.2519
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	779.4351	1392.4557

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

```
lm(formula = frm)
```

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-1.00654	-0.38986	0.00658	0.42513	1.34706

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.8745	0.1185	24.257	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.3416	0.1485	2.300	0.0238 *
HCHH.culturenormal	-1.1843	0.1290	-9.178	1.94e-14 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.5689 on 87 degrees of freedom

(44 observations deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.5785, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5688

F-statistic: 59.71 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)

Formula: log head A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 195.479163307029

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	3.5027652	2.8493417	3.6988423	0.14044555	24.940379
0.000000000000000					
lTA	0.3273051	-0.3353057	2.4347579	0.23408874	1.398210
0.16560442825750					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.5877603	-1.1151096	0.8211811	0.09401927	-6.251487
0.00000001464939					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(head A) = 2.874 + 0.342 log(TA) + -1.184 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(head A) = 3.503 + 0.327 log(TA) + -0.588 HCHH.culturenormal

Model: log inhalation A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	101.5315315	330.97728	428.7562	705.2123	2136.261
normal	50	0.5208333	57.84375	156.5365	390.4583	2165.625

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	116.78287	42.39534
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	583.91437	211.97668
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	2919.57183	1059.88341
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	37.86361	44.61349
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	189.31804	223.06743
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	946.59018	1115.33717

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:

lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.55824	-0.20138	0.01866	0.22641	1.06065

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.98988	0.07295	27.278	< 2e-16 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.48726	0.09787	-4.979	0.00000316 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4614 on 88 degrees of freedom
 (44 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.2198, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2109
 F-statistic: 24.79 on 1 and 88 DF, p-value: 0.000003159

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
 Formula: log inhalation A/TA ~ HCHH.culture

N: 90 tau: 0.95 AIC: 159.415483991196

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.32628809	2.2825014	1.797693e+308	0.1780171	13.06777750
HCHH.culturenormal	0.02214808	-0.6551251	2.110937e-01	0.2518236	0.08795078
					0.9301156

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

log(inhalation A) = log(TA) + 1.99 + -0.487 HCHH.culturenormal

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

log(inhalation A) = log(TA) + 2.326 + 0.022 HCHH.culturenormal

=====
 Model: log inhalation A ~ log TA + HCHH.culture

Table of measured values:

	n	min	50%	75%	95%	max
dense culture	40	101.5315315	330.97728	428.7562	705.2123	2136.261
normal	50	0.5208333	57.84375	156.5365	390.4583	2165.625

Table of predicted values (95th percentile):

	TA	HCHH.culture	lTA	LS.95	QR.95
1	0.2	dense culture	-0.69897	253.90712	127.89291
2	1.0	dense culture	0.00000	779.58394	333.82387
3	5.0	dense culture	0.69897	2528.82618	871.34129
4	0.2	normal	-0.69897	66.02013	69.90183
5	1.0	normal	0.00000	207.54022	182.45654
6	5.0	normal	0.69897	690.19760	476.24490

Summary of LS fit (mean):

Call:
 lm(formula = frm)

Residuals:

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.41240	-0.16074	-0.00015	0.23767	1.20649

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.12507	0.09405	22.596	< 2e-16 ***
lTA	0.73970	0.11788	6.275	0.0000000132 ***
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.56726	0.10240	-5.539	0.0000003182 ***

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4515 on 87 degrees of freedom
 (44 observations deleted due to missingness)
 Multiple R-squared: 0.5543, Adjusted R-squared: 0.544
 F-statistic: 54.1 on 2 and 87 DF, p-value: 5.417e-16

Summary of RQ fit (95th percentile):

```
Call: rq(formula = frm, tau = 0.95)
Formula: linhalation A ~ logTA + HCHH.culture
```

```
N: 90      tau: 0.95      AIC: 158.884027565652
```

	coefficients	lower bd	upper bd	Std. Error	t value
Pr(> t)					
(Intercept)	2.5235174	2.1658532	3.088993	0.2224206	11.3456984
0.00000000					
lTA	0.5961213	-1.2403115	2.018214	0.2510519	2.3744941
0.01977204					
HCHH.culturenormal	-0.2623580	-0.7886172	0.235646	0.2933158	-0.8944557
0.37354600					

Formula for mean (based on LS-estimate):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = 2.125 + 0.74 \log(\text{TA}) + -0.567 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

Formula for 95th percentile (based on quantile regression):

$\log(\text{inhalation A}) = 2.524 + 0.596 \log(\text{TA}) + -0.262 \text{HCHH.culturenormal}$

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